

The Evolutionary Dynamics of Consumer Behavior: A Multi-Level Modelling Framework Integrating Behavioral Triggers and Decision Intelligence in Complex Market Leveraging Data Analytical Systems.

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1 Introduction

Human existence cannot be separated from the environment humans live in. People are constantly interacting with their environment to maintain and improve their living conditions. This interaction with natural systems supports the existence and viability of societies and cultures. Early hunter-gatherer societies relied on the wildlife and the availability of edible plants and fruits to provide for food. Many of those societies existed for long periods, because they managed the natural resources as communal property, using them with moderation. However, because of natural disasters, severe winters and over-harvesting, both the natural resources and the people often struggled to survive, frequently without success.

The introduction of agriculture, propelled by the development of ploughing, drastically changed the relation between man and natural systems. Land was being cultivated, which facilitated the production of larger quantities of food. This allowed for sustaining larger numbers of people and the storage of food stocks to survive droughts and winters. Because farmers could produce far more food than they required for themselves, a further specialisation of societal roles became possible. This specialisation stimulated the development and improvement of skills such as the processing of the agricultural products (milling of grain, baking of bread) and the production of agricultural tools and infrastructure (food storage, irrigation). Some of the agricultural societies remained for very long periods (e.g. in the Nile-valley \pm 7000 years; Ponting, 1993). However, despite the fact that agriculture lessened the vulnerability of societies in bad periods, many of these cultures collapsed after periods of flourishing (e.g., the Mesopotamians - 2000 BC and the Mayas - 800 AD). The initial success of these societies often stimulated population growth, which in its turn led towards an increased demand for food. This forced the farmers to cultivate lower quality land (forests, hills), thereby also accelerating processes of erosion. Plato, for example, lamented in his *Critias* that agricultural activities had transformed the land of Attica. Moreover, the soils became often exhausted because of intensive growing, or too salt because of intensive irrigation. This process often culminated in series of bad harvests, famine, large migrations and the collapse of cultures (see e.g., Ponting, 1993). These societies, whilst sometimes flourishing for centuries, were in the end not capable of satisfying their own and future generations' needs.

The industrialisation in the 19th century, propelled by the invention of the steam engine, had great effects on man and the environment. Forests were cut at a high rate to fuel the increasing number of steam engines. It is hard to imagine that the bare landscape of Scotland was once covered with the Caledonian forest. When many forests had been cut, coal provided fuel for industrialisation. The enormous economic growth associated with industrialisation resulted in financial wealth for many people, however, many more 'working class' people suffered from bad working and living conditions. Environmental quality dropped because of deforestation, air-pollution and water pollution.

At present, the socio-economic systems of many countries appear to overshoot their natural resource basis, which often causes regional environmental problems.

Examples are the erosion in Kenya because of agricultural practices and the gathering of fuel-wood, water shortages in various regions of the world (e.g., the Middle East, California, England), the burning of woods in Indonesia for agricultural purposes and floods in Korea as a result of deforestation. However, during the last decades awareness has emerged that the environmental impacts of our socio-economic system not only affect the regional or national level, but also have an impact on the world as a whole. These global changes, such as global warming, the thinning of the stratospheric ozone layer and large-scale deforestation, seriously jeopardise basic existential conditions.

The critical question in understanding environmental problems is why people so frequently over-exploit and damage natural resources, thereby endangering their own (future) living conditions, whereas other people use the same type of natural resources with moderation to preserve them. This question directly relates to the concept of *sustainability*, which deals with man's relation with nature, and in particular the exploitation of natural resources. Concisely defined, a sustainable society implies that the needs of the people are met without endangering the needs of future generations (Brundtland, 1987). The basic concept of sustainability stems from the biological concept of carrying capacity, which indicates a critical level of resource use. A resource use that exceeds this critical level will cause the resource to deplete, depriving future generations from its benefits.

Sustainability

Many discussions have been devoted to the technological innovations, institutional changes and changes in morality that would be necessary to reach the goal of a sustainable society. However, an 'objective' definition of sustainability has not been met (Sikor and Norgaard, 1999, p. 49). The perception of sustainability is subject to social and cultural values regarding what type of resources should be maintained, the level at which these resources should be maintained, and the appropriate means to do so. Moreover, it includes notions of who is responsible for implementing these means and the distribution of benefits and costs. Consequently, managing sustainability can be considered as a process aimed at integrating various views (ecological, economical, social, technical, moral). These views can be used in striving towards the satisfaction of needs of the current population, whilst creating sufficient opportunities for future generations to meet their needs. The social processes that can stimulate a more sustainable resource use are protection, investment, co-operation and innovation (Sikor and Norgaard, 1999).

To exemplify the different perspectives that actors have, and the social processes between these actors that may stimulate sustainability, let us consider the management of fishing grounds. Here, we deal with different actors having different perspectives on the use of this resource. For a local fishing company the perspective is focussed at the economic benefits to be gained by harvesting consumption fish. The perspective of environmentalists is focussed at the biodiversity of the fishing grounds, and as such they value the ecological system as a whole, involving all living animals, plants, nutrients and water quality. For residents in a coast town that largely depends on fisheries the fishing grounds determine the prosperity and viability of the town, creating an environment that provides good working and living conditions. Striving towards a sustainable use of fishing grounds involves, for example, the protection of the different actors from forces that would jeopardise the desired qualities of the resource. For example, closing the fish-grounds for foreign fleets may stimulate the local fishing companies to develop a long-term perspective on managing the fish-stock. Investment implies, for example, the

introduction of a fishing season, a minimal mesh-size of the nets and an agency enforcing these rules in order to guarantee the regenerative capacity of the fish-stock. Co-operation involves that the different actors work together in protecting the fish-stock, e.g. in advising national policy makers on issues dealing with the fishing grounds. This involves that the different actors learn to understand each other's perspective, and to recognise shared goals, such as the importance of biodiversity for a strong regenerative capacity of the fish-stock. Innovation involves the development of new technology and institutions to preserve the resource for future generations. Examples are the use of other types of nets and the introduction of a quota system.

Human behaviour and sustainability

Despite the fact that people often have ideas on the natural resources that are being jeopardised and the possible courses of action that would decrease the associated environmental problems, the actual behaviour of people is often far from sustainable. This may be due to different reasons (see also Vlek, 1996, p. 19). First, people may be unaware of the environmental problem. Second, they may be uncertain or underestimate the consequences of the environmental problem. Third, they may be incapable of changing their behaviour due to a lack of abilities. Fourth, changing behaviour in a more sustainable direction may seriously impair their quality of life (satisfaction of needs). Fifth, they may perceive that their individual behavioural change will hardly have an effect on the collective environmental problem. And sixth, they may be willing and able to change their behaviour, but may be inclined to wait until other persons change their behaviour first, thereby avoiding to be 'the sucker'. This latter reason is especially prevalent when the resource is not being perceived as a communal property, and social norms promoting a moderate use are lacking.

All these reasons, indicating why people often do not behave in a sustainable manner, deal in some sense with the cognitive processing of people. Habits, limited cognitive abilities, uncertainty, trust, personal motivation and needs all play an important role in determining the effort people make in obtaining information, when and with whom they compare, and what behaviour they will perform. Moreover, because natural resources are often public commodities, the people that use them are interdependent regarding their outcomes. This implies, for example, that the quantity of fish caught by one fisherman affects the size of the fish-stock available for other fishermen. In such situations, which bear a *social-dilemma* character, people often end up behaving in an unsustainable manner, whereas a more restricted resource use would yield higher outcomes in the long run.

The recognition that a natural resource is at danger in many cases stimulates governments to implement measures aimed at promoting sustainable behaviour. These measures are often being developed from a technological and/or an economic perspective. This is no surprise, because especially the natural sciences and economics have contributed a lot to understanding the principles of sustainability. However, these measures often do not anticipate on the behavioural dynamics affecting the effectiveness of these measures. As a consequence, such measures often do not yield the expected results and they frequently cause unexpected side effects. Examples of such developments are the very rapid increase of air traffic (business, tourist and freight), the increase of freight traffic generated by internet business ('e-commerce') and the increased paper consumption associated with computer use (remember the 'paperless office?').

The introduction of a psychological perspective in the process of searching for sustainability may add to our understanding of both the behavioural determinants of (un)sustainable behaviour and possible strategies to develop effective measures aimed at behavioural changes.

What psychology has to offer

Despite (or because of) being a relatively young science, psychology has developed a fair number of theories explaining different but often overlapping processes of human behaviour. In Chapter 5 several theories that are relevant in the context of environmental behaviour will be discussed.

In studying the processes that guide people's behaviour, all theories may contribute important insights. However, not all theoretical insights are relevant at the same time. For example, habitual behaviour can be understood using conditioning theory. However, when the habit changes, processes of attitude formation, reasoned action and social comparison may also play a role. Therefore, to understand the processes that lead towards unsustainable behaviour it is necessary to have a comprehensive perspective explaining in what situation which theoretical insights are relevant. It is precisely this perspective that is the starting-point of this monograph.

A conceptual meta-model is being developed that integrates simplified versions of the various specific or expert-theories as listed above. This integration allows for a dynamical description of behavioural processes, e.g., habit formation and change. A conceptual meta-model can not only be used in diagnosing the behavioural processes that lead towards unsustainable behaviour, but it also provides a perspective on which types of measures can be used in which order, to change this behaviour. Such a meta-model should be tested in order to prove and improve its validity and related applicability. A practical approach here is to formalise the model in terms of mathematical relations. Not only does this force one to be very specific regarding the relations between the various model parts, but it also offers the possibility of running and testing the model on a computer.

A formalised meta-model of behaviour that runs on a computer offers two major advantages. First, it becomes possible to perform simulations to experiment with behavioural dynamics. Such simulations can be used to explore for example the dynamics of resource use and consumptive behaviour and to formulate process explanations of empirically found effects. The second advantage of formalisation is that the mathematical basis makes it possible to exchange data with other disciplines and provide rules that can be used by others too, for example in integrated models of ecological-economic systems.

A formal model of behaviour

The concept of 'model' has many connotations, ranging from models like Claudia Schiffer and Naomi Campbell, miniaturised objects, organising structures, to mathematical models and computer simulations of complex systems. Within the natural and the economic sciences, models usually refer to mathematical formalisations of (parts of) real world systems, e.g., a formalised relation in terms of a mathematical equation. Models play a crucial role in science because their formalisation allows comparing outcomes with developments in the real world. Consequently, models are testable, allowing for decisions about which of two formal descriptions is better describing a real world process. The development of models often proceeds through isomorphisms, that is, by hypothesising that two different real-world systems share the same formal description. This modelling-

by-analogy has played an important role in economic science in describing complex economic (sub)system(s). For instance, there are clear isomorphisms between neo-classical equilibrium theory and the laws of chemical equilibrium as formulated by a.o. Guldberg and Waage (1867) and between economic production theory and classical thermodynamics.

In psychology, the principles of the telephone exchange and later the computer provided analogies for the theoretical modelling of cognitive processes and the functioning of the brain. Most psychological theories that have been discussed before can be considered as organising structures, elucidating which factors and variables affect other factors and variables. The formalisation of these relations is often based upon statistical data, which allows for attributing weights to various determinants. These weights vary depending on which data sets are being used in formalising the model. Because this type of formalisation is based on fixed relations between relevant variables, these models are not applicable in a simulation setting designed to study the dynamics of human behaviour.

Multi-agent simulation offers a tool to model interacting agents, and thus in principle it is appropriate for studying the dynamics of human behaviour. Within psychology the use of computerised models is not very common. However, more and more researchers discover the possibilities of computer modelling. Up to now, the application of behaviour simulation models has primarily been performed in game-theoretical research (see e.g., Gilbert & Troitzsch, 1999; Liebrand and Messick, 1996). However, these models are focussed at developing and testing outcome-optimising strategies, and they therefore lack the psychological richness required for studying behavioural dynamics in the context of sustainable development.

This monograph is aimed at demonstrating how a conceptual meta-model of behaviour may be used in developing a behavioural simulation model. The resulting methodology is called the 'consumat approach'. First, this consumat approach is demonstrated in the context of a simple resource dilemma, as is often studied in laboratory settings with real people. Next the consumat approach is being used to study the behavioural determinants of the so-called 'lock-in' effect, that involves the market domination of one product over other similar products. Finally, an attempt is being made to apply the consumat approach in the context of an integrated model, thereby introducing behavioural dynamics in ecological-economic models aimed at studying issues of sustainability. To elaborate on the modelling approaches within integrated modelling, the next section will shortly describe a perspective on integrated modelling and the role of behaviour.

Integrated modelling

Integrated models are relatively new approaches for discussing the issue of sustainability. These models are aimed at bringing together the knowledge of various disciplines in assessing the developments in ecology and economy. Starting in the 1970s, many researchers have attempted to integrate various relevant systems into a comprehensive model. Different concepts and modelling approaches emerged in the 'integrated modelling society'. Among these are system dynamics, environmental economics, industrial ecology, ecological economics, systems ecology and integrated assessment modelling. Despite the different approaches, all models that have been developed share one essential property: the inherent impossibility to make accurate predictions for long-term future developments, no matter the level of detail in the model. This is caused by the complexity of systems

involving ecology and human behaviour, which confronts us with the fundamental limits of predicting future system behaviour. Notwithstanding these serious limitations of integrated models, they can help us to show the interdependence of the various activities and their consequences in time, place and scale. In that way models can be used to communicate knowledge on relevant system dynamics from the scientific community to policy makers and stakeholders.

Currently, integrated models are being applied on various issues at different scale levels. Several integrated models focus on ecological-economic developments at a regional or local scale. In these models, socio-economic developments and interactions with the environment are simulated in spatial detail. Examples of such models are ISLAND (Engelen, White, Uljee and Drazan, 1995) and Lakeland (De Greef and De Vries, 1991). The issue of global climate change has also stimulated the development of integrated models of global systems. Examples of such global models are IMAGE (Rotmans, 1990; Alcamo, 1994) and TARGETS (Rotmans and De Vries, 1997).

These various models all deal with the interaction between man and the environment, and thus they address the issue of human behaviour, be it explicitly or implicitly. Up till now, integrated models primarily communicate the insights (and the objectives) of natural science and (neo-classical) economics. Regarding human behaviour, this means that usually the 'rational actor' approach is being applied, or that empirical demand-price-elasticities are being used to calculate the effect of (financial) system changes on behaviour. A 'rational-actor' approach is being used frequently to explicitly formalise 'the human agent' in integrated models (see also Chapter 3 on optimisation). In this approach a single, rational actor with perfect foresight and having a single, individual set of preferences is taken to represent large aggregates of people. Moreover, this rational actor is optimising it's individual outcomes.

However, in real life people do not behave in such a systematic manner (e.g., Gintis, 2000). The rational-actor approach does not account for behavioural dynamics such as habits, imitation and social comparison processes. To explore how such behavioural dynamics affect the sustainability of ecological-economic systems, it would be practical to apply the consumat approach in an integrated modelling context. This would contribute to improve the behavioural dynamics in integrated models. Some first modest steps in this direction are being made by applying the consumat approach in the integrated model 'Lakeland' (De Greef and De Vries, 1991).

Scope and organisation of this dissertation

The first aim of this dissertation is to present a conceptual meta-model of human behaviour that integrates various theories relevant for understanding environmental behaviour. Subsequently, this meta-model is being used to develop a simulation model for consumer behaviour. A multi-agent approach is chosen following state-of-the-art developments in the field of computer simulation in the social sciences. This multi-agent approach allows for the modelling of interactions between agents, thus allowing the formalisation and simulation of processes of imitation and social comparison. Although agent-based modelling is not new (e.g. Bossel and Strobel, 1978; Langton, 1989; Arthur, 1989; 1994; Holland and Miller, 1991; Epstein and Axtell, 1996), the contribution of this dissertation is that the behavioural rules used are based on a conceptual meta-model of behaviour. This increases the psychological richness and possibilities of validation of the simulated behavioural dynamics. In most other agent-based models the definition of the

rules is rather *ad hoc* (Durlauf, 1997) or the models are describing a more specific behaviour in a restricted environment.

Having such high ambitions, we may easily fail. Although this dissertation proposes some interesting improvements in simulating environmental behaviour, many problems remain, and some problems have not even been addressed yet. Therefore, this dissertation is intended at least to stimulate the debate on modelling human behaviour and the simulation of behaviour in various scientific contexts.

This monograph is organised in the following way. In Chapter 2 a picture will be drawn of environmental behaviour using the perspective of the commons dilemma (in which many individuals are relying on a common resource). Being focused at human behaviour in relation to renewable resources, the commons dilemma is a widely used paradigm in economics and psychology. Chapter 3 is devoted to the paradigms and techniques available for the modelling of human behaviour. Recent years have shown a rapid growth in the development of methodological tools. Therefore, it is important to deliberate on these approaches in light of their suitability for the modelling of behaviour. Chapter 4 will present an overview of simulation research in the social sciences.

In Chapter 5 a conceptual meta-model of behaviour is being discussed, combining various theories of behaviour in a single framework. This conceptual meta-model will be used in Chapter 6 to formalise the decision rules for the simulated agents in the so-called '*consumat approach*'. In Chapter 7 the consumat approach is being applied to a simple resource management task. The environmental relevancy of this topic was a first reason to select this issue. Moreover, much research has been performed in studying the factors determining the way in which people manage a renewable resource, including many simulation experiments. This makes this issue suitable for testing and experimenting with the consumat approach. In Chapter 8 the lock-in of consumption goods is being studied using the consumat approach. Often some new technology may conquer a large market share, whilst an alternative is available which is about equally good. From the perspective of environmental management it is important to understand how these processes work, because this would provide a perspective on avoiding lock-ins for environmentally harmful products, and stimulating lock-ins for environmentally benign alternatives.

In Chapter 9 the consumat approach is being applied in the context of an ecological-economic model. The simulation experiments in this chapter demonstrate the application of the consumat approach in a more complex simulated environment, and they thus demonstrate how the consumat approach can be applied in an integrated-modelling context. This demonstration shows that the micro-level behavioural rules of the consumat approach are significant for the macro-level indicators of sustainability. In Chapter 10 conclusions are drawn regarding the applicability and validity of the consumat approach. In that chapter we will also discuss the limitations and possibilities of the consumat approach.

2 The commons dilemma

Introduction

Man's relation with ecosystems is a double-faced one. On the one hand we depend on ecosystems as resources for food, building materials and a healthy environment to live in. On the other hand we often plunder and pollute ecosystems as if we were independent from them. This often results in the depletion of natural resources. The central question here is why people bite the hand that feeds them. In this chapter the commons dilemma paradigm will be used to explain the management of natural resources. The research traditions in this field as well as an inventory of experimental results will be presented. Finally, some limitations of the research in this paradigm are being discussed.

Economists were one of the firsts to put resource depletion on the agenda. In the late 18th and early 19th century, Malthus, Ricardo and Mill all concluded that scarcity of natural resources could lead to diminishing returns, and thus to a reduction in economic growth (Norton, 1984). According to Malthus (1789), land resources were a limiting factor to feed the increasing population. Ricardo (1817) distinguished different types of land, and argued that first land of the best quality is used, before land of a lower quality is used, a process leading to increasing marginal costs of increasing land use. According to Mill (1848) resource productivity could be maintained or even improved through technological development.

The arguments from the early days of economics still hold in the current discussions on the limits to growth (e.g., Köhn, Gowdy, Hinterberger and Van der Straaten, 1999). Since renewable resources play an important role in this monograph, resource economics will be discussed in more detail. A renewable resource, such as a fish stock, has a maximum carrying capacity depending on the environmental conditions. Changes in environmental conditions may change the carrying capacity of the resource. The maximum sustainable yield of a renewable resource is the maximum possible harvest that would not reduce the size of the resource after its renewal (e.g., restoration of fish-stock, regeneration of timber that is harvested).

From a classical economic perspective however, one is not interested in this sustainable yield but in the level of extraction (e.g., harvest, catch) that maximises the returns on investments. The optimal level of extraction is the level where the marginal costs equal the marginal returns from extraction. If one considers extraction during a number of periods, economists are interested in maximising the present value of extraction, that is the discounted stream of costs and benefits from the efforts to extract. Since discounting is dependent on returns from other investments, depletion of the renewable resource is likely when re-investing the revenue from resource extraction is more profitable, e.g., fishermen investing their revenues in better ships. When more agents have access to the resource, the situation becomes that of a common property. Here the individual agents are not primarily concerned with their marginal effect on the resource, but with the actual returns from extraction they derive for themselves. This leads to a higher extraction rate, which increases the chance of biological depletion, but certainly

results in economic over-fishing (Norton, 1984, p.119). This focus on individual returns causes for example that many private owned ships are put in service to exploit fish-grounds, whereas the collective revenue would be higher if fewer ships would return with a higher catch.

The *commons dilemma* describes situations where the individual and collective rationalities in determining an optimal resource use collide. A commons dilemma starts from the perspective of the resource, addressing environmental problems in terms of their behavioural causes. In a commons dilemma a collective opportunity exists for all individuals to consume. If this collective opportunity has a certain growth capacity, we may conceive it as a renewable resource. If such a resource, e.g., fresh water or natural forest, is being consumed at a rate that overshoots its natural growth, the availability of the resource will decrease. If consumption remains at a high level, the resource may even cease to exist. The risk of exhaustion is determined both by the consumption of the resource and the growth capacity of the resource. A certain limitation to the consumption of the resource is required to preserve it for a longer time, allowing its consumption to be sustainable. Many environmental issues where no property rights exist on a certain exhaustible resource can be understood as a commons dilemma. Examples are ocean fishing, waste dumping, fresh water consumption and forest management.

The commons dilemma paradigm has proven to be fruitful in describing a variety of situations where individual and collective interests collide. Such conflicts between individual and collective interests have intrigued scientists since Machiavelli (1525), who addressed this issue in the context of the political consequences of social (in)equality. Hardin's (1968) frequently cited article on the commons dilemma describes how this conflict affects the management of collective resources, explaining why people often tend to overexploit them. In his article Hardin (1968, p. 1244) presented the story of the decline of the common pastures for herding cattle. This story originates from a publication of Lloyd (1833). The story is told in the following way:

The tragedy of the commons develops in this way. Picture a pasture open to all. It is to be expected that each herdsman will try to keep as many cattle as possible on the commons. Such an arrangement may work reasonably satisfactory for centuries because tribal wars, poaching, and disease keep the numbers of both man and beast well below the carrying capacity of the land. Finally, however, comes the day of reckoning, that is, the day when the long-desired goal of social stability becomes a reality. At this point, the inherent logic of the commons remorselessly generates tragedy.

As a rational being, each herdsman seeks to maximize his gain. Explicitly or implicitly, more or less consciously, he asks "What is the utility to me of adding one more animal to my herd?" This utility has one negative and one positive component.

- 1) *The positive component is a function of the increment of one animal. Since the herdsman receives all the proceeds from the sale of an additional animal, the positive utility is nearly +1.*
- 2) *The negative component is a function of the additional overgrazing created by one more animal. Since, however, the effects of overgrazing are shared by all the herdsmen, the negative utility for any particular for any particular decision-making herdsman is only a fraction of -1.*

Adding together the component particular utilities, the rational herdsman concludes that the only sensible course for him to pursue is to add another animal to his herd. And another; and another. . . . But this is the conclusion reached by each and every rational herdsman sharing a commons. Therein is the tragedy. Each man is locked into a system that compels him to increase his herd without limit - in a world that is limited. Ruin is the destination toward which all men rush, each pursuing his

own best interest in a society that believes in the freedom of the commons. Freedom in a commons brings ruin to all.

Hardin (1968) uses this example to notify that for many problems no technical solutions are available. He exemplifies this with the arms-race between the east and the west that worried many people in that era, illustrating that for both parties it was more attractive to arm to increase their safety. This, however, resulted in both parties being heavily armed, constituting a more dangerous situation than had both parties restricted their military investments. Hardin (1968) specifically relates the concept of the commons dilemma to issues like the use of national parks and pollution in light of the growth of human population.

Hardin (1968) argued that the ‘rational’ use of a commons by many individuals cumulates to tragic overuse and depletion of the common resource. To prevent this depletion, Hardin proposes to introduce a socialistic system (central authority) or to privatise the common resource. However, these solutions are not always effective. For example, empirical studies show that the pasturelands in Russia, which has a state-owned collective agriculture, and in China, where pastureland has been privatised recently, have degraded to a much larger extent than comparable pasturelands in Mongolia, which are being managed by traditional group property institutions (Sneath, 1998). Many more examples exist of commons that are properly being managed by groups of people that have developed norms regarding the use of the resource (see e.g., Ostrom, Burger, Field, Norgaard and Policansky, 1999). These findings indicate that the management of common resources involves more complex processes than the metaphor of Hardin’s commons suggests. To better understand what factors affect the management of environmental commons dilemmas, it is first necessary to make an inventory of the precise structure of the dilemma. This is being done in the next section. Following that, we will discuss research traditions in the study of the commons dilemma, and discuss a number of factors that have experimentally been found to affect harvesting behaviour in a commons dilemma.

The environmental commons dilemma

The commons dilemma paradigm has been useful for understanding how people manage common resources. It has been used as a conceptual framework for understanding the processes leading towards many environmental problems, such as deforestation, over-fishing and air-pollution. Such environmental commons dilemmas are usually quite complex because of the various personal and collective outcomes involved, the specific dynamics of the resource and uncertainty about the outcomes. The people confronted with an environmental commons dilemma thus have to weigh several aspects in order to make decisions on how to behave. This weighting may be a very deliberate act, but more often it is a less conscious process. Vlek and Keren (1992) distinguish between the following four types of weightings that people have to make, which take the form of dilemmas¹.

¹ The text delineating these four dilemmas is based on Vlek & Keren (1992, pp. 250-251).

- 1: The everyday *benefit–risk dilemma*: if security, comfort and wealth are primary human desires, then to what extent should the level of achievable benefits be restricted to keep associated risks acceptably low? It is assumed here that benefit and risk levels across sets of human activities are correlated so that optimal benefit-risk combinations must be identified (Coombs and Avrunin, 1977).
- 2: The *temporal dilemma*: if the principal task of individuals, groups and organisations is to survive ‘now’, to what degree should current security, comfort and wealth be restrained in order to safeguard future survival conditions (which one may not live to see)? Or, in other words, how much attention and effort could best be devoted to short-term survival and how much is worth allocating to long-term survival?
- 3: The *spatial dilemma* underlies environmental degradation: if it is our principal task to survive here (in this place), to what extent should our local security, comfort and wealth be limited so as to secure more general survival conditions, such as the quality of seas and forest areas?
- 4: Environmental degradation can bring about a *social dilemma*: if one's principal task is to survive as an individual, then to what extent should individual security, comfort and wealth be restricted in order to maintain collective survival conditions such as public utilities, education, transport and health care?

An environmental commons dilemma can be regarded as a combination of these four dilemmas. This complex dilemma addresses the balancing of short-term local outcomes (mostly benefits) at the individual level with long-term global outcomes (mostly costs) at the collective level. The latter result from the combined externalities of many acting individuals. Assuming that consumers assign greater importance to financial and material benefits, and to present, local, and individual outcomes, the dilemmas will work as *traps*, tempting consumers to maximise their own short-term and local benefits whilst ignoring collective, long-term and global risks (Hardin, 1968; Dawes, 1980; Vlek, 1996).

An important factor regarding the character of an environmental commons dilemma is the perspective that an actor has on the dilemma. An actor may not perceive the dilemma or be insecure about the existence of the dilemma because of several reasons (e.g., Vlek, 1996). First, the actor may be unaware of the collectively damaging externalities of his behaviour. Especially when these negative externalities emerge slowly and/or in the long run, as may be the case with climatic changes, the actor is not likely to draw a relation between his behaviour and the negative collective outcomes. For example, examining information on the toxic emissions of one's car may convince one of the environmental harmlessness of one's car. However, as the emission of CO₂ still contributes to the greenhouse effect, the accumulation of these emissions may have a significant effect on the environment.

Second, the actor may be unaware of the seriousness of the accumulation of externalities. For example, an actor may be aware of the relation between CO₂ emissions and the greenhouse effect, but think that a global rise of temperature has no serious consequences for the climate.

Third, people may think that the negative collective outcomes are relatively small in comparison to the individual benefits (of many people). For example, the European policy on fisheries seems to prioritise the economical outcomes (work, income) over biological outcomes (fish populations, quality of sea-bottom) in allocating fishing quota.

Fourth, people may be aware of the collective risk, but perceive it to be the result of an autonomous development that cannot be controlled. Consequently, these people

may experience a 'no-choice' situation, and therefore do not perceive a dilemma despite their perception of the negative outcomes. For example, one may be convinced that forest-burning in order to gain agricultural land is ultimately destroying one's environment, but what else can one do if the alternative is starvation.

These points illustrate that the behaviour of people in an environmental commons dilemma both depends on the characteristics of the dilemma as well as individual characteristics. Many of these characteristics have experimentally been studied in the so-called *resource dilemma paradigm*. A resource dilemma can be considered as a specific type of commons dilemma. Basically, the resource dilemma offers each individual the choice between harvesting now a lot at the risk of exhausting the resource, versus harvesting less so as to sustain the resource. The more people harvest a lot, the quicker the resource may get exhausted. Whereas in the basic social dilemma the individual has the choice between a cooperative and a defective choice, where the cooperative choice yields the highest collective outcomes, the resource dilemma is more complex. Here, a significant restraint in personal harvesting, which can be considered to be cooperative, may not yield the highest collective outcomes. Because the resource can grow, a consumption level that is significantly lower than its growth capacity can be understood as under-using the resource (De Vries and Wilke, 1992, pp 82). Given that the growth function of the resource is known, an optimal collective harvest (OCH) can be determined. As long as the harvesting does not exceed this OCH, an increase in harvesting has no negative consequences for the resource. However, if the OCH is being exceeded, the resource will decrease and the outcomes will become smaller.

Research traditions in the study of the commons dilemma

Economics, being the study of the allocation of scarce resources for the satisfaction of human needs, and the problems of choice that are involved in this allocation process, has a large tradition in the study of commons dilemmas. In the economical research of exhaustible resources, much attention has been given to the study of renewable resources, which are in principle accessible for every individual, such as fish-stocks, oil wells and clean air. Economists argue that there exist several rationalities that may guide man's use of renewable resources. For example, different types of rationality lead towards individual rationality, the Nash equilibrium, Pareto efficiency and strong equilibrium (Dasgupta and Heal, 1979). Individual rationality implies that a person is following a strategy that maximises its individual outcomes. A Nash equilibrium (Nash, 1950) holds that an individual cannot find a strategy that further improves its outcomes, provided that all the other people do not change their behaviour (an unilateral behaviour change decreases outcomes). Strong Equilibrium (Aumann, 1995) holds that no group of people can all gain by unilaterally changing their behaviour (strategies). A Pareto optimal choice implies that society as a whole is economically the best off. However, this may imply that only a few rich people experience higher outcomes, whereas poor people may be worse off, thus indicating that an economically Pareto optimal outcome may not be socially desirable (see Norton, 1984, pp. 76)

Economic research clarifies that certain rationalities, when applied to a renewable resource, may yield outcomes that are less optimal and sometimes even disastrous. For

example, individual rational behaviour may result in uneconomic harvesting behaviour, even if such behaviour does not jeopardise the resource in itself (Norton, 1984).

Much economic research is aimed at the conditions under which these different types of rationality are dominating, and what types of measures are feasible to affect this domination. Usually this involves finding the conditions that favour an optimal resource depletion rate, provided that the actors employ an optimising strategy. Moreover, it can be calculated which governmental measures are necessary to attain an optimal depletion rate, given that all agents are following such an optimising strategy. In such calculations, economists employ the 'rational actor' approach, working with the assumption of agents that have perfect knowledge and try to optimise their outcomes. This approach provides an essential back-curtain against which the fallacies of actual economic behaviour may be perceived.

Luce and Raiffa's *Games and Decisions* (1957) awakened a fascination for the conflict between individual and collective interests in many social scientists also outside the economic tradition. Where economics is generally a normative science studying the optimal way of allocating scarce resources, social psychology is more a descriptive science studying the actual decision-making of human actors. Social psychology is focussed at questions of why people do not behave in an optimal manner, and what factors play an important role in actual behaviour. Combining a social-psychological view on behaviour with the economical principles that apply to renewable resource management, may add to the understanding of the discrepancies between optimal and actual behaviour.

Game theory, originating from Von Neumann and Morgenstern (1944), formed the basis on which Luce and Raiffa (1957) developed experimental games to study the actual behaviour of people in *social dilemmas*. Formally, a social dilemma can be described as a situation in which each decision maker is best off acting in his own self-interest, regardless of what the other persons do. Each self-interested decision, however, creates a negative outcome or cost for the other people who are involved (Van Lange, Liebrand, Messick and Wilke, 1992, pp. 4). In the experimental gaming approach, subjects have to choose between a defective and a cooperative action. Because the outcomes of their choice also depend on the choice of the other subject, subjects are interdependent. The defective action yields the highest expected individual outcomes, no matter the choice of the other subject. However, if both subjects choose the defective action they both obtain lower outcomes than had they chosen the cooperative action.

Experimental games can be thought of as empirical research tools that can be used to test the predictive accuracy of the formal theory of games (Van Lange *et al.*, 1992, pp. 4). Many experiments have been performed in this experimental game tradition, using different experimental games and identifying psychological variables that affect choice behaviour in such situations (Rapoport and Orwant, 1962; Rapoport and Chammah, 1965, Deutsch, 1960; Pruitt and Kimmel, 1977; Wrightsman, O'Connor and Baker, 1972, Colman, 1982; Hamburger, 1979). Many of these experiments taught us much about the basic forces driving people's behaviour in dilemmas. However, also critique was uttered regarding the lack of mundane realism and the associated external validity of many experiments (e.g., Nemeth, 1972, Pruitt and Kimmel, 1977; Kelley and Thibaut, 1978; Hamburger, 1979; Colman, 1982; Liebrand, 1983; Liebrand *et al.*, 1992). Many experimental games involved only two subjects, whereas real dilemmas often involve large numbers of people. Often the experimental games were played in a single trial, whereas in real dilemmas people repeatedly make choices. In experimental games the subjects usually

have an identical (symmetric) harvesting ability, whereas in real dilemmas usually several abilities play a role, which often display a skew distribution (asymmetric harvesting abilities). In experimental games the subject often has to choose between a cooperative and a defective choice, whereas real dilemmas usually offer a range of possible choices.

Two paradigms that in particular tried to increase mundane realism are the *resource dilemma paradigm* (see above) and the *public goods paradigm* (see Van Lange *et al.*, 1992, pp. 11). The resource dilemma is inspired by the commons dilemma as described by Hardin (1968). In this paradigm subjects are confronted with a common resource and they have to decide how much to take from that resource. Because this experimental game may last for a prolonged period of time, people have to take the long(er)-term effects of their behaviour on the resource in account. Typical founders in this tradition are Jerdee and Rosen (1974), Rubinstein, Watzke, Doktor and Dana (1975) and Brechner (1977). The public goods paradigm, inspired by Olson (1965), structurally resembles the resource dilemma paradigm, only the subjects now have to decide how much to *contribute* to a freely accessible resource. Despite the structural resemblance between the resource dilemma paradigm and the public goods paradigm, the psychological difference is large, as is denoted by their respective names *take-some game* and *give-some game* (Hamburger, 1979). Whereas the public goods dilemma can be applied to practical situations such as tax paying, the resource dilemma appears to be the most relevant in describing man's relation with the environment.

In the following section attention is given to the results of experimental games that appear to be relevant in the context of commons dilemmas. Some of these results originate from the social dilemmas paradigm, some from the resource dilemma paradigm, and some from the public goods paradigm. However, all the experimental games touch upon the conflict between the individual and collective level that constitutes the heart of the commons dilemma. Therefore, results originating from the different experimental paradigms are being summarised conjointly.

Factors affecting behaviour in experimental games

Two lines of research may be distinguished in the laboratory study of human resource management. The first line is focussed on group factors that may affect the harvesting behaviour of the individual subjects. The second line is focussed at the personal factors that affect harvesting behaviour.

A typical experiment on group factors confronts a group of subjects with a common resource, and one (or more) group factor(s) is experimentally being varied. Group factors apply to all the people in a dilemma, and refer to structural/situational characteristics of the dilemma. Examples of such factors are the possibility of direct (visual) contact with other group members, the visibility of the harvesting behaviour of others and the familiarity with others in the group. Whereas experimental games are useful in studying the effect of group factors, it is less practical for studying individual factors. Because individual factors such as a person's social orientation cannot be experimentally varied, it is virtually impossible to develop an experimental design with exactly the same distributions of person characteristics in each of the experimental conditions. Moreover, the differing individual factors may result in behavioural dynamics that are not known beforehand, and thus stand in the way of getting clear experimental results. A much used

solution for this problem is offered by the ‘false feedback’ procedure, in which subjects are led to believe that they interact with other subjects, but actually are interacting with computerised subjects with predisposed behavioural strategies. Because this implies that there are no real other subjects to play the game with, these are strictly spoken no experimental games. The behaviour of the other ‘subjects’ can be programmed beforehand, and thus is amenable to experimental manipulation. Subjects with differing individual characteristics can be confronted with the same computerised subjects, thus allowing to systematically study the effect of person factors on people’s behaviour in a resource dilemma, with ‘typically’ behaving other subjects (e.g., all computerised others behave cooperative or defective). Below, we will first discuss a list of group factors. Thereafter, a list of personal factors affecting harvesting behaviour will be discussed.

Group factors influencing behaviour in a dilemma

The following group factors have been shown to affect the harvesting behaviour of individuals in an experimental dilemma.

- Group size. When there are more persons caught in a dilemma, the level of cooperation will decrease (e.g. Fox and Guyer, 1977). This effect typically becomes visible if the group size increases from two to about seven or eight persons. Above the eight persons it does not make a difference if there are e.g. seven or twenty persons involved in the dilemma (Liebrand, 1984). Olson (1965) recognised this effect very early and attributed it to the lower efficacy that people experience in larger groups.
- Pay-off structure of the dilemma. It is not surprising that cooperative behaviour in a dilemma is promoted by decreasing the incentive associated with noncooperative behaviour and/or increasing the incentive associated with cooperative behaviour. This was found in the classic study of Kelley and Grzelak (1972) and repeatedly found in later studies (see e.g., Van Lange *et al.*, (1992)).
- Communication in the dilemma. Several studies have been directed at the effect of communication on people’s behaviour in a N-person dilemma. Some studies report that communication enhances cooperation (Jerdee and Rosen, 1974; Liebrand, 1984; Jorgerson and Papciak, 1981), whereas other studies report weak or no effects of communication (Caldwell, 1976; Loomis, 1959). The classic study of Dawes, McTavish and Shaklee (1977) showed that only communicating about what decision to make is effective in stimulating cooperative behaviour. The effect of communication may be based on the setting of a commitment norm and the enhancement of a group identity, which processes may also amplify one another (Van Lange *et al.*, 1992; Orbell, Van de Kragt and Dawes, 1988).
- Identifiability of the behaviour. Jorgerson and Papciak (1981) found that cooperative behaviour is promoted if the other people can observe one’s personal choice behaviour. This effect only occurs when there is no communication. This suggests that identifiability has about the same effect as communication, namely the promotion of ‘social control’ to exercise personal restraint. This ‘social control’ mechanism may be responsible for the fact that people are more willing to work hard under conditions of high visibility than in more anonymous settings (Williams, Harkins and Latané, 1980). Group size also plays a role in the identifiability of behaviour: the larger the group, the more anonymous one is.

- Group identity. If the persons in a dilemma experience a strong group identity, they feel more responsible for the outcomes and are more inclined towards cooperative behaviour (Brewer, 1979; Edney, 1980). Brewer and Kramer (1986) showed that the effects of group identity were the strongest in large groups, suggesting that personal responsibility is more important in large groups.

Personal factors influencing behaviour in a dilemma

The following personal factors have been found to affect harvesting behaviour of individuals in an experimental dilemma.

- Personal restraint. If the persons involved in a resource management task believe that personal restraint is essential to maintain the shared resource pool (sustainable use), people are more likely to cooperate, (e.g., Jorgerson and Papciack, 1981; Samuelson, Messick, Rutte and Wilke, 1984).
- Uncertainty. The more uncertain people are regarding the size and growth, and thus the optimal collective harvest (OCH) of a collective resource (environmental uncertainty), the more people tend to harvest from that resource (Wit and Wilke, 1998; Hine and Gifford, 1996; Suleiman and Rapoport, 1989; Messick, Allison and Samuelson, 1988). It appears that people, who become less quickly uncertain following unforeseen developments in the resource growth, tend to harvest less than people who become more quickly uncertain (Wit and Wilke, 1998). This indicates that not the fluctuations of the resource, but rather the person's sensitivity for these fluctuations trigger feelings of uncertainty.
- Expectations of other persons' behaviour. The expectations regarding the behaviour of other persons is an important behaviour-determining factor (Dawes *et al*, 1977; Messick, Wilke, Brewer, Kramer, Zemke and Lui, 1983; Schroeder, Jensen, Reed, Sullivan and Schwab, 1983; McClintock and Liebrand, 1988). If one expects that most other people will cooperate, one is more likely to cooperate too. However, if one expects that many others will defect, one will avoid being the 'sucker' whose cooperative behaviour is being exploited by the defecting others. Consequently, if one expects that most others will defect, defecting oneself seems a reasonable action. Other explanations that Van Lange *et al.* (1992) mention for this expectations-choice relationship refer to the inference of social norms on the basis of one's expectations, the conformity of people, the expectation that others will do as oneself, and a *post hoc* justification for one's choice behaviour (Messé and Sivacek, 1979).
- Trust. People differ with respect to the degree to which they trust other people (Yamagishi, 1988). People having a high trust in others are more willing to cooperate. People with a low trust in other people will be less likely to cooperate. Moreover, with respect to policy strategies to resolve a dilemma it appears that people low on trust are more in favour of a sanctioning system that imposes sanctions on noncooperative choices (Van Lange *et al.*, 1992, p. 17).
- Social Value Orientation. The social value orientation of a person, defined as preference for a particular distribution of outcomes for oneself and others, is an important behaviour-determining factor in social dilemmas (Messick and McClintock, 1968; McClintock, 1978). Whereas in principle eight typical social value orientations exist, the three empirically most frequent occurring orientations have been the topic of theorising and empirical study. These three orientations are (1) cooperation, aimed at maximising the outcomes of self and the other, (2) individualism, aimed at maximising

one's own outcomes, and (3) competition, aimed at maximising one's own outcomes in contrast to others' outcomes. An important conclusion from research on social value orientations is that not all people are *a priori* inclined to value only their own outcomes, or to see the pursuit of self interest as rational (Van Lange *et al.*, 1992, p.17). Including the outcomes of others in some way in a subjects own outcome matrix leads to a transformed outcome matrix, which may yield other optimal choices than pure self-interest would prescribe (Kelley and Thibaut, 1978; Kuhlman and Marshello, 1975; McClintock and Liebrand, 1988).

- Personality factors. Extraversion and agreeableness are personality factors affecting the harvesting behaviour in a resource dilemma (Koole, Jager, Van den Berg, Vlek and Hofstee, in press). Under the condition of a depleting resource it was found that people high on extraversion and/or low on agreeableness tend to harvest significantly more.
- Personal responsibility. Personal responsibility is a factor which is somewhat related to identifyability (Van Lange *et al.*, 1992, p. 20). A classic study by Latané and Darley (1968) showed that people are less helpful when more people are involved. The idea is that the more people are involved, the more the responsibility for the outcomes is diffused across the members of the group. Fleishman (1980) found that people felt more responsible the more others depended on one's contribution. Moreover, people who felt responsible contributed more, which suggests that responsibility enhances cooperative behaviour.
- Morality. People tend to cooperate more if they previously discussed the morality of cooperation and immorality of defecting (Dawes, 1980). The morality of (non)cooperation is often a topic of discussion in groups involved in a dilemma (Dawes, McTavish and Shaklee, 1977). Individuals who perceive the social dilemma as a moral issue tend to cooperate more often (Van Lange, Liebrand and Kuhlman, 1990).

Limitations of the experimental gaming research

The previously mentioned experiments represent only a small part of the large number of studies that have been conducted in the field of social dilemmas, resource dilemmas and public goods. Empirical studies in this field taught us a lot about the factors that influence human behaviour in a dilemma. However, the laboratory setting of this research differs significantly from real-world dilemma situations. A first difference deals with the time scale of the dilemma. Whereas experimental games in a laboratory setting seldom exceed a time limit of one hour, in the real world, negative collective outcomes (extinction of a resource) may occur only after several years, decades, or even generations. This raises questions regarding time-discounting effects in real world dilemmas. Wit, Wilke, Van Der Geest, Hofstra and Vahrenkamp (1996) experimented with two generations of players that were managing a collective resource. They found that people in the first generation only restrain their consumption when their outcomes were made dependant of the outcomes the next generation obtained. This suggests that people will only restrain their harvesting behaviour when they find it important that their successors can harvest at the same level as themselves. In practice this restriction will especially occur when the successors are children, family or members of the same tribe, clan or people.

Second, real world dilemmas usually involve large numbers of people. Whereas in experimental games the number of subjects seldom exceeds a dozen², in the real world hundreds, thousands and millions of people can be caught in the same type of dilemma. When global warming is regarded as a negative outcome of the intensive energy-use of many people, it may be concluded that the world population as a whole is being caught in a commons dilemma. The laboratory-fact that above a number of seven or eight subjects a further increase in the number of subjects does not result in lower cooperation suggests that this factor is not relevant in discriminating between large and very large dilemmas (e.g., thousands versus millions of people). However, as far as we know, empirical research has not been directed at such large groups, and it can be postulated that in a group of thousand people it will be easier to address group characteristics such as communality and culture than in groups of millions.

A third difference refers to the type and relevance of outcomes. In the experimental games the outcomes usually are framed in terms of credit points or money, and depending on the number of points the subjects collected they will receive more or less money at the end of the experiment. The size of the monetary reward will usually have no significant effects on the subjects' daily lives. In the real world the outcomes are usually much more diverse and significant. For a fisherman in a developing country the catching of more fish yields more money, which can be spent on e.g., better fishing equipment, education for his children or luxury items. Catching less fish may result in poorer living circumstances for his family. Another example is a rich person living, e.g., in California, who consumes a lot of energy for transportation (large car, travelling by air), climate control of the home and household appliances. A serious decline in his energy use implies a change of activities that will have negative consequences for his social life, the comfort of his house and his social status. These outcomes are very personal, direct and clear, whilst the negative outcome of global warming is very general, to be expected in the future and relatively uncertain as is indicated by the vivid discussions in the scientific community on the seriousness of the enhanced greenhouse effect. These examples show that in comparison to experimental games, real life dilemmas confront people with choices that involve important outcomes. Moreover, these outcomes are multidimensional in the sense that the satisfaction of several needs depends on the behaviour people perform. Whereas the choices that people make while playing an experimental game usually have no far-reaching consequences for their lives, in real-life dilemmas the choices one makes may determine one's quality of live to a far extent.

These three limitations have stimulated several researchers to employ behaviour simulation models in their research to tackle the points discussed above. Two main directions can be distinguished in the application of simulation models. First, several researchers tried to increase the realism of natural resource systems by developing computer simulations of more complex systems. Such simulations provide a tool to study the behaviour of people in more realistic yet controllable situations, thereby compressing long-term processes in short experimental simulation sessions. Second, several researchers developed simulations of behaviour itself, operationalising agents via algorithms that represent certain decision processes. This approach allows for testing different algorithms against each other, and to evaluate these in terms of the sustainability of the underlying processes. Moreover, this approach allows in principle for experimentation with far-

² The study of Fleishman (1980) reporting a N of 100 seems to be one exception.

reaching outcomes, such as famines when a food resource is being over-harvested, and the 'death' of unsuccessful agents.

Chapter 4 provides an overview of historic developments and current issues in the use of simulation models in the social sciences. Here, various examples of the two directions of simulation research will be discussed. However, before discussing simulation in the social sciences, it is important to understand the principles behind different simulation techniques and the relation of such simulations to real world processes. Therefore, Chapter 3 will be devoted to the methodologies that are being used in social scientific simulation models.

3 A methodology of modelling

In this chapter, we will focus on the methodology that is being used in scientific models. We will first present an inventory of the metaphors that underlie scientific models. These form the necessary basis to describe the various modelling paradigms that are being used in the social sciences. Because agent-based modelling offers a methodology to model the dynamics of interacting agents, we will focus on the conceptual tools that are being used in that modelling paradigm. This chapter will conclude with a discussion on the application of models.

In Chapter 1 we stated that scientific models can be conceived as formal descriptions of systems. The development of scientific models usually proceeds through isomorphisms. These isomorphisms can be considered as general metaphors, which implies that the modelling of a certain system is based on the formal description that is available of another system (e.g., Khalil, 1992). For example, a better formal understanding of chemical processes also triggered the development of analogous economic models. On the basis of formal models it is possible to develop simulation models that to a certain extent behave like real-world systems. Doran and Gilbert (1994) argue that the technique of computer simulation is an appropriate methodology to study social phenomena that are not directly accessible for research in the classical tradition, as is the case with man-environment interaction. Such a lack of accessibility may be due to the complexity of a phenomenon, which does not allow for understanding it on the basis of observational data, or because the phenomenon in question does not exist anymore, as is the case with historical processes.

Modelling as a metaphor

Considering a simulation model (computerised or not) as a metaphor of a real-world process yields the question ‘To what extent can a certain metaphor capture a real-world process?’ To answer this question, it is first necessary to realise that different types of metaphors exist, and that the type of metaphor underlying a simulation model has consequences for the applicability and outcomes of simulations with it.

According to Khalil (1992) there are at least four types of metaphors. The *superficial metaphor* refers to an observed similarity but is not meant to indicate any functional likeness. An example is ‘He’s got a head like a potato’. Superficial metaphors may be used as illustrations, but, because they do not refer to a deeper similarity (e.g., at the functional level), it is not recommendable to use them in a scientific context.

The *heterologous (or analogous) metaphor* refers to a similarity of analytical functions. Khalil (1996) mentions as an example the comparison of the wings of a bat with the wings of a butterfly, which perform the same function but which have totally different (evolutionary) origins. The previously mentioned example of economic models that were developed analogous to chemical processes is one example of this type of metaphor that is being widely used in science.

The *homologous metaphor* designates a similarity from the resemblance of contexts. An example is the similar origin of the forelimbs of the bat and the mouse, which have the same origins but have different functions. This type of metaphor may be describing the similarity between e.g., fighter-jet training simulators and flight-simulator games, which have the same origin, but have been developed to fit very different functions. This type of metaphor is hardly relevant for the formalisation of scientific models.

The *unificational metaphor* expresses similarities arising from the same law. For example, Newton's law of gravitation can be understood as a metaphor that expressed celestial movement (Kepler's laws) and terrestrial gravity (Galileo's laws) in terms of the same law or principle. The genetic algorithms used in simulating processes of adaptive behaviour (e.g., Holland, 1975) can also be understood as an unificational metaphor, being isomorphic to the principles underlying the genetic recombination of DNA (Watson and Crick, 1953), which explains the laws of heredity as formulated by Mendel (1865).

Regarding the degree to which a scientific model captures real-world processes the relevant question becomes 'What type of metaphor underlies a particular simulation of a real world system?' Regarding the development of scientific simulation models, we concluded that both the *heterologous* and the *unificational* metaphor play an important role, whereas the *superficial* and *homologous* metaphors are unimportant. In developing simulation models, scientists may use different theories, laws and appropriate insights as metaphors to formalise a system to be studied. It should therefore come as no surprise that various modelling approaches exist. Whereas all these approaches use some basic common concepts, such as a mathematical basis, they differ regarding the theories and procedures for constructing and testing models. These differences can partly be attributed to the metaphors used in modelling. A major source of metaphors is provided by the natural sciences, a discipline that was among the first to apply mathematics in practical settings. According to Meadows and Robinson (1985), all mathematical models share a general biased starting point by assuming that the world is not only knowable by a rational process of observation and reflection, but is also assumed to be controllable. Of course, this holds in different degrees for various modelling approaches, as system dynamical models are assuming a much larger controllability than e.g. models of adaptive systems using genetic algorithms. Because these differences stem from different (implicit) assumptions of how the real world system works, these various modelling approaches seem to fit the concept of paradigm (Kuhn, 1970). New insights in principles of system behaviour may cause a paradigmatic change, thereby disqualifying an 'old unificational metaphor' as a heterologous metaphor. This implies that the scientific usefulness of metaphors depends on one's paradigmatic perspective. In the following section some important modelling paradigms and the underlying assumptions will be discussed.

Metaphors as modelling paradigms

The developments in the natural sciences influenced the number and nature of modelling paradigms to a large extent. The start of mathematical modelling can be dated to the 17th century, in which physical science developed a mechanistic, reversible, reductionistic and equilibrium-based explanation of the world. This proved to be very successful in calculating trajectories of moving objects (e.g. cannon balls) and predicting the positions of celestial bodies. Especially the work of Newton, culminating in the *Principia Mathematica*

Philosophiae Naturalis (1687), was and still is very influencing. The associated rational and mathematical way of describing the world around us was also applied in social science, economics and biology. Despite the fact that later developments in the natural sciences seriously constrained the applicability of the mechanistic paradigm, its relative simplicity had a large appeal on scientists from various disciplines working with models. However, despite the wide-spread use of this approach, the mechanistic paradigm becomes increasingly criticised. The foundations of the mechanistic view: reversibility, reductionistic, equilibrium-based and controllable experiments fade away in the light of a number of ‘new’ scientific insights.

First, the discovery of the Second Law of Thermodynamics brought down the notion of reversibility. The Second Law states that the entropy of a closed system is increasing. This means that heat flows from hot to cold, so that less useful energy remains. One of the consequences of the Second Law is the irreversibility of system behaviour and the single direction of time. Changes within systems cannot reverse back just like that (irreversible). This is in contrast to many mechanistic models, in which the time can easily be reversed to calculate previous conditions.

Second, the equilibrium view on species was brought down by Darwin’s (1859) book on the origin of species. The static concept of unchanging species was replaced by a dynamic concept of an evolution by natural selection and adaptation of species, thereby fundamentally changing our view of nature. Natural systems are in continuous disequilibrium, being interdependent and constantly adapting to changing circumstances.

Third, the theories of quantum mechanics confronted us with a fundamental uncertainty regarding knowledge about systems, especially on the level of atoms and particles. Well known is the uncertainty theorem of Heisenberg (1927), stating that it is impossible to simultaneously measure the position in space and momentum (mass times velocity) of any particle. The statement by Laplace (1805–1825) that if every position of every atom was known, the future might be predicted exactly, became therefore a lost illusion. Moreover, the notion of fundamental uncertainty implied that fully controlled experiments are strictly spoken not possible.

Notwithstanding the fact that the just described developments in the natural sciences changed our perception of the world, mathematical models are still mainly based on a mechanistic view on systems. However, the rapid growth of computing power and the increase in simulation research has also yielded a new modelling paradigm and associated tools. This new paradigm uses the metaphor of the organism, including notions of adaptability and learning. Whereas the computer is a typical product of the mechanistic worldview, it allows to model irreversible, non-equilibrium, unpredictable and uncontrollable processes that are typical for organic systems. Because no organic counterpart of mechanistic mathematics exists, special tools have been developed to simulate organic processes using mechanistic model rules. Agent-based modelling, which implies formalising a multitude of relatively autonomous agents that interact, proved to be a successful approach within this organic modelling paradigm. The associated notion of distributed intelligence is being used in a rising number of simulations of complex adaptive systems.

For further reading on the gap between mechanistic and organic views on systems, see e.g., Allen (1990), Toulmin (1990), Geels (1996) and Janssen (1998). In the following section various modelling approaches that are used nowadays within integrated modelling will be discussed.

Multiple regression models

Many scientists in the social sciences are developing models using the statistical technique of multiple regression analysis to discover systematic patterns of relations in large data sets. In this line of modelling, scientists describe the system of interest in terms of simultaneous equations, linear relations, many exogenous driving variables, and observable statistics. The multiple regression model is based upon the significant relations that have been found between variables, emphasising the $p < .05$ criterion of chance occurrence. Empirical data are rigorously used to determine model parameters, while frequently less effort is spent on estimating the relevance and representativeness of the data. For example, often the reliability of (historical) data is unknown. Because of the correlational basis of the multiple regression modelling approach, no causal relations can be inferred between variables. Often theoretical models (or less formalised mental maps) are being used to interpret relations between variables as a means to introduce causality in the models.

Multiple regression models can be used to extrapolate trends of past developments. Despite the fact that quite complex extrapolation techniques have been developed, the fact remains that the relations between model variables are treated as static, whereas in the real world these relations may be dynamically changing. This implies that multiple regression models are not capable of reflecting the dynamical processes of real world systems. Because multiple regression models do not allow for assessing processes of structural changes or adaptation, the use of most multiple regression models is limited to the short-term precise forecasting of developments and the exploration of possible future developments in scenarios. Because multiple regression models do not capture real world dynamics, it can be said that multiple regression models constitute a heterologous metaphor of real world systems.

Optimisation

Models that involve the optimisation of behaviour are widely used in economics, as has been noted in Chapter 2. In this modelling approach, rational agents are assumed that have perfect foresight and that are maximising their discounted sum of utility of consumption. Hence, the question is one of how much to consume now, and how much to invest in capital goods to increase consumption later. Maximising such a single utility function over finite time reflects the supposed existence of a single generation, or even a single individual, which exists forever. Regarding the modelling of human behaviour, the general critique on using optimisation models is that real people do not always optimise their outcomes, but rather use more simple heuristics to manage their limited cognitive resources. Consequently, the optimisation approach does not deal with behavioural processes such as habit formation, imitation and social comparison. Gintis (1998) mentions four postulates on rational-actor behaviour and explains why this approach entails a limited description of human behaviour. First, the rational-actor approach postulates that people have outcome-regarding preferences, which apply to the quantity of goods and services that are produced, consumed and exchanged. However, people also have process-regarding preferences, which are related to the distribution of these goods and services (thinking about fairness, reciprocity).

Second, the rational-actor approach postulates that self-regarding preferences reflect the potential contribution of opportunities to the own level of need satisfaction. However, people are also other-regarding, deliberately performing behaviour to affect the wellbeing of other persons, which also relates to the concept of social value orientation

(see Chapter 2 on personal factors influencing behaviour in a dilemma). For example, rewarding and punishing other people may go against one's self-interest.

Third, the rational-actor approach postulates that the well-being of an individual depends on the degree to which his/her preferences are satisfied. However, often people perform behaviours that decrease their level of need satisfaction, for example, drug abuse and obsessive status seeking. Also people may change their preferences to obtain a higher level of need-satisfaction. This can be considered as changing one's perspective on what is perceived as satisfying.

Fourth, the rational-actor approach postulates that the preferences are exogenous, which implies that people's preferences are not determined and affected by economic policy and institutions. However, the preferences of people are often affected by their own experiences, by what other people do (e.g., high-status examples) and by other social forces such as advertisement (endogenous preferences).

Because the optimisation approach describes the principles of deliberate decision-making (outcome optimising), this approach can be considered as an unificational metaphor. The optimisation approach is also being used to explain non-outcome-optimising behaviours that save cognitive effort, such as habit formation, imitation and social comparison. These strategies are aimed at balancing the outcomes of the behaviour and the amount of cognitive processing. Optimisation often correctly describes the outcomes of such behaviour, provided that large groups of people are taken into consideration. However, the fact remains that the processes that guide the behaviour of real people differ from the rational actor being formalised in the model. As such, when applied to the non-outcome-maximising behaviours as mentioned above, the optimisation approach can be considered to be a heterologous metaphor. Many discussions between mainstream economists and psychologists who study behavioural processes originate from the use of different types of metaphors about human behaviour.

System Dynamics

In the system-dynamic modelling paradigm, processes of the real world are represented in terms of conglomerations of interacting feedback loops. Stocks of material and information and flows between these stocks are being modelled using non-linear equations and time-delays. This implies that a model gives a precise description of a system's behaviour, which can be compared with the behaviour of the real world system. An example is the use of Lotka-Volterra equations to simulate a predator-prey system (Lotka, 1925; Volterra, 1931). Lotka and Volterra independently developed the necessary manipulation of logistic equations that constitute one of the stock phrases of ecological modelling.

Many natural processes involve flows of materials, which can be adequately described using a system dynamic approach. This holds that the same mechanism underlies both the real world processes and the model, implying that the model constitutes an unificational metaphor. However, the (adaptive) processes that govern human behaviour (and many ecological systems involving behaving organisms) can not be captured fully in terms of stocks and flows. Therefore, behavioural (economic) models that are based on a system dynamical framework can be considered as heterologous metaphors. In many situations the behaviour of the real system can be mimicked quite well using a system dynamical model. However, because the laws and principles that lie behind

the real world and the simulated system differ, this type of simulations can hardly be used to test hypotheses regarding the laws and dynamics of the simulated system³.

Because system-dynamic models are very suitable for studying long-term system behaviour, this approach is frequently being used to model issues like population growth, biochemical cycles, economic processes, land-use and ecological systems. Moreover, in integrated assessment models, simple versions of such expert models are being integrated in a system-dynamic framework (see also Chapter 1 on Integrated models).

Despite the fact that more realistic simulations of e.g. fish stock systems may be available, many researchers prefer to use system dynamical simulations because they guarantee efficient programming and they offer a good experimenting tool to study e.g., the way in which people manage resources. In such experimenting tools the processes behind the simulation are not important for the research, as long as the output is mimicking the real world system in a convincing manner. Consequently, within such a 'mimicking context' simulations are being used as an experimental tool, not as an object of scientific study in themselves.

In the development of system dynamical models, usually much effort is spent on the development of a model structure that resembles the stocks and flows in the real world. Here, the multiple regression of empirical data can be helpful in validating the outcomes of system dynamical models. The estimation of parameter values in the model often gets less attention. This is partly due to the difficulty of formulating parameter values on the aggregated level of a model on the basis of disaggregated, not suitable or even missing data.

Important studies employing a system-dynamical modelling approach are the Club of Rome models of the early seventies (Forrester 1971; Meadows, Meadows, Randers and Behrens, 1972; Meadows, Behrens, Meadows, Naill, Randers, and Zahn, 1974). Some models include insights from psychology/cultural anthropology to include adaptive agents (Bossel and Strobel, 1978), although these more advanced descriptions of behaviour remain exceptions. Later integrated assessment models using a system-dynamic framework are IMAGE1 (Rotmans, 1990) and TARGETS (Rotmans and De Vries, 1997).

Stochastic simulation models

Due to the complexity of the real world, many processes are unpredictable, and hence uncertain. To capture this notion of uncertainty in simulation models, system dynamical models have been equipped with stochastic variables. Instead of using fixed values to describe certain relations in the model, events and/or parameter values are being formalised as probability distributions. These distributions are frequently based on empirical data or educated guesses from scientists. The introduction of a stochastic element in a simulation model implies that model-runs that start with identical initial settings may yield very different outcomes. Therefore, usually many runs are being performed, and means and reliability intervals are being reported.

Because a 'stochastic' is being used to model the unpredictability following from the complexity of real world systems, it can be said that the stochastic simulation approach is a heterologous metaphor. Instead of studying system characteristics, this modelling

³ However, this type of simulations may be useful to demonstrate the behaviour of a system, as is clearly demonstrated with e.g., the relation between predators and prey described by Lotka-Volterra equations.

approach is mostly fit to develop research tools as mentioned under system dynamic simulation models.

Agent-based models

Many macro-level processes that can be observed in social systems, such as crowding, over-harvesting and stock-market dynamics, emerge from the interactions between a multitude of individual agents. Here, an agent is being considered as a system that tries to fulfil a set of goals in a complex, dynamic environment, and 'agent' thus may refer to e.g., bacteria, plants, insects, fish, mammals, humans households, firms and nations. Agent-based modelling implies that agents are being formalised as making decisions on the basis of their own goals, the information they have about the environment and their expectations regarding the future. The goals, information and expectations an agent has are being affected by interactions with other agents. Usually, agents are adaptive, which implies that they are capable of changing their decision strategies and consequently their behaviour.

The multi-agent simulation approach allows formalising several interacting agents in a model, and thus provides a tool to study how processes at the micro-level may affect macro-level dynamics. Many multi-agent simulations have been developed, which are focussed on a variety of social processes (see e.g., Conte, Hegselmann and Terna, 1997). These simulations differ with respect to the level of detail in the agent rules. Many researchers apply very simple agent rules to study how macro-level behaviour emerges from very simple micro-level rules. An example is the 'Tit-for-Tat' rule (Axelrod, 1980a, 1980b) that is being used to study the emergence of cooperation in large-scale prisoners' dilemmas (see Chapter 4 for examples). Simulations using such simple agents are being used to formulate (mathematical) theories on social system behaviour. However, it is often questioned to what extent such theories are validly describing real-world processes, because they are based on agent rules that lack psychological validation. Yet, these theories are aimed at describing the basic micro-level processes that guide the macro-behaviour of real world systems, and consequently such models constitute a homologous metaphor.

If the simulated processes are not intended to resemble a real world process, the simulation forms a world in itself, and there is no metaphor at all. However, sometimes such simulations lie at the basis of the discovery of new laws that appear to be valid in both the simulated and real world systems. Phenomena that were observed in simulations as well as in the real world, e.g., swarms, self-organisation, emergent behaviour, then appear to be understandable from the same principle. Here, simulations of artificial societies that were not (directly) meant as metaphors for real world processes helped to discover laws and principles that hold both in real and in simulated worlds. Examples of such laws and principles are the importance of diversity (e.g., why is a 'rich' forest more viable in times of change), how lock-in effects work (e.g., how VHS video became the standard, why most people use Microsoft software) and the importance of contingency (e.g., small causes may breed large effects, and the fundamental unpredictability of complex systems). It is important to realise that these dynamics are not programmed explicitly in the simulation as laws or principles, but emerge from the simulations. Once such laws and principles have been identified, they often can be recognised in real world systems. With respect to the discovery of such 'laws of complex systems', the unificational metaphor adequately describes the relation between a simulation model and the real world

Researchers that develop more complex agents clearly consider their simulations as a metaphor, as their goal is to enhance the mundane realism and hence the practical relevance of their simulation models. Here, it is important that the rules of the agents are being modelled after valid theory or data, so as to obtain at least some valid resemblance with the behaviour of real world social systems. This usually results in a more complex set of agent rules. Ernst (1998), who employs theory on attitude formation in developing agent rules, provides a representative example of such a simulation. This example will be discussed in the next chapter. Here, the agent rules are carefully designed on the basis of valid behavioural theory. However, because of the lack of suitable meta-models of behaviour, many simulation models lack such a theory-based validation of agent rules. This causes many simulation models to lack ecological validity, which makes them less convincing tools for studying real world systems.

Conclusions

It appears that several modelling approaches exist, and that questioning the appropriateness of these approaches for developing a simulation model directly relates to the goals one has with simulation. In general it can be stated that if the purpose of a simulation model resides in the study of how people or agents interact with it, it is sufficient that the simulation model mimics the behaviour of the real world system, e.g. a fish-stock. The simpler the model, the better it is, as this makes the model easier to program and to work with. A researcher may prefer a system dynamical approach to simulate a fish stock as a tool to investigate people's harvesting behaviour, being aware of the fact that a multi-agent model would more correctly describe the dynamics of a real fish stock. However, if one is mainly interested in mimicking the natural fluctuations of a fish stock, it may even be the case that a simple equation-based model yields more realistic outcomes than a badly formalised multi-agent model. A more realistic modelling of the processes does not guarantee that the outcomes of the model are more realistic as well. However, if one intends to use simulation techniques to study the behavioural dynamics of a system, it is essential to choose a paradigm that is capable of capturing the processes of interest. For example, in modelling a macro-economic system it seems appropriate to use a system-dynamical modelling framework, whereas the modelling of processes that involve social interactions requires a multi-agent framework.

This monograph is focussing on human behaviour in changing environmental systems. Although the modelling approach will contain elements of all the above-mentioned paradigms, it will mainly be based on elements from agent-based modelling and system dynamics. Being focussed at the behavioural dynamics that affect the resource management of agents, it is necessary to use a multi-agent modelling approach to allow for the simulation of interdependent agents in a commons dilemma situation. Moreover, this multi-agent approach is also necessary to allow for the simulation of processes such as social comparison and imitation. The agents' behaviour will be studied in a changing environment. The agents' activities may change the environment, which in turn may change the abilities and opportunities of the agents. The system-dynamical approach will be used for the modelling of the environment the agents behave in. As such, the resulting integrated model combines modelling techniques originating from different paradigms.

Because the modelling of behaviour is the central issue of this monograph, the next section will be focussed at the tools that are being used in agent-based modelling.

Conceptual tools for agent-based modelling

The modelling of autonomous agents has become increasingly popular in the last decade. Along with this increase, also the variety of tools to model such agents by software (computer-programs) and hardware (robots) has increased. The tools that are currently being used in this field are neural networks, cellular automata, fuzzy logic, genetic algorithms, cybernetics, artificial intelligence and sets of non-linear differential equations (chaos and catastrophe theories). Within the scope of this monograph it is not possible to discuss all these tools in detail. Therefore, only the tools that are most common in social-scientific research are being discussed: genetic algorithms, cellular automata and artificial intelligence. Those readers interested to learn more about other kinds of modelling tools are referred to, e.g., Langton (1989; 1995), Holland (1995), Goldberg (1989), Rietman (1994) and Sigmund (1993).

Genetic Algorithms

In the sixties John Holland and colleagues developed the concept of genetic algorithms by means of trying to abstract and explain the adaptive processes of natural systems (e.g. Holland, 1975, 1992a, 1992b, 1995; Goldberg, 1989). The basic notion is to consider each agent in a population as a solution to a problem. Technically, a binary bit string of fixed length represents an agent. The sequence of 0s and 1s can be recoded into decimal numbers that represent a solution, for example, the value of a decision variable of a problem. The bit-string length depends on the number of possible solutions taken into consideration. The relative success of each agent to solve the problem is considered to be its fitness. A higher fitness increases the chances that the agent produces offspring that constitutes the next generation. This offspring (child) is identical to the parent agent, as graphically depicted in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: *Identical offspring*

This rule follows the principle of natural selection (survival of the fittest), and causes that an original population, consisting of many agents differing in abilities and fitness, will in a number of generations result in a much more homogeneous population. A major risk here is that when the circumstances change, it may be so that other abilities become important, and these may have been lost in the natural selection process. A homogeneous population lacks the adaptive capacities that are required to cope with changing environments. The identical offspring population lacks the necessary capacity to adapt.

To include adaptation, and to prevent a population to end up with a small set of unchangeable solutions, the mutation rule can be included. This rule implies that in the reproduction process each bit has a small chance of flipping, as is depicted in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: *Mutation*

The process of mutation can produce new genetic information and is a powerful operator in finding ways to adapt to a changing environment. Even if a homogeneous population exists, the mutation rule guarantees that new types of solutions will emerge, which, if their fitness is high, may be very successful in reproducing.

However, the mutation rule is working randomly, and is relative slow in finding successful solutions. A much faster strategy is provided by sexual reproduction, where the principle of crossing-over is being used to create new kinds of solutions. Here, the bit-string of two parent agents is being cut at a random point, which is the same for both parents, and the two fitting pieces are being pasted in the child, as is depicted in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Crossing-over

Combination of crossing-over and selective reproduction on the basis of fitness yields a powerful tool to find effective solutions in a very complex environment. However, to avoid the risk of ending up with a homogeneous population it remains necessary to include a small chance of mutation.

Examples of integrated models that employ the genetic algorithm tool are the work of Janssen and De Vries (1998a) and Janssen and Carpenter (1999), who developed a model for the climate change issue with agents that change their behaviour if their observations differ significantly from what they expect, and Janssen and Martens (1997) who assess the integrated impact of changes of climate and policy control on the malaria problem.

Cellular Automata

A cellular automaton consists of an array of cells in which each cell can assume one of a predefined number of discrete states at any one time. Figure 3.4 shows such a small checkerboard type of cellular automaton, in which the black automaton in the centre can only observe its eight direct neighbours (Moore environment), which are coloured grey. Each cell in the grid represents an agent.

Figure 3.4: A small cellular automaton consisting of 25 cells

When the checkerboard is formalised so that the edges are fixed, the world is a so-called island model. This kind of ‘world’ is very suitable to represent a physical environment such as a square or a region. When the checkerboard is formalised so that the edges are being pasted together (e.g., moving left from the left border brings you to the right border), the resulting world is a torus, as is being shown in Figure 3.5. The torus shape is very suitable for the study of more abstract systems, because possible disturbing effects caused by the fixed border can be ruled out.

Figure 3.5: A cellular automaton with the edges pasted (Hegselmann and Flache, 1998)

In a cellular automata-based simulation, time progresses in discrete steps, and all cells change state simultaneously. The changing (or not) of the cell state depends on the specific function underlying the cell state. Usually, this function consists of a specified set of transition rules that use historic information on the own state together with the states of the neighbouring cells (e.g. Gardner, 1970; Tobler, 1979). A famous example that uses very simple rules is the LIFE algorithm (Gardner, 1970). Consider a torus-like world. Each cell has eight neighbours, and a cell has only two states: empty or occupied. If a cell happens to be empty, it remains empty in the next generation (i.e. time-step), except if exactly three of its neighbouring cells are occupied: in that case, it will be occupied in the next generation. Conversely, if a cell happens to be occupied already, then it remains occupied whenever two or three of its neighbours are occupied. If not, the cell becomes empty in the next generation. This simple set of rules already leads to processes of self-reproduction and complex self-organising structures.

Applications of the cellular automata in the field of sustainable development involve more complex rules, and more possible states of the cells. The cellular automata tool is very suitable to model issues in which spatial relations play a role. Examples are the ISLAND model (Engelen *et al.*, 1995), which is a demonstration version of a framework capable of modelling a complete island or part of a coastal zone in an explicitly dynamic and spatial manner, and Sugarscape (Epstein and Axtell, 1996), which will be discussed in Chapter 4.

Artificial Intelligence

Currently, the autonomous agents research or behaviour-based artificial intelligence (AI) dominates the study of Artificial Intelligence. This approach, which is highly inspired by biology (e.g., Wilson, 1991), studies the behaviour of adaptive autonomous agents in the physical world (robots) or in cyberspace (software agents). The phenomena of interest are those traditionally covered by biology and ecology (in the case of plants and animals) or

psychology, sociology and ethnology (in the case of humans). The agents are usually equipped with sensors to perceive the environment (e.g., constructing a map of the environment). In order to behave efficiently, the agents are equipped with intelligent functions such as perception, planning, and learning. This approach is usually being used to study the dynamics following from the interaction between agents and environment. Here, researchers have a powerful tool to experiment with a wide variety of characteristics and processes of both the agents and the environment.

The use of several interacting agents is a recent development within the study of artificial intelligence (Bond and Gasser, 1988). For an overview of this field see for example Steels (1995) and Maes (1995). Research employing such a 'distributed artificial intelligence' approach is focussing on the properties of sets of communicating agents existing in a common environment. This research pursues different goals. First, it may be aimed at studying the properties of such systems in an abstract way. An example is the work of Steels (1995, see also Chapter 4), who studies emergent behaviour in a group of electric-powered robots that 'live' together in a physical environment and that have to cooperate every now and then in order to reload energy. A second aim is to design systems of immediate practical use, such as expert systems or training simulations for the management of complex environments. An example is the Driving Simulator of the Centre for Environment and Traffic Psychology (Van Wolffelaar and Van Winsum, 1996, see also Chapter 4), which contains a traffic system consisting of a multitude of interacting cars. A third aim is the development of a programmed multi-agent system as a model of a human or other real-world system. This third aim is the central aim of the model that is being developed and applied in this dissertation.

The aims that one has with a simulation model also confront the researcher with the application of the model. Sometimes very sophisticated models are being built, but hardly being used because the researchers did not deliberate much on the use of the model. The next section is focussed on the use of simulation models.

The application of models

Simulation models are frequently being used in a passive way, presenting only the results of experiments performed with the model. Regarding the application of a model on a well-defined topic this may be a good strategy. Here, presenting a series of experiments leading to a set of clear conclusions may be a good strategy to make a convincing point. However, when the simulation models are being used as a common language to exchange knowledge from different disciplines, it is usually better to use models in a more active manner, letting people experiment with the settings of the model themselves. Especially when the topic of research involves a complex system, which implies that the predictive value of a model is very low, people who experience the system dynamics will yield a better understanding of the model than people who more passively read about a series of experiments. Therefore, gaming and policy exercises are being developed and used to communicate the knowledge of the researchers on the processes which they put into the model. This requires the models to be relatively simple.

Policy exercises have the goal to let people experience the problem in a virtual world, thereby offering a situation to learn about the complexities that determine the developments in the real world system. In a simulation game like Fishbanks (Meadows,

1989) the different interdependent players in the game make decisions about fishing strategies (how many boats and of what type) and the computer computes the fish catch. Therefore, a computer model represents the environment of the players, and the players have only limited control over the state of the environment. Another game is SusClima (De Vries, 1998) where different players representing governments control two or more countries. Climate change may occur as a consequence of their decisions. The countries have to negotiate what kind of control strategy to implement. Here, the players are confronted with a commons dilemma, in which the consequences of their behaviour refer to climate change in a computer simulation model of the world climate. Another interactive model in the climate change debate is the Interactive Scenario Scanner developed by Berk and Janssen (1997). They built a very simple model around the key issues of the climate change negotiations and held interactive sessions with policy makers where the software functions as a communication tool to facilitate discussion.

Another way of interactively using computer models is the use of microworlds to study how people achieve control over some aspects of a complex system (Brehmer, 1992; Brehmer and Dörner, 1993; Dörner and Schaub, 1994). The computer simulations provide interactive and dynamic scenarios of complex problems that allow for repeated and detailed observations. These simulation models of real world systems condense time such that the participants are being confronted with the long-term effects of their decisions. Consequently, the players have to cope with the emotional strains of failures and have to adjust their strategies. This kind of studies performed by applied psychologists may help to discover systematic mistakes and biases that affect human decision-making in complex situations.

The simulation model of human behaviour that is being developed and tested in this monograph is being presented in a rather passive way. A large number of experiments have been performed with the simulation model, and the results are presented in graphs and tables. When it comes to validation of the simulation model this presentation has some advantages, as it is possible to systematically present results in comparison to other experiments that have been performed. However, when the behavioural model is being applied in the context of an integrated assessment model, it would be worthwhile to let various scientists and policy makers work with the model. This would provide them with more knowledge regarding the behavioural dynamics behind environmental issues. Moreover, it would confront them with outcomes that are relevant in the context of human existence, such as level of need satisfaction and (in)equality, instead of focussing at macro-level indicators of economy and ecology.

Chapter 4 will provide an overview of a number of representative simulation models that are being used within psychology.

4

Simulation models in the social sciences

Introduction

This chapter is aimed at providing an overview of the role that simulation models play in the social sciences. Following a short history of simulation in the social sciences, we will discuss a number of typical simulation models. First, some simulations of real world systems excluding human behaviour are being discussed. Second, a number of simulations of behaviour in the context of social dilemmas are being discussed. Finally, a number of multi-agents simulations are being discussed that are aimed at simulating human behaviour in complex environments.

Simulation is a young and rapidly growing field in the social sciences (cf. Axelrod, 1997, pp. 21). The development of simulation models originates from the field of mathematics. Only in the last ten years a rapid growth can be witnessed in the field of psychology. The growth in computer processing speed was one of the important conditions that facilitated this. Overviews of this new and rapidly developing area can be found in Vallacher and Nowak (1994), Doran and Gilbert (1994), Gilbert and Conte (1995), Conte, Hegselmann and Terna (1997) and Gilbert and Troitzsch (1999). Many scientists and/or computer programmers, have been, and still are, fascinated by the possibilities computers offer for modelling some part of the world. Computerised models make it possible to simulate the behaviour of part of a real word system (i.e., the target system). The aims one has with a particular simulation model usually determine which characteristics of a real-world system are being formalised. Consequently, it is possible to develop various models that all describe different aspects of the same target system. As Doran and Gilbert (1994, p. 6) state:

'It is usually possible to classify this multitude of models in various ways. Some models will be relatively concrete, some abstract. Some will be much more complex than others, and different models will relate to different aspects of the target system. For example, we may have a very simple and abstract or a very complex and detailed model of an eagle; and one model may concentrate upon the eagle's ability to fly, while another may focus on its digestive tract.'

Consequently, the applicability of any model depends on the relation between the purpose one has with the model and the characteristics of the real-world system that are (not) included in the model. As such, a given simulation model may be applicable for one purpose, whilst being inappropriate for another purpose, as has been discussed in Chapter 3 on simulated fish-stock exploitation. Axelrod (1997, pp. 23-24) identifies seven purposes simulations can be used for: 1: prediction (e.g., weather forecasting), 2: performance (e.g., medical diagnosis), 3: training (e.g., flight simulators), 4: entertainment (e.g., flight simulators, SimCity2000), 5: education (e.g., simulations of medical interventions), 6: proof (e.g., proof of the thesis that 'complex behaviour results from simple rules'), and 7: discovery (e.g. of new principles and relationships).

Within the social sciences, many simulation models have been developed in more recent years. As the social sciences cover a broad array of topics, a multitude of very differing models has been developed, ranging from abstract game-theoretical simulations

to simulations of micro-worlds. However, a clear community of social scientists using computer simulations does not exist yet⁴. Axelrod (1997) illustrates this with his observation that publications are scattered over various journals, which are often not primarily social scientific journals. The purposes of these simulations however are quite uniform: prediction of developments, proof of principles and discovery of effects. In this chapter, some contemporary examples of simulations pertaining to social science problems will be discussed. For a more extensive listing and information, the reader is referred to Brehmer and Dörner (1993), Garson (1994), Gilbert and Doran (1994), Gilbert and Conte (1995) and Conte *et al.* (1997). This chapter will end with a discussion on the use of existing behavioural theories in the development of algorithms for the simulation of social systems. But first, a short history of simulation in the social sciences will be sketched.

A short history of simulation in the social sciences

In the beginning of computing, when the first programming languages became available, some social scientists had large expectations about the possibilities of capturing behavioural processes in computer models. For example, Newell, Shaw and Simon (1958) postulated a theory of human problem solving that resembled a computer programme. Their theory consisted of three parts: (1) a control system consisting of a number of *memories*, (2) a number of *primitive information processes* which operated on the information in the memories, and (3) a perfect definite set of rules for combining the processes into whole *programs* of processing. Newell *et al.* (1958) state that at this level of theorising, the observed behaviour of an organism is explained by a program of primitive information processes that generates this behaviour. Their article ends with the optimistic conclusion that *'the vaguenesses that have plagued the theory of higher mental processes and other parts of psychology disappear when the phenomena are described as programs'* (Newell *et al.*, 1958, pp. 166).

Hovland (1960) made a comparison between humans and computers with respect to solving theorems in Euclidean geometry, and concluded that these problems were solved in an analogous manner. Hovland (1960) further elaborated on future possibilities with respect to learning computers. He suggested that it would be possible to program a computer for 'reading' slides with cancer cells and to identify them as malignant or non-malignant. Hovland suggested that the use of larger sets of object characteristics would enable computers to determine the species of, e.g., a flower just by reading a picture. With respect to psychology, Hovland (1960, pp. 692) states that *'Computer methodology may make possible a broadening of our understanding of behavior by emphasizing the simulation of single individuals and then studying variations between them. The integration of these complementary approaches in new computer work will help us to reduce the gap between group averages and individual processes'*.

The large expectations in the beginning of the sixties stimulated a lot of researchers to experiment with the simulation of social behaviour. Besides Newell *et al.* (1958) and Hovland (1960), Abelson (1968) mentions several other researchers who developed simulation programmes. Colby, Watt and Gilbert (1966) worked on simulating a neurotic belief system and on a simulated interviewer ('doctor') that could 'talk' with the 'patient'.

⁴ However, a social scientific community is emerging in this field, as is indicated by e.g. the First International Conference on Computer Simulation and the Social Sciences (Cortona Italy, 1997) and the start of The Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation (<http://www.soc.surrey.ac.uk/JASSS/JASSS.html>).

These programs aimed to simulate a particular single individual, in contrast to e.g., the Elementary Perception and Memory (EPAM) simulation (Feigenbaum and Simon, 1963), which was aimed at simulating unspecified or average individual behaviour. Cohen (1963) tried to model social influence within the Asch paradigm. McWhinney (1964) tried to simulate information exchange in small groups. Hägerstrand (1965) tried to simulate the innovation diffusion among farmers with a spatially oriented model. Coleman (1965) modelled teenage smoking as depending on the smoking habits of friends and the choice of friends. Raino (1965) used a stochastic theory of social interaction to simulate and study sociometric group structure. Abelson and Bernstein (1963) simulated the change of opinions on fluoridation in a community. For a discussion of the social science simulations developed in the sixties the reader is referred to Abelson (1968) and Nowak, Szamrej and Latané (1990).

Despite the large expectations that arose in the sixties, the use of computer simulations would not flourish in the social and behavioural sciences. Nowak *et al.* (1990, pp. 371) suggested that this occurred *'perhaps as a result of the ad hoc quality of many of the assumptions in the models, perhaps because of dissatisfaction with the plausibility of their outcomes despite their dependence on extensive parameter estimation, or perhaps because they were introduced at a time when computers were still cumbersome and slow and programming time-consuming and expensive'*. As a result, the interest in computer simulations vanished. The decline lasted for a quarter of a century, while computing power increased and faster personal computers conquered the desks of many scientists. Then the development and use of computer simulations really started to flourish. Garson's (1994) inventory of simulation programmes in the social sciences clearly shows that in the 80's this discipline became productive, and in the 90's, where desk computing power nearly exploded and graphical interfaces strongly improved, this productivity showed an exponential growth. Currently one can witness an enormous growth in the number of scientists who have (re)discovered simulation as a tool to study various social processes.

Within the scope of this monograph it is impossible to provide an inventory covering a wide range of simulation programmes. Therefore, several representative simulation programs will be presented to illustrate the principles of simulation and to show how these models are used within the behavioural sciences.

Looking at the many simulation programs that exist in the social sciences, one can make a distinction between three types of simulations. First, many simulations have been developed aiming to describe a certain real-world system (e.g. Meadows, 1989; Strohschneider, 1991; Haslam & Wright, 1993). Usually, these simulations are being used as a tool to study the behaviour of real people interacting with or managing such a simulated system. Within this category fall the simulations of more complex resources (e.g., fish-stocks), used to experiment with the decision-making of real people in a commons dilemma. In some cases, such simulations also describe changes in human factors, such as population growth and employment. However, in most cases this does not imply that several active agents are being formalised, but rather that some passive dependent variables inform the model user about supposed developments regarding human behaviour.

Second, many simulations are being focused at the decision rules of actively behaving simulated agents (e.g., Axelrod, 1980a, 1980b; Conte, 1996; Macy, 1996). Logically, these agents are being confronted with an environment they 'live in', but the focus is at the experimentation with behavioural strategies of agents. This type of

simulations typically employs multi-agent simulation as a modelling tool, because this allows for studying the behavioural dynamics following from interactions between agents. Within this category fall the simulations of agents in a repeated prisoners' dilemma.

Third, a number of simulations is primarily directed at studying the interactions between the behaviour of many agents and an environmental system (e.g., Epstein and Axtell, 1996; Steels, 1995; Ernst, 1998). These simulations combine a multi-agent approach with the simulation of a real world system.

In the following sections several simulations will be presented and discussed that fit within the three categories sketched above. First, some real-world system simulations are being presented, some of which are being applied in the study of human behaviour in commons dilemmas. Following that, a separate section is describing some representative multi-agent simulations of behaviour. These refer to multi-agent simulations of social dilemmas. A subsequent section is being devoted to simulations of behaviour in more complex simulated environments. Recapitulating on the previous sections, a final section is discussing the use of multi-agent techniques for simulating environmentally relevant behaviour.

Simulating real-world systems

Many systems, such as the immune system, food chains and the economy, change and reorganise their component parts to adapt to their ever changing environments (Holland, 1992). This also holds for many issues involving the management of natural resources. Such systems can be conceived as 'moving targets', because they are constantly changing without reaching an equilibrium. Consequently, they are difficult to understand and to control. Despite the fact that these systems at first glance appear to have no common characteristics, the mechanisms that underlie them are similar with respect to three characteristics: evolution, aggregate behaviour and anticipation. Evolution refers to the adaptation of systems to changing environments. Aggregate behaviour refers to the emergence of overall system behaviour from the behaviour of its component parts. Anticipation refers to the expectations the agents involved have regarding future outcomes. Systems that have these three characteristics can be grouped under the name of *complex adaptive systems* (Holland, 1992; Trisoglio, 1995). Theories of complex adaptive systems confront us with our fundamental limits to understand, control and manage social behaviour, and they force us to deal with unpredictability.

Many simulation models describe some real world system, for example a town, fisheries or a tribal society in a relative simple manner. In the simulation of what is called a *microworld* (Brehmer and Dörner, 1993) a limited set of variables and relations (feedbacks) between those variables is being formalised. However, despite their simplicity, such a microworld may demonstrate unpredictable behaviour because of its structural complexity. A limited number of variables, interacting with each other following certain rules and feedbacks involving delays, may yield system behaviour that is very difficult to understand without knowing the rules. Even if one knows the rules, it may take some time experimenting with the system to learn about the dynamics of the systems' behaviour. The more realistic (i.e., often complex) the dynamics captured in a simulation, the more difficult it becomes to understand the behaviour of the microworld its reactions to (human

induced) changes. Such simulations can therefore be understood as describing a complex adaptive system.

Because in simulated microworlds the variables and their relations are known, at least to the researcher, the complexity of the relevant situations is better known than that of real world systems. Ideally, the relations as formalised in the microworld are based upon empirical data, so as to guarantee a maximal ecological validity of the microworld. A major advantage of such simulations is that one can simulate a period of years in just a couple of minutes, and thus may study the long-term effects of behaviour in a relatively short period of time.

Just like in real-world systems, the behaviour of a microworld partly depends on how people interact with it, for example because of their perception (cognitive representation) of the microworld⁵. People thus can behave in a self-regulative manner, just like in field settings. Comparing the actual system with the system as perceived by decision-makers allows for studying how (mis)representations of the system develop in time and what the consequences are for the system's behaviour and decision-making process.

The development of microworlds thus yields a tool that allows for the experimental study of how people behave (manage) in ecologically valid situations, allowing for causal interpretations that are hard to obtain in field research. As such, the use of microworlds in research may bridge the gap between laboratory and field studies in psychology (Brehmer and Dörner, 1993).

Simulating resource dilemmas

The experimental games that have been discussed in Chapter 2 can be regarded as very simple simulations (representations) of real-world resource systems. As concluded by a.o. Nemeth (1972) and Pruitt and Kimmel (1977), these games do not bear any mundane validity, which makes it questionable to translate experimental results to real-life resource dilemmas. Since then, more attention has been given to translating the properties of real-world dilemmas into experimental games (e.g., Messick and Brewer, 1983).

The introduction of the resource dilemma paradigm yielded an important increase in the mundane realism of experimental games (e.g., Jerdee and Rosen, 1974; Rubenstein *et al.*, 1975; Brechner, 1977, see also Chapter 2 on research traditions in the study of the commons dilemma). The introduction of a collective resource allowed for playing sequential games in which the subjects had a multiple choice in deciding how much to harvest. The simplest system consists of a resource that is being exploited by a number of persons. Each time-step or round of the experiment, the common resource grows with a certain number of units. However, each round of the experiment the participants may take a number of units out of the resource. Making the growth-rate of the resource dependent on the number of units available in the previous round signifies the social dilemma: each person has the choice of harvesting as much as possible now, at the risk of over-exploiting the resource, resulting in a decrease or even a collapse in future harvesting opportunities. A sustainable use of this renewable resource requires that one restricts the number of units taken per round. This may lead towards a larger outcome in the long run, as one may harvest resource units for a long time.

⁵ A consequence is that, unlike in most 'classical' laboratory settings, no clearcut distinction between dependent and independent variables can be made.

Many researchers employed simulations that explicitly deal with the management of such a limited resource (e.g., Kramer, McClintock and Messick, 1996; Birjulin, Smith and Bell, 1993; Samuelson *et al.*, 1984; see also Messick and Brewer, 1983). However, the resources containing abstract ‘units’ or ‘points’ hardly resemble real-world systems. To enhance the realism of these experiments, the units were, for example, translated into fish (e.g., Mosler, 1993). Hence, the above-described abstract resource-game was translated into a sea with a stock of fish, where the persons playing the game could consider themselves as fishermen. The realism is captured in the easy to understand notion that if the fish-stock is low due to over-fishing, the players should restraint from harvesting for a considerable time before the fish-stock has grown to match its original size. Moreover, over-fishing eventually may lead towards extinction of the fish. Despite the fact that the introduction of the noun ‘fish’ increased the psychological realism of the resource, the resource dynamics were still far from realistic, causing the system behaviour to be incorrect (e.g., incorrect growth dynamics).

The increasing computing power allowed for the development of more elaborated fish-stock simulations, e.g. Fish-Banks (Meadows, 1989) and FISH (Gifford and Wells, 1991).

Fish-banks

Fish-banks (Meadows, 1989) can be considered as a game in which teams of people run fishing companies aiming to maximise their assets. To do so, they can negotiate with other companies and seek out and make strategic use of available information. The computer program calculates all their financial transactions and tracks the status of the fish population, based on fish catch, births, and deaths. The players have to decide how much to catch and invest in new boats on the basis of their perception of the fish-stock, the assets of their firm and their expectations (trust) regarding the behaviour of the other firms. The players thus deal with ecological, economic, and psychological forces in managing their fishing company and negotiating with the other firms. Fish-banks is a simulation model that is typically being used for educational purposes, by letting people experience the complexities associated with managing renewable resources.

FISH

FISH (Gifford and Wells, 1991) is a resource game that includes aspects such as the initial fish-stock (pool size), number of seasons (trials), probability of harvest (catching a fish), various income and cost variables, degree of certainty about the size of the fish-stock, spawning (regeneration) rate, length of the time permitted for a cast and the amount of off-season time required for spawning (Hine and Gifford, 1996). This yields a fine instrument for studying the effects of various system properties on individual harvesting behaviour. For example, Hine and Gifford (1996) used this simulation model to study how environmental uncertainty affects harvesting behaviour.

Despite the appeal and mundane realism Fish-banks and FISH, the fish-system as used in such simulations does not employ actual data on fisheries. Hence, they do not capture the real-world dynamics of fish populations (Summers, 1996). The fast developments in computing power allowed scientists working on ecological models to develop running simulations of complex ecological systems. Introducing such ecologically validated simulation models in the study of resource management broadens the scope of possible

research topics. Whereas in the previous simulations the behaviour of man was the prime object of study, the introduction of ecological simulations allows for studying the interactions between man and ecology. Here, research questions address the relation between e.g., management strategies and ecological developments. Simulation models that employ a more realistic modelling of this 'fishing-dilemma' are for example 'Individual Choice and Social Effects' (Summers, 1996), and the fish-simulation of Moxnes (1998), as discussed below.

'Individual Choice and Social Effects'

Summers (1996) uses the Atlantic fisheries to look at conflicts between immediate need satisfaction and long-term sustainability. Thirty years of government statistics on fisheries supply the 'Individual Choice and Social Effects' model with the necessary empirical data. To further increase mundane realism, Summers developed a multi-media interface, presenting on-screen movies, moving graphs of results, still photos, cartoon animations and audio instructions. The variables in his simulation include fish-stocks, replenishment rate, average household expenses, value per ton of fish, amount of fishing per year, number of competing fishermen (up to 30.500) and their harvesting strategies, actual fish-catch per year, yearly income and the levels of harvesting that would maintain a sustainable level of the fish resource. The player himself may specify the decision strategy for the competitors. Four different strategies are being formalised for the competitors, namely maximising, discounting (a non-linear strategy, where short-term interests are disproportionately valued), maximimum take (maximising the minimum harvest, which is still a sustainable strategy) and Tit-for-Tat (do what the other player did in the previous time-step). All the competitors behave the same, and react only on the behaviour of the player. Consequently, the number of competitors constitutes a multiplying factor representing the pressure on the fish-stock. Because this involves that all fishermen are being represented in a single 'meta-actor', the competing fishermen cannot interact with one another, as would be the case in a multi-agent model. The goals of this simulation tool are twofold. First, it offers an opportunity to collect data on decision-making in commons dilemmas. Second, it may be used for public/educational presentations to demonstrate the character of complex commons dilemmas.

The cod simulation of Moxnes

Moxnes (1998) confronted experienced fishermen with a virgin fish-stock of simulated cod, and allowed them to fish for 20 virtual years. The cod-model was being developed followed a standard cohort-model with fixed mortality, and non-linear recruitment (young fish). The fishermen had information on the economic situation (e.g., revenue, operating costs, interest) and on the fish (catch, estimated maximum catch and estimated stock size). Using this information the fishermen had to decide on investments in and utilisation of the fleet. Moxnes calculated an optimal resource level that would yield the highest outcome level for the fishermen. The fishermen were given exclusive rights on the fish-stock (no competitors), thereby avoiding the commons problem. However, the fishermen over-invested 60% in fishing capacity, leading towards a resource size of 15% below the optimal level. This experiment demonstrated that it is not only the commons structure that leads to over-harvesting, but also the misperception of feedback from the ecological system.

Besides simulated fishing, which forms a natural clear-cut example of a social dilemma, also other natural systems have been captured into simulations. MORO (Strohschneider, 1991; 1994a; 1994b) provides a beautiful example of a simulation of a complex system that is being used to investigate human management behaviour.

MORO

MORO (Strohschneider, 1991; 1994a; 1994b) entails a simple system consisting of a tribe of semi-nomads living in a natural system. The system comprises variables such as population, amount of cattle, groundwater level, number of tse-tse flies and number of pastures. The tribe is being formalised as a single meta-actor, and hence the model does not comprise interactions between tribe members. People who are playing with MORO have the task to manage this system, maintaining good living conditions for the Moros. To do so, they may effectuate different policy measures, such as setting up a field hospital, spraying insecticides, and sinking water-wells. The resulting dynamics are often hard to forecast by players. For example, to decrease famine, people may want to cultivate more pastureland, and therefore decide to sink water-wells. Whereas this results in an increase of living conditions in the short term, in the long run the groundwater level decreases and the pastureland becomes unusable, thus leading to a more severe famine than in the situation where no water-wells were situated. MORO is being used as a tool to study the choice behaviour of real people managing such a system⁶. Strohschneider's (1994a) main results indicate that non-analytical, short-term oriented troubleshooting behaviour is very typical for human planning in such systems.

Whereas MORO represents simulations of relatively limited complex systems, other programmers made efforts to model more extended complex systems. An example of such a simulation is SimCity2000, which is aimed at simulating the management of a city.

SimCity 2000

In SimCity 2000 (Haslam and Wright, 1993) the player is in the position of a mayor of a town. Simulated citizens, the so-called 'Sims', inhabit the town. If your town provides good living conditions for the Sims, their population will grow and they will build homes, stores and working places. If, however, the living conditions are poor, the Sims will leave town. It is possible to start with existing scenario cities, but it is also possible to build your own city, ranging from a small rural town up to a huge metropolis. As a mayor the player is responsible for planning (zoning, long- and short-range strategies), the city infrastructure (water, power, transportation), government services (police, fire brigade, hospitals, prisons), education (schools, colleges, libraries and museums), recreational facilities and open spaces (parks, zoos, stadiums, marinas), the city budget and taxes, land manipulation and the health, wealth and happiness of the Sims in the city. Most actions of the mayor, e.g., constructing a power plant, cost money. To raise this money, you may impose taxes on the Sims and their enterprises. A good infrastructure is important for the living

⁶ However, simulations of this type can also be used for training purposes. An example is Code Red (United States Fire Administration, 1985), which simulates a forest area with occasional fires. This simulation model is being used to train employees of the U.S. Fire Administration on budgetary, regulatory and zoning decisions. Another example of a (road) environmental simulation that is also being used for training purposes is the Driving Simulator of the Centre for Environmental and Traffic Psychology, which will be discussed later in this chapter.

conditions of the Sims and the development of the town. However, raising the taxes to develop and maintain the infrastructure may impose too heavy a burden on the Sims and their businesses, which results in decreasing living conditions and Sims leaving town. The toughest challenge is thus to maintain a huge city without sacrificing your Sims' quality of life, without going broke maintaining the infrastructure, and without raising taxes so high that businesses relocate (Haslam and Wright, 1993, pp. 2).

Whereas SimCity 2000 offers a great tool for playing with infrastructural planning, the behaviour of the Sims is modelled in a rather simple way. The Sims are not modelled individually, but like in MORO they are represented by a single 'macro-actor'. In a 'population window' the player can get information on the number of people and the age-distribution, their health and their educational level. Moreover, it is possible to get spatial information on population density and population changes. However, SimCity 2000 does not involve social interactions between the Sims, because it does not employ the multi-agent approach to model such interactions. Consequently, SimCity 2000 is not equipped to simulate changes in behaviour and the effects of various policy measures that address behaviour. Policy is limited to infrastructural changes and taxes. As such, it can be concluded that SimCity 2000 offers a rather technocratic vision on the development and management (government) of cities. Currently, in SimCity 2000 certain (parts of) cities existing in the real world have been modelled, and users can implement various plans, e.g., where to plan a new residential area, to test their functionality. Regarding infrastructural planning this seems to be a useful application of SimCity 2000 because it confronts the planner in a systematic way with the many pro's and con's of several infrastructural planning decisions

Comments on the simulation of real-world systems

Several simulations of real-world systems can and are being used as tools to study how real people manage such systems. If a renewable resource is simulated in an ecologically valid way, it is possible to study the behaviour of real people in a realistic yet controllable situation. Especially in comparison to experiments where subjects are being confronted with abstract resources, these real world system simulations add mundane realism to the experimental game paradigm. Consequently, they add to our understanding of how people manage such systems, and what factors affect people's harvesting strategies.

Two limitations can be identified in the models that have previously been discussed. First, the fact remains that no matter how realistic the real-world system is being modelled, only a few persons are performing the management task in an experimental setting, and the outcomes of the simulations do not significantly affect their lives. Second, many real-world systems, especially environmental-economic systems, involve the behaviour of many people. Here, the management task involves the interaction between human behaviour and the environmental system instead of the environmental system alone. Strategies that are aimed at changing behaviour play a crucial role in this management task. Therefore, to resolve these limitations, it is necessary to include relevant behavioural processes in the simulation of real-world systems. Such simulations should, for example, reveal the behavioural dynamics that underlie resource depletion, and offer a tool to experiment with measures aimed at changing behaviour.

Above, both MORO and SimCity2000 were discussed as simulation programmes of real-world systems. Yet it was mentioned that these simulations included the behaviour of people (a tribe and the 'Sims' respectively). Because both MORO and SimCity2000 use

a single macro-actor in calculating the ‘state of the population’, these simulations do not simulate actual behaviour but only calculate behavioural outcomes at the macro-level. Therefore, these two simulation models are not being discussed under the topic of ‘simulations of behaviour’. Being mainly aimed at mimicking behavioural outcomes instead of simulating the behavioural dynamics that lead towards those outcomes, these formalisations of behaviour constitute heterologous metaphors. The behavioural parts in these models yield macro-level outcomes that bear some resemblance with the real-world outcomes, but they have no valid resemblance with the actual micro-level behavioural processes that generate these macro-level outcomes. That this approach can be very appealing is demonstrated by SimCity2000, which suggests very convincingly that thousands of Sims are actually living in an artificially created town.

However, to study processes of behaviour such as interacting, learning and adaptation, it is necessary to formalise humans as interacting individual agents. This requires the validation of agent-rules at the micro-level, translating empirically validated psychological laws into simulated agents, thus constituting an unificational metaphor. To simulate processes of interaction, it is necessary to let at least two simulated agents interact, thus using a multi-agent simulation approach. In the next section, some representative examples of multi-agent simulations originating from social dilemma research will be discussed.

The simulation of behaviour in social dilemmas

A main research field on human interdependency is that of social dilemmas (see Chapter 2). The social dilemma paradigm, originating from game theory, refers to situations where individual and collective rationality collide. These situations may range from two persons interacting a single time to the management of natural resources such as fish-grounds and forests. The commons dilemma, typically involving many people interacting repeatedly can be considered to be a special type of social dilemma.

Liebrand and Messick (1996a, pp. 215) state that the research field of social dilemmas is ‘characterised by an abundance of simple-main and lower-order interaction effects.’ Many factors that determine if an actor is more likely to cooperate or to defect have been studied in relative isolated settings. For example, (1) laboratory experiments revealed that decreasing the incentive for defective behaviour and/or increasing the incentive for cooperative behaviour stimulates cooperative behaviour (Kelley and Grzelak, 1972), (2) people tend to cooperate more often in smaller groups than in larger groups (e.g., Fox and Guyer, 1977), and (3) cooperation is promoted when actors believe they can be punished for defecting or rewarded for their cooperative behaviour (Komorita and Barth, 1985; Komorita, 1987).

To derive a systematic picture of how these three factors interact would require a lot of experimenting with real people. And of course, many more factors could be included in such experiments. Therefore, it is understandable that a theoretical model that describes the dynamics between individual decision-making and the characteristics of a social group is still lacking. However, such a theoretical model is necessary in order to reflect and improve our understanding of: (1) the rules that people apply in social dilemma situations, (2) how the combination of (different or similar) individual rules leads towards certain outcomes at the collective level, and (3) to understand how these individual rules

are apt to change as a result of a changing situation (interactions between the micro- and macro-level).

Experiments that would provide insights in such dynamics require that the decision strategies or rules that the actors use are (1) exactly known and (2) consistently used. It seems obvious that these requirements cannot be fulfilled using real people as research subjects. Yet these requirements are important, because only if the decision strategy of each actor is precisely known and stable, the possibility arises to systematically investigate the dynamics between individual decision-making and collective behaviour. Moreover, because a slightly different starting situation, e.g., one actor being a bit more cooperative, may result in very different outcomes, a lot of experiments would have to be conducted in order to identify the relevant dynamics. It would be worthwhile to be able to control for the starting situation. Finally, because some dynamics may be recognised only after many time-steps (e.g., the occurrence of an equilibrium or steady state), it would be necessary to use experimental designs with many time-steps. All these requirements make it clear that experimenting with the behaviour of real people is very hard if not unattainable.

Multi-agent computer simulations provide a methodology that allows for studying such processes using simple agents as heterologous metaphors of real human beings. Here an agent is formalised as an 'automaton' consisting of clearly defined rules. The agents can interact and are interdependent regarding the outcomes of their individual behaviours. Consequently, outcomes arise that shed light on the relevant micro-macro dynamics of systems. The main advantages of this computer simulation approach are: (1) the agent decision rules can be defined beforehand, resulting in perfect knowledge regarding the decision strategies of each agent, (2) many (slightly) different or exactly similar simulations can be run in a relatively short period of time, and (3) simulations involving many time-steps can be run in a relatively short period of time.

Three types of simulation tools are being applied in multi-agent simulations of social dilemmas: (1) the cellular automata approach, (2) social network approaches and (3) neural network approaches (Liebrand and Messick, 1996b). Here, the approaches mentioned under 2 and 3 are considered to be subcategories of artificial intelligence (see Chapter 3 on tools for agent-based modelling). Each of the three types of simulation is shortly explained, and one or more representative examples are briefly described.

Cellular Automata

A cellular automaton can be conceived as an abstract machine with a set of rules. These rules define what action the machine takes (e.g., cooperate or defect) given its current state. This state (e.g., a certain energy level) can be visualised by means of a particular colour (e.g., green is high in energy, red is low). The machine can exist in only one state at the time, and there are a limited number of possible states. In simulation experiments a group of such machines are spatially positioned in a matrix (checkerboard) constituting a 'virtual world'. Every time-step results in a new state, depending on the previous state and the state of the neighbouring machines. The 'natural laws' in this universe are the rules which describe the conditions for a change of state.

A major factor determining the behaviour of real people in social dilemmas is the (defective or cooperative) behaviour of the other players. This factor is easy to translate in terms of simple rules or strategies for a machine. For example, one could design rules like 'if more than half of the neighbouring cells cooperated in the previous time-step, then cooperate in the next time-step'. Liebrand and Van Lange (1996a) used such a cellular

automata approach in simulating a repeated prisoners' dilemma. In their simulations the automaton 'decides' to defect or to cooperate on the basis of previous outcomes of self and the neighbouring automata. Using this simulation technique, they formalised automata with different decision heuristics, such as Win-Stay, Lose-Change (WSLC) and Win-Cooperate, Lose-Defect (WCLD). Using these automata in their simulations, they studied the effects of group size on cooperation level, clustering, accumulated payoffs, initial dependence and the speed of achieving a stable level of cooperation. The simulation experiments revealed that when a large group of agents is caught in a prisoners' dilemma, and they use a competitive type of social comparison for the evaluation of their outcomes, cooperation may end up being the stable dominating strategy (Liebrand and Van Lange, 1996a, pp. 231). A general conclusion is that these computer simulations provide a powerful tool to investigate the dynamics of social dilemmas.

Axelrod (1980a; 1980b; 1984) arranged a computer tournament in which various rules and/or strategies were tested in an iterated game. A very successful strategy appeared to be cooperation unless the other automata defected in the previous round. This strategy is known as Tit-for-Tat (TfT). Two TfT automata will quickly arrive at stable cooperating behaviour. However, if one of the automata makes a mistake (formalised as 'noise'), the stable cooperation disappears. In this situation the automaton accidentally perceives the cooperative behaviour of the other as defective, or accidentally takes an action different than the intended one. As a result of this mistake they fall into a cycle of alternating revenges (Lindgren and Nordahl, 1995). To avoid that, different strategies were developed that keep track of history. Some of these strategies are deterministic, for example: 'defect if opponent defects two times in a row' (Tf2T). Other strategies were probabilistic, for example a TfT-like strategy that forgives a defective choice of the other with a probability that depends on the historical choice behaviour of the other (Molander, 1985; Nowak and Sigmund, 1992). Besides 'fixed' strategies, also evolutionary strategies have been developed, using the technique of genetic algorithms (see also Chapter 3 on conceptual tools for agent-based modelling). For example, Axelrod (1987) applied a genetic algorithm that had a history of six time-steps. This simulation showed that, starting with a random configuration, in most populations first the uncooperative strategies dominated, but further in the process more cooperative strategies tended to dominate on the basis of reciprocity.

The cellular automata modelling approach has been used to study social dilemmas by, e.g., Axelrod (1980a; 1980b; 1984) Nowak and May (1992; 1993), Nowak and Sigmund (1992), Bruch (1993), Hegselmann (1994; 1996), Kirchkamp (1994), Messick and Liebrand (1995) and Liebrand and Van Lange (1996a).

Social networks

The social networks approach resembles in many ways the cellular automata approach. The main difference, however, is that the relationships between the agents are variable, which goes beyond the fixed checkerboard grid. The relations between the agents may change in time as a consequence of the behaviour of those agents (Liebrand and Van Lange, 1996b, pp. 7). Whereas in the cellular automata approach the cells are 'condemned' to interact with their fixed neighbours, in the social network the agents may contact whomever they like.

Conte (1996), for example, used a social network approach to study rational interaction in cognitive agents. She formalised the social dependence of agents as their

dependency on the performance of other agents to reach their goals. The computer-programmed model, called DEPNET, allowed her to study the emergence of social structures (dependency networks) and rational strategies. DEPNET allows one to program the agents' architecture in terms of goals, resources, actions, plans and beliefs about other agents' states. The agents could interact by means of: (1) influencing, where an agent attempts to influence another agent to have a new goal, (2) social exchange, where an agent complies with an other agent's request in order to obtain reciprocation from the latter, and (3) cooperation, where agents accomplish a share in a multi-agent plan aimed to achieve a common goal. Conte (1996) found that cooperative strategies are often more convenient than, e.g., social exchange strategies. That is, in situations of mutual dependence to reach a certain goal, cooperation provides a more rational solution in comparison to influencing and exchange strategies.

Neural networks

The parallel processing of information in neural networks constitutes the most important difference with the cellular automata and social networks approaches (Liebrand and Messick, 1996). Each neuron has several input lines and a single output line. This allows for the simulation of constantly adapting networks, which are even more flexible than social networks.

Macy (1996), for example, used a genetic-algorithm approach in an artificial neural network to study processes of natural selection and social learning with respect to strategies in an iterated prisoners' dilemma. The agents had 'softwired' strategies, that is, they could change their strategy in reaction to low outcomes. Whereas 'hardwired' strategies like Tit-For-Tat are not capable of altering their programming, 'softwired' strategies can do so in order to adapt their behaviour to changing circumstances. As such, using such a 'reinforcement learning approach', two (or more) agents may show an evolution in their relationship. Macy (1996) used the technique of genetic algorithms (Holland, 1975) to program such an adaptive agent. In his simulation experiments, he introduced perceptual and behavioural mistakes, that is, agents may misread the input or by accident give the wrong output. The agents kept track of history, that is, they memorised the behaviour of their partner for a number of rounds. The agents played 50 rounds against a fixed partner (randomly chosen from 100). Following these 50 rounds, a natural selection algorithm gave the fitter strategies a larger chance of returning in the next generation. The total experiment lasted for 10^5 rounds. The simulations showed that the Win-Stay-Lose-Shift (WSLS) strategy was a clear evolutionary winner, not Tit-for-Tat (TfT).

Comments on the simulation of social dilemmas

The above-mentioned simulations teach us a lot about the basic micro-macro dynamics that affect the use and the management of common goods. However, these simulations are primarily focussed at developing and testing outcome-maximising strategies. The 'basic mathematical approach' of these simulations is aimed at the discovery of laws of interdependent behaviour. In this approach, the agents 'live' in a simple one-dimensional world, where only one 'good' can be consumed. This good is formalised in terms of abstract points, and an agent is implicitly assumed to have an everlasting motivation to consume more of these points, irrespectively of the number it has consumed before.

Consequently, the agents are equipped with a single unsatisfiable need for points⁷. The first point consumed is considered to be equally satisfying as the consumption of point number 100. Thus, a next unit of goods will contribute the same to the agents need satisfaction, independent of the number of goods consumed previously. This formalisation of needs does not match with theoretical conceptions of needs in psychology and economy (e.g., McDougall, 1928; Maslow, 1954; and Max-Neef, 1992).

In real life, the more of a certain good is being consumed, the less motivated one usually is to consume another unit of that good (there is diminishing marginal utility). Moreover, people have multiple needs and abilities, and consumption goods are capable of satisfying several needs simultaneously and may address different abilities at the same time. To optimise their efforts as well as their outcomes, people may engage in different processes such as deliberation, social comparison, imitation and habit formation in deciding how to behave. Whereas some of these processes are formalised in a rudimentary way, e.g., social comparison, the fact remains that the decision rules of the agents have not been developed on the basis of psychological theory. The researchers in this field acknowledge this. For example, Liebrand and Messick (1996, pp. 232) conclude that their theoretical model is still rudimentary and that it is necessary to introduce more richness into the reconstruction of social decision processes in dilemma situations. For example, the automatons in their simulations were programmed to compare their state with that of neighbouring automatons on every time step, and to act upon the outcomes of that comparison. The social comparison process has been defined as, e.g., cooperate unless the other player did not cooperate in the previous round (Tit-for-Tat), or, if your outcome exceeds the average outcome of your neighbours, then it is a win and then you will cooperate in the next round. These rules have no link with psychologically important factors such as similarity and uncertainty, which often determine if social comparison is likely to occur.

Yet the fundamental dynamics that are being identified and explored in such simulation models may be valuable in interpreting and understanding outcomes of more elaborated simulation models. On the other hand, it is a challenge to extend the existing social dilemma simulations with a greater variety of outcomes and agent needs. This would allow for experimentation with more psychologically valid heuristics in familiar experimental situations.

The next section will present some exemplary simulations of behaviour in more complex systems. Because this also allows for the programming of more complex behavioural rules, the resulting behavioural dynamics have more resemblance with real-world dynamics.

⁷ The researchers in this paradigm implicitly acknowledge the existence of more needs, as indicated by their use of acronyms such as KISS (Keep It Simple Stupid) and EROS (Enhancing Realism Of Simulations) (First International Conference on Computer Simulation and the Social Sciences (ICCS&SS) 1997).

Multi-agent simulations of behaviour in complex environments

In the previous sections some examples were presented of simulated real-world systems, and of simulations of behaviour in social dilemma situations. Combining these approaches for simulating behaviour in a complex environment would serve two goals. First, it would allow for studying the behavioural dynamics of resource depletion. Second, it would provide a tool to study the management of complex systems involving human behaviour, such as traffic flows, the use of natural resources and the behaviour of different large crowds in particular environments.

In this section we will discuss a number of multi-agent approaches that are aimed at simulating more complex human behaviour dynamics. Some of these simulations refer to a restricted area of behaviour, e.g., car-driving in the driving simulator of the University of Groningen Centre for Environmental and Traffic Psychology (Van Wolffelaar and Van Winsum, 1996). Other simulations refer to human behaviour in a very broad context. For example, Epstein and Axtell (1996) discuss the results of their simulation Sugarscape in terms of human civilisation. All simulations here have in common that they intend to capture the processes that determine the behaviour of real humans.

The COV Driving Simulator

The Driving Simulator of the Centre for Environmental and Traffic Psychology (Dutch acronym: COV) allows for studying car driver behaviour in a simulated environment (Van Wolffelaar and Van Winsum, 1996). The simulator consists of a real car (without engine) with a wide, semi-circular screen in front of it. On this screen the simulated environment is being projected, which consists of roads with other cars, buildings, traffic signs, crossroads et cetera. Letting other cars (agents) drive autonomously in the simulated micro-world enhances the realism of the simulation. The agents that steer these simulated cars know the traffic rules, and adapt their driving behaviour to the actual traffic situation, which includes the behaviour of the real driver. To attain realistic behaviour in the driving behaviour of the simulated agents, they are programmed to perceive the environment, evaluate behavioural rules and respond autonomously. The evaluation of behavioural rules serves three goals of the agents, namely to avoid collisions, not to endanger other vehicles and not to disrupt the flow of traffic. At a higher level the agents have a navigational goal, consisting of either a random route or a predetermined route (following a scenario script).

The object of the studies performed with the COV's simulator is to study the driving behaviour of real human subjects in a controlled setting, not to study the behaviour of the simulated drivers. Studies have been directed at (1) the assessment of individual driving performance in various specific situations, where the drivers were normal, healthy people, or people with functional disabilities, or people who used medicinal drugs, (2) the evaluation of on-board navigational systems, (3) the evaluation of road designs, and (4) driver training and selection (Van Wolffelaar & Van Winsum, 1996). However, the traffic model appears to be also suitable to study the dynamics of traffic flows. Running the traffic model on a personal computer would provide a tool to experiment with the dynamics of traffic-jams as a function of road design and driver behaviour.

Sugarscape

To simulate the fundamentals of human societies Epstein and Axtell (1996) have developed a simulation model called Sugarscape. The simulation model may reflect the emergence of, e.g., sex, culture, conflict, and trade. The processes that emerge in these simulations sometimes show a remarkable resemblance with processes in the real world. However, the agents modelled in Sugarscape have little in common with real people (see Durlauf, 1997).

Sugarscape is a cellular automata model of an agent-environment system. The environment consists of a matrix (checkerboard), where some areas (groups of cells) contain more 'food' (sugar), and other areas are relatively impoverished with respect to food. In this environment several agents are 'living'. These agents need sugar to keep alive and moving. To find the sugar, the agents are equipped with a limited vision of the environment. The simplest agents have the instruction to 'look around as far as your vision permits, find the spot with the most sugar, go there and eat the sugar'. Every move the agent makes costs some sugar, and as such, they have a simple metabolism. The quantity of sugar an agent consumes determines its need-satisfaction. The more sugar an agent consumes, the higher its ability to move. Even with these relatively simple rules phenomena can be identified which are mimicking real-world processes. For example, environments are capable of supporting limited numbers of agents (the principle of environmental carrying capacity), and skewness may arise in the distribution of sugar consumption among the agents, resembling the distribution of wealth in human societies represented by, e.g., the Gini-index (Gini, 1912).

Epstein and Axtell (1996) performed large numbers of experiments with Sugarscape, and tested the effects of various extensions of their simulation programme. One of the first extensions was the introduction of birth and death in Sugarscape. Moreover, they gave agents 'cultural' attributes and rules for the transmission of these attributes. Their goal was to simulate the following 'proto-history':

In the beginning, a small population of agents is randomly scattered about a landscape. Purposeful individual behaviour leads the most capable or lucky agents to the most fertile zones of the landscape; these migrations produce spatially segregated agent pools. Though less fortunate agents die on the wayside, for the survivors life is good: food is plentiful, most live to ripe ages, populations expand through sexual reproduction, and the transmission of cultural attributes eventually produces spatially distinct "tribes". But their splendid isolation proves unsustainable: populations grow beyond what local resources can supply, forcing tribes to expand into previously uninhabited areas. There the tribes collide and interact perpetually, with penetrations, combat, and cultural assimilation producing complex social histories, with violent phases, peaceful epochs, and so on (Epstein and Axtell, 1996, page 8).

Starting with simple agents, Epstein and Axtell (1996) experimented with various extensions of the agent rules. For example, rules were developed for attacking agents belonging to a different tribe, resulting in a plundering of sugar from weaker tribes. The introduction of a second commodity, 'spice', allowed for the emergence of trade. Simulations were run for neo-classical agents, that live forever and have fixed preferences, and for non-neo-classical agents, which are born and die again, and which may change their preferences. In comparison to the neo-classical agents, the non-neo-classical agents caused a higher variance in the distribution of trade prices. Moreover, the horizontal inequality, which refers to the differences in welfare, increased even further among the

non-neo-classical agents. Last but not least, in the runs with non-neo-classical agents no equilibrium (as postulated in the First Theorem of welfare economics, see e.g., Richardson, 1959) emerged. Even credit networks were simulated, and diseases were 'developed'.

No matter how elegant Sugarscape may be, the insights it provides thus far are not new to social science. Moreover, Durlauf (1997) in his review remarks that '*...the sorts of microeconomic structures employed in Sugarscape preclude the possibility of providing an explanation of the macro-phenomena of interest. In the absence of behavioral assumptions which sensibly embody the objectives of agents, any match between the model's predictions is almost by definition unenlightening*' (Durlauf, 1997, p. 48). Durlauf's critique is in line with our earlier observation that many multi-agent simulations lack individual agent rules that are based upon behavioural theory. This also accounts for the agents in Sugarscape, which, for example, have only a single need and do not engage in social comparison. Despite the fact that the simulations with Sugarscape show very interesting processes, the lack of psychological rules forces one to be cautious with respect to interpreting the simulation results in terms of actual processes in human society.

Simulating fishermen's society

Bousquet, Cambier, Mullon, Morand and Quensiere (1994) developed a model to simulate a society of fishermen. This model is being used to simulate the fisheries of the central delta of Niger. The authors chose to use an object-oriented design of their simulation model. This approach implies that a system is being modelled by representing the various constituent objects. Two main categories of objects in this simulation are concerned with the ecological dynamics (including fish) and the dynamics of fishing (including households). The model is aimed at simulating the decisions made by households (the micro-level) in a fluctuating environment. The ecological dynamics refer to the reproduction, growth, mortality, migration and competition of fish in four different biotopes (river, channels, ponds and flooded areas). In the simulation, various characteristics of the fish population may change (e.g., evolution of biomass, weight and age structure) depending on the fishermen's decisions and fishing strategies.

From a psychological standpoint, the modelling of the fishermen's decision-making is the most interesting part of the modelling. 'Household objects' are included in the simulation that may differ in size and ethnicity. The distribution of these household characteristics resembles the distribution of households in the region. For example, the mean number of persons per household approximates a normal distribution with a standard deviation of 2. In the simulation, the households decide on their activities and behave accordingly. The decision-making model that Bousquet *et al.* (1994) use distinguishes four phases: building, perception, decision (selection) and action. In the *building* phase all the activities that can be performed in the environment are recorded. The *perception* phase consists of getting information on the potential activities. This information can be represented in two ways. First, the quantitative description indicates an expected catch under certain circumstances. This information may be based upon previous experiences, and may be perceived either optimistically (as a minimum) or pessimistically (as a maximum). Second, a qualitative description may be used to qualify activities as favourable, unfavourable, impossible or compulsory. In the *selection* phase the household chooses a possible action. A top-down approach here resembles the anthropologist viewpoint: the choice for an action is a function of two group characteristics, namely household-type and ethnicity. A bottom-up approach starts at the household level, e.g.,

considering a rule like ‘look at your neighbours and copy the action of the most successful neighbour’.

Their first simulations started with economically rational households. Simulation of a two-year period with two flood periods showed that all fishermen reacted on the same moment in the same way, depending on the state of the ecosystem. That is, they all started fishing in either the river, the channels (if filled), the ponds (if not dry), the plains (if flooded) or they started working on the land (agriculture), all depending on the water level.

A second simulation tried to include environmental and human variability by means of variability of catch. Also in this simulation the fishermen tended to react in the same way on the same moment, however, the changes were less immediate (there was more diversity) than in the previous simulation. As such, during some moments in time some fishermen were fishing in the river whilst others are working on the land. A third simulation introduced a variable risk perception. The optimistic fishermen selected their behaviour by reference to their best achievement in the previous two weeks. The pessimistic fishermen referred to the worst achievement in the last two weeks, and the risk-neutral fishermen referred to their average achievement. Equipping the fishermen with different risk-perceptions (1/3 optimistic, 1/3 risk-neutral and 1/3 pessimistic) further increased the diversity in behaviour.

Thus far, the households did not communicate directly with each other. To introduce communication, a next simulation allowed households to have two or five social relations. Bousquet *et al.* (1994) concluded that the size of the communication network might change the use of space, although the results are not clearly interpretable. A next simulation used anthropological data on where certain tribes are fishing. Not surprisingly the simulation shows that fishermen belonging to different tribes (‘Bozo’ vs. ‘Somono’) are fishing at different locations. The various simulations summarised here also revealed differences with respect to the resource dynamics, that is, the number and biomass of fish during the two-year period in the simulation.

Bousquet *et al.* (1994) demonstrate that the simulation of a human-environment system may contribute to a better understanding of how certain characteristics of the ‘human system’ interfere with the dynamics of natural resources. However, the psychological realism of the agents is up for further improvements. In the current simulation the fishermen have only one need, i.e., food. Consequently, a lot of relevant behavioural processes that deal with the balancing of more than one need cannot be accounted for in this version of their simulation tool. Also the rules for social comparison can be elaborated further. For example, the rules do not account for when a fisherman is eager to socially compare, and with whom. Another remark concerns the absence of trade in the simulation. Trade is important, because selling fish may provide the money to buy valued goods. Increased fishing to earn money instead of just obtaining food may have important consequences for resource dynamics. For the simulation of such processes it is necessary to enhance the psychological richness of the simulated agents

Steels’ robots

Steels (1995) employs physical agents (robots) in his study of behaviour-oriented Artificial Intelligence (AI). Whereas the knowledge-focussed approach of AI-research, fostered mainly by cognitive psychology and linguistics, has encountered serious problems because the top-down approach required very complex rule-systems, the autonomous agents research, behaviour based or bottom up artificial intelligence has witnessed a rapid

development in recent years (Steels, 1995, see also Chapter 3 on artificial intelligence). Scientists from various disciplines have been working on what is called 'artificial life route to artificial intelligence' (Steels and Brooks, 1993), bottom-up AI (Brooks, 1986), the Animat approach (Wilson, 1991), Behaviour-based AI (Steels, 1990) and Animal Robotics (McFarland, 1992), see also Steels (1995).

The success of this research is defined as the success in building agents capable of maximising their own self-preservation in interaction with a dynamically changing environment. Whereas other scientific programs simulate behaviour in a virtual world, Steels' agents actually behave in the real world. There are more examples of behaviour simulations using physical robots, for example in the study of group behaviour of robots (Mataric, 1996). An analogy can be made with flying: in a computer simulation of a flying bird one can develop a flying machine that moves its virtual wings and responds to differences in, e.g., velocity, altitude and air-pressure, but the simulation does not actually fly in the real world. The use of physical robots allows one to study the behaviour of agents in (a limited part of) the real world.

Steels (1995) argues that emergent functionality (finding new useful capacities by yourself) is the only way for a robot to autonomously increase its capability. Equipping robots with rules that allow for emergent behaviour yields two advantages. First, no additional structure is necessary to get additional capabilities. As a result, the robot will be capable of adapting to a changing environment. Second, the behaviour will be robust, being less dependent on accurate sensing and action, and it makes fewer fixed assumptions regarding the state of the environment it is living in. Consequently, the robot is more flexible in coping with changing environments and it is capable of dealing with mistakes it made earlier. A disadvantage of emergent behaviour is that it is less efficient. It will often cost a lot of time before efficient behaviour emerges, whilst the programming of such behaviour will of course directly produce such behaviour. To learn more about the benefits and disadvantages of different behavioural competencies, Steels (1995) argues that it is important to experiment with agents with many different behavioural competencies, that are operating in ecosystems with a multitude of challenges.

The approach of Steels and others is aimed at exploring the basics of intelligent behaviour. Intelligence is framed within the general context of biology. Steels has no intention to simulate the behaviour of humans, and as such, the behavioural rules of his robots are not based upon psychological theories. Only self-preservation can be considered as a psychological need. Whereas the bottom-up approach Steels adheres to teaches us a lot about some basic principles of behaviour, such as the role of emergence, the decision rules used to model robot behaviour are very simple and not based upon a behaviour-theoretical framework. Yet this approach may be informative about deeper biological rules that partly determine human behaviour. However, because of the absence of factors such as multiple needs and uncertainty, Steels' robot rules do not provide a tool to simulate processes such as social comparison and habit formation that play an important role in human behaviour.

The commons dilemma simulated by Grant and Thompson

Grant and Thompson (1997) state that the integration of physical, biological and human systems in formal models is one of the most exciting challenges for ecological modellers. In their model they simulate 'the commons' as described in the classical text by Hardin (1968). They combine models of the resource (pasture land), cows and farmers. Two

agents, representing farmers, are confronted with the choice to add or withdraw a cow from the common resource. The agents are equipped with a Tit-for-Tat or with a pure optimising strategy. The optimising strategy utilises information regarding the behaviour of the complete system, whereas the Tit-for-Tat strategy only examines the behaviour of the other agent at $t - 1$. If both actors employ a Tit-for-Tat strategy a sustainable resource use is reached because the actors succeed in cooperating. If one of the actors follows an optimising strategy, the system collapses because of the commons dilemma structure. The interesting point here is that despite its simplicity, the Tit-for-Tat strategy outperforms the optimising strategy in reaching a sustainable resource use. However, despite the more elaborated modelling of in particular the foraging of the herd and the associated rate of animal weight gain, the behavioural rules are based on game-theoretical principles instead on behavioural theory.

Ernst's simulation of agents in resource dilemmas

Ernst (1998) developed an artificial agent that is based upon psychological theory. Summarised, agents have ecological knowledge (about the resource), social knowledge (about others' ecological knowledge, intentions and motives) and action knowledge (schemata that allow to react flexibly to situations whilst preserving the strategically defined goal). Each agent has three prototypical motives: (1) to maximise individual gain, (2) to maximise overall resource outcome, and (3) to minimise the differences between participants. Motives, knowledge, the ecological and the social environment determine the goals an agent has. For example, the motive of maximising resource outcome (prescribing reasonable use) can lead towards over-harvesting when the ecological knowledge is poor. Combining various motives and knowledge structures allows one to model a variety of agents.

These artificial agents have been tested in the Fishing Conflict Game (Spada, Opwis, Donnen, Schwiersch and Ernst, 1987). This is a resource-management game where several people try to manage a replenishable fish stock. The fish stock dynamics are formalised on the basis of a dynamic, non-linear function fitting to biological data. The results showed that the behaviour of the artificial agents was comparable to the behaviour of people playing the Fishing Conflict Game. Moreover, people could play the game with the artificial agents without identifying them as computer-simulated agents. The agents thus performed behaviour that went beyond the rational/optimal resource-management strategies that have been used in many other modelling approaches.

In testing the performance of the Tit-for-Tat strategy in this simulation context, Ernst (1998) found that this strategy is not a viable way to promote a sustainable use because of three reasons. In the first place, retaliating the over-harvesting of someone with over-harvesting oneself leads to a further decrease of the resource, and thus may jeopardise one's future outcomes. Second, the one that is retaliating is less trusted by the others, and thus will decrease the intention of other players to limit their harvesting. Finally, the group equity level shifts towards a higher resource use, which may stimulate other users to increase their harvesting behaviour.

Ernst's approach is an outstanding example of how psychological theory can be applied in a multi-agent simulation. He translates knowledge from attitude theory into decision rules for agents. Because Ernst concentrates on attitude theory, processes like social comparison and habit formation are not included in the model. The agents in his simulation have to deal with a single outcome and thus, implicitly, appear to have one

need. Moreover, the simulated agents predict the behaviour of the other agents without directly interacting with them. Consequently it is not possible to experiment with the dynamics of behaviour such as social comparison and habit formation.

Comments on multi-agent simulations of behaviour in complex environments

Whereas the various simulation models discussed in the current section provide valuable tools to simulate and/or to explore human behaviour in complex environments, the main critique refers to the psychological layout of the simulated agents. This ranges from very poor (Sugarscape: Epstein and Axtell, 1996) to an elaborated formalisation of attitude theory (Ernst, 1998). Up to now no simulation contains agent rules on the basis of a meta-model of human behaviour that integrates various processes and factors that have been identified as relevant in the context of environmental behaviour. Therefore, processes and variables like the satisfaction of various needs, quality-of-life, reasoned action habit formation and social comparison are not commonly used in simulation models. It is essential to include such behavioural factors and processes in agent rules. Such rules would first allow for studying the behavioural dynamics of environmental resource depletion. Second, it would provide a tool for studying how people manage systems that involve interactions between the behaviour of many humans and a complex environment

A meta-model of human behaviour that incorporates the relevant theories of behaviour would be helpful in formalising a set of agent rules that capture the most important behavioural dynamics. Such a model should indicate under what conditions a certain behavioural theory is relevant. The meta-model can thus be used to specify the conditions under which an agent engages in particular types of behavioural processing. These agent rules should be simple in order to keep the simulations understandable and accessible for research. In comparison to the enormous complexity of real human beings such agent rules appear to be very simple. However, despite this simplicity, modelling some general laws that represent a broad range of behaviour may significantly improve simulations of environmental behaviour.

In the next chapter a conceptual meta-model will be described that is aimed at integrating various behavioural theories that are relevant in the context of environmental behaviour. This conceptual meta-model will be used to develop a coherent set of simple agent rules.

5

A conceptual meta-model of human behaviour

Environmental behaviour refers to all the actions of man that are significantly related to the natural environment, such as the consumption of environmental resources and space, the pollution of water, soil and air, the production of noise and waste, and man-made changes of landscapes. A broad range of behaviours falls within this definition of environmental behaviour, such as the production and the consumption of food, the buying of a house, working, transportation, various activities at home and shopping. The commons dilemma underlying many problems of environmental degradation (see Chapter 2) becomes clear if we realise that a lot of these behaviours satisfy our personal needs here and now (at the micro-level). However, the aggregated behaviour of many people together may in the long run affect natural environmental qualities at the macro-level. Also, the aggregated behaviour of many people affects the human environment, which refers to the technical environment people live in, the economy, the cultural environment, institutions and demographic developments. All these macro-level developments may have repercussions on the individual behaviour at some later time. For example, more intensive use of soil may yield larger harvests, which may sustain a more comfortable life-style. However, if all farmers adopt such more intensive agricultural activities, the chance of erosion will rise, which may cause a possible famine in the long run. Often however people are not aware of long-term negative developments, e.g., because they are behaving habitually, i.e. without much deliberation. This implies that they follow a cognitive processing style that does not involve an incorporation of the macro-level developments in their mental map.

The description above indicates that environmental behaviour can be conceived as a cyclical process, in which the micro-level behaviour of many individuals and the macro-level outcomes mutually affect each other. This cyclical pattern is being depicted in Figure 5.1, to be discussed below.

Regarding the degradation of the natural environment, the critical question has been formulated in Chapter 1: “Why do people so frequently over-exploit and damage natural resources, thereby endangering their own (future) living conditions, whereas in other conditions they use such resources with moderation so as to preserve them?”. In Chapter 2 this question was abbreviated as “why people bite the hand that feeds them” In answering this question it is important to study the process as sketched in Figure 5.1. This implies that attention should be given to the macro-level developments as *determinants* of behaviour, the *processes* that determine the micro-level behaviour, and the *strategies* for behaviour change that are being employed by governments, industries and other interest parties. Consequently, the challenge resides in the formalisation of a behavioural model that captures the dynamics of the micro-macro interactions as depicted in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: The cyclical pattern of micro-level behaviour and macro-level changes

Towards a meta-model of behaviour

The discipline of psychology has a lot to contribute regarding how people behave, what processes guide that behaviour, and which factors affect these processes. Psychology is a relatively young science, taken to be founded in 1879, when Wilhelm Wundt started the first formal psychological laboratory at the University of Leipzig. Modern psychology comprises a large number of theories explaining different but often overlapping aspects of human behaviour. As regards environmental behaviour, relevant theories deal with issues like attitude formation and change, the principles of reasoned action, human needs and motivation, classical and operant conditioning, social learning and social comparison processes, self-awareness theory, social facilitation and inhibition, cognitive dissonance, equity and justice, and the likelihood of elaboration.

In studying the processes underlying people's behaviour, various psychological theories may contribute more or less important insights. However, because these theories are describing aspects, parts, or episodes of the processes underlying consumer behaviour, not all theoretical insights are relevant at the same time. For example, habitual behaviour, which is often triggered by environmental circumstances, can be described using conditioning theory. However, when a habit is being changed, also processes of attitude formation, reasoned action and social comparison may play a role. Moreover, some theories appear to be very general, and therefore important, such as a theory on human needs, whereas other theories are very specific and less important, such as self-awareness theory.

Up to now, no integrative models of human behaviour exist that link the various psychological theories together, thereby indicating when which theory is relevant. Whereas, for example, physics is working on a grand unifying theory that integrates a multitude of theories on various phenomena (see, e.g., Hawkins, 1998), psychology lacks such an integrative framework. According to some scholars there is a need for a meta-

theory of human behaviour (Vallacher and Nowak, 1994). Such a meta-theory should provide an organising framework to integrate simplified versions of relevant specific theories of behaviour. In this chapter a step in the direction of such a meta-theory is being offered. A conceptual meta-model will be discussed that combines basic principles of various relevant theories in an integrative fashion. This proposed conceptual meta-model is a revised version of the conceptual model that has been described in Jager, Van Asselt, Rotmans, Vlek, and Costerman Boodt (1997).

The description of the meta-model starts with the macro-level driving factors of human behaviour, which refers to the block on the left-hand side of Figure 5.1. Here, a perspective will be sketched on developments in the natural environment, technological change, economy, demographic developments, institutions and culture.

Following that, the micro-level driving factors of human behaviour will be discussed. These refer to personal needs, the opportunities to be used, the abilities that consumers may have, and the uncertainty people experience.

A next section is devoted to the conceptualisation of the cognitive process that people employ, which constitutes the heart of the meta-model. We assume that people usually employ only one cognitive processing strategy at the time. For example, they are deliberating about what product to buy or they are buying it habitually. The type of cognitive processing a person engages in depends on various driving factors, which refer to the person's state and the environment (s)he is living in. For example, if a person is very satisfied with driving a car, it is likely that this person uses the car in a habitual manner, instead of deliberating on alternative modes of transportation before every trip. Consequently, the meta-model should specify under what conditions which theory-based rule will guide the agent's cognitive processing strategy. Moreover, the meta-model should incorporate feedbacks in order to deal with dynamical processes of change. The conditions wherein a certain process will prevail can often be deduced from the corresponding behavioural theory. Consequently, behavioural theory is necessary to develop a set of simple rules that describe both the cognitive processes as well as the conditions under which a particular cognitive process is being used. Integrating the various relevant theories in a meta-model thus implies indication of the conditions in which a certain behavioural mechanism will prevail.

The next section is devoted to the opportunity consumption that follows from cognitive processing. This opportunity consumption involves changes in the macro-level, as well as in the micro-level determinants of behaviour.

At this point the dynamical circle of Figure 5.1 is completed, and we are capable of schematising the conceptual meta-model of behaviour. In a subsequent section we will discuss dynamical processes of behaviour that involve several cycles of the model. Especially the behaviour-dynamical principles of herd behaviour and habit formation are being discussed.

Whereas processes of behavioural change may often emerge autonomously, many deliberate actions are being taken to change consumer behaviour. In the final section of this chapter we will present a perspective on behaviour change that involves the changing of (micro- and macro-level) determinants, the connection with cognitive processes and various general strategies that can be used for changing behaviour.

The macro-level driving factors of human behaviour

In determining the driving factors that affect human behaviour, it is practical to distinguish between macro-level factors that are roughly equal for all persons, and micro-level factors that often differ between persons. The macro-level driving factors refer to the natural and human environment a person lives in, and they largely determine the behavioural options he or she has. The macro-level and micro-level of behaviour determinants are interdependent. The macro-level affects, for example, the opportunities people can choose from, whereas the aggregated consumption of many persons affects the environment they live in.

The natural environment people live in refers to living organisms and non-living materials which provide the basic survival conditions for humans. In the context of a commons dilemma (see Chapter 2), this natural environment refers to resources such as clean air, fish stocks, natural forests, pastureland and the like. Environmental problems usually touch on this natural level, e.g., global warming, deforestation, the depletion of fishing grounds, the loss of bio-diversity and pollution.

Many human-induced macro-level processes affect the condition of the natural environment. Because of their human origin, these processes are referred to as the human environment people live in. Different large-scale developments in the human environment affect the behaviour of many individuals. Well known is the IPAT-formula as introduced by Ehrlich and Holdren (1971), who define the environmental impact of a certain society as $I = P * A * T$. Here, environmental Impact equals the product of Population size, the degree of Affluence per person and the environmental damage from the Technology used to produce one unit of affluence. According to this formula, reducing environmental degradation is a battle on three fronts: (1) limiting population growth, (2) limiting affluence and consumption growth, and (3) reducing the environmental impact of production and consumption technology (Goodland, Daly and Kellenberg, 1994). Because of the mutually compensatory character of P, A and T, fighting this battle on just one front may not be sufficient to reach sustainable development. For example, just increasing the level of 'clean' technology (T), while ignoring the growth of population (P) and affluence level (A), may still result in a significant growth of total environmental impact (I).

If we start investigating the socio-behavioural causes of population growth, increasing affluence and the ever growing power of technology, two other driving forces behind environmental overexploitation can be recognised, i.e. *institutions* as vehicles for constituting and governing human societies, and *culture* as the conglomerate of socially shared beliefs, values and attitudes. On this basis, Opschoor (1989), Stern (1992) and Vlek (1995) consider environmental overexploitation as being driven by technological, economic, demographic, institutional and cultural developments (abbreviated as the T.E.D.I.C. complex). Especially in the 20th century the T.E.D.I.C. complex has propelled an acceleration in environmental over-exploitation. From left to right in the T.E.D.I.C. complex, it seems that we are dealing with forces varying from easy-to-change to hard-to-change, or, from modifiable to 'given'. Therefore the more fundamental the determinants addressed by an environmental policy aimed at reducing environmental overexploitation are, the more politically sensitive and harder to implement this policy becomes. This explains the popularity of technical solutions to environmental problems, which may, however, in fact only scratch the surface of a much deeper-rooted set of problems (Vlek, 1995). The following sections describe the developments in the industrialised countries

with respect to macro-level factors in terms of technological, economic, demographic, institutional and cultural developments. These sections are adapted from Gatersleben and Vlek (1997).

Technological developments. In current industrial society, many goods, services and materials are available now that 50 years ago did not exist. For example, in 1950 the washing machine came on the market. The first machine only made mechanical movements and it had no supply- or drainpipe. Nowadays, the washing machine does everything for us; we merely have to put in the laundry and the soap and push the buttons. The washing machine and other household goods such as the micro-wave oven deliver services that were also delivered before. There are also many goods that deliver new services, such as a TV set, or the personal computer. Apart from a growing availability of goods and services there are also more different goods that deliver the same service. Technological developments also indirectly influence household consumer behaviour because they make goods and services available that people need in order to be able to use other goods, such as roads to drive a car, or pipe-connections to the gas-, water-, or electricity distribution systems.

Economic developments. While technological developments have led to many new goods, economic developments led to an increasing amount of money to consume and produce these goods. Of course these two go hand in hand; goods that are developed in technology are sold, and profits are used for further development. Not only is there more money to produce; there is also more money to consume. Since 1950 the purchasing power of individual households has strongly increased. Because of mass production, prices have decreased and more people were able to afford a particular good. Furthermore, for some goods, the prices per service unit have decreased. Household goods such as a washing machine have become more efficient and therefore use less energy, which makes the service they deliver relatively cheaper.

Demographic developments. Demographic developments can be seen as a multiplier, because when there are more people more goods and materials are needed and may be consumed. For example, from 1950 to 1990 the Dutch population has grown by a factor of 1.5 (from about 10 to 15 million) and is estimated to grow by another 0.6% towards 2010. The number of households has increased even more, due to a decreasing average household size.

Institutional developments. Striving for economic and technological growth can also be found in the way in which society is organised in social structures and institutions. According to Opschoor (1989), today's industrial capitalism originates not only in technological and scientific developments, but also in the development of the free-market system, which is aimed at increasing the material well-being of individuals and society by focusing on efficiency as reflected in market values. Natural resources used for industrial production generally do not have a market value and therefore are traditionally not seen as contributing to the economic value of goods.

Cultural developments. Consumption and consumption growth have penetrated into cultural norms and values as well: well-being these days seems to depend largely on how much people earn and possess; and how one is perceived by others is influenced by one's material possessions. The importance of nature tends to be reduced to the extent to which it is able to serve human needs. This stems from a traditional Christian belief in human domination over nature (or anthropocentrism: man as the measure for everything; White,

1967), a belief in material prosperity, the free-market mechanism, and a materialistic culture in which norms and values are expressed in quantifiable units (Opschoor, 1989).

Macro-level developments following the T.E.D.I.C.-complex such as described above are important to understand the behavioural pressures affecting the individual consumer. For example, if the population grows, everything else being equal, the availability of consumption opportunities per capita will decrease because it has to be shared with more people. Moreover, the aggregated behaviour of many individual consumers affects macro-level outcomes such as environmental quality. The developments following the T.E.D.I.C.-complex can thus be considered as emergent properties originating from the behaviour of many individual consumers. Consequently, linking macro-level developments to the driving factors of individual consumer behaviour allows us to incorporate the micro-macro dynamics of consumer behaviour into one integrative model.

The micro-level driving factors of human behaviour

At the micro-level the basic driving forces of behaviour refer to human *needs and values*, behavioural *opportunities*, consumer *abilities* and consumer *uncertainty*. These four basic driving forces will be discussed in separate sections. Combining needs with opportunity consumption results in a *level of need satisfaction*, which determines their motivation to consume certain opportunities and to elaborate on opportunities. This level of need satisfaction will be discussed in the section on needs and values. Combining consumer abilities with opportunity demands yields a *behavioural control*, indicating the feasibility of opportunity consumption, which also affects the consumers motivation to elaborate on alternative opportunities. This behavioural control will be discussed in the section on abilities. The consumers level of need satisfaction, behavioural control and uncertainty are key factors that determine the type of cognitive processing he or she is most likely to engage in.

Human needs and values

The concept of need has many connotations (e.g., Gasper, 1996). First, it can be used both as a verb and a noun. The verb 'need' usually refers to wanting a certain item as a prerequisite for a certain behaviour, without referring to the deeper source of that wanting. For example, one may need a car to travel to work. The noun 'need' has many meanings, which can be grouped in three generic categories (Gasper, 1996, p. 5). The first refers to needs as related to wants or desires. Theories in this realm posit needs as underlying internal forces that drive our actions, e.g. the theories of McDougall (1928), Maslow (1954) and Max-Neef (1992). For example, the need for safety refers to the desire people have to feel safe. This desire may elicit various behaviours, depending on the circumstances. The second meaning refers to needs as an external (environmental) requirement for achieving an end. Theories in this area analyse satisfaction and try to identify what makes people fulfilled, happy or content (e.g. Scitovsky, 1992; Argyle, 1987). This approach, for example, studies the conditions in which people feel safe. The third meaning refers to needs as justified requirements for performing behaviour. Corresponding theory is concerned with normative and ethical aspects of needs and arguments about which prerequisites have a priority status (e.g., Doyal and Gough, 1991).

We will henceforth adopt the first ‘noun’ meaning of needs, referring to internal forces that drive our actions, as an appropriate perspective for our modelling exercise. The theories of McDougall (1928), Maslow (1954) and Max-Neef (1992) offer starting points to model needs as driving factors of behaviour. McDougall (1928) identified eighteen human needs (innate propensities or instincts). Examples are the need to seek (and perhaps to store) food, the need to explore strange places or things, the need to cry aloud for assistance when our efforts are utterly baffled, and the need to laugh at the defects and failures of our fellow-creatures. McDougall’s listing of what people need represents an early attempt to state universal motivational forces. However, the listing lacks a theoretical perspective on the relationships between the various needs.

Maslow (1954) has presented a well-known hierarchical ordering of needs, assuming that needs low in the hierarchy must be at least partially satisfied before needs higher in the hierarchy may become important sources of motivation. From the bottom to the top of his needs-pyramid, represented in Figure 5.2, Maslow (1954) discerns physiological and safety needs, needs to belong and be loved, and esteem, cognitive, aesthetic and self-actualisation needs.

Figure 5.2: Maslow's hierarchy of needs

A more sophisticated description and classification of human needs than those of McDougall (1928) and Maslow (1954), is postulated by Max-Neef (1992). This classification will be used in the conceptual meta-model to be presented. Max-Neef (1992) identifies nine fundamental needs that all people have: subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, leisure, creation, identity and freedom. Whereas the first seven needs have existed since the origins of *homo habilis*, and, undoubtedly, since the appearance of *homo sapiens*, the latter two are assumed to have been developed later in the evolutionary process. Furthermore, Max-Neef (1992) hypothesises that needs nowadays felt by some people, e.g. the need for Transcendence, may somewhere in the future evolve into a universal need. According to Max-Neef (1992), needs can be fulfilled by satisfiers, which are defined as ‘...everything which, by virtue of representative forms of being, having, doing and interacting, contributes to the actualisation of human needs’. Thus, the above-mentioned needs are related to four types of existential categories: being, having,

doing and interacting respectively. Linking the nine types of universal needs to the four types of existential categories yields a matrix as represented by Table 5.1, in which specific satisfiers can be categorised as cell entries.

	<i>Being</i>	<i>Having</i>	<i>Doing</i>	<i>Interacting</i>
<i>Subsistence</i>	1/ Physical health, mental health, equilibrium, sense of humour, adaptability	2/ Food, shelter, work	3/ Feed, procreate, rest, work	4/ Living environment, social setting
<i>Protection</i>	5/ Care, adaptability, autonomy, equilibrium, solidarity	6/ Insurance systems, savings, social security, health systems, rights, family, work	7/ Co-operate, prevent, plan, take care of, cure, help	8/ Living space, social environment, dwelling
<i>Affection</i>	9/ Self-esteem, solidarity, respect, tolerance, generosity, receptiveness, passion, determination, sensuality, sense of humour	10/ Friendships, family, partnerships, relationships with nature	11/ Make love, caress, express emotions, share, take care of, cultivate, appreciate	12/ Privacy, intimacy, home, spaces of togetherness
<i>Understanding</i>	13/ Critical conscience, receptiveness, curiosity, astonishment, discipline, intuition, rationality	14/ Literature, teachers, method, educational policies, communication policies	15/ Investigate, study, experiment, educate, analyse, meditate	16/ Settings of formative interaction, schools, universities, academies, groups, communities, family
<i>Participation</i>	17/ Adaptability, receptiveness, solidarity, willingness, determination, dedication, respect, passion, sense of humour	18/ Rights, responsibilities, duties, privileges, work	19/ Become affiliated, co-operate, propose, share, dissent, obey, interact, agree on, express opinions	20/ Settings of participative interactions, parties, associations, churches, communities, neighbourhoods, family
<i>Leisure</i>	21/ Curiosity, receptiveness, imagination, recklessness, sense of humour, tranquillity, sensuality	22/ Games, spectacles, clubs, parties, peace of mind	23/ Day-dream, brood, dream, recall old times, give way to fantasies, remember, relax, have fun, play	24/ Privacy, intimacy, spaces of closeness, free-time, surroundings, landscapes

<i>Creation</i>	25/ Passion, determination, intuition, imagination, boldness, rationality, autonomy, inventiveness, curiosity	26/ Abilities, skills, method, work	27/ Work, invent, build, design, compose, interpret	28/ Productive and feedback settings, workshops, cultural groups, audiences, spaces for expression, temporal freedom
<i>Identity</i>	29/ Sense of belonging, consistency, differentiation, self-esteem, assertiveness	30/ Symbols, language, religions, habits, customs, reference groups, sexuality, values, norms, historical memory, work	31/ Commit oneself, integrate oneself, confront, decide on, get to know oneself, recognise oneself, actualise oneself, grow	32/ Social rhythms, everyday settings, settings which one belongs to, maturation stages
<i>Freedom</i>	33/ Autonomy, self-esteem, determination, passion, assertiveness, open-mindedness, boldness, rebelliousness, tolerance	34/ Equal rights	35/ Dissent, choose, be different from, run risks, develop awareness, commit oneself, disobey	36/ Temporal/spatial plasticity

Table 5.1: A categorisation of need satisfiers according to Max-Neef (1992). Along the rows, nine basic needs are listed. Along the columns, four existential categories are ordered. The cells indicate a variety of need satisfiers.

The satisfaction or dissatisfaction of human needs results in experiencing feelings or emotions. As the concept of emotion is associated with general arousal of the Sympathetic Nervous System (Schachter, 1964), and the satisfaction of a need may actually decrease one's level of arousal, we prefer to relate the (dis)satisfaction of needs to the concept of *feelings*. (Un)pleasant feelings about something can be conceived as one of the constituent parts of emotion (Frijda and Mesquita, 1992). Feelings may be positive or negative (e.g., McDougall, 1928: pleasure and pain, and Siminov, 1970: positive and negative emotions). It is assumed here that the satisfaction of a need yields positive feelings, whereas the dissatisfaction of needs will yield negative feelings. Extending the typology of needs as presented by Max-Neef (1992) with positive and negative feelings yields the following list of feelings as presented in Table 5.2.

If a need is not satisfied, the related negative feeling will arouse a *drive* to satisfy this need. For example, if the need for subsistence is not satisfied because of a lack of food, the negative feeling will be hunger, arousing the drive to eat. If confronted with an (real or imagined) opportunity that is perceived to be capable of satisfying the need in question, this drive will result in a motivation to use that opportunity. Often there are several opportunities for satisfying one's needs. For example, if one is hungry, one could eat a tuna sandwich, a banana, and a varied number of other foods. Thus, a consumer may be motivated to use many different opportunities. The satisfaction of a need will evoke

positive feelings. If a need is fully satisfied, no drive will emerge and the motivation to use a relevant opportunity will be low.

<i>Basic need</i>	<i>Satisfaction of needs: positive feelings</i>	<i>Dissatisfaction of needs: negative feelings</i>
<i>Subsistence</i>	satiated, repleted	hungry
<i>Protection</i>	safe	in danger, anxiety
<i>Affection</i>	love/being loved	hate/indifference
<i>Understanding</i>	intellectual well-being, smart, clever	intellectual frustration, dumb, stupid
<i>Participation</i>	belonging, related, involved	lonely, isolated, forsaken
<i>Leisure</i>	playful, relaxation	boredom/bored, weary, stressed
<i>Creation</i>	creative, inspired	uninspired
<i>Identity</i>	self-assured, confident, positive self-image	uncertain, insecure, negative self-image
<i>Freedom</i>	free, independent	entangled, chained, bounded, captured, tied

Table 5.2: A categorisation of feelings according to the typology of needs (Max-Neef, 1992).

The satisfaction of needs is bounded to the here and now because needs indicate the ‘state of the system’ at the present time. For example, your current need for subsistence depends on the biophysical state of your body (e.g., hunger, thirst), and your need for leisure may depend on your psychological state (e.g., tension, stress) at this moment. Consequently, we need water now, and not tomorrow, and we feel we need a vacation now, and not next month. Despite the fact that needs are only felt at the current moment, people can (to some extent) manage their needs because they can forecast future situations. For example, if you hike through the mountains, you’ll make sure to take sufficient water and food supplies with you, and perhaps a raincoat. These supplies can be considered as a stock that can be used if a need is becoming apparent. For example, with respect to food, a self-supporting farmer may store this year’s harvest in his barn, and households may have a refrigerator for storing food⁸. For all types of needs such a ‘stock’ is imaginable. Some of these stocks may deplete and replenish at a relatively quick rate, for example, a food stock in a refrigerator may deplete in a relatively short period of time (days), but can be replenished very quickly (by shopping). Other stocks deplete more slowly, for example, upon returning from a vacation in the mountains you may feel ‘ready, willing and able’ to start working again, but after a couple of months’ working you might feel the ‘need for a vacation’ again. Some stocks may be conceived as not depleting at all, such as having a

⁸ One step further is that we can go from storing natural supplies that directly satisfy needs, such as food, to storing an unnatural supply such as money. Money can be spent on various goods that satisfy several needs. Thus, money should be considered as a capacity that people have, and it will therefore be discussed under the topic of consumer abilities.

good partner relation, which serves to satisfy one's need for affection, or having a raincoat, which may (partly) satisfy one's need for protection (against rain) for a lifetime.

In the conceptual model we consider these various need-satisfying stocks as reservoirs that have an outflux (depletion). Consumption (influx) is necessary to refill the reservoirs, so as to keep need satisfaction at an acceptable level. The depletion time of a need-satisfying stock can be conceived as the speed at which its reservoir level drops if no refill occurs. This depletion time may differ significantly for different types of need-satisfying stocks.

In principle, need-satisfying stock levels are not bounded by a maximum value. For example, one could accumulate a food stock that lasts a lifetime. However, people tend to store that amount of food that guarantees the satisfaction of their subsistence need for a certain period of time. For a self-supporting farmer this period may take a year to the next harvest, and for households it may take a week to their next supermarket visit. Storing more food will be less useful (unless you are trading food), because the satisfaction of the underlying need is already guaranteed. Because of this satisfaction, the actor's motivation to further increase the relevant stock level will be low. Stated differently, if the stock level is already high, the utility (in terms of need satisfaction) of another unit of that stock is low. As such, the need-satisfying capacity of an opportunity (e.g., consumption good, activity) follows a diminishing marginal utility function along with increasing stock level. This well-known principle of micro-economics explains that the more of a good one has, the less utility one gets from obtaining yet another unit of that good. In Figure 5.3 this principle is graphically displayed.

Figure 5.3: *The need-satisfying capacity of food as a function of the stock level*

Figure 5.3 illustrates that the contribution of an opportunity to one's level of need satisfaction gets smaller the higher the stock of a certain need satisfier (opportunity) is. An obvious example is that a hungry man (with a low nutrient stock) will experience a higher need satisfaction per sandwich than the man who already ate five of them (providing a high nutrient stock), whilst the need-satisfying capacity (nutrient value) of sandwiches is constant. Of course, the exact function depends on the need-satisfying capacity (NSC) of the relevant opportunity. This NSC is defined as the increase in the level of need

satisfaction after the consumption of one unit (e.g., kilogram, litre and minute) of an opportunity given that the initial stock level is zero.

If a stock level is low, the actor will be strongly motivated to consume opportunities that satisfy the associated need, because the utility per unit of opportunity is maximal. In case a stock level is very high, and the associated need is highly satisfied, there are usually other needs that are more depleted, and the actor will be more inclined towards the consumption of opportunities that satisfy these other needs.

Human values are often referred to as relatively stable beliefs about the personal or social desirability of certain behaviours and modes of existence (Rokeach, 1973). For example, whereas some people attach great value to comfortable living, adhering to a materialistic life-style, other people are more concerned with the environment and adhere to a more non-material life-style. In this section we will relate values and related concepts as basic orientors and cultural perspectives to the level of need satisfaction people experience.

When the environment people live in is relatively stable, they are most likely to experience a relatively stable need satisfaction. For example, having a good relation with spouse, family and friends, being secure of a job, living in a city with a lot of street-crime and owning a house, will provoke a relatively stable level of need satisfaction. In this example the need for protection is not satisfied because one is living in a city with a lot of crime. We suggest that the values that govern human behaviour can be related to the profile of need satisfaction.

The person in the example has relatively high levels of need satisfaction for subsistence and affection, but the level of need satisfaction for protection is relatively low. In evaluating opportunities, protection will thus be an important aspect determining the person's choices to a large extent. For example, it will not be the taste of the bread that will be the criterion to choose between two bakers, but rather the relative safety of the street they are located in. When one (or more) needs dominate the evaluation of a various range of behavioural opportunities, an enduring preference for certain opportunities may become visible. Such a preference can be conceived as a general value that affects most behaviour in a systematic way. Various values can be distinguished, depending on which (combinations of) need(s) or *need satisfaction profile* dominates the preferences for certain types of opportunities.

When the overall profile of need satisfaction changes, also a person's cherished values will change. Many people live in relatively stable environments and thus their values will be quite stable. However, serious changes in one's natural or human environment may cause a persevering change in one's prevalent need satisfaction profile. This may cause one's values to change in a direction that is more strongly focussed at the dissatisfied needs. Examples of such (natural and human) environmental changes that may cause one's values to change are war, famine, economic crisis (e.g., unemployment), the manifestation of a physical handicap, or the loss of a loved one. The concept of value orientations provides a general perspective on which values (orientations) are associated with the deprivation of which needs.

In determining if certain environmental states would also stimulate the emergence of related values or basic orientors, Krebs and Bossel (1997) performed a series of simulation experiments. These involved the creation of different simple environments and the observation of the type of behaviour a learning agent ('animat') would adopt. Krebs and Bossel defined six environmental states on the basis of six basic properties of normal

environments (Bossel, 1977, 1994). These six environmental states are: (1) normal state (stable and sufficient food availability), (2) sparse resources, (3) variety, (4) fluctuation, (5) change, and (6) other systems (i.e. animats). To survive in such environments, an agent must be able to, respectively: (1) physically exist in this environment, (2) effectively harvest necessary resources, (3) freely respond to environmental variety, (4) protect itself from unpredictable threats, (5) adapt to changes in the environment, and (6) interact productively with other agents. Simulations with learning agents showed that the agents developed strategies that balanced the six theoretically postulated basic orientors: (1) existence, (2) effectiveness, (3) freedom of action, (4) security, (5) adaptability, and (6) coexistence. The weights that the agents attached to these orientors depended on the type of world the agents were placed in. For example, security was very important in an unpredictable dangerous world, resulting in cautious behaving agents.

These results shed light on the relation between the environment one lives in and the conceptualisation of values as described before, because the basic orientors can be linked very easily to the needs as discerned by Max-Neef (1992), as will be demonstrated in Table 5.3 below.

Besides a link between human needs and basic orientors, Bossel (1996) also postulates a link between his basic orientors and the worldviews people may have according to the Cultural Theory of Thompson, Ellis and Wildavsky (1990). Cultural Theory postulates five different cultural perspectives, viz. the *Individualist*, the *Hierarchist*, the *Egalitarian*, the *Fatalist* and the *Hermit*. The *Hermit*, supposed to be 'withdrawn' from society, will be left out of consideration.

Two common social dimensions are supposed to underlie the different cultural perspectives (Thompson *et al.*, 1990): (1) one which reflects social restrictions placed on individual autonomy ('grid') and: (2) one which contrasts solidarity with egocentrism ('group'). Contrasting high and low values on the 'grid' and 'group' dimensions results in four cultural perspectives, namely: the *Hierarchist* (high 'grid' and high 'group'), the *Egalitarian* (low 'grid' and high 'group'), the *Individualist* (low 'grid' and low 'group') and the *Fatalist* (high 'grid' and low 'group'). These perspectives partly determine the way in which people perceive the world and behave in it. However, the four perspectives are considered to be extreme archetypes, because most consumers exhibit biases and preferences that belong to more than one perspective. In line with this, we can identify a survival strategy for each cultural type fitting the four elementary dilemmas (benefit-risk, temporal, spatial and social) described in Chapter 2 on the environmental commons dilemma.

The *Individualist* tends to estimate achievable benefits in financial and material terms. Freedom of action is an important value of the *Individualist*, suggesting the dominance of the need for freedom in the need satisfaction profile. In line with the *Individualist's* risk-seeking strategy, his/her perception of financial and material gains will result in a positive attitude towards a given behaviour pattern, even if appreciable risks are involved. With regard to the social survival dilemma, the *Individualist* evaluates outcomes in terms of benefits and risks for him/herself. Also, the *Individualist* emphasises present outcomes over future gains and losses, while in the spatial survival dilemma, the *Individualist* assigns a higher value to local benefits whilst ignoring outcomes elsewhere.

Egalitarians, however, who are characterised here as being risk-averse, tend to stress the risk side of behaviour, instead of the benefits. Benefits are also expressed in terms of quality of life, in which material gains are subordinate. Coexistence is the important value of *Egalitarians*, suggesting that the need for participation is dominating

the need satisfaction profile. Egalitarians tend to feel responsible for humanity everywhere at any time. Therefore, with regard to the temporal and spatial survival dilemmas they take serious account of future and global consequences. In line with the Egalitarian definition of solidarity with others, which ascribes a higher value to the collective as a whole than to separate individuals, Egalitarians emphasise collective outcomes in the evaluation of behaviour.

The Hierarchist, for whom social stability is the primary driving force, aims to maintain a balance between benefits and risks, present and future outcomes, local and global impacts, and collective and individual gains and losses. Security is the important value of Hierarchists, suggesting that the need for protection dominates their need satisfaction profile.

The Fatalist has no predefined position with respect to three of the four dilemmas. The Fatalist will not evaluate behaviour in the terms described above, but is merely trying to cope with the circumstances, which are regarded as beyond human control. This implies that he/she focuses on individual rather than collective outcomes of behaviour. The important value of Fatalists refers to existence and subsistence, suggesting that the fulfilment of basic living conditions is dominating their need satisfaction profile.

Besides the four commonly recognised perspectives, Bossel (1996) also identifies the perspectives of the *Organiser* and the *Innovator*, which are usually the important movers and shakers of societal development, but which fall outside the explanatory group-grid dimensions. The Organiser's most important value refers to effectiveness, suggesting that the needs for understanding and leisure are dominating their need satisfaction profile. The Innovator has adaptability as his/her dominant value, suggesting that the need for creation dominates his/her need satisfaction profile. Including the perspectives of the Organiser and the Innovator, we end up with six cultural perspectives.

In Table 5.3, based on Bossel (1996), a classification is presented that indicates which needs are at the focus of which perspectives. Whereas a particular value and the associated needs may be most important for a person adhering to a certain perspective, the other needs will also play an important role in determining behaviour, especially when these are not satisfied.

Cultural perspective (Thompson <i>et al.</i> , 1990, extended by Bossel, 1996)	Basic orientors/values (Bossel, 1977)	Personal + social needs (Max-Neef, 1992)
Fatalist	Existence Subsistence	Subsistence
Organiser	Effectiveness	Understanding Leisure
Individualist	Freedom of action	Freedom
Hierarchist	Security	Protection
Innovator	Adaptability	Creation
Egalitarian	Coexistence	Participation
All perspectives	Psychological needs	Affection Identity

Table 5.3: Cultural perspectives, basic orientors/values and focal needs. Based on Bossel (1996).

The personal needs 'affection' and 'identity', which Bossel (1996) notifies as 'psychological needs', are not dominating the behaviour of any of the cultural perspectives in particular. These needs can thus be regarded as equally important for all perspectives. The dissatisfaction of affection and identity needs may focus the behaviour of people in very different directions. For example, one person may want to acquire a group identity, whereas another person satisfies his or her need for identity by feeling unique. This variety may imply that an enduring dissatisfaction of affection and identity needs is not being reflected in a clear behavioural value.

Within a certain population it is possible to observe a certain distribution of the different perspectives. For example, empirical studies show that egalitarianism is dominant in the Nordic countries and the Netherlands, whereas fatalism is dominant in Great Britain, Ireland and southern Europe (e.g., Grendstad, 1999). Various cultures from different parts of the world may differ regarding the distribution of cultural perspectives and the predominant values and needs.

Opportunities

Opportunities are the products and services (commodities) that one can use and that have a certain capacity to satisfy one's needs. Thus, in line with Max-Neef (1992), an opportunity can be conceived as a potential need-satisfying stock. The need-satisfying capacity is conceptualised as a person's increase of the stock of a need satisfier following the consumption of one unit of an opportunity (e.g., kilogram, litre or minute), provided that one starts with an empty stock. The concept of need satisfying capacity is abbreviated as NSC.

A single opportunity may satisfy several needs simultaneously. For example, eating caviar may fulfil the need to eat (Subsistence), to relax (Leisure) and to demonstrate one's prosperity (Identity). However, the less fulfilled a particular need is, the more it will dominate the evaluation of available opportunities. For example, a hungry consumer will tend to evaluate food primarily on its nutrient potential.

Also, a single need may be satisfied by means of various different opportunities. For example, the need for Leisure may be fulfilled by playing, watching television, taking a holiday, practising sports, and so forth. Thus, the relation between opportunities and needs is a complex one, as some opportunities may, in fulfilling a specific need, simultaneously either fulfil or impair other needs. In exploring the relation between needs and opportunities, Max-Neef (1992) discerns five types of satisfiers:

- 1: *Violators and destructors*: these supposedly satisfy a given need (usually protection) but in fact often annihilate the possibility of satisfying this need and impair the satisfaction of other needs. For example, a strong governmental bureaucracy aims to offer protection for unfair treatment, but frequently people are treated unfair by lengthy bureaucratic procedures. Also other needs are annihilated by strong bureaucratic procedures. For example, strong bureaucratic procedures may impair people's understanding of the decision making process, may incite the feeling of being treated as a number, and may impair people's freedom by capturing them in procedures and rules (cf. Table 5.1).
- 2: *Pseudo-satisfiers* stimulate a false sensation of satisfying a certain need, but they may in fact impair the fulfilment of that need. For example, status symbols may be used to fulfil the need for identity, but a preoccupation with the acquisition of status symbols (e.g., expensive brands of clothing) may actually impair the satisfaction of one's identity needs.

- 3: *Inhibiting satisfiers* may satisfy one need, but inhibit other needs in the process. For example, obsessive economic competitiveness may satisfy the need for (economic) freedom, thereby yielding a larger material prosperity. However, this may be attained at the cost of, e.g., the time spent with family and friends (affection), the quality of the environment (subsistence), and time to relax and enjoy oneself (leisure).
- 4: *Singular satisfiers* satisfy one need without interfering with other needs. For example, insurance systems satisfy the need for protection against the financial consequences of, e.g., illness, accidents and burglary without inhibiting the satisfaction of other needs.
- 5: *Synergic satisfiers* satisfy a certain need, and they simultaneously stimulate and contribute to the satisfaction of other needs. For example, popular education spreads knowledge that satisfies people's need for understanding, but it also helps people to strive towards better living conditions (protection), to enhance their influence on social decision processes (participation) and their self-confidence (identity).

The more an individual perceives an opportunity as potentially need-satisfying, the more he or she will be motivated to use this opportunity. This motivation is an internal behavioural tendency of the consumer. However, the consumers' perception is susceptible to external information about the supposed need-satisfying capacities of opportunities, as, for example, provided by advertisements and the consumptive behaviour of other persons.

Besides perceived need-satisfying attributes of opportunities, which may trigger someone's internal motivation, also external factors constitute an opportunity. These external factors deal with the feasibility of the opportunity use rather than with their need-satisfying capacity. Examples of external factors are the availability of consumer goods, the publicity (advertisement) for them, the prices that have to be paid, the places where they can be bought, and the like. The use of opportunities may demand various abilities from the consumer, such as monetary investments, permits, personal knowledge and skills.

These abilities can be conceived as the personal resources that the consumer has available. The more constraints the use of an opportunity imposes on a consumer, the higher the opportunity's *resource demands*. General strategies aimed at a behaviour change (e.g., Sheth and Frazier, 1982; Cook and Berrenberg, 1981; Stern, 1992) often involve a change of the resources demanded by opportunity use. Four general types of personal resources are distinguished: (1) physical resources, (2) juridical and regulatory resources, (3) financial-economic resources, and (4) social and cognitive resources. The demands for these four types of personal resources associated with opportunity use can be captured under the headings of *physical characteristics*, *laws and rules*, *prices and costs*, and *social and cognitive demands*, respectively

Physical characteristics refer, in the first place, to the availability of certain products and services. This availability largely depends on the developmental stage a given society is in. For example, in Western society, the availability of coal and wood as a heating fuel is very low because the availability of natural gas and electricity allows for a much more convenient way of home heating. Due to the low demands for coal, the market mechanism has reduced this opportunity to almost zero⁹. However, in regions where the availability of natural gas and electricity is low, people are more dependent on coal and wood (e.g. Gatersleben and Vlek, 1997). If available, coal and wood form the major home-

⁹ Wood-fuelled fireplaces and stoves have recently experienced increased popularity, but mostly for reasons of homely comfort (cosiness).

heating opportunities in those regions. Secondly, physical availability refers to the places where certain products can be obtained. As such, both the infrastructure (e.g. for the distribution of gas, water and electricity) and the location of shops and service centres determine the physical availability of products. Other physical characteristics refer to, for example, the distance travelled and the amount of energy (e.g. physical strength) needed for consumption, and the quantity that can be consumed at one time.

Laws and rules refer to the legal regulations associated to the use of certain products. Some products are not allowed to be sold in a given region (country) because they do not conform to given product standards (e.g. ingredients, energy use, or environmental effects) or trade-agreements (origins of the product). Some may only be used with a permit or allowance (e.g. driver's licence, residential permits).

Prices and costs refer to the amount of money that products and services cost. Developments in mass production have resulted in decreasing prices of consumer goods, especially in the Northern regions (Gatersleben and Vlek, 1997). This in itself has led to an increased consumption. Furthermore, the availability of consumer credits (loans) also allows for the consumption of products, even if people lack a sufficient amount of cash.

Social and cognitive demands refer to the skills, knowledge, cognitive capacity and social support and/or restrictions required for using a particular opportunity. Some opportunities require training (education) before one can use them, e.g., for using a computer and driving a car. Moreover, some opportunities are not widely used and therefore relatively unknown. Cognitive effort is then necessary to find these opportunities and learn about their characteristics. Furthermore, the amount of publicity (advertisement and information) that is associated with the marketing of a given product plays a significant role. Advertising usually tries to persuade consumers to buy the product. Along with the development of the media (newspapers, radio, television, the Internet), advertising has grown into a huge industry, stimulating people to consume whatever is being produced. Consumer information is commonly more neutral in presenting both the pros and the cons of a given product. Besides the formally defined rules, such as documented in official laws, also informal cultural rules determine the opportunity to consume a certain product. For example, the consumption of pork and alcohol is restricted in Islamic countries (often also according to the law), and the smoking of cigarettes is socially restricted in the USA and Europe (also laws have been issued, banning smoking from public buildings).

The more opportunities are alike with respect to their need-satisfying attributes, the more they are interchangeable. This interchangeability functions in processes of *substitution*. For example, for medium-distance travelling, the train offers a better substitute for the car than the bike. If an opportunity is not attainable (any more), a consumer may look for alternatives that satisfy his/her needs as much as possible in the same way. Sometimes substitution processes cross the borders of different activity domains. For example, a consumer may decide to travel longer in order to achieve better living conditions (e.g. housing). In this situation the satisfaction of needs in one domain (good housing, serving Protection, Identity and Freedom) is increased at the cost of the satisfaction of needs in other domains (less spare time: Leisure and Freedom).

Abilities

The concept of ability refers to the set of capacities and/or skills an actor (individual, or household) has for actually using or acquiring an opportunity. In line with the resources

demanding, as discussed in the previous section, abilities can be conceived as the personal resources that a consumer has available. Important aspects of ability refer to physical means and skills, permits and licences, financial means, and social and cognitive abilities to buy and use consumer goods.

Physical resources refer firstly to one's personal health, fitness and strength. These physical capacities allow for the use of certain opportunities, such as cycling, working on the land, carrying water, and the like. Secondly, also the physical tools and circumstances one has available are conceived as physical abilities. As such, owning a car, a house, and having good (storage) space are regarded as physical abilities. For example, owning a car increases one's radius of action, thereby bringing more opportunities in reach, and a larger house provides more room for useful appliances (e.g., a washing machine, cooling equipment.). The physical resources a consumer has available are variable by nature, that is, they can increase and decrease as a function of aspects like age, satisfaction level of certain needs (e.g. hunger decreases one's physical strength) and consumption of certain opportunities (e.g. owning a car).

Permitted and licensed resources refer to the permits and licences one has for using certain opportunities. Examples of such abilities are having a driver's licence, a necessary educational grade and a permit to install a solar energy device on top of the roof. Besides permitted and licensed abilities such as provided by governments, the socio-cultural environment also provides abilities. For example, the (officially) abandoned caste system in Indian society allowed the use of certain opportunities only to members of a particular caste. Also, various cultures more or less accept the consumption of alcoholic beverages, pork and cigarettes. Rules and norms such as imposed by governments may be reflected in the cultural norms and beliefs of a given society. Permitted and licensed resources are variable, that is, they may be granted or denied on the basis of age, gender, identity, culture and the like.

Financial resources refer to the income a consumer has. The higher the income of a consumer is, the higher his/her ability to buy more and expensive consumer goods. Money deserves some special attention here, because it is a resource that can be earned by means of working, and it allows one to buy a variety of commodities that are capable of satisfying needs. Money, however, is not capable of satisfying all needs, which inspired the Beatles in writing their song 'Can't buy me love' (1964). Especially in the industrialised societies the combination of increasing mean annual income and decreasing prices of consumer goods has led towards a strong increase in consumption (Gatersleben and Vlek, 1997). The financial resources a consumer has are variable, depending on income and spending patterns.

Social and cognitive resources refer, firstly, to one's knowledge, cognitive capacities/skills, attitudes, values and norms. These factors determine one's ability to understand the outcomes associated with opportunity use. This may lead to the perception of a low behavioural control, viz. the physical or social feasibility of a particular opportunity use. Secondly, the time that people have available determines their ability to elaborate cognitively on outcomes. Finally, one's social status (a social resource) may also allow the use of certain opportunities. People having a high social status generally have easier access to information, a larger social network providing one with information, and more social support than people having a low status. Social status can be seen as a function of one's physical, permitted and financial resources, as well as the level of one's needs satisfaction. Cognitive resources may be conceived as a function of educational level

and heredity. Knowledge is a personal resource that hardly decreases, but which may become outdated. For example, new opportunities often demand more or new cognitive resources, as the introduction of the personal computer illustrates.

The abilities that people may have strongly depend on the developmental stage of the society they are living in. For example, in a 'hunter-gatherer' society, people have other abilities than in an industrial society. The same goes for the availability of opportunities.

Behavioural control is defined as a balance between the resources an actor has available and the resources that are demanded by a certain opportunity. Behavioural control indicates if he/she can easily consume a certain opportunity, or that its consumption is difficult or impossible. Theoretically there exists a certain degree of behavioural control for each actor over every single opportunity. Because consumers have limited knowledge, no consumer precisely knows his/her behavioural control over all possible opportunities. We assume that people estimate their behavioural control over opportunities during cognitive processing. Behavioural control will be further discussed in the later section on cognitive processing.

Uncertainty

The stability of (parts of) the environment people live in and of the (natural) resources they use may vary considerably. For example, fishermen may be confronted with sudden drops in their catch after periods of relatively stable catches, commuters may be confronted with unexpected traffic-jams, bad harvests may result in unexpected food shortages et cetera. As a result of such unexpected outcomes, people often become uncertain about which behaviour to perform. Should a fisherman increase his time fishing after an unexpected drop in catch, should the jammed commuter choose for a new route to his work, and what is the best action to avoid hunger when food is scarce? Uncertainty also pertains to the question if the own abilities are sufficient to engage in certain consumptive behaviour.

In such situations it is often a smart strategy to look at how successful the actions of other people are. Especially the behaviour of people having about the same abilities is of interest, because their actions are most likely to be also feasible for oneself. Social processing is therefore stimulated by uncertainty about opportunities and abilities and thus about outcomes.

Uncertainty tolerance indicates how sensitive people are to uncertainty of outcomes. Whereas a person with a low uncertainty tolerance may be looking at others after the slightest difference between his/her expected and actual outcomes, persons with a higher uncertainty tolerance may be less sensitive to such differences.

In the next section a perspective will be presented on the different cognitive processing strategies people may employ in their consumption behaviour.

Cognitive processing

Whereas the previous section was focused at the micro-level driving factors of human behaviour, this section is devoted to the cognitive processes people may employ and how these may be affected by the various driving factors. Cognitive processing refers to the strategies a person may employ in determining which behaviour to perform.

People may engage in different cognitive processes such as deliberation, social comparison, imitation and habit formation in deciding how to behave. Several general theories describe these processes, and explain under what conditions people are most likely to engage in them. These theories have been developed from a particular paradigmatic perspective. For example, in the behaviouristic tradition much research is focussed at how rewards and punishments shape routine behaviour, whilst the cognitivist tradition is concerned with mental processes such as information acquisitions and attitude change. Thus, theories in different traditions are focussed on different cognitive processes and associated factors.

Because environmental behaviour involves various kinds of behaviour processes and determinants, it is important to represent the different types of processing adequately in the conceptual meta-model of consumer behaviour. The model should integrate the several main cognitive processing types. This requires the specification of the conditions under which a certain cognitive processing style is most likely to be employed by a person. The different theories specify more or less explicitly under what conditions people are most likely to engage in the relevant processes. On the basis of these conditions two dimensions have been identified along which cognitive-processing theories can be organised. These two dimensions are, respectively, *reasoned* versus *automated* processing, and *individually* versus *socially* determined processing.

Reasoned versus automated processing

Reasoned processing implies that one is elaborating about need fulfilment, the characteristics of opportunities and/or strategies to improve one's abilities, thereby taking possible future outcomes into account. Reasoned processing is directed at the optimisation of possible outcomes. However, because people have limited cognitive resources, many of their daily routines are automated. Here, optimising is not focused exclusively on behavioural outcomes, but also on managing cognitive resources. Automated processing implies that one is using relatively simple heuristics in choosing what behaviour to perform, thereby focussing at the here and now. This automating of behaviour prevents people from e.g., spending hours in supermarkets deliberating over the various brands of products they can buy. Instead, people often habitually repeat their originally deliberate choices for as long as the outcomes are satisfying. However, a current habit may yield far from optimal outcomes because, for example, new better behavioural opportunities may have been introduced in the meantime.

The central factors that determine if an actor is more likely to engage in either reasoned or automated processing are: (1) the level of need satisfaction (LNS) of the actor and (2) the actor's behavioural control (BC). Frequently, actual behaviour is not satisfying anymore. This implies that one or more need-satisfying stocks are getting depleted. If a stock is so low that need satisfaction is seriously impaired (LNS gets below a critical value), one will be highly motivated to elaborate on alternative opportunities for consumption. This also holds for situations where the resource demands of an opportunity increase,

and/or the consumption abilities of an actor decrease. In such situations the actor may experience that an opportunity that formerly could be consumed without problems, has become unattainable. This causes the behavioural control (BC) over the previously consumed opportunity to become low, forcing the consumer to elaborate on alternative opportunities for consumption. For example, a person having plenty of financial resources and a driver's license may be very satisfied driving a car. However, if this person is increasingly being confronted with traffic jams, his or her satisfaction with car driving may get seriously impaired. Or suppose that the finances of this person drop significantly. This would result in a decrease in his/her behavioural control, possibly causing this person to be unable to afford a car anymore. In such cases the person will elaborate on alternative feasible opportunities to satisfy his/her needs. Returning to the example, our person could end up using the public transportation system, this being the only affordable opportunity that could satisfy his or her needs.

In situations where needs satisfaction is low and/or behavioural control is low (low LNS and/or low BC) it is a good strategy to elaborate on opportunities that are satisfying and feasible. In the process of elaboration, the person memorises information. In our conceptual model we have incorporated a 'mental-map' which functions as memory. Reasoned processing implies that the mental-map is being updated with actual information before a behavioural choice is made. Especially when one's abilities are low it is very hard (if not impossible) to find opportunities that both satisfy one's needs and are affordable in terms of behavioural control (BC). Often, one first has to increase one's abilities before one can afford a satisfying opportunity. Working to earn money is one of the main strategies to increase one's financial abilities, but also criminal activities may constitute an efficient (though risky) strategy. Sometimes, people cannot increase their abilities nor satisfy their needs sufficiently, which forcing them to live in poverty, crime, and/or sickness. If, however, people regularly find effective means to satisfy their needs, the urge to elaborate extensively on one's behavioural options diminishes and one can afford to behave in a more automated level.

If actors are satisfied with the opportunities they use, it appears that their need-satisfying stocks are filled sufficiently, guaranteeing a sufficient level of needs satisfaction (LNS). As long as their LNS is high, their motivation to further increase the stock levels is relatively low (increases are subject to diminishing marginal utility). Because of this, the actor will not be motivated to spend a lot of cognitive effort in scanning all the possible opportunities and updating his/her mental map. On the contrary, because the actor is satisfied it appears that his/her mental map functions adequately in guiding behaviour. As long as the actor is satisfied, he/she will not be motivated to update the mental map with new, actualised knowledge. However, because the environment may change, the mental map may become outdated. As a consequence, new, even more satisfying opportunities may be neglected, just as the negative or sub-optimal long-term outcomes of the current behaviour.

The consumption of an opportunity may demand more resources than the actor has available. In that case the actor's Behavioural Control (BC) is low (negative) and he/she has to find another opportunity that satisfies the particular need, or to increase his abilities (e.g., by earning money). This implies that the actor will shift towards a reasoning process. Updating the mental map may then reveal new satisfying opportunities or confront the actor with long-term negative outcomes.

Individual versus social processing

If an actor is gathering and processing information without considering the behaviour of others as a main source of information on behavioural opportunities, we speak of individual processing. A person may, however, incorporate expectations of how others are going to behave while processing individually, e.g., as in chess. If an actor is observing the behaviour of other actors as a means to get information on which opportunities are attractive to perform for oneself, we speak of social processing. Several factors determine the likelihood that an actor engages in individual or social processing. *Individual* processing is stimulated by:

- Relative certainty about the availability and the need-satisfying capacity of opportunities: The more stable the outcomes, the more certain the actor will be. Moreover, the fewer needs a certain category of opportunities satisfies (e.g., a refrigerator), the easier it gets to gather information on these need-satisfying capacities, and consequently, the more certain the actor will be. Finally, the higher is the cognitive ability of an actor, the more certain he/she will generally be.
- Visibility of opportunity use: The more private a given opportunity use is, the less information on other people's behaviour is available, and the less apparent the norms on proper opportunity use will be. Consequently, the comparison of possible opportunities for private use will be done in an individual manner.
- The cultural perspective of a consumer: For example, an individualist, experiencing few rules (low 'grid') and with hardly any group identity (low on 'group') will be more inclined towards individual information processing.
- The type of needs prevailing in a certain situation: More individually relevant needs, e.g. the need for subsistence, will entail a more individual style of cognitive processing.

Factors that stimulate *social* processing are:

- Relative uncertainty about availability and the need-satisfying capacity of opportunities: Especially when outcomes bear an unstable character, these outcomes may differ significantly from the expectations one had (in the mental map). In such a situation the change in actual need satisfaction and/or consumption ability as a result of behaviour is quite different than the consumer may have expected. As a consequence one may become uncertain. Moreover, the more needs are involved with a certain category of opportunities (e.g., dwelling, which is associated with the satisfaction of various needs), the harder it is to gather information on all stock-increasing capacities, and thus uncertainty will be larger. Finally, the lower the cognitive ability of an actor, the less certain he/she will generally be.
- Visibility of opportunity use: The more public an opportunity use is, the more information on other people's behaviour is available, and the more prevalent the norms on proper opportunity use will be.
- The cultural perspective of a consumer: For example, a hierarchist, experiencing many rules (high 'grid') and with a strong sense of belonging to a group (high on 'group') will be more inclined towards social information processing.
- The types of needs prevailing in a certain situation: More socially relevant needs, e.g. the need for identity, will entail more social processing styles.

Four cognitive processing styles

In the previous section the two dimensions of cognitive processing were discussed separately, first reasoned versus automated processing, followed by individual versus social

processing. These distinct dimensions yield a fourfold categorisation of existing behavioural theories. Several theories that are relevant for understanding the cognitive processes guiding consumer behaviour, can be organised in this fourfold perspective. For matters of clarity, the four processing types are labelled as *deliberation*, *social comparison*, *repetition* and *imitation*, respectively. These labels appear to grasp the essence of the cognitive processes described by the theories in the four quadrants of Table 5.4.

	Automated (high LNS, high BC)	Reasoned (low LNS, low BC)
Individually determined (certainty, private, individualist CP, personal needs)	Repetition (1) - Classical conditioning theory - Operant conditioning theory	Deliberation (2) - Decision and choice theory - Theory of reasoned/planned behaviour (attitude and perceived control)
Social determined (uncertainty, public visibility, egalitarian CP, social needs)	Imitation (3) - Social learning theory - Theory of normative conduct	Social comparison (4) - Social comparison theory - Relative deprivation theory - Theory of reasoned/planned behaviour (social norm)

Table 5.4: A classification of eight major theories on human behaviour. LNS = level of need satisfaction, BC = Behavioural Control and CP = Cultural Perspective (based on Jager et al., 1997)

The theories presented in Table 5.4 provide a comprehensive framework explaining under what conditions which type of cognitive processing is most likely to occur. In the following sections the different theories on behaviour are briefly discussed under the heading of the cognitive processing styles they apply to.

Repetition: theories of individually automated behaviour (quadrant 1 of Table 5.4)

Theories of individual automated behaviour apply mainly to situations where consumers have a relatively high level of need satisfaction and behavioural control. Therefore, elaboration on finding alternative opportunities and/or on increasing their own abilities is not necessary. Moreover, these theories apply to situations where outcome-uncertainty is relatively low, opportunity use is less publicly visible, the needs in question are more individually relevant, and consumers have a more individualistic cultural perspective.

Cognitivist theories on reasoned behaviour emphasise the cognitive processes of deliberation and choice before performing a given behaviour, whilst they are more or less presuming that the consumer is a rational actor. In contrast, behaviouristic theories rely more on the *reduction of drives* as pressures towards behaviour, and as such they emphasise the outcomes of a performed behaviour. The dissatisfaction of a given need is assumed to lead towards a drive to satisfy that need. If the need is fulfilled, the drive is reduced. For example, ingesting food is a need, whereas hunger is the drive to fulfil that need. People are conceived as being biologically motivated to reduce drives with respect to basic physiological and safety needs (Maslow, 1954; Max-Neef, 1992; see above in this chapter). Behaviours that are successful in reducing those drives are experienced as *rewarding*.

The *Classical Conditioning Theory*, as studied by Pavlov (1927), describes the process of how the performance of behaviours can be linked to stimuli that are indirectly related to the reduction of a drive. Pavlov's most famous experiment showed that, after a light was

repeatedly turned on before a dog was fed, the dog salivated already in response to the light itself. Instead of showing the unconditional or natural response: salivating when confronted with food, the dog had learned that the turning on of the light preceded the presentation of food. As a result, the salivation at the light developed as a *conditioned* response. This is called *response acquisition*. As long as the conditional stimulus is followed by an unconditioned reward, a conditioned response will occur. When the reward is omitted, the conditioned response will continue to occur for some time, but it will eventually diminish, thus revealing *extinction* of the relevant behaviour. Conditioned stimulus-response relationships in fact are simple, primitive ‘if-then’ rules by which behaviour is automated and cognitive processing is strongly reduced. For example, a popular conditioned stimulus-response mechanism is; *if* you have to travel for more than two kilometres, *then* you take your car, because you ‘automatically’ expect positive travel experiences when doing so.

Where classical conditioning is based on linking existing natural responses to new, ‘unnatural’ stimuli, *Operant Conditioning Theory* (Skinner, 1938; 1953) describes the process of learning new, previously nonexistent responses. If, in a given stimulus situation, an immediate reinforcement or a punishment is experienced after performing a (coincidental) behaviour, the principles of operant conditioning apply. Positive reinforcements or rewards stimulate the repetition of the relevant behaviour. After experiencing a reward, people are motivated to repeat the preceding behaviour. Eventually, even an occasional rewarding of the behaviour (e.g. only 1 out of 10 times) will suffice to let the behaviour continue to occur. Furthermore, people may try to find out if similar rewards appear when the behaviour is slightly altered or performed in somewhat different situations. Following this *principle of contingent reinforcement*, the behaviour can evolve and be performed in comparable situations. Negative reinforcements are concerned with the experience of physically or socially negative outcomes after performing a given behaviour. Thus such behaviour will be unlearned or extinguished. Negative outcomes may be avoided by performing another behaviour to which they are not associated. The performance of new behaviour may thus be motivated either by the expectation of still higher rewards, or by the desire to avoid negative outcomes associated with current behaviour.

Because classical and operant conditioning theories only apply to situations with a small time interval between behaviour and ‘contingent’ reinforcement, long-term outcomes can only affect behaviour through explicit cognitive processing (reasoning). Furthermore, one has to experience outcomes that can be clearly attributed to one’s individual behaviour. Therefore, classical and operant learning theories imply that time-dispersed and collective outcomes largely occur beyond the scope of (individual) conditioning processes because of: (1) the large time interval between performing behaviour and experiencing the corresponding outcomes, and (2) the impossibility of precisely identifying one’s own contribution to collective outcomes. In some cases, where performing a specific behaviour leads to rewards in the short term, but to negative outcomes in the long run, conditioned and cognitive response processes may conflict. If one is well aware of the negative long-term outcomes resulting from a given behaviour but unable, at the same time, to give up the short-term positive outcomes, we can speak of *addictive behaviour*.

Deliberation: theories of individually reasoned behaviour (quadrant 2 of Table 5.4)

Theories of individually reasoned behaviour apply mainly to situations where consumers have a relatively low level of need satisfaction and/or behavioural control. Thus,

consumers are forced to elaborate on alternative opportunities and/or on increasing their abilities. Moreover, these theories apply to situations where outcome-uncertainty is relatively low, opportunity use less publicly visible, the needs in question more individually relevant, and where consumers have a more individualistic cultural perspective.

Decision and Choice Theory addresses the process of cognitive elaboration that precedes the making of deliberate choices. Decision theory deals with the question of how people actually decide (descriptive research) and how they should optimally decide (prescriptive research). Because the prescriptive branch of decision theory is more relevant in the context of strategies for behaviour change, this will be discussed in the section on policy instruments and behavioural change. Within the descriptive branch of decision theory, Janis and Mann (1977) discriminate between an optimising and a satisficing strategy. Optimising refers to a decision strategy leading to maximal expected utility. This strategy requires the elaboration of all available information. To apply an optimising strategy, an actor must be highly motivated, have strong cognitive abilities and sufficient decision-making time. Three stages can be identified in the optimising strategy: (1) information acquisition, (2) structuring the decision-making problem and (3) evaluating alternative options (opportunities) and making a choice (Vlek, Timmermans and Otten, 1993). Economic theories on consumer behaviour typically regard consumers as rational individuals (see also Chapter 3 on optimisation of behaviour). In this view, consumers try to optimise their utility (welfare), given their available budget (Green, Tunstall, N'Jai, and Rogers, 1990; Opschoor, 1993).

Often people lack the motivation, the cognitive ability and/or the time to employ an optimising strategy. Furthermore, people have a limited capacity to store and elaborate upon information (Newell and Simon, 1972; Shiffrin, 1975). Consequently, people often use a satisficing strategy, which involves choosing an option that is 'good enough' for them (Simon, 1976; Janis and Mann, 1977). For instance, one can select the option with the highest score on the most important attribute. If two or more options score equally well, the procedure can be repeated for the second important attribute (this is the *lexicographical decision heuristic*). A comprehensive listing of decision heuristics is given by Timmermans (1991). These heuristics allow for quick and effective decision-making, albeit through reduced information processing, so that more preferable options may be overlooked. In general, the type of decision process one follows depends on one's information processing motivation (driven by the importance of the related needs), the complexity of the opportunities one has to choose from and one's cognitive and temporal abilities.

The *Theories of Reasoned Action and of Planned Behaviour* (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 1985, 1991) are based on the assumption that individuals are rational human beings who make systematic use of the information available to them when choosing between alternative opportunities. The concepts employed in the theory of reasoned action are fundamentally cognitive in nature, i.e., the behaviour is supposed to depend on the intention to perform a given behaviour. The stronger a person's *intention*, the more he/she is willing to try to act in the corresponding way, and the greater the likelihood that such behaviour is actually being performed. The *Theory of Reasoned Action* (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975) specifies two conceptually independent determinants of *intention*. The first is a personal factor termed the *attitude towards the behaviour* and refers to the individual's positive or negative evaluation of using an opportunity. This attitude consists of one's *beliefs* that using an opportunity will lead to certain outcomes, weighted by the *evaluations* of those

outcomes. The second determinant of behavioural intention is a social factor, called the *subjective norm*, or one's perception of what other people consider to be appropriate (the 'injunctive norm', see below), which will be discussed in the section on socially reasoned behaviour.

The *Theory of Planned Behaviour* (Ajzen, 1985, 1988, 1991) is an extension of the *Theory of Reasoned Action* (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The extension consists of including the concept of *perceived behavioural control*, i.e., the person's belief as to how feasible the use of an opportunity is likely to be. Both one's abilities and opportunities can interfere with control over the intended behaviour. The more personal resources individuals think they possess and the fewer resource demands they anticipate, the greater their perceived behavioural control. Perception of control has an important impact on a person's behavioural intention (Ajzen and Madden, 1985). Generally, the greater the perceived behavioural control, the stronger is a person's intention to try to perform the relevant behaviour. A low level of behavioural control can lead to a negative adjustment of formerly positive attitudes (Golob, Horowitz and Wachs, 1979). However, the perceived behavioural control also affects behaviour in a more direct manner, e.g., by making it impossible to perform a certain behaviour despite one's positive intentions towards it. Figure 5.4 schematically represents the *Theory of Planned Behaviour*.

Figure 5.4: The Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1985, 1988, 1991; Ajzen and Madden, 1985)

Imitation: theories of socially automated behaviour (quadrant 3 of Table 5.4)

Theories of socially automated behaviour apply mainly to situations where consumers have a relatively high level of need satisfaction and behavioural control. Therefore, elaboration on alternative opportunities and/or on increasing abilities is not necessary. Moreover, these theories apply to situations where personal outcome-uncertainty is relatively high, opportunity use is publicly visible, the needs in question are more socially relevant and consumers have a more egalitarian cultural perspective.

Besides directly experiencing personal reinforcement, seeing someone else being reinforced following his/her behaviour may also affect one's behaviour. Such processes are expressed in *Social Learning Theory* (Bandura, 1977; 1986). Social learning may occur directly while seeing someone being reinforced. However, also the media (such as radio and television, e.g., Liebert, Neale, and Davidson, 1973) and verbal representations (e.g., stories) may evoke social learning. Teaching new behaviour using exemplary behaviour is called *modelling* (Bandura, 1977). Because one has to be aware of someone else's experiences, social learning theory asserts the occurrence of reasoned processes in addition

to plainly automated processes. From being aware of someone else's (rewarding) behaviour towards performing that behaviour yourself, five steps have to be taken. These are, respectively, being *attentive* to the behaviour of someone else, *understanding* and *remembering* that behaviour, being able to *reproduce* that behaviour, and experiencing *reinforcement* after performing the behaviour yourself (Bandura, 1977). As such, social learning involves the abilities one has (for attention, understanding, recollection), the opportunities and skills to reproduce the behaviour, and the motivation as driven by expected reinforcement.

Socially automated behaviour may also occur in the form of simple compliance to social norms. According to the *Theory of Normative Conduct* (Cialdini, Kallgren and Reno, 1991), three distinct types of norms affect human actions. First, social norms of the *descriptive* kind guide one's behaviour via the perception of how most other people (would) actually behave. Second, social norms of the *injunctive* kind guide one's behaviour via the perception of how most other people would approve or disapprove of one's behaviour. Third, *personal* norms guide one's behaviour via the perception of how one would approve or disapprove of one's own behaviour oneself. The behaviour of people is likely to conform to the norm that is currently in focus, even when the other types of norm dictate contrary behaviour.

Social comparison: theories of socially reasoned behaviour (quadrant 4 of Table 5.4)

Theories of socially reasoned behaviour apply mainly to situations where consumers have a relatively low level of need satisfaction and/or behavioural control. Therefore, people are forced to elaborate on alternative opportunities and/or on increasing their abilities. Moreover, these theories apply to situations where personal outcome-uncertainty is relatively high, the opportunity use is publicly visible, the needs in question are more socially relevant and the consumers have a more egalitarian cultural perspective.

As shown in the previous section, the *Theory of Planned Behaviour* (Ajzen, 1985, 1988, 1991) also includes a social factor, the *subjective norm*, which refers to a person's perception of the opinion of others about him/her performing the relevant behaviour. The subjective norm is proposed as a function of one's *beliefs* that referents think whether the person should or should not perform the behaviour (called the injunctive norm), weighted by the *motivation to comply* with those referents (see *Figure 5.4*). Becoming aware of a subjective (social) norm would involve an assessment of relevant others and an appreciation of their behavioural intentions. Specific theories on social norms describe both reasoned and automated behaviour. In this respect, the *Theory of Planned Behaviour* overlaps with the *Theory of Normative Conduct* (Cialdini *et al.*, 1991; see the previous section on imitation).

Social Comparison Theory (Festinger, 1954) states that people are motivated to consciously compare their opinions and abilities with those of other people. These comparisons follow dimensions such as the possession of material goods, financial means, status, principles, attitudes and skills. With respect to opinions, people have a drive to roughly conform to others. With respect to abilities, people have a drive to be (somewhat) superior to others. Especially in new (unfamiliar) situations, these comparisons provide information about what is/are proper behaviour and opinions. Social comparison processes not only occur at the individual level, but also at the group level (Faucheux and Moscovici, 1972). Two important factors determine the degree of comparison between persons in a group (Festinger, 1954): the more *similar* group members are, and the more *cohesive* a group is, the more strongly members are motivated to compare themselves with

others in the group. More recently, social comparison processes with respect to personal status and achievements have been the focus of research (Buunk and De Vries, 1991). Theories on relative deprivation describe social comparison processes in terms of social justification and indicate that one's achievements relative to others are often valued more than one's absolute achievements (e.g. Masters and Smith, 1987). For example, someone driving a new Volkswagen in an average small town may experience more status than someone driving the same Volkswagen in Beverly Hills may. Because people generally prefer a positive outcome of a social comparisons, this process appears to stimulate a continuous upward social mobility, a permanent striving towards the improvement of one's own position compared to the position of relevant others.

Opportunity consumption

The cognitive process a consumer follows eventuates in a behavioural choice. This involves the consumption of one or more (or a part of) opportunities. People usually perform different behaviours in time, and in doing so they combine the use of various opportunities. For example, during the day people may work, travel, eat, watch television and play. Considering each type of activity as a separate opportunity, it is appropriate to describe the behaviour of a consumer in terms of distribution of opportunity consumption. Such a distribution shows how frequently certain types of opportunities are being used. Within this context, work is also being considered as an opportunity, because it usually increases the (financial) abilities of a consumer, and thus indirectly contributes to the satisfaction of needs. However, work may also involve intrinsic need-satisfying characteristics, such as identity, participation and creation.

The dynamical structure of the conceptual meta-model (Figure 5.1) implies the idea that the consumption of opportunities involves feedbacks towards the driving forces of behaviour. At the micro-level, opportunity consumption yields changes of personal stock-levels related to need satisfaction, changes in experienced uncertainty and changes in ability. At the macro-level, the aggregated opportunity consumption of many consumers yields changes in the natural and the human environment, which in turn affects the opportunities available at the micro-level. These different outcomes are being discussed into detail in the following sections.

The satisfaction of needs

The utilisation of opportunities may satisfy (or frustrate) several consumer needs. If a need is satisfied, a person's immediate motivation to use the relevant need-satisfying opportunity again will decrease, for as long as the need remains satisfied. In the situation where the consumption of a particular opportunity does not satisfy a certain need, the consumer's motivation to use this opportunity again will decrease. These feedbacks from opportunity consumption to the satisfaction of needs regulate the frequency and intensity of opportunity use, and they guide the cognitive process.

With respect to the need-satisfying outcomes of opportunity use, it can be stated that the more his or her needs are satisfied, the better off the consumer will be. The need satisfaction resulting from a (combined) opportunity use can be conceived as a contribution to one's *quality of life*. The concept of *quality of life* (QoL) is defined here as the

extent of multivariate need satisfaction, in terms of a taxonomy such as presented in Tables 5.1 and 5.2.

Changes in abilities

Behaviour will also affect the abilities a consumer has. Some behaviours like working are mainly performed to increase one's (financial) abilities. However, as stated before, such behaviours may also satisfy needs, e.g., working may satisfy one's needs for participation and creation. Opportunity consumption often costs abilities (e.g., money) or requires a certain level of an ability (e.g., knowledge). For example, the purchasing of a car will have consequences for the consumer's physical abilities (e.g., a higher mobility), financial means and social life. Regarding changing abilities, we distinguish between four basic types of outcomes: (1) physical outcomes, e.g. one's ability to move around, (2) regulatory and enforcement outcomes, e.g. the withdrawal or granting of a license, (3) financial-economic outcomes, e.g. one's available budget and (4) social and cognitive outcomes, e.g. changes in knowledge and social support. These changes of consumer abilities may be positive (e.g. increasing knowledge) and negative (e.g. financial budget reductions). Also, performing a certain behaviour may affect the attainability of other behaviour. For example, the purchasing of a car may reduce one's financial abilities to afford a proper house. That car, however, may provide the means to develop the skills for running a freight transport business. Thus, the use of a certain opportunity will affect one's abilities, and thus one's behavioural control over other opportunities. These feedbacks and interactions reflect the process of substitution between different opportunities, and they refer to the autonomous or self-regulating processes that guide consumption and behaviour change.

If the actor's abilities are insufficient to consume a certain opportunity, yet the actor is very motivated to consume it, he/she may try to increase his/her abilities. Work is a main strategy to increase financial abilities. Education and training are strategies to increase knowledge and skills.

Changes in uncertainty

Consumers always have certain expectations regarding the outcomes of their behaviour. However, if the actual outcomes of behaviour are different from these expectations, the consumer may experience uncertainty. For example, the fisherman may be confronted with an unexpected drop in the fish-catch and the commuter may suddenly be confronted with traffic jams. Especially when the expectations follow from an outdated mental-map (no reasoned processing having taken place for a long time), the chances rise that a large difference emerges between expectations and actual outcomes. The uncertainty tolerance of people reflects their sensitivity to such differences.

Changes in the natural and human environment

The behaviour of many consumers yields aggregated outcomes that affect the natural and human environment. The consumption of various opportunities involves the use of natural resources such as forests, live-stock, plants, energy (renewable and non-renewable), water, materials, space, environment and the like, as well as the production of waste. To assess the environmental outcomes of a particular opportunity distribution, the resulting amount of resource use will have to be translated into environmental impacts. At this stage, information on the natural (environmental) outcomes of the behaviour is needed. For example, the energy use of an actor will depend on the type of work (s)he has, the

mode of travelling, the use of household appliances and the like. Here, the outcomes of human consumption are indicated in terms of litres of water, miles of transportation, kWh electricity, m³ natural gas, but also in terms of natural resources that are being consumed or wasted (e.g., fish, clean air, woods). Here, the link can be made with scientific knowledge about the dynamics of ecosystems, which are often formalised in models of environmental processes. If a behavioural model is formalised to assess consumption volumes, these volumes could be used as inputs for environmental models. On the other hand, environmental models may provide the necessary input to assess changes in the natural environment as a macro-level determinant of consumer behaviour. Depending on the level of consumption and the type of opportunity (e.g. exhaustible, renewable, recyclable), a scarcity or even a depletion of natural resources may occur. Especially in the case of renewable resources, over-consumption may be understood as the overshooting of the carrying capacity of a certain provision system. Such developments at the macro-level have direct repercussions for the availability of opportunities for individual consumers. Sources of opportunities thus may change as result of their use.

The human environment involves developments in technology, economy, demography, institutions and culture (the T.E.D.I.C.-complex as described earlier in this chapter). The aggregated outcomes of consumer behaviour also have impacts on these developments. For example, new opportunities may be developed, the prices of opportunities may change, more people may have to share the same common resources, institutions may impose restrictions on certain types of opportunity use, and the cultural perspective of large groups of people may change as result of sustained changes in need satisfaction. Because these developments interact with developments in natural ecological systems, researchers often integrate them in so-called ecological-economic models (e.g., ISLAND; Engelen *et al.* 1995; Lakeland; De Greef and De Vries, 1991, see also Chapter 1 on integrated modelling).

The human environment also involves the characteristics of consumers who are using certain opportunities. The need-satisfying characteristics of an opportunity can be affected by information on which type of consumer uses a certain opportunity. For example, if only high-status consumers use a particular opportunity (e.g., playing tennis), other consumers may subsequently perceive this opportunity as more socially rewarding (e.g. satisfying the need for identity), and they thereby may become more motivated to use this opportunity as well. The more people use that particular opportunity, the less it will satisfy the need for identity of the people that originally consumed that product. This will increase the motivation of these people to find new opportunities that will satisfy their need for identity (e.g., playing golf). This process, in which people 'chase' one another in consumptive behaviour in order to demonstrate their social status is often referred to as 'keeping up with the Jones'', where the Jones' stand for the average middle-class family. In the short run, this process seems to work within relatively homogeneous groups, where neighbours and friends are comparing themselves with one another. In the long run, these effects lead to behaviour of 'higher classes' being adopted by 'lower classes', while 'higher classes' have to develop new standards to keep up their high-status identity. Elias (1984) extensively discusses these processes in his work on the civilisation process. Processes of feedback, involving information on which kind of people use which opportunities, seem to be essential in understanding this societal drive.

Strategies for behavioural change

Various interest parties, e.g., individuals, governments, producers, churches and consumer organisations, use various strategies to influence people's behaviour. Many of these interest parties operate on the micro-level of society. For example, my little daughter has an arsenal of strategies that she applies in attempting to change my behaviour from reading a newspaper to playing with her. These strategies range from acting pitiful in order to draw attention, to making it physically impossible for me to read the paper. In a similar manner, many people in our daily lives act upon our driving forces. In general, family, friends, colleagues and strangers are interest parties at the micro-level that frequently attempt to change our behaviour.

Whereas the forces applied to us by micro-level actors are often short-term oriented, bear no systematic character and are usually being directed at a single person, actors at the macro-level usually try to affect the behaviour of larger groups of people in a systematic way. Two main interest parties at the macro-level that spend a lot of effort in changing (or consolidating) consumptive behaviours are the government and the suppliers/producers. However, also various consumer organisations, environmental organisations, interest groups, churches and the like may spend efforts in trying to change consumer behaviour. Many strategies aimed at changing behaviour are being employed, such as taxes, advertisement, laws and product development and innovation. Within the context of stimulating a sustainable development of consumer behaviour, these systematic efforts are the most interesting in making an inventory of strategies for behavioural change.

Changing the driving forces of behaviour

In order to make a systematic inventory on the strategies and tactics that can be used in changing behaviour, it is necessary to draw a perspective of how policy measures may affect the driving factors of behaviour. In terms of the conceptual meta-model, policy measures are aimed at changing the driving factors of behaviour. These changes thereby may affect the cognitive process consumers engage in, and they are ultimately aimed at changing the resulting behaviours. Strategies to change consumer behaviour are generally focussed at four types of driving factors: (1) the need-satisfying capacity of opportunities, (2) the resource demands of opportunities, (3) the abilities of consumers and (4) the perspective on people's preferred mode of need satisfaction.

Changing the need-satisfying capacities of opportunities indirectly affects the consumer's *motivation* to use an opportunity. This motivational change will only occur if one actually perceives the opportunity change. The consumer's perception of opportunity changes may be the result of personal reflection, external information and/or persuasion, own experiences with the need-satisfying characteristics of consumer goods and services, or via the observation of other consumers' behaviour and outcomes. If a consumer is not aware of a change before using an opportunity, there will be a difference in expected and actual need-satisfying outcomes. Outcomes that differ from the expectations one had may give rise to uncertainty and stimulate processes of social comparison.

Increasing need-satisfying aspects often is relatively easy to do, and many suppliers of opportunities (e.g. producers) make large efforts to increase the need-satisfying aspects of their products by improving existing products and developing new ones. Decreasing the need-satisfying capacity of an opportunity is often hard because people may find it hard to

accept such a loss of need satisfaction. For example, very few consumers would like measures that make cars less comfortable or long-distance holidays less appealing.

Changing the resource demands of opportunities can be achieved by using laws, prices, information, and the like. As such, opportunities that are not preferred by the government may be taxed or prohibited, and preferred opportunities may be subsidised or propagated. Policy measures that address the sheer availability of opportunities may also be conceived as affecting the resource demands. Changing the resource demands of an opportunity obviously influences the *behavioural control* a consumer has. Increasing the ability demands of an opportunity results in a decrease in consumers' behavioural control. Decreasing ability demands results in an increase in behavioural control. Furthermore, if a consumer is unaware of a change in the resource demands of an opportunity, he or she may experience a difference between expected and actual outcomes, resulting in insecurity and thus stimulating processes of social comparison.

Changing the abilities of consumers (consumer resources) involves instruments that increase or decrease consumer abilities. For example, income taxes decrease the financial abilities a consumer has, and education increases the knowledge of consumers. Changing consumer abilities also changes the *behavioural control* of consumers. Increasing abilities will result in an increasing behavioural control, whilst decreasing abilities result in a decreasing behavioural control. Thus, as discussed before, consumer abilities (resources) and opportunity resource demands are two sides of the same coin.

Changing the perspective people have on the preferred mode of need satisfaction is based on the notion that the level of need-satisfaction is partly determined by the cultural perspective a consumer adheres to. Consumers with an equal type of consumption may experience different levels of need-satisfaction (quality-of-life) due to their differing cultural perspectives. For example, a consumer with an individualistic perspective will be more focussed at personal needs satisfaction, whereas a person adhering to a more egalitarian perspective will be more likely to include the outcomes for other people and the environment in his/her consumption decisions. Consequently, a change in cultural perspective may change one's experienced level of need satisfaction, thereby changing one's motivation to consume certain opportunities. Moreover, such a change in cultural perspective may also change one's perception of the need-satisfying capacities of opportunities in general, thereby (indirectly) also changing one's motivation to consume certain types of opportunities. Such a change in motivation may pertain to general categories of consumer activities such as eating, transport and holiday-making. Consequently, strategies aimed at a change of cultural perspective might be effective in changing coherent patterns of consumer behaviour, thus changing people's life-style. The cultural perspective a consumer adheres to may be changed via modifications in people's values, norms and morality underlying people's satisfaction with their current and/or expected future quality-of-life. This may be accomplished through 'value debates', confrontations with others adhering to different cultural perspectives and concomitant life-styles, resulting in a different (not lesser) quality of life.

The dynamics of behavioural change

The efficacy of policy instruments directed at behavioural change depends on how well a behavioural process is approached. For example, if a consumer is highly motivated to use an opportunity, but is lacking an adequate behavioural control, he or she will be motivated to elaborate on alternative opportunities and/or on strategies to increase behavioural

control, and it is likely that new information will be taken into consideration. In contrast, a consumer with a low motivation to elaborate will not consider new information; inducing a behaviour change then requires other (combinations of) instruments. As said before, policy measures affect the driving forces of behaviour and thus may cause a shift in the cognitive process people engage in. A clear example may be derived from attempts at changing habits. As previously stated, habitual behaviour involves minor cognitive processing. Only direct positive outcomes will maintain the perseverance of a habit. Policy measures aimed at changing a given habitual behaviour may be focussed at the elimination of direct positive outcomes, the administration of direct negative outcomes, or the increase of resource demands. Because this means that the habit is not satisfactory and/or feasible anymore, people will engage in reasoned processing (deliberation or social comparison) in order to find new need-satisfying opportunities. During reasoned processing the consumer may include information on long-term outcomes in his/her evaluation of behavioural opportunities. Consequently, information may play an important role in the change of habitual behaviour, but only if people are 'being forced' to engage in reasoned processing. If a more need-satisfying opportunity is found, and the consumer has a high behavioural control over that opportunity, a new habit may emerge, which involves a shifting back to (a new) automated behaviour.

The four types of cognitive processes (Table 5.4) thus differ regarding their sensitivity to changes in the various driving forces. Because behavioural change is a process in which people frequently switch between the cognitive processes that guide their behaviour, it is necessary to use a *combination* of instruments to guide the total process of behavioural change. These instruments must be targeted at the relevant cognitive processes at the right time in order to tackle the relevant behavioural dynamics. Therefore, it is necessary to make an inventory of what the different theories of behaviour, that apply to the four cognitive processing types, have to say on changing behaviour. But first it is necessary to make an inventory of the general strategies that can be used in changing these cognitive processes and the resulting behaviour.

Five general strategies for behavioural change

There are five scientific disciplines that deal explicitly with behaviour change, namely technical science, law, economics, psychology/ sociology and moral philosophy/cultural anthropology¹⁰. This categorisation by and large reflects the categorisation of strategies by, e.g., Sheth and Frazier, 1982; Cook and Berrenberg, 1981; De Young, 1993; and Vlek and Michon, 1992. In line with these disciplines, five corresponding types of general strategies for behavioural change are recognised: (1) providing physical alternatives and arrangements, (2) regulation and enforcement, (3) financial-economic stimulation, (4) social and cognitive stimulation, and (5) changing values and morality.

1. Provision of physical alternatives and (re)arrangements may change the consumer's set of opportunities. New behavioural opportunities are shaped or existing opportunities are deleted through changing technology and infrastructure. The basic assumption is that changing the physical environment in which behaviour takes place can shape this behaviour. Firstly, this strategy may change the need-satisfying capacity of opportunities. This would subsequently change the consumer's motivation to use opportunities. For

¹⁰ In the policy development process the focus is usually at technical science, law, economics and psychology/ sociology, at the neglect of moral philosophy/cultural anthropology.

example, making public transportation more comfortable may result in an increasing motivation to actually use it. Secondly, this strategy may change the physical resource demands of an opportunity. This involves a change of the behavioural control a consumer has. For example, closing a street for car-traffic (e.g. during certain hours) will substantially decrease consumers' behavioural control over driving there. If this decrease of behavioural control is significant, consumers cannot drive there by car (as much as they used to) and may become motivated to elaborate on alternative travelling opportunities and strategies to increase ability (substitutions). Some exemplary types of physical alternatives and (re)arrangements are:

- Optimisation of existing technology (e.g., improving efficiency). For example, cars can be made to run more kilometres on a litre of gasoline, and more energy-efficient wood-fired cooking stoves can be produced.
- Innovation and development leads to new technologies refers to the development of new opportunities. For example, new small-scale types of windmills have been developed for the generation of electricity and the pumping of water. Cars with electric engines have been developed, to reduce harmful emissions.
- Infrastructural change refers to the change of a system of opportunities or the development of a new system. For example, a new railway offers new opportunities to travel, and the development of computer networks (Internet) provides new opportunities for communication.

2. *Regulation-and-enforcement* serves to restrict or extend the set of behavioural opportunities one has. This strategy is based on the issuing and enforcement of laws, rules, regulations and standards adopted by the government. Their violations - if detected - are met with some kind of punishment, fine or disapproval. This requires an adequate organisation for supervision, monitoring and enforcement. Regulations typically change opportunity demands and/or consumer abilities, thereby altering the behavioural control consumers have. It is assumed that regulations eventually will be internalised, thereby leading to a motivational change, i.e., a change in the perceived need-satisfying capacities of an opportunity. Some exemplary types of regulation-and-enforcement are:

- Civil law determines the rules that apply to interactions between citizens. For example, civil law provides rules for business transactions between citizens and rules concerning private property.
- Constitutional law determines the rules that the government imposes on its citizens. For example, constitutional law determines product characteristics (e.g. rules for additives in food) and speed limits.
- International law determines the rules that apply to the interaction between states. For example, governments may take measures like boycotting a country to force it to conform to international civil rights and may regulate the freedom of trade (e.g. the NAFTA agreement) and travelling (e.g. the Schengen agreement).

3. *Financial-economic stimulation* is aimed at changing the pay-off structure of a set of opportunities. Preferred behaviours may be financially rewarded using subsidies and discounts, while unpreferred behaviours may be financially punished using taxes and fines. The basic assumption is that the behaviour of people is susceptible to the price mechanism, and that the demand-price elasticities involved are reasonably high. Financial-economic stimulation can be directed at specific (types of) opportunities, thereby altering

the behavioural control consumers have. Moreover, the financial ability consumers have may be changed, e.g., by changing the tax system. Some exemplary types of financial-economic stimulation are:

- Micro-economic measures are exploiting the price mechanism. They are directed at changing the financial abilities that the use of an opportunity requires. Examples are the taxing of luxury goods and the subsidising of public transportation.
- Macro-economic measures mainly address the financial abilities of consumers in a country. Examples are measures to change interest rates, budgetary deficits and national debts.

4. *Social and cognitive stimulation* may be aimed at increasing public problem awareness and altering problem perception, thereby motivating people towards preferred behaviours. This strategy involves giving information, education, arguments, social rewards, behavioural examples (role models), prompts and advice. Changes in attitudes and values, seeing role models being rewarded and changes in people's perceptions of their quality-of-life are assumed to change the perception of the need-satisfying capacities that opportunities have, thereby changing consumers' motivation. Also, offering knowledge and advice can increase consumers' ability to change their behaviour. The basic assumption is that specific behaviours are determined by cognitions and by social factors, such as social norms and customs. Some exemplary types of social and cognitive stimulation are:

- Informing consumers about the (dis)advantages of certain opportunities, which may change their motivation and subsequently their behaviour.
- Social modelling and support, which may change consumers' motivation. For example, if high-status persons propagate and demonstrate the use of a certain opportunity, consumers may perceive that opportunity as status-increasing (need for identity). Also, exemplary behaviour may facilitate the reproduction of that behaviour, because copying behaviour often requires fewer consumer abilities than extensive elaboration on the outcomes of that behaviour.

5. *Changing values and morality* involves appeals to the conscience of consumers. This may involve attempts to enhance their 'altruism' or 'cooperativeness' towards other actors and future generations, e.g., by means of increasing their trust in other consumers' behaviour. However, also individualism, nationalism and religious extremism may be the targets of this general strategy. Changing values and morality may also entail a change in people's conceptions of quality-of-life, particularly in the relative importance they attach to collective and environmental qualities as components of their notion of human welfare and sustainable development. It is assumed that a change in morality is reflected in a changing cultural perspective, e.g., a consumer may move from a more individualistic perspective towards a more egalitarian perspective. Such a change of values or morality implies that one's perception and motivation to consume opportunities in general may change. Consequently, this strategy might be effective in changing life-styles.

The strategy of changing or preserving values and morality is by nature the domain of religious and other ideological and cultural groups and organisations. Also the government has means to influence existing values and morality, e.g. by means of the educational system, general campaigns and the media. For example, stressing the fact that some behaviours have negative outcomes for other people (or the collective), and

appealing to the principle of reciprocity, may both motivate people to change their behaviour for reasons of fairness.

Levels of strategies for behavioural change

The above mentioned general strategies may be directed at individual consumers (the *micro-level* of society), but also at organisations such as industries, special interest groups, public services and so forth, and at the level of countries and international organisations such as the World Bank and the OECD (the *macro-level*). Especially when the behaviour of individuals is embedded in or determined by organisational structures of a higher level, applying the strategies at the macro-level may indirectly affect the behavioural opportunities one may employ at the micro-level. For example, setting energy-use standards for the appliances produced by an industry (regulation-and-enforcement at the macro-level) may indirectly affect the opportunities a consumer at the micro-level can use, via the (derived) strategy of providing other physical alternatives and (re)arrangements. Strategies employed at the macro-level may strongly affect the behavioural processes at the macro and micro-levels of society. For example, a free-trade agreement may have effects on both the producers and consumers of goods and services.

Dimensions of strategies for behavioural change

The five strategies just discussed can, alone or in combination, be incorporated in specific policy instruments. A policy instrument may include elements of different strategies. Policy instruments are defined as ‘all means an actor has decided to use to achieve one or more policy goals’ (Klok, 1991). Van der Doelen (1989) discerns three dimensions to categorise the great variety of possible policy instruments. The first differentiates between *directing* and *constituting* instruments. Directing instruments are aimed at influencing the behavioural process directly, e.g., by means of information, prices and prohibitions. Constituting policy instruments are aimed at creating preconditions for a behavioural change, e.g. by means of education, developing infrastructure and issuing constitutional law.

The second dimension differentiates between *collective* and *individual* policy instruments. Collective instruments are aimed at influencing simultaneously many consumers in different situations, e.g., by means of mass-media campaigns, regulating prices and general laws. Individual instruments are aimed at influencing specific groups of individuals in specific situations, e.g., by means of advice, levies and licences.

The third dimension discerned by Van der Doelen (1989) refers to instruments that either *restrict* or *extend* people’s freedom of choice. Restrictive instruments are aimed at decreasing the behavioural control consumers have over an opportunity, e.g., by means of propaganda, raising prices and prohibitions. As such, restrictive instruments are usually directed at restricting the use of opportunities not favoured by policy. Extending instruments are aimed at increasing the behavioural control consumers have over a desired opportunity, e.g., by means of information, subsidies and privileges. As such, these instruments are usually directed at stimulating the use of opportunities favoured by policy.

In the previous sections we have drawn a perspective on the general strategies that can be used in changing behaviour, and how they can be used in policy measures. In the following section we will describe how these strategies affect the cognitive processes and what the relevant theories have to say about changing behaviour.

Cognitive processing and behavioural change

When one makes an inventory of psychological knowledge on behavioural change, one will observe that most of the body of knowledge originates from theories that have been organised here under ‘cognitive processing’ instead of under ‘driving forces of behaviour’. That does not imply that those theories have nothing to say about the driving forces of behaviour. However, because they are focussed on particular cognitive processes they do not take account for the various driving forces simultaneously. Moreover, they do not provide a perspective on processes of behavioural change that involve switching between different cognitive processes. Yet, it is useful to have knowledge on how the different cognitive processes can be tackled in order to stimulate a behavioural change. Therefore, we have organised the theoretical perspectives on behavioural change along the two dimensions that have been used for cognitive processing (see Table 5.4), thus discussing strategies for behavioural change under the heading of deliberation, social comparison, repetition and imitation, respectively.

1. Repetition: changing individually automated behaviour. As discussed in the above section on social processing, *classical and operant conditioning theories* on behavioural change address changes in opportunities. This implies changing the *reinforcement schedules* associated with the use of opportunities. Two methods can be distinguished, namely *rewarding* the preferred behaviour and *punishing* the unwanted behaviour. Both rewards and punishments can be developed using all five strategies: providing physical alternatives (1), regulation-and-enforcement (2), financial-economic stimulation (3), social/cognitive stimulation (4) and changing values and morality (5). The experiencing of a reward or punishment after employing an opportunity directly affects one’s motivation to use that opportunity (again). Indirectly, certain types of rewards and punishments may also imply changes in people’s ability to actually use an opportunity.

Rewarding the preferred behaviour can be accomplished in two ways. Firstly, new positive outcomes may be connected to the use of an opportunity. Secondly, existing negative outcomes associated with the opportunity may be removed. *Punishment* may also be administered in two ways, viz. by connecting new negative outcomes to an opportunity or by removing existing positive outcomes. Some guidelines for effective punishment are (Azrin and Holz, 1966):

- The punishment must be unavoidable;
- The punishment stimulus must be immediate at a profound level instead of increasing gradually;
- The punishment should follow immediately after performing the unwanted behaviour;
- The frequency of punishment should be as high as possible;
- Prolonged periods of punishment should be avoided, as one could get accustomed to the punishment, especially when the punishment is moderate;
- Positive reinforcements should be eliminated as far as possible;
- Feasible alternative opportunities must be available;
- If direct punishment is not feasible, a punishment-related stimulus should be used.

When using effective punishment, the unwanted behaviour will be extinguished and, consequently, further punishment will be unnecessary. When using rewards, a minimum level of rewarding should always be guaranteed. A combination of punishing the unwanted behaviour and rewarding the wanted behaviour will be most effective.

2. *Deliberation: changing individually reasoned behaviour.* The theoretical frameworks to consider individually reasoned behaviour are decision theory and the theory of planned behaviour (see the above section on social processing). *Decision theory* offers two main perspectives on behavioural change. First, one may change a person's decision situation. This implies a change of opportunities to choose from, e.g. offering new opportunities, eliminating existing opportunities and changing the value attributes of opportunities. Such changes may lead to preference shifts, whereby new opportunities come to be chosen over old ones. This perspective utilises the strategies of providing physical alternatives (1), regulation-and-enforcement (2) and financial-economic stimulation (3).

The second perspective, emerging from the prescriptive branch of decision theory, involves methodical decision support. This applies to situations where consumers lack sufficient abilities to apply an optimising strategy and therefore use a satisficing strategy. Procedures, sometimes computer-programmed, are available to assist decision-makers in structuring a problem and selecting the most preferred opportunity. See, e.g. the Multi-Attribute Utility-model (MAU model, Keeny and Raiffa, 1976; Edwards and Newman, 1982). Such decision support may be helpful in evaluating a set of opportunities on several need-satisfying characteristics. Consequently, the greater use of information in the decision-making process may result in shifting preferences. Decision support is a typical social and cognitive stimulation technique (4).

The first perspective on behavioural change offered by the *Theory of Planned Behaviour* (Ajzen, 1985) entails changing attitudes. Attitudes may change as a consequence of providing information on (changed) need-satisfying characteristics of (new) opportunities and/or the resources required for their consumption. If consumers are made aware of an opportunity change, they may subsequently change their beliefs that certain outcomes (satisfaction of needs, required resources) result from using that opportunity. Moreover, if a consumer becomes aware of an increase in required resources for a specific opportunity use, this would decrease his or her perceived behavioural control. Information, communication and education (strategy 4) can be employed to inform consumers about changing opportunities. This strategy mainly addresses consumer abilities in comprehending apparent opportunity changes.

Besides changing opportunities, the evaluations of outcomes also can be changed. Stated in terms of decision theory this means the changing of the subjective weighting of attributes. As this subjective weighting partially depends on the predominant values and morality (associated with a cultural perspective), a change in values and/or morality may change a consumer's motivation to use an opportunity, thus resulting in a behavioural change. Especially changing values and morality (strategy 5) may be aimed at the changing of values and/or morality.

The second perspective on behavioural change offered by the *Theory of Planned Behaviour* (Ajzen, 1985) entails changing subjective norms, which involves socially reasoned behaviour. This perspective will be discussed below in the corresponding section on socially reasoned behaviour.

The above mentioned perspectives also address the *process* of attitude change. The *Elaboration Likelihood Model* (ELM; Petty and Cacioppo, 1986) discerns a *central* and a *peripheral route* to attitude change. The central route pertains to the elaboration of pure arguments in a persuasive message and/or new information. The peripheral route is concerned with the elaboration of form aspects or cues of a message such as the number of arguments, the credibility and the attractiveness of the source. The extent to which

people follow these two routes depends on their motivation to elaborate (MtE) and/or their ability to process information. If MtE and/or cognitive processing ability is low, people will only elaborate the cues in a message, using simple cognitive schemata (*heuristic process model of persuasion*). If MtE and/or cognitive processing ability is moderate, people will assess the motives of the source to deliver the message (*attribution process model of persuasion*). This combined use of central and peripheral routes requires more cognitive elaboration than the use of heuristics. If MtE and/or cognitive processing ability is high, people will explicitly elaborate the information in the message, relating it to existing knowledge structures (*cognitive response model of persuasion*). Generally spoken, attitude changes resulting from central processing are enduring, while peripheral processing results in only temporarily attitude shifts. This implies that if people have a high MtE and/or cognitive processing ability, a persuasive message is most likely to be effective if it entails relevant arguments and new information. If people have a low MtE and/or cognitive processing ability, it is advisable to identify strategies to increase MtE and/or cognitive processing ability, and subsequently provide arguments and new information.

3. *Imitation: changing socially automated behaviour.* The perspective of *Social Learning Theory* (Bandura, 1977; Liebert *et al.*, 1973, see the above section on social processing) on behavioural change addresses the use of representative behaviour as performed by role models. This technique, often referred to as *modelling*, comprises the confrontation with role models that are rewarded or punished as discussed in the foregoing section on classical and operant conditioning. Role-models may be present in one's direct social surroundings, but they may also be provided via media such as television, newspapers, magazines etc. As such, modelling falls under strategy 4 (social and cognitive stimulation).

According to the *Theory of Normative Conduct* (Cialdini *et al.*, 1991, see the above section on social processing), the activation of norms to change behaviour may best be directed at *injunctive norms*: one's ideas about what other people regard as proper behaviour. The activation of *descriptive norms* will only be effective if most people already behave in a desirable way, and thus offers fewer possibilities for the development of policy instruments. Finally, the activation of *personal norms* will only be effective if these norms are already congruent with the preferred behaviour. This changing of personal norms is similar to the changing of socially reasoned behaviour as discussed before. The activation of norms falls under strategy 4 (social and cognitive stimulation).

4. *Social comparison: changing socially reasoned behaviour.* The *Theory of Planned Behaviour* (see the above section on social processing) also offers a perspective on changing behaviour by changing one of its three components, viz. the subjective norm. Changing the beliefs that a consumer has regarding the social appropriateness of a given behaviour involves providing information, communication and education (strategy 4) and changing values and norms (strategy 5). Especially the belief that similar people approve or disapprove certain behaviour will be effective. As a result, a consumer may change his or her (social) evaluation of an opportunity.

According to *Social Comparison Theory* (Festinger, 1954) and the *Theory of Relative Deprivation* (Masters and Smith, 1987, see the above section on social processing), a change in the salient dimensions of comparison would result in a change of behaviour. For example, if status and achievements were defined in a more sustainable way, with lesser emphasis on material consumption as a main focus of comparison, upward social mobility

would come to be directed at being more sustainable than others. Such a drastic change of morality, although hard to realise in one generation (e.g., Elias, 1984), would mainly fall under strategy 5 (changing values and norms).

The preceding two perspectives on behavioural change originate from cognitive behaviour theories, and they are directed at changing both the situation (in terms of opportunity characteristics) and the consumer (in terms of motivation and ability) in a direct way. The following two behaviouristic perspectives, however, address only situational changes, implying that indirect changes in consumer motivation and ability.

In the previous sections we discussed which driving factors of behaviour can be targeted with policy measures, and what behaviour-theoretical principles apply to the targeting of different cognitive processes. In the next sections we will discuss the level at which policy measures can be applied and the dimensions that can be discerned.

The conceptual meta-model of behaviour

In the previous sections a perspective has been drawn regarding the driving factors of behaviour at the micro- and macro-level, the cognitive processes that people engage in, the outcomes of behaviour and strategies for behavioural change. Moreover, the various factors and processes have been related to each other. In Figure 5.5 these relations are schematically presented in a meta-model of consumer behaviour. This model is an elaborated version of the model presented in the introduction of this chapter (see Figure 5.1).

Cognitive processing is forming the heart of this meta-model. Dependent on the uncertainty and level of need satisfaction of a consumer, he/she will engage in one of the four cognitive processes. Cognitive processing involves the greater or lesser use of a mental map, which functions as a memory, in which one's abilities, the characteristics of the opportunities, and the behaviour of similar other consumers are being stored. The mental map is used to determine if a particular opportunity consumption would be satisfying and attainable (when behavioural control is positive). Only when the consumer is reasoning (deliberation or social comparison), he or she will update the mental map. Following cognitive processing, the consumer will decide on what opportunities to consume. This opportunity consumption will yield outcomes that feed back to the micro-level (level of need satisfaction, uncertainty and abilities), and to the macro-level (natural and human environment), which in its turn may change the opportunities that the consumer has available.

Figure 5.5: Schematic representation of the conceptual meta-model of behaviour

The dynamical structure of the conceptual meta-model involves that it can be used to describe and interpret behavioural dynamics that may evolve over time. This will be demonstrated in the next section on the dynamics of consumer behaviour.

The dynamics of consumer behaviour

Following the conceptual meta-model of behaviour in Figure 5.5, consumptive behaviour is considered as a process that evolves over time. Feedbacks, both within and between consumers may give rise to regularities in behaviour that can be observed in many situations. Two behavioural dynamics that deserve special attention are herd behaviour and habit formation.

Herd behaviour

Herd behaviour implies that people are imitating one another, and thus it typically involves interactions between people. When many people are satisfied but uncertain, they tend towards imitating the behaviour of others. The more people start behaving in the same way, the larger may be the change at the macro-level. This in turn may increase uncertainty

in other people, stimulating them to engage in imitation, too. In this way a 'snow-ball effect' may occur, causing many people to behave similarly. This process also refers to the 'lock-in' effect of consumptive behaviour, which implies that the more people consume a certain opportunity, the more attractive it becomes for other people to consume that opportunity as well.

This herd-like behaviour may have negative consequences, as for example rumours causing uncertainty in stock-market brokers may cause a crash or an unfounded growth ('hype') in the stock market. Or, when rumours about a forthcoming scarcity of food are being spread, and some people have already started to create a private food-stock, this may cause other people to imitate that behaviour. This may result in massive hoarding behaviour, which may actually result in unnecessary depletion of food stores. As a consequence, scarcity may emerge, which may endanger the level of need satisfaction of those people who did not succeed in acquiring their own private stock. Herd-behaviour may thus incite a self-fulfilling prophecy.

Habit formation

A second important dynamical process is the formation of *habits*. When certain behaviour is satisfactory, and one is feeling certain about the behavioural outcomes, the experienced reinforcement will make it likely that this behaviour is being performed repeatedly. Here, the cognitive process is being automated to a certain degree, resulting in a *habit*. Habits and cognitive automations are related concepts (Huizing, Zaal and Miedema, 1995). Fiske and Taylor (1991) distinguish a continuum of automations. The strongest automation is a preconscious one (Fiske and Taylor, 1991), i.e., behaviour which can hardly be influenced at all (as in reflexes). Habits are considered to be weak automations that are more susceptible to change. Much consumptive behaviour is embedded in relatively stable consumption patterns, which can be conceived as forms of habitual behaviour. Consequently, behaviours like the buying of food, the use of appliances (cars, showers, domestic appliances) and the disposal of rubbish are mostly performed in a habitual manner.

The origins of a habit may lie in earlier reasoned or imitative behaviour of a person. An important condition for habits to develop is that individuals are able and motivated to repeat that earlier behaviour (Verhallen and Pieters, 1984). Regardless of the nature of the cognitive processes that originally led to the behaviour, frequent repetition leads towards automation of the behaviour, thereby saving (limited) cognitive capacity (abilities) for other tasks. When opportunity consumption satisfies current needs and entails a high behavioural control, the likelihood increases that this behaviour will be repeated, thus constituting a habit. By habitually performing the behaviour, the evaluations of the relevant aspects of the alternative behaviour patterns are saved and stored in one's memory as a *script* (Fiske and Taylor, 1991). The minute a given behaviour may be conducted, a person appeals to such a script instead of comparing and elaborating the opportunities over and over again. Thus, individuals do not have to explicitly evaluate all aspects of the available opportunities any more, which enables them to use their limited abilities in other domains. However, a current habit may yield far from optimal outcomes because new, better behavioural opportunities may have been introduced in the meantime. Consequently, whereas habits are frequently very efficient and necessary strategies that help us to perform routine behaviour, this automating of behaviour may also cause people to behave in an inefficient or even detrimental manner.

Because the use of a behaviour script implies the absence of extensive cognitive elaboration, the principles of classical and operant conditioning are most applicable to the cognitive process. Thus it is assumed that mainly short-term, individual and local (detectable) need-satisfying outcomes will determine a habit. Outcomes that emerge only on the long term, and that are collective and more dispersed, will hardly affect the habit, irrespective of the fact that they are positive or negative. As long as the short-term outcomes are positive, the habit is likely to persist, often despite one's *cognitive* awareness of the risk of long-term negative outcomes (consider e.g., smoking and over-eating). As soon as negative outcomes are experienced directly following the behaviour, i.e., when using that opportunity no longer satisfies the consumer's needs, one is likely to abandon the script and shift towards the cognitive (reasoning) mode of information processing. A cognitive re-evaluation of the habitual behaviour may include the elaboration of long-term, collective and dispersed outcomes. This cognitive elaboration may evoke a behavioural change. Eventually, the new behaviour, if sufficiently repeated and positively reinforced, develops into a new habit of opportunity use.

The relation between reasoned and habitual behaviour has been explored and characterised by Triandis (1977), Bentler and Speckart (1979), Ronis, Yates and Kirscht (1989), Aarts, Knippenberg and Verplanken (1992), Verplanken and Aarts (1994) and Eagly and Chaiken (1993). They suggest that with regard to the prediction of behaviour, there is a trade-off between deliberate intention and habit: when habit is strong the intention-behaviour relation is weak and vice versa. Or as Triandis (1977, p. 205) expresses it: "...when a behaviour is new, untried and unlearned, the behavioural-intention component will be solely responsible for the behaviour, while, when the behaviour is old, well-learned, or overlearned and has occurred many times before (.), it is very likely to be under control of the habit component".

The effectiveness of policy measures

The dynamical process of consumer behaviour implies that many driving factors of behaviour are constantly changing. First, these changes may be autonomous, following from the consumption process itself. Second, producers of products and services bring about many changes in the opportunities they offer. Third, many other interest parties are often trying to change the behaviour of people. The resulting complexity is further increased because the interactions between the various actors touch upon different time-scales. For example, the life-cycle of many food products spans a period of days, whereas the life-cycle of e.g., an industrial process involves years, and the life cycle of, e.g., railway infrastructure may exceed a century. Because of this complexity, developments often take unexpected courses, and policy measures may yield disappointing or even opposite effects. From this perspective it is understandable that many deliberate actions of authorities to change behaviour in a certain direction actually fail.

Policy makers usually have a certain representation of the dynamics that determine the system they are managing, and develop measures on the basis of this representation. However, policy domains in which consumer behaviour plays an important role are usually very complex. This makes it hard to acquire a complete and correct representation of the system. An incomplete or incorrect representation may lead to unpredicted and often unwanted outcomes of policy measures, fostering beliefs such as "nothing can be done to manage consumer behaviour" or "the price-mechanism is the only effective measure to change consumer behaviour". Effects like this have been found in experiments where

decision-makers had to manage an artificial system of which the underlying dynamics were only known to the researchers (e.g., Strohschneider, 1991, 1994a, 1994b; Brehmer and Dörner, 1993).

A better understanding of the dynamics that underlie such complex systems is needed to improve their management. This would facilitate an early diagnosis of potentially unwanted developments, thereby increasing the chances that relatively small measures are capable of redirecting unwanted developments. Such dynamical policy-making requires knowledge about the most relevant behavioural dynamics of consumer behaviour. In recent years theories and tools have been developed to investigate and simulate the dynamics of complex systems. Chapter 3 provided an inventory of techniques that can be used for the simulation of such systems. In the next chapter the consumat approach we have developed will be presented, translating the conceptual meta-model of behaviour into a provisional set of simple but coherent rules for an 'artificial consumer'. The consumat approach developed so far allows for simulating the behavioural dynamics of a group of consumers in various ways.

6

Formalising the conceptual model

Experimental laboratory research has taught us a lot about the factors that affect behaviour in commons dilemmas. These factors have been discussed in Chapter 2. It was concluded that experimental laboratory research has serious limitations regarding the time-scale of the experiments, the number of people involved in the dilemma and the type and relevance of the outcomes. To compress long-term dynamics in a short period, and to enhance the relevance of the outcomes, several researchers are employing computer simulations of collective resources, to study the harvesting behaviour of people in an experimental setting (usually fish-stocks, see Chapter 4 on simulating real-world systems). However, most of the limitations of laboratory research cannot be resolved easily, which makes that experimental results cannot be translated directly to real-life situations.

Field experiments and observations may provide the data that allow for inferring behaviour-determining factors in real-life situations. Field experiments, however, also provide data of limited validity, because they are based on limited (quasi)-experimental variations during relatively short time periods. Observational data usually do not allow for drawing causal inferences because the complex relations between behavioural determinants and behavioural outcomes are not well known.

The computer simulation of artificial agents offers an additional tool in studying the factors that affect harvesting behaviour in a commons dilemma. First, simulating behaviour allows for the experimentation with more extreme conditions and with long time-series. Second, because a simulation model of behaviour yields a running model instead of a static description of effects, it allows for the experimentation with behavioural dynamics, e.g., manipulating the kind of cognitive process the agent employs. Because computer simulations are usually quite simple in comparison to the real world, and they can be repeated over and over again, it is possible to systematically explore the behavioural dynamics of resource harvesting. This may contribute to a better understanding of the dynamics of real-life dilemmas. Simulation thus offers a methodology that, in combination with other methodologies, contributes to the understanding of why people in commons dilemmas behave like they do and what strategies may be viable in altering less sustainable behaviour. Moreover, simulated behaviour can be integrated in other models. For example, the integration of behavioural dynamics in ecological-economic models allows for studying the interactions between human behaviour and the environment.

To validly simulate behaviour in a commons dilemma it is essential that the rules that determine the behaviour of simulated agents reflect the processes that guide the harvesting behaviour of real people. Without psychologically relevant algorithms it seems impossible to simulate the behavioural dynamics behind environmental degradation in a valid way. In Chapter 4 it was concluded that many algorithms used in simulating (parts of) human behaviour seem to have been developed on a rather ad-hoc basis or assuming rational actors that deliberately maximise tangible outcomes. In real life however, people may sometimes engage in deliberate reasoning, sometimes perform behaviour without thinking, and often look at what others do in deciding what action to perform. Actually, people's behaviour is based on multiple processes that involve intangible outcomes. As expected in Chapter 5, to optimise their efforts as well as their outcomes, people engage in

various cognitive processes such as deliberation, social comparison, imitation and repetitive behaviour (habits); see Figure 5.5.

The conceptual meta-model of behaviour presented in the previous chapter integrates various behavioural theories on these cognitive processes and underlying driving factors in a single dynamical framework. In the current chapter this conceptual meta-model is used to develop a set of rules for an artificial agent, the *consumat*. The conceptual meta-model serves as a theoretical framework that facilitates the development and organisation of a coherent set of behavioural rules and algorithms for the consumat. Formalising several consumats that interact with one another yields a multi-agent model that allows for simulating the behavioural dynamics of consumer behaviour. The rules constituting the consumat can be considered as a toolbox which is relatively independent from the simulated environment. A central question that arises then is “To what level of detail should we model human behaviour?”

The level of detail in agent rules

In Chapter 5 several behaviour theories have been discussed and linked in a conceptual meta-model. In order to develop a ‘running model’ of behaviour, these theories have to be formalised in rules for the consumat. A central question here is to what level of detail the theories should be formalised in consumat rules in order to obtain useful knowledge from a simulation. For example, should we develop complex agent rules, including variables such as the visibility of opportunity use, the cultural perspective of an agent, all nine needs as distinguished by Max-Neef (1992; see Table 5.1), norms and reinforcement schedules? Or should the consumat rules constitute a simple set of rules, that captures the essence of the major theories and factors?

The discussion on the optimal level of detail in agent rules also emerged at the First International Conference on the Simulation of Social Systems (Cortona, September 1997) where several multi-agent simulations ranging from abstract mathematical approaches to practice-oriented simulations were presented. Whereas some participants stressed the importance of using simple agents, others advocated the use of more complex agents in simulations. Hegselmann (1997) postulated that two ‘parties’ could be distinguished, one being focused at simple agents, and the other at complex agents. This distinction between two parties is not absolute, but should be regarded as framing the extremes on a continuum of simulations in the social sciences.

On the one end of the continuum we find the simulations with very simple agents, which for example use a tit-for-tat strategy in a repeated prisoners’ dilemma (e.g., Axelrod, 1980a, 1980b). These simulations are aimed at studying the effects of interdependence on the functioning of social systems. Researchers in this tradition use simple agent rules by which they are capable of describing what can be considered to be the basic mathematics of interdependence. However, despite the simplicity of the agents and the mathematical approach, surprises may still occur. For example, some simulations of choice behaviour of adaptive agents in a repeated prisoners’ dilemma showed stable cooperation for thousands of runs, suggesting that convergence has been reached. However, in a sudden flash, ‘defection’ may spread through the population, proving that there was no equilibrium at all (e.g., Nowak and Sigmund, 1992; Majeski, Linden, Linden and Spitzer, 1997). As concluded in Chapter 4, the rules that constitute the agents in this type of simulations lack psychological validity. This implies that such agents do not demonstrate behavioural

dynamics that bear resemblance to real-world processes. This type of agent is not directly applicable in a more practical context.

At the other end of the continuum we find multi-agent simulations explicitly developed to model social behaviours in a more realistic manner. Examples are fishermen's society (Bousquet *et al.*, 1994), Sugarscape (Epstein and Axtell, 1996) and Ernst's (1998) agents in a resource dilemma (see Chapter 4). In this type of simulations the agent rules are more complex. Other simulations that explicitly deal with real processes are, e.g., fish markets (Weisbuch, Kirman and Herreiner, 1997), urban developments (Papini and Rabino, 1997), and budgetary decision-making (Chattoe and Gilbert, 1997). The simulations of this type are often less transparent with respect to the behavioural dynamics underlying the outcomes. Generally, the more complex a simulation is, the more difficult it becomes to relate certain macro-level processes to micro-level agent rules. This implies that building a very complex agent and placing it in a complex environment will not yield results that are easy to understand and validate.

Our approach is aimed at combining both the simple and the complex approach. First, the different parts of the conceptual meta-model (Figure 5.5) are being translated in simple agent rules. This will, for example, result in simple decision rules for the four different types of cognitive processing: repetition, deliberation, imitation and social comparison. These cognitive processes can be applied alone or in combination in a simple environment, yielding a transparent picture of how these strategies function in the consumat. Moreover, selecting an issue that has been empirically well researched can test the validity of these rules. When simple experiments have yielded a good understanding and validation of the basic agent rules, the full set of agent rules can be placed in a more complex simulated environment. This would, for example, allow for investigating the dynamical interactions between human consumption and ecological and economic systems. These latter simulations are less suitable for the testing of agent rules. Summarising, our strategy involves starting with simple rules in a simple environment, and subsequently applying them in a more complex environment.

The behavioural rules of the consumat

The conceptual meta-model of behaviour discussed in Chapter 5 follows a system-dynamic framework that can be understood as a flow diagram. The model links various theories that are relevant in the context of consumer behaviour, and it specifies under what conditions which behavioural processing style is being used. On the basis of this conceptual meta-model a comprehensive set of behavioural rules for the consumat has been developed.

To develop a computer simulation of consumer behaviour, the most important factors and relations between these factors as depicted in the conceptual meta-model (Figure 5.5) have to be formalised into programmable rules. This simplification also serves the comprehensibility of the simulation results. Several model variables and processes will be translated into a set of simple behavioural rules. In doing so we will capture the basic principles of the relevant theories. The rules together will constitute the behavioural repertoire of the artificial human agent. In behaviour-based Artificial Intelligence (AI) the term *animat*, referring to artificial animal coined by Wilson (1985), is frequently used. In this monograph the term *consumat* is introduced to notify the artificial human consumer.

The variables and relations that have been organised in the conceptual model (Fig. 5.5 in Chapter 5) will be formalised. This involves that Figure 5.5 will be transformed in a flow diagram. This flow diagram directs the translation into computer language or software package. The reader must bear in mind that several consumats may be formalised simultaneously in a simulation. This implies that the consumats actually interact with one another. The following sections are devoted to the definition of the consumat rules and the consumption opportunities, following the structure of the conceptual meta-model. We thus capture the driving factors of behaviour at the macro- and micro-level, the four different cognitive processes, the consumption of opportunities, and the strategies for behaviour change.

The macro-level driving factors of human behaviour

The formalisation of macro-level developments implies a description of changes in the natural environment and in the human environment. These macro-level developments have to be translated into changes in needs, opportunities and abilities of individual consumats. Regarding the natural environment many models can be used, ranging from very simple fish-stock models, as has been described in Chapter 4, to more complex models of natural systems. The effects of macro-level changes in the natural environment must be translated in micro-level terms. For example, soil erosion may affect consumers' need for subsistence and protection, reducing the opportunities to grow food, thereby negatively affecting the possibility to earn money (an ability). Which micro-level factors will change as result of changes in the natural environment will depend on what type of issue is being modelled.

Changes in the human environment refer to changes in technology, the economy, demography (population), institutions and culture (T.E.D.I.C.-complex, Vlek, 1995, see Chapter 5). These changes affect the needs, opportunities and abilities of individual consumats.

- Technological changes may occur in physical ability (means) necessary to perform certain behaviour. This category also includes the mechanisms of increasing production if demand is increasing;
- Economical changes may occur in the financial resources of the consumat or in the prices of opportunities;
- Demographical changes in population size (the number of consumats) may take place, e.g., affecting the availability of consumption opportunities;
- Institutional changes may, e.g., lead to free trade between consumats;
- Cultural changes may occur in the relative importance of needs.

Environmentally negative outcomes can be formalised as the pollution per unit of opportunity use (work, or consumption of goods). This pollution may affect the environmental system in a predefined manner, and a degraded environment may have consequences for the satisfaction of needs. For example, a degraded environment may affect the health of consumats; a decreasing health may be related to consumats' ability to work. Moreover, it can be simulated that only consumats staying *under* a certain ability level will be affected by pollution.

The micro-level driving factors of human behaviour

The micro-level driving forces involve consumats' needs, opportunities, abilities and uncertainty. Current levels of need satisfaction and of uncertainty are affecting the type of cognitive processing a consumat engages in.

The needs of the consumat

As described in the previous chapter, Max-Neef (1992) identifies nine fundamental needs: Subsistence, Protection, Affection, Understanding, Participation, Leisure, Creation, Identity and Freedom. Including all these needs in the simulation right from the start, provided that we *could* formalise them right away, may result in dynamics that are hard to understand. Therefore it seems to be practical to start with a sparse set of needs. For example, one could start with two needs, e.g. subsistence and leisure. Depending on the type of behaviour (domain) and the prevalent needs to be modelled, more or fewer needs can be incorporated in the model. In the following we develop a framework consisting of the nine needs as proposed by Max-Neef (1992). However, the reader must bear in mind that the application of the model, e.g. in the experiments described in the following three chapters, may require a reduction to just a few needs.

Technically, the level of need satisfaction for need i (LNS_i) is represented by an index varying between 0 (fully dissatisfied) and 1 (fully satisfied). For example: a consumat may have a lack of food (low nutrient stock) and as a result experience hunger (LNS for 'subsistence' is close to 0). The relation between stock-level and LNS follows a *diminishing marginal utility* function, which implies that the more of an opportunity has been consumed, the less utility one gets from consuming yet another unit of that opportunity. Such functions are commonly used in economics. The level of LNS_i depends on the stock-level of need satisfiers following from individual opportunity consumption $o_{1..n}$. For need i and opportunity j the level of need satisfaction LNS at time t can be formulated as a diminishing marginal utility function, with parameter α indicating the sensitivity of LNS_i for the consumption of opportunity o_j :

$$(1) \quad LNS_{it} = (1 - \exp(-\alpha * o_j)),$$

This function implies that the increase in LNS_i , given the input of a specific opportunity ' o_j ' with a certain capacity to satisfy need ' i ' (NSC_i), depends on the actual stock-level of the need satisfier in question. The higher the stock-level is, the lower the increase in LNS_i after consuming opportunity ' o_j '. Figure 6.1 shows the shape of such diminishing marginal utility functions determining the sensitivity of the consumat's LNS_i for consumption. The relation between opportunity consumption and the level of need satisfaction of a given consumat can be visualised as the position a consumat has on the function line. Starting with a fully depleted need, the consumption of one ' o_i ' yields an increase of LNS from 0 to .50, moving the consumat from the 0 point to position X on the function line. Consuming two ' o_i ' would move the consumat to position X', resulting in a LNS of .75. The LNS thus increases with .25 in comparison to consuming one ' o_i '. Consuming three ' o_i ' would move the consumat to position X'', yielding a LNS of .80, implicating an increase of LNS with only .05 in comparison to consuming two ' o_i '.

Figure 6.1: Sensitivity functions of LNS_i for different α 's

The shape of the function line describing the relation between consumption and need satisfaction is determined by the factor α , which may be used to formalise 'quick-needs' versus 'slow-needs'. As Figure 6.1 shows, the function line with a high α shows a need that is much quicker satisfied than the function line based on a low α . This allows to distinguish between, e.g., the need for subsistence that is quickly satisfied, but also quickly depleted again (e.g., satisfied by consumption of food), and the need for, e.g., 'identity', which is a much 'slower' need. A high α results in a quicker increase of LNS_i as a function of individual consumption than a low α (e.g., $1 - \exp(-1) = 0.63$ versus $1 - \exp(-2) = 0.86$).

Besides distinguishing between quick and slow needs, the value of α may be also used to formalise individual preferences as depicted in the shape of their diminishing marginal utility functions. For example, two consumats that consume equally may experience different changes of their LNS because of different α 's. Because the relative importance of a need is dependent on one's cultural perspective, calibration of the α 's may also be used to formalise different perspectives. Consumats with different perspectives will perceive the Need-Satisfying Capacity (NSC) of an opportunity differently, and may act accordingly. The default setting of the α 's is equal for all consumats, indicating an equal diminishing marginal utility function for all consumats.

The overall level of need satisfaction of a consumat at time t is a weighted multiplication of the satisfaction of the nine needs involved (Formula 2). A multiplication appears to be more realistic than a simple addition because this prevents that the dissatisfaction of one need can be compensated by a higher need-satisfaction of another need. Using a multiplication implies that if one need is seriously being depleted, the consumat's overall level of need-satisfaction is low. This prevents situations where a consumat that is starving, while its other needs are satisfied, has an overall high level of need satisfaction. The value γ functions as weighting factor regarding the relative importance of the different needs in the overall level of need satisfaction. Here, γ may be used to formalise differences between (groups of) consumers regarding the experienced importance of needs. The sum of the different γ 's is set at 1, which causes the overall $LNS_{i,q}$ to range between 0 and 1. Formula 2 captures the overall level of need satisfaction

at time t as a weighted multiplication of the nine levels of need satisfaction i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p and q .

$$(2) \text{LNS}_{i..q,t} = \text{LNS}_i^{\gamma_i} * \text{LNS}_j^{\gamma_j} * \dots * \text{LNS}_q^{\gamma_q}, \text{with } \sum \gamma_i.. \gamma_q = 1.$$

A critical value LNS_{min} is defined. If $\text{LNS}_{i..q} < \text{LNS}_{\text{min}}$ the consumat is dissatisfied, and when $\text{LNS}_{i..q} \geq \text{LNS}_{\text{min}}$ the consumat is satisfied. The consumat is satisfied when its needs are satisfied above the minimum level as defined by LNS_{min} (i.e., when $\text{LNS}_{i..q} > \text{LNS}_{\text{min}}$). LNS_{min} can be defined for each consumat separately, allowing consumats to differ regarding their critical satisfaction level. The satisfaction of a consumat plays an important role in determining the type of cognitive processing it engages in. We assume that if the consumat is satisfied, it will engage in automatic processing (i.e., repetition or imitation), whereas a dissatisfied consumat engages in reasoned processing (i.e., deliberation or social comparison).

Opportunities

Opportunities are the behavioural options formalised in the simulation model. Consumats may use opportunities in order to satisfy their needs (e.g., consuming food) or to increase their abilities (e.g., working for money). Several sets of opportunities $O_{1..n}$ may be defined, each representing a coherent group of opportunities, e.g., various fishing opportunities, modes of transportation or types of food. The specific level of opportunity consumption from a specific set O_j (e.g., fishing) is being denoted as o_j , which stands, e.g., for a certain number of hours spent fishing.

As has been explained in the previous section, the use of opportunities may satisfy several needs of the consumat. The need-satisfying capacity NSC of an opportunity indicates how the level of need-satisfaction of the consumat changes after consuming o_j . Consequently, for opportunity o_j it is possible to formalise a $\text{NSC}_{i..q}$, indicating o_j 's need-satisfying capacity for all nine needs.

Besides the satisfaction of needs, opportunity consumption also results in the changing of abilities. Opportunity consumption is assumed to have predefined consumat-resource demands (RD). Consumer goods and activities require the investment of, e.g., money, or a certain level of ability to use them, e.g., a driver's license. Moreover, opportunity use may cost time, which of course is a limiting factor. Depending on the abilities being addressed in a simulation model, more or less consumat-resource demands can be defined for each opportunity. In many cases these resource demands take the form of *operational costs*, that is, they require the use of abilities. For example, shopping in a supermarket costs money. In some cases the resource demands refer to *front investments* an actor has to make before he is able to use the opportunity, for example, buying a car costs money. In other cases the resource demands refer to a kind of *threshold*. To be able to consume a certain opportunity, the actor must have an amount of ability that exceeds the threshold level. The use of the opportunity, however, does not decrease the ability level. For example, driving a car to a certain destination requires a license and knowledge of the area, but driving does not cost you an 'amount-of-license' and/or knowledge. And working requires but also increases ability, according to a 'learning by doing' effect. In Chapter 5 a distinction was made between four general types of personal resources: (1) physical resources, (2) juridical and regulatory resources, (3) financial-economic resources, and (4) social and cognitive resources. Additional to these four personal resources or

abilities, we acknowledge that the use of an opportunity may cost time, which is of course limited. Formalised, one unit of opportunity use costs or requires p physical resource units, l legislative units, f financial units, c social/cognitive units and t hours.

The consumat can increase its (mainly financial) abilities by means of working. Many opportunities for consumption (e.g., food) cost money, forcing the consumat to work for a living. Depending on the abilities (skills) of a consumat, it may earn more or less money during one unit (e.g., hour) of work. Simulation functions can be developed for work opportunities that describe the relation between ability (skill) and income.

The availability of certain opportunities may be restricted. Especially in situations where many consumats intend to use the same opportunity, scarcity may emerge. Two typical simulation functions can be implemented. First, a price-demand function can be formalised. Such a function relates the price to the availability of an opportunity (the lower the availability, the higher the price). Second, a production function can be formalised. Such a function would describe the opportunity production in response to the demand (high demand results in high production). Both functions imply variable opportunity demands (e.g., price, availability). Also the need-satisfying capacity of opportunities can be made variable. For example, the need-satisfying capacity for identity (status) of an opportunity may depend on the number and type of other consumats that use this opportunity.

Abilities

The consumat has physical, financial, legislative and social/cognitive resources available. These abilities determine the consumats behavioural control over various opportunities. Moreover, all consumats have 24 hours a day in which all of their opportunity use should fit. Some abilities can be understood as means that can be invested. The most important investments refer to the amount of available time (A_t) and the financial budget (A_f). Other abilities bear a threshold-like character, e.g., physical capacities (A_p), social/cognitive abilities (A_c) and permissions/licenses (A_l). Consumats must exceed the threshold-level to be capable of consuming certain opportunities. The level of ability can be understood in different ways. A_p and A_c can have a score between 0 (no ability at all) and 100 (maximum ability). A_l can be formalised as a boolean (yes or no). A_f can have all values, as there is no theoretical limit in financial means. Moreover, if the consumats are allowed to make debts or loan money, A_f may have a negative value. The different abilities a consumat has available are being denoted as A_{plfc} . The time available is always 24 hours a day.

Differences in abilities can be used to classify consumats and to represent a certain society. Classes of consumats can be formed on the basis of their income, licenses et cetera. Every class of consumats, e.g., the consumats with a high income and a licence, represents a more homogenous group of consumats, which are assumed to behave in a comparable way. In principle each separate consumat may be representing a group of people, as the simulations will not include as many consumats as people in the real world (or the domain to be modelled). As such, the consumat can also be understood as a 'meta-actor', which stands for a larger group of people.

Behavioural control

The behavioural control over an opportunity is defined as the consumat's ability, i.e. its available resources, minus the resource demands of the opportunity. For each of the separate abilities a specific BC can be calculated. For example, the financial behavioural

control over opportunity l equals the financial ability of the consumer minus the financial resource demands of opportunity l . In formula:

$$(3) \quad BC_{lf} = A_f - RD_{lf}$$

If one of the specific BC's < 0 , the consumption of that opportunity is impossible. The higher BC gets, the 'easier' consumption of that opportunity becomes.

Uncertainty

Uncertainty U relates to the difference between the expectations of the consumat and the actual outcomes of behaviour. The formalisation of uncertainty can be based on the absolute difference between expected opportunity consumption (EC) and actual consumption (AC) of opportunities, where opportunity stands for the distribution of opportunity use $o_{1..n}$. In formula:

$$(4) \quad U = \text{ABS} (EC_{o_{1..n}} - AC_{o_{1..n}})$$

If the actual outcomes are close to the expectations, the uncertainty U of the consumat is small. If however there is a large difference between expectations and actual outcomes, the uncertainty U of the consumat will be large.

Cognitive processing

In the conceptual model as described in Chapter 5, two dimensions were being introduced as an organising principle for theories on behavioural processing. The first dimension distinguishes reasoned from automatic processing, and the second dimension distinguishes individual from social processing. On the basis of these two dimensions four cognitive processing styles are being distinguished: deliberating (individually reasoned), repetition (individually automatic), social comparison (socially reasoned) and imitation (socially automatic). For each of these four cognitive processing styles a heuristic has been written that is aimed at capturing the essence of that type of processing, yet is simple enough to be computer-programmed. Which of the four heuristics is being used at a given moment in time is being determined by decision rules that involve the consumat's level of need satisfaction, behavioural control and uncertainty.

The four heuristics make use of a memory, which is being referred to as the mental map. This mental map contains a representation of the consumat's own state (e.g., needs, abilities) and the state of the natural and human environment (e.g., available opportunities and the behaviour of other consumats). Because the mental map is being used under all heuristics, it is practical to describe the mental map first. Following that, we will describe the decision rules for the style of cognitive processing the consumat will follow. Finally the four heuristics that represent the four cognitive processing styles are being explained.

The Mental Map

The consumats are equipped with a mental map that contains their perception of their own state and the state of the natural and human environment. The mental map thus functions as a memory. The information in this memory may be more or less accurate,

depending on how often it is being updated. The updating of the mental map takes place during reasoned behavioural processes (i.e., deliberation, social comparison).

First, the consumat memorises its previous behaviours. This implies that the need-satisfying capacities and ability-changing properties of opportunities are memorised. A consumat thus may memorise that consuming opportunity o_1 may have a certain need-satisfying capacity $NSC_{i..q}$, and certain resource demands RD_{plfc} . This provides information that can be used in estimating the change in the level of need satisfaction $\Delta LNS_{i..q}$ associated with a certain consumption pattern, and the changes in abilities ΔA_{cplf} .

Also stored in the mental map is information about which other consumats serve as comparison-consumats, as well as the behaviour these consumats performed in the previous time step (t-1). Finally, the mental map contains the perception of the consumat's own abilities A_{plfc} , e.g., what the financial budget is at a particular moment and how much money can be earned by a certain type of work.

Reasoned versus automatic processing

A high level of need satisfaction LNS implies that the consumat performs behaviour (uses a certain distribution of opportunities) that adequately satisfies its needs. In this case the consumat will not elaborate extensively on alternatives, thus following an automatic type of processing. A low level of need satisfaction indicates that the consumat performs behaviour that does not adequately satisfy its needs. The consumat will then be motivated to elaborate on alternative behaviours that would increase its level of need satisfaction, and thus is inclined to engage in reasoned processing. LNSmin is being formalised to define the critical level of need satisfaction below which the consumat will engage in reasoned processing:

(5) IF $LNS_{i..q} < LNS_{min}$, THEN (reasoned processing), ELSE (automatic processing)

Also if the Behavioural Control (BC) the consumat has is negative (< 0), it will be 'forced' to elaborate on more feasible need-satisfying opportunities, thus engaging in reasoned processing. Scanning all opportunities to calculate the BC for each opportunity before deciding to process in a reasoned or automatic manner appears to be a contradiction. It seems more realistic to calculate BC after a decision has been made on what opportunity to consume. If $BC < 0$, then the consumat is forced to elaborate on alternative opportunities. In case of automatic processing, this implies that the consumat is being forced to switch towards reasoned processing.

Social versus individual processing

As stated in the section on driving factors of consumption, uncertainty (U) is the key-factor that determines if a consumat engages in individual or social processing (see also Chapter 5). A maximum uncertainty tolerance UT is formalised as the critical level. If $U > UT$, then the consumat will engage in social processing, else the consumat will engage in individual processing. The precise values of U and UT depend on the issue that is being modelled. In the following section the four heuristics will be explained, which refer to Table 5.4.

Repetition (individually automatic, $LNS > LNS_{min}$, $U < UT$)

Repetition stands for automatic individual processing, and relates to classical and operant conditioning theory. Repeating behaviour implies that the consumat does not update its mental map. It will just repeat the previous behaviour. Thus, the consumat is motivated to consume the previous consumed opportunity. This heuristic will be followed as long as the consumat's needs are sufficiently satisfied ($LNS_{i..q} > LNS_{min}$) and the consumat is certain ($U < UT$), in which situation habitual behaviour will be performed. New or changing opportunities are not being updated in the 'mental map'. The consumat will not perceive the availability of new opportunities or changes in existing, non-used opportunities. Consequently, the consumat may persist behaving in a manner that once was optimal, but actually may be sub-optimal. The behaviour of the consumat is only changing when the NSC's of the consumed opportunities decrease or when the consumats' behavioural control over these opportunities drops. In that case the consumat's LNS will decrease below the critical level of LNS_{min} , and thus the consumat will perform reasoned behaviour and consequently update its mental map.

Deliberation (reasoned individual: $LNS < LNS_{min}$, $U < UT$)

Deliberating stands for reasoned individual processing, and relates to decision and choice theory and theory of reasoned action. Deliberating implies that the consumat will first update its mental map. Then it will elaborate on the opportunity that is expected to optimise its outcomes. Here, the consumat calculates for all opportunities the expected consequences ($E[LNS_{i..q}]$) of using each of the opportunities. The time-horizon the consumat employs in this calculation (cognitive ability) is an important factor. The consumat will be motivated to consume the opportunity distribution with the highest perceived multiple need-satisfying capacity. More formally: the consumat will be most motivated to consume the opportunity with the highest positive $\Delta LNS_{i..q}$. Subsequently, the consumat will calculate the behavioural control to assess the feasibility of consuming this opportunity. If feasible (i.e., when $BC \geq 0$), the consumat will consume that opportunity, else it will search for another opportunity.

Imitation (socially automatic: $LNS > LNS_{min}$, $U > UT$)

Imitation stands for automatic social processing, and relates to social learning theory and the theory of normative conduct. When the consumat engages in imitation, it will read its mental map and recall the consumat that functioned most recently as the comparison-consumat. Next, the consumat will read what this consumat did in the previous time step and then do the same. The consumat is thus motivated to consume whatever the other similar consumat is consuming for as long as $LNS_{i..q} > LNS_{min}$, $U > UT$ and the behavioural control over the imitated behaviour is positive ($BC > 0$). The consumat that is using this strategy can be thought of as following an 'idol'. The consumat does not have to spent energy on the cognitive process, yet may adapt his behaviour to keep its needs satisfied. This strategy requires that the consumat has performed socially reasoned processing at an earlier moment in order to have a 'comparison other' available. In the simulation the situation may occur that a consumat is inclined towards socially automatic behaviour, but has not compared with another consumat before. In that case a random consumat is chosen from the comparison group.

The cognitive processing usually ends (for the time being) with a choice for action. This action may consist of consuming certain opportunities and/or increasing one's

abilities (e.g., work). However, if no affordable opportunities are available, and there are no adequate means to improve one's abilities, one may end up doing nothing.

Social Comparison (socially reasoned: $LNS < LNS_{min}$, $U > UT$)

Social Comparison stands for reasoned social processing, and relates to social comparison theory, relative deprivation theory and theory of reasoned action (social norms). While engaging in social comparison, the consumat will first update its mental map. Then it will observe the consumptive behaviour of other consumats. The consumat will select a set of other consumats that are more or less similar regarding their abilities. A critical degree of similarity can be formalised that indicates the range of other consumats being considered as similar. The similar consumats will serve as comparison consumats. The consumat will calculate the expected outcomes ($E[LNS_{i,q}]$) for imitating the behaviour of the similar consumats. Here, different formalisations can be used. In some situations, e.g., referring to decisions on quantities, it may be preferred to calculate the average behaviour of the other similar consumats. In other situations, e.g., where the behavioural choice is binary, the behaviour of a random similar consumat may be imitated. Finally, it is also possible to calculate which of the similar consumats' behaviour yields the highest expected outcomes. If the expected outcomes of the behaviour of a similar consumat are higher than the expected outcomes of the consumats' current behaviour, and the behavioural control over this opportunity is positive, then the opportunity consumption of the similar consumat is being adopted. The consumat thus will be motivated to perform either the other consumats' behaviour, or its own previous behaviour, depending on the highest perceived multiple need-satisfying capacity of both opportunities. This implies that an unsatisfied and uncertain consumat, being confronted with similar consumats that are worse off, will not change its behaviour.

Opportunity consumption

Opportunity consumption describes the resulting behaviour, namely the consumption of available opportunities. Moreover, three feedbacks can be distinguished, namely the satisfaction of needs, changes in ability and uncertainty. Finally, opportunity consumption yields changes in the natural and human environment.

Consumption of the opportunity

Opportunity consumption can be formalised as a quantity (units) of goods consumed. This quantity may be expressed in sheer numbers, but also in physical units (kilograms, cubic metres). To allow for the simulation of activities that do not (directly) refer to physical consumption such as work and leisure, the units can also be defined as time spent on a certain activity. Assuming that a certain quantity of goods can be consumed in a given period of time, it is possible to use the variable *time-spent-on-an-activity* to represent the consumats' consumption of that activity.

The satisfaction of needs

The change in the level of need satisfaction $\Delta LNS_{i,q}$ depends on the previous level of need satisfaction $LNS_{i,q, t-1}$, the need-satisfying capacity $NSC_{i,q}$ of the actual opportunity

consumption and the α 's that determine the shape of the diminishing marginal utility function. The $LNS_{i,q}$ of the consumat may change with every time-step.

Changes in ability

The consumat's abilities are subject to change as a result of opportunity consumption. It depends on the type of opportunity consumption if and how abilities change. For example:

- Work will usually increase financial resources, but at the cost of time resources;
- Work may increase social/cognitive abilities, e.g. via learning by doing;
- Consumption of a good may cost money, thus decreasing financial ability;
- Some opportunity consumption requires a license, however, this license does not change in the process of consumption.

The exact formalisation depends on which abilities are being addressed in the simulation of a specific issue.

Changes in uncertainty

The actual outcomes of behaviour as described above may differ from what the consumat expected to obtain. This difference is being used to calculate a new level of uncertainty, as defined earlier.

Changes in the natural and human environment (macro level)

The aggregated opportunity consumption of a multitude of consumats yields changes in the natural and human environment. Depending on how the natural and human environment is being formalised, these changes may have repercussions for the need-satisfying characteristics of opportunities and the availability of opportunities. For example, if a consumat is working, and the work is related to a certain resource, the outcomes will depend on the state of the resource. The larger the number of consumats and the more they harvest, the lower the outcomes of the resource will be. Another example is that the status-value of an opportunity may depend on the number and type of consumats consuming that opportunity. Similar processes can be postulated for the change of resource demands. For example, a specific relation can be formalised between the number of consumats that consume a certain opportunity and the price of this opportunity (market mechanism).

Strategies for behavioural change

Different strategies can be formalised that may influence consumats' behaviour. These policy measures can be developed from the perspective of a producer or of the government. Policy measures may influence the need-satisfying capacities (NSC) and resource demands of opportunities as well as the abilities and cultural perspective of consumers.

Changing the NSC of opportunities

Changing the need-satisfying capacity of opportunities is done by changing one or more of their nine need satisfying capacities in $NSC_{i..q}$. For example, some opportunities may be made more attractive by increasing one or more need-satisfying capacities, whereas other opportunities may be made less attractive by decreasing one or more need-satisfying capacities.

Changing the resource demands of an opportunity

In a similar vein as changing the NSC of opportunities one may change the resource demands of an opportunity. For example, one may increase the price of one unit of an opportunity, decrease the amount of physical ability that is required, or withdraw the necessity of having a license. A typical example here is the introduction of a simulation function that describes the relation between price and demand. To include the adaptability of the suppliers (at the macro-level) in a simulation, the market mechanism can be formalised as 'the more an opportunity is being used, the lower its price gets'.

Changing consumat abilities

The abilities of a consumat can be changed in several ways. For example, one may formalise an increase of the consumats' physical ability as 'harvesting more in the same period of time'. Also the finances a consumat has available may be in- or decreased. Groups of consumats may have different abilities. For example, in a simulation run there may emerge a group of financially prosperous consumats versus a group of relatively poor consumats. Policy measures can be developed that are aimed at altering the abilities of specific groups of consumats, e.g., taxes that are differentiating between levels of income and wealth.

Changing the consumat's cultural perspective

The consumat's cultural perspective can be changed by changing the relative importance of the needs, thus altering the α 's in the overall level of need satisfaction $LNS_{i..q}$. As the motivation to consume a certain opportunity depends on the relative importance of the needs, consumats with different α 's will have different preferences.

Conclusions

Although this chapter provides a formal description of the conceptual meta-model of behaviour, many variables have not been addressed explicitly. Only if a particular issue has been chosen to be modelled, these variables and the relations between them can be addressed explicitly. For example, modelling the management of a natural resource (e.g., a fish-stock) requires that the availability of opportunities is being formalised on the basis of a representation of the relevant resource dynamics. Modelling the consumption of certain products requires, for example, that attention is given to the formalisation of price-demand relations that form part of the opportunity characteristics. Moreover, depending on the issue that is being modelled, one may be primarily interested in certain types of needs. For example, in the resource management task, subsistence is expected to be a need of crucial importance, whereas in the modelling of product consumption the need for identity may be of interest. In the present chapter, nine needs were being addressed. However, in the modelling of a particular issue it is important to take only those needs into consideration that are of interest. This is necessary to keep the simulation model simple and the results transparent for interpretation.

Certain simulations, especially for testing and validating the consumat rules, may be focussed at studying the behaviour of consumats in a very simple structured environment, e.g., the management of a rather simple resource. However, eventually the aims are also to apply the consumat approach in issues that bear a larger resemblance to real-world systems. This implies that such systems have to be modelled to provide an environment in which the behaviour of consumats can be studied. For example, a simulation of the management of fish-grounds will require an adequate model of a fish population. In the simulation of transport choice behaviour it will be necessary to formalise different transportation systems and opportunities. Because the dynamics of simulated real-world systems may be very complex, it will be less transparent how the behavioural rules at the micro-level interact with the developments at the macro-level. As such, simulations of real-world systems do not offer the appropriate environment to test and validate the rules characterising the consumat. Therefore, it is necessary to start with very simple prototypical issues to test the behavioural rules. In the next chapter the issue of renewable resources is being formalised in a simulation model to test and validate the consumat approach.

7 Consumats in a commons dilemma¹¹

The choice of a first issue for testing the consumats is an important one. Several aspects have to be balanced in this choice. First, the topic has to be relevant in the context of environmentally relevant behaviour. Second, the topic has to be simple, so as to allow for a relatively quick programming and to keep the simulated behavioural dynamics understandable. Third, it would be an advantage if the simulation results can be compared in some way with existing empirical, preferably experimental data. And last but not least, the topic should be fitting in a social-scientific paradigm, thus making simulation result communicable within such a paradigm. Considering these aspects, the issue of *resource dilemmas* will serve as a good starting point for the simulation of behaviour. Summarising, the resource dilemma offers an issue that:

- 1: Is relevant with respect to environmental behaviour;
- 2: Has been investigated by many scientists, offering a paradigm with an abundance of experimental research, providing an empirical touchstone for the simulation results;
- 3: Has a tradition in using simulation as a research tool, thus provides a scientific paradigm and a community for discussion.

Applied to environmental problems, the commons dilemma addresses the behavioural mechanisms of environmental overexploitation. In a commons dilemma a collective opportunity, or resource, exists from which all individuals may consume. If this collective opportunity has a certain growth capacity, we may conceive it as a renewable resource. If such a resource, e.g., clean fresh water, fish, pasture land or natural forest, is being consumed at a rate that overshoots its natural growing rate, the availability of the resource will decrease. If consumption remains at a high level, the resource may even vanish. A certain limitation to the consumption of the resource is required to preserve it for a longer time, allowing its consumption to be sustainable. In Chapter 2 the commons dilemma and many factors affecting human behaviour in commons dilemmas have been discussed extensively. It was concluded that the laboratory setting of this research differs significantly from real world situations regarding the time scale and the seriousness of outcomes. Computer simulation offers the possibility to experiment with more extreme conditions and with long time-series. In Chapter 4 many social-scientific simulations were being discussed, including simulations of resource dilemmas. It was concluded that to capture processes like social comparison, imitation and habitual behaviour, it is necessary to develop behavioural rules on the basis of an meta-model of behaviour. A conceptual meta-model of behaviour has been discussed in Chapter 5, and in Chapter 6 this meta-model was being formalised as a 'consumat'. This formalisation was incomplete, as the full formalisation of the consumat approach into a running computer model requires that a specific issue be modelled. In the following, this formalisation will be done for consumats being confronted with a simple resource. Along

¹¹ This chapter is largely based on Jager, Janssen and Vlek, (1999).

with the general formalisation as described in Chapter 6, the various driving factors and cognitive processes will be specified for this model.

The driving factors of behaviour

The macro-level driving factors of behaviour refer here to the resource the consumats can harvest from. This resource will be discussed under the micro-level determinant of opportunities, because the resource provides opportunities for consumption. The micro-level driving factors of behaviour refer to needs, opportunities and abilities. The associated levels of need satisfaction and uncertainty determine the cognitive processing the consumats engage in; see Chapter 6.

The needs of the consumat

In the commons dilemma experiments reported in this chapter, consumat i is equipped with two needs: (1) a need for subsistence (LNSs) and (2) a need for leisure (LNSl). Consuming from a resource R (which will be described next under opportunities) results in a certain quantity of individual consumption. The higher the individual consumption (CI_{it}) of consumat i at the current time-step t , the higher its need satisfaction for subsistence of consumat i at t (LNS_{sit}). The LNSs follows a diminishing marginal utility function, and ranges from 0 to 1. The value of α_{is} indicates how sensitive the consumat's LNSs is for consumption.

$$(1) \quad LNS_{sit} = 1 - \exp(-\alpha_{is} * CI_{it})$$

The need for leisure is the second consumat need being formalised. The satisfaction of the need for leisure LNSl for consumat i at time-step t increases at a decreasing rate with the amount of time left over for leisure. The amount of time spent on working is denoted by x , ranging from 0 (0 hours of working) to 1 (24 hours of working). The time for leisure can be denoted as $1 - x$, and ranges from 0 to 1. The value of α_{il} here indicates how sensitive the consumat's LNSl is for leisure-time. Equation 2 captures the level of need satisfaction for leisure following from leisure time and α .

$$(2) \quad LNSl_{it} = 1 - \exp(-\alpha_{il} * (1 - x_{it}))$$

The overall level of need satisfaction of consumat i at time-step t is a weighted multiplication of the satisfaction of the two needs. The value of γ functions as weighting factor for consumat i regarding the relative importance of the two needs in the overall level of need satisfaction. Setting γ at a value of .5 results in equal weighting of both needs in the overall level of need satisfaction. Equation 3 captures the overall level of need satisfaction as a weighted multiplication of the level of need satisfaction for subsistence and leisure respectively.

$$(3) \quad LNS_{it} = LNS_{sit}^{\gamma} * LNSl_{it}^{1-\gamma}$$

This implies that overall LNS may be insufficient when only one specific need is unsatisfied. A critical value LNS_{min} is being used to determine if a consumat's overall LNS is sufficiently satisfied or not. LNS_{min} ranges from 0 (always satisfied) to 1 (never satisfied).

Opportunities

A renewable resource R is defined that functions as the artificial environment of the consumat. Consuming from this resource provides means for subsistence. CT denotes the total consumption of all consumats. The resource grows every time-step with a factor λ , which is stochastic. This stochastic part allows for variation in the growth rate of the resource, thus simulating natural variability of the resource (e.g., fluctuating weather conditions) in a very simple manner. When the stochastic part of λ is large in comparison to the non-stochastic part, it may happen that the resource shows a decline for a few time-steps. Equation 4 captures the size of the resource at time-step t as the growth factor at time t , times the resource size in the previous time-step, minus the total consumption in the current time-step.

$$(4) \quad R_t = \lambda_t * R_{t-1} - CT_t$$

On average λ is equal to λ_a , the non-stochastic part of the growth factor λ . A random selection from a normal distribution N with a standard deviation σ is used to simulate stochastic variability, as is depicted in equation 5.

$$(5) \quad \lambda_t = \lambda_a + N(0, \sigma)$$

In case of deterministic experiments (no variability in the resource growth factor) λ_t is equal to λ_a (σ is set at 0). In the simulation experiments in this chapter we set λ_a at 110%, a percentage that is often being used in resource dilemma experiments. Without consumption, the resource grows exponentially with 10% at every time-step. A consumption level that consistently exceeds this 10% growth would result in the gradual depletion of the resource.

To satisfy both needs, subsistence and leisure, the consumat has to decide on how much time it should spend consuming from the resource. This consumption can be understood as harvesting behaviour, which we shortly denote as 'working'. The consumat is allowed to work for a maximum of 16 hours a day, thus having a minimum of 8 hours a day for leisure. This minimum has been set to refer to the minimal time that is needed for sleeping and eating. The consumat decides how much to work in units of one hour. Consequently, the following 17 opportunity distributions are available:

Opportunity Distributions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Hours of work	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Hours of leisure	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8

Table 7.1: The 17 opportunity distributions the consumats can choose from

The level of need satisfaction for subsistence depends on how much the consumat is able to consume during one hour of work. This is one of the characteristic abilities of the consumat, and will be discussed in the next section.

The abilities of the consumat

In the simulation experiments to be presented in this chapter the consumat has two abilities, namely a cognitive ability a_{ci} and a physical harvesting ability a_{hi} . The consumat's cognitive ability refers to the time-horizon (TH) it employs when elaborating on the expected outcomes. When the consumat is motivated to elaborate (i.e., when overall $LNS_{it} < LNS_{min}$), and engages in deliberation or social comparison, it will calculate the outcomes of behaviour. The longer the TH the consumat employs, the earlier it detects a possible depletion of the resource. This allows the consumat to restrain its current consumption in order to sustain a higher consumption level in the long run.

The physical ability refers to the quantity of consumption-units the consumat can harvest from the resource R during one hour of work, and is expressed with a value ranging from 0 (no ability) to 1 (maximum ability). A physical ability of 1 implies that the consumat is able to harvest $1/16^{\text{th}}$ (0.0625) consumption-units of the resource per hour. This value is chosen because working for the maximum number of 16 hours adds up to a harvest of exactly 1 consumption-unit. These figures hold for resources that are always equally accessible for harvesting, no matter how abundant or depleted the resource may be.

It is also possible to make the resource less accessible for harvesting the more depleted it is, thereby simulating that the more depleted the resource, the less one can harvest in one hour. A depletion factor π is being introduced to formalise this relation. In the depletion factor we calculate the resource size in the previous time-step (R_{t-1}) divided by the initial resource size (R_{t0}). A factor $\pi \geq 0$ defines the accessibility of the resource as depending on the difference between the initial and previous resource-size (see equation 6). Setting π at 0 results in $(R_{t-1}/R_{t0})^\pi$ being equal to 1. In this case, the resource is always equally accessible for harvesting. The harvest depends on the time spent working times the ability to harvest, provided the resource is not depleted. Increasing π results in a lower harvest-per-hour the more depleted the resource is. For example, setting π at 2 implies that when the size of the resource has been halved the harvest per hour will be quartered. The factor π thus allows for the specification of the depletion dynamics of a resource.

On the basis of the resource development and its own abilities the consumat calculates an expectation regarding its consumption in the next time-step. The time spent working (x_{it}) is being chosen in the cognitive process, and will be further discussed in the section on cognitive processing. The expected individual consumption $E[CI]_{it}$ is equal to the amount of time spent on harvesting, times the consumat's ability to harvest, a_{hi} , and the depletion dynamics. These depletion dynamics involve the resource-size at the previous time-step divided by the initial resource size.

$$(6) \quad E[CI]_{it} = x_{it} * a_{hi} (R_{t-1}/R_{t0})^\pi$$

This expected individual consumption is being used for the calculation of the consumat's uncertainty.

Uncertainty

The uncertainty index U_{it} , which ranges from 0 to 1, is here formalised as the difference between the actual consumption at $t - 1$ and the expected consumption for $t - 1$. This expected consumption for $t - 1$ has been constituted at $t - 2$. Differences between $E[CI]_{it-1}$ and CI_{it-1} may occur due to changes in the resource size (e.g., due to depletion), which causes differences in harvesting efficiency.

$$(7) \quad U_{it} = \text{ABS}(E[CI]_{it-1} - CI_{it-1})$$

That is, uncertainty will be larger the larger the absolute difference between expected and actual consumption at the preceding time-step. The uncertainty tolerance UT is being formalised as the critical value that is being used to indicate above which level of U the consumat engages in social processing (c.f., Chapter 6, the section on cognitive processing). UT ranges from 0 (always uncertain) to 1 (never uncertain). Consumat i is considered to be uncertain and engage in social processing at time-step t when $U_{it} > UT_i$.

UT_i can be defined for each consumat separately, thus allowing to formalise consumats with different uncertainty tolerances. In the experiments to be reported all the consumats in a single simulation run will have identical UT 's as to keep the results transparent for interpretation.

Cognitive processing

The contents of the mental map and the specific operation of the four cognitive processing styles are being formalised for the resource dilemma simulation.

The mental map

First, in the mental map information is being memorised on the consumat's previous opportunity consumption. This implies that the need-satisfying capacities of the various opportunities and the resource size are being memorised. Moreover, it is memorised which other consumat(s) serve as comparison-consumats, as well as the behaviour these consumat(s) performed in the previous time-step ($t-1$). Finally, the mental map contains the perception of the consumat's own abilities, in particular the physical ability to consume.

Repetition

Repetition (habitual behaviour) will occur when $LNS_{it} > LNS_{min}$, and $U_{it} < UT$ (see Chapter 6). Repetition implies that the consumat simply repeats the previous behaviour without updating its mental map. Thus, the consumat is motivated to consume an amount equal to the amount consumed in the previous time-step. Only when it appears that the behavioural control (BC) over this opportunity has dropped below zero, the consumat will switch towards deliberation to find an opportunity that is both satisfying and feasible. For example, when the

physical harvesting ability A_h is smaller than is demanded to repeat the previous behaviour 'x' (RD_{xh}), then $BC < 0$. In our experiments a repeating consumat i at time-step t spends the same number of hours on harvesting as it did in the previous time-step, as indicated below.

$$(8) \quad x_{it} = x_{it-1}$$

Deliberation

Deliberation will occur when $LNS_{it} < LNS_{min}$, and $U_{it} < UT$ (see Chapter 6). Deliberation starts with updating the mental map. This updating implies that information is gathered regarding the need-satisfying capacities of the opportunities, the resource demands of the opportunities and the consumat's own abilities. This information is used to calculate the behavioural control (BC) over the possible opportunities, and the expected outcomes in terms of LNS of consuming opportunities. In calculating the expected outcomes the consumat uses a certain time-horizon (TH), which indicates its cognitive ability. The consumat will be motivated to consume the opportunity with the highest perceived multiple need-satisfying capacity, that is feasible in terms of BC. In our experiments the 17 opportunities involve different numbers of hours spent working versus leisure time. Working for more than 16 hours implies that the consumat would have less than 8 hours for leisure, which is an absolute minimum. Consequently, we can state that the behavioural control over these opportunities is negative. The deliberating consumat will choose that number of hours working that maximises the overall level of need satisfaction, provided that its behavioural control over that opportunity is positive (equation 9).

$$(9) \quad MAX_{xi} [LNS_i] \text{ for } BC_{ix} > 0$$

This maximal level of need satisfaction is based on a maximisation of the weighted product of both levels of need satisfaction as formalised in equations 1 and 2.

In deliberating on this maximal level of need satisfaction, the consumat takes the total resource consumption by other consumats into account. On the basis of the desired consumption for all consumats j , the deliberating consumat calculates an expected total consumption of all consumats which is necessary to project the resource depletion. For simplicity's sake the consumat assumes that the other consumats consume the same quantity as in the previous period which is an amount equal to $CT_{t-1} - CI_{i,t-1}$. Multiplying this with the relative change in the depletion factor as introduced in equation 6 we derive the total desired consumption of the other consumats. The consumption of consumat i itself is equal to $x_{i,t} * a_{h,i} * (R_{t-1}/R_{t0})^\pi$ as indicated in equation 6. This results into

$$(10) \quad CET_t = (CT_{t-1} - CI_{i,t-1}) * (R_{t-1}/R_{t-2})^\pi + x_{i,t} * a_{h,i} * (R_{t-1}/R_{t0})^\pi$$

This allows the consumat to calculate the expected resource size for the time-horizon it employs.

$$(11) \quad R_{t+ci} = R_{t-1+ci} * \lambda - CET_t$$

Where c_i = cognitive ability of consumat i , expressed as the time-horizon in time-steps.

Imitation

Imitation occurs when $LNS_{it} > LNS_{min}$, and $U_{it} > UT$ (see Chapter 6). When the consumat engages in imitation, it will read its mental map and recall the consumat that functioned most recently as comparison-consumat. It will do what this consumat did in the previous time-step. The consumat is thus motivated to consume whatever the other similar consumat was consuming. Only when it appears that the behavioural control over this opportunity is below zero, the consumat will switch towards social comparison. In our simulation experiments this implies that the consumat follows another consumat with about similar harvesting abilities (a_h). If the number of consumats is larger than 2, the comparison consumat is initially chosen at random. After engaging in social comparison a comparable consumat is being available in the mental map. Equation 12 states that the time spent working of consumat i at time-step t is equal to the consumption of the comparison consumat j at $t-1$.

$$(12) \quad x_i = x_{j \ t-1}$$

Social Comparison

Social comparison occurs when $LNS_{it} < LNS_{min}$, and $U_{it} > UT$). While engaging in social comparison, the consumat will first update its' mental map. Then it will observe the consumptive behaviour of other consumats having about the same abilities. When other consumats' abilities differ no more than a certain percentage from the own abilities, those consumats are assumed to be similar, and thus comparable. The range within which other consumats are considered as comparable is denoted with the comparison-factor ϵ If ϵ is set at 0, only other consumats with exactly equal abilities are being considered as comparable, whereas when setting ϵ at 0.5, also consumats with half or twice as much ability are considered as comparable. In our experiments, only the ability to harvest (a_h) is taken into consideration in calculating the comparison factor ϵ Only when there is another comparable consumat j the consumat can engage in social processing, as is denoted in equation 13.

$$(13) \quad ABS(a_{hi} - a_{hj}) > \epsilon, \text{ then social processing}$$

If the number of consumats is larger than 2, the comparison consumat is initially chosen at random. After engaging in social comparison a comparable consumat is selected on the basis of similarity in ability (equation 13). This comparable consumat is being memorised in the mental map, and is being used as comparison consumat in situations where the consumat engages in imitation.

Having selected a comparison consumat, the consumat will calculate the expected outcomes for reproducing the opportunity consumption the other consumat manifested in the previous time-step. This calculation employs the full time-horizon the consumat is able to use. Also the behavioural control over this behaviour is being calculated. If the expected outcomes of reproducing the other's consumption are higher than the expected outcomes of

not changing one's opportunity consumption, and the behavioural control over this opportunity is positive, then the consumat will reproduce the other consumat's opportunity consumption. The consumat thus will be motivated to perform either the other consumat's behaviour, or its own previous behaviour, depending on the highest perceived multiple need-satisfying capacity of both opportunities (according to equation 9). In our experiments the consumats will determine which number of hours spent working yields the highest LNS, either reproducing the behaviour 'x' of the comparable consumat 'c', or not changing its (previous) behaviour (equation 14).

$$(14) \quad x_i = \text{MAX LNS}_i [x_{ct-1}] [x_{it-1}]$$

Opportunity consumption

The direct outcome of the cognitive process is that the consumat chooses to consume a certain quantity of the available opportunities. In the current simulation experiments the actual consumption of the individual consumat i at time-step t (CI_{it}) depends on the number of hours spent working (x_{it}), times the ability to consume (a_{hi}). This is being multiplied with the depletion dynamics, to include the (possible) effect of the resource-size on the consumption per hour. Finally, this all is being multiplied by the total consumption (CT) at time-step t divided by the desired consumption (CD) at time-step t . This is done to allocate consumption over the consumats when the total desired consumption is larger than the total possible consumption (equation 15).

$$(15) \quad CI_{it} = x_{it} * a_{hi} (R_{t-1}/R_{t0})^{\pi} * (CT_t/CD_t)$$

The total consumption of the population at time-step t (CT_t) depends on the maximum available resource and the sum of the expected individual consumption (CI_t) of all agents. As long as the resource is large enough to allow for the desired consumption to be realised, the total consumption will be equal to the desired consumption, resulting in (CT_t/CD_t) having a value of 1. However, if the desired consumption is larger than the resource allows for, this value becomes smaller than 1. Then the consumption is allocated over the consumats, and they consume the whole resource. Equation 16 states that the total consumption at time-step t is the lowest value of either (1) the resource size at time-step t or (2) the sum of the expected individual consumption of all agents

$$(16) \quad CT_t = \min((1+\lambda)*R(t-1), \sum_i E(CI)_{it})$$

Following consumption, the levels of need satisfaction according to equation 1 and 2 and the resource-size will change, resulting in new values for the driving forces of behaviour.

In the simulation experiments presented in this chapter, the behavioural dynamics are being studied without experimenting with deliberate changes of the driving forces during the process. No experiments are being done using simulated policy measures.

The following sections present a series of experiments that have been performed with the consumats as circumscribed above. The first series of experiments is intended to demonstrate the performance of the different consumat rules. A next section presents a second series of experiments, intended to investigate the effects of environmental uncertainty. A subsequent section describes the effects of variations in the accessibility of the resource. These experiments are aimed at gaining a better understanding of the behavioural dynamics that provoke over-consumption of a limited natural resource.

Experimenting with the consumat rules

Now that the consumat rules and the resource have been formalised, it is time to start experimenting with the consumats. Many experiments are possible with the consumat approach as sketched above. In this section we aim to demonstrate the various behavioural rules by presenting a series of simple experiments. Whereas later experiments will include two or even twenty-five consumats, the first experiment only involves a single consumat that engages purely in deliberation. This basic simulation offers a good reference point from where new variables and factors can be introduced.

Varying the time-horizon of a single, deliberating consumat

The first simulation experiments are aimed at investigating how a single consumat manages a limited resource when it is exclusively engaging in deliberation (c.f. Table 5.4). To guarantee that the consumat is only deliberating, both LNSmin and UT are set at a value of 1. This implies that the consumat is never satisfied ($LNS < LNS_{min}$) and always certain ($U < UT$). The time-horizon of the consumat is varied. At each time-step the consumat calculates what opportunity (i.e., amount of time spent working) would result in the maximum need-satisfaction (LNS) for the time-horizon (TH) being considered (equation 9 - 11). It will be observed how variations in time-horizon affect the opportunity consumption of the consumat, its level of need satisfaction and the resource size.

Given a cornucopious resource (setting the initial resource-size at 10 yields a situation where maximum consumption $<$ resource growth per time-step) the single consumat has complete consumptive freedom, because there is no risk of depleting the resource. We equipped the consumat with a harvesting ability of 1, and varied the time-horizon the consumat employed in calculating its optimal harvesting behaviour. As initial setting ($t = 1$) the consumat is working for 8 hours a day. It was observed that the consumat always engages in a stable behaviour pattern of working for 9 hours a day (consuming 0.5625 per time-step), and using the remaining 15 hours for leisure. This pattern results in the consumat experiencing a stable level of need satisfaction for subsistence (LNSs) of 0.94 and a level of need satisfaction for leisure (LNSl) of 0.89. The time-horizon (TH) the consumat employs while deliberating has no effect on its behaviour, because it is not being confronted with a possible future depletion of the resource. Instead, the resource size is consistently increasing.

Next, things are made less easy for the consumat. Setting the initial resource size at 2.5 yields a resource that is vulnerable to overexploitation but which, however, is large enough to allow for a sustainable consumption. It is assumed, however, that an early anticipation of

possible resource depletion is critical to arrive at sustainable behaviour. Consequently, if the consumat elaborates on its consumption using a long time-horizon (TH), it will detect a possible future resource depletion much earlier than in case of using a short time horizon. Consequently, employing a long time horizon enables the consumat to react early to possible resource depletion by moderating its consumption.

The first experiment with an initial resource size of 2.5 involves a consumat with a very short time perspective of $TH = 1$. This implies that the consumat optimises its LNS for the current and the next time-step. This consumat, not being able to perceive the longer-term consequences of its behaviour, quickly increases its time spent working from 8 hours (initial setting) to 9 hours a day. The associated consumption increases from 0.5 to 0.56 units per time-step, at which level consumption remains stable for 5 time-steps because of the optimal outcomes. This level of consumption is quite satisfactory for the consumat ($LNSs = 0.94$ and $LNSl = 0.89$), and mirrors the situation of the cornucopious resource sketched above, until $t = 7$, when the resource has been depleted such that this consumption level can no longer be sustained (see Figure 7.1). At $t = 7$ the consumat can work productively for only three hours, consuming 0.18 of the resource and leaving the resource almost completely depleted at $t = 8$. By consequence of this depletion the $LNSs$ drops to 0, whereas the $LNSl$ goes to 1. At $t = 19$ the remains of the resource have grown to a volume that can be consumed in one hour of working, which the consumat then does, thereby completely depleting the resource. Following that, the situation is completely stable, the consumat being completely dissatisfied for subsistence because the resource is empty, but being maximally satisfied regarding leisure.

Figure 7.1: Resource size and consumption level (vertical) for a deliberating consumat with $TH = 1$, $TH = 10$ and $TH = 20$, as a function of time.

It can be observed that the resource-size at $t=1$ is about 2.25 instead of the initial setting of 2.5. This is due to the fact that at $t = 1$ the resource has grown with 0.25 (equation 5), but the initial consumption of 0.5 at $t = 1$ is being subtracted from that growth.

Setting the TH at 10 makes a large difference (see Figure 7.1). The initial setting of 8 hours of working yields a level of consumption that, if continued, will lead towards a depletion of the resource. The consumat calculates which opportunity-use would yield the highest level of need satisfaction for the next ten time-steps. It concludes that moderating its time spent working down to 5 hours a day would be optimal, and so it does at $t = 2$. This implies a consumption of 0.31 units, resulting in a fair level of need satisfaction (LNSs of 0.80 and a LNSI of 0.97). For the next time-steps, working for five hours a day remains the optimal solution, but the resource is clearly depleting in the longer run. At $t = 6$ the consumat perceives that this level of consumption is too high to achieve a maximal need satisfaction for the next ten time-steps. The deliberating consumat now concludes that working should be decreased to 4 hours a day, resulting in a consumption of 0.25. This process repeats at $t = 11$, where the consumat further decreases its time spent working to 3 hours a day, consuming 0.19, and at $t = 17$, at which time it works 2 hours a day, consuming 0.13. This level is being sustained for quite some time (until step 30).

However, we observe that the resource is still decreasing (Figure 7.1), and at $t = 30$ the consumat ‘concludes’ that it may work for only one hour a day to prevent the resource from depleting. From that moment on the consumat switches between one and two hours working, maintaining the resource level between 0.73 and 0.75. The consumat thus ends up sustaining its consumption, however, not being very satisfied regarding its subsistence need (LNSs switches between 0.46 and 0.27), but being very satisfied regarding its leisure needs (LNSi = 0.99).

Increasing the TH to 20 time-steps further illustrates the importance of the time-horizon on the resource consumption. After the first consumption the consumat perceives that it should moderate its consumption now so as to guarantee optimal outcomes in the long run. At $t = 1$ the consumat thus reduces its time spent working from 8 to 4 hours a day. This implies a consumption of 0.25, resulting in a LNSs of about 0.71 and a LNSI of about 0.98. After $t = 6$ the consumat occasionally reduces its time spent working with one hour. As Figure 7.1 shows, this secures the resource to remain at a high level, thus allowing a satisfactory future consumption level. During the periods of diminished consumption, which last for one or two time-steps, consumption drops to 0.19 and the LNSs drops to about 0.61.

Conclusions

These first experiments demonstrate that sustainable use of a resource by a single deliberating consumat is strongly affected by the time-horizon being used in deliberating about future consumption. Neglecting future outcomes results in a large consumption and need satisfaction at first, causing a quick depletion of the resource, and a fully dissatisfied need for subsistence later on. Deliberating while using a longer TH results in a quick reduction of consumption so as to avoid depletion of the resource. Being aware of a longer TH (20) here proves to be far more efficient than considering a shorter TH (10) in achieving an optimal level of need satisfaction in the long run. *Ergo*, the longer the time-horizon the consumat

employs, the more sustainable its consumption will be, because the resource is being maintained.

Introducing repetition as processing style

In the previous experiment the consumat engaged only in deliberation, which had been accomplished by making it unsatisfiable ($LNS_{min} = 1$) and certain ($UT = 1$). However, it would be worthwhile to make the consumat satisfiable. This implies that the consumat, when satisfied, engages in repetitive (habitual) behaviour. Introducing repetition as cognitive processing style enhances the realism of the consumat, since real people, when satisfied about their behaviour, do not tend to deliberate much about alternatives. During repetitive behaviour, however, the consumat does not update its mental map, thus it is not aware of a possibly depleting resource.

To allow repetitive behaviour to occur in the present experiment, the minimum level of need satisfaction LNS_{min} is set at 0.75. This implies that as long as LNS is larger than 0.75, the consumat is satisfied and will engage in repetition (c.f. equation 3). The time-horizon (TH) of the consumat is set at 20. Otherwise the previous experiment is replicated.

In the current experiment, it appears that in the first time-step the consumption level of 0.50 following from the initial setting of 8 hours working per day is high enough to keep LNS above the critical value of 0.75. The consumat is thus satisfied regarding its needs for subsistence and leisure. As a result of that, the consumat will continue with the repetitive processing style, and thus will continue to work for 8 hours a day. This, however, is no sustainable consumption level, and when the resource has been depleted completely at $t = 7$, consumption will drop to zero and so does LNS s. Consequently, at $t = 8$ the consumat will engage in deliberation, only now taking account of TH. However, there is nothing left to deliberate about for consumption.

This experiment demonstrates what looks like a rather naive type of behaviour. As long as the consumat's needs are satisfied, it remains totally unaware of what happens with the resource. One of the reasons for this naive behaviour can be attributed to the character of the resource, which is always equally accessible for harvesting. No matter if the resource is abundant or almost depleted, during one hour of work the consumat will obtain 0.0625 consumption units. The only factor that determines the consumption level is the consumat's ability to consume, that is, for as long the resource is not depleted. It would be more realistic to make the consumption level also depending on the size of the resource.

Introducing variability in the accessibility of the resource

To improve the realism of the experiments, a resource should be formalised that makes harvesting more difficult the more depleted the resource is. Such a resource would be more resistant against depletion and it would alert the consumat earlier by means of decreasing harvests in case of a (strong) decline of the resource. Moreover, such a resource is more realistic. For example, when fishing, the harvest not only depends on one's fishing ability and the time spent fishing, but also on the available fish-stock. A resource function is introduced that makes the harvest dependent on the time spent working and on the resource size. The smaller the resource gets, the less a consumat can harvest per unit of time. The depletion dynamics are being changed by setting the accessibility factor π at 2 (c.f. equation 6). This

implies that when the resource has been halved, one's harvest per hour will reduce to a quarter. This causes that the 1 on 1 relation between the time spent working and the consumption (harvest) level, which characterised the experiments above, has been transformed into a more complex relationship. Therefore, in the experiments to come, we will graphically present the time spent working in addition to the consumption level.

Setting LNSmin at 0.75, we observe that the consumat is engaging in repetition as processing style until $t = 8$, when LNSs drops below 0.75. At that moment the consumat starts deliberating, and TH becomes relevant. The consumat will then increase or decrease its proportion of time spent working, depending on the time-horizon (TH) it employs when deliberating (see Figure 7.2).

Until $t = 8$ the consumat engages in repetition, so TH does not matter. At $t = 8$, however, the consumat with a TH of 1 immediately increases its time spent working to increase its LNSs. At $t = 11$ this consumat further increases its time spent working. The resulting increase in consumption yields a significantly smaller resource and a lower consumption level in the longer run ($t > 13$) compared with the consumat that employs a TH of 20. This latter consumat 'concludes' at $t = 8$ that it should moderate its time spent working so as to guarantee the highest outcomes in the long run. The consumat with a TH of 20 will therefore more quickly reach a stable consumption pattern, as can be seen in Figure 7.2. At $t = 22$ this consumat increases its time spent working a little bit because the relative stable level of the resource indicates that a higher level of consumption would yield optimal outcomes for the consumat.

Figure 7.2: Resource size, consumption level and proportion of working time for a single consumat engaging in repetition and deliberation, TH = 1 and TH = 20.

The above simulation experiment has been replicated, while equipping the consumats with a LNSmin of .20. Under this condition the consumat is engaging only in repetition, thus the time-horizon (TH) has no effect on its behaviour. Consumats with LNSmin = .20 therefore continue to work for 0.5 of the time, thus working equally or more than consumats with LNSmin = 0.75 and TH = 20, and they are working equally or less than consumats with LNSmin = 0.75 and TH = 1. Compared with the latter consumat, the consumats with LNSmin = 0.20 will consume less, and thus not deplete the resource that quickly. Consequently, in the longer run, consumats with LNSmin = 0.20 will obtain a higher level of need satisfaction than the consumat with LNSmin = 0.75 and TH = 1.

Conclusions

When consumats engage in repetition (habitual behaviour), they do not employ the TH. This may cause that they are not aware of a depleting resource. When the resource has significantly depleted the LNS of consumats may drop below the critical level of LNSmin. However, deliberation when the resource has already been depleted is too late to find a level of consumption that is satisfactory and sustainable. However, including repetition (habitual behaviour) does not always yield less sustainable outcomes. The previous experiment demonstrates that under the condition of a short time-horizon, habitual behaviour of easily satisfied subjects may be more sustainable and yields a higher LNS in the long run than reasoned behaviour of difficult-to-satisfy subjects.

Experimenting with two consumats

The experiments as discussed above are relevant for temporal dilemmas (see Chapter 2), confronting the consumat with the choice of how much to harvest now versus in the future. In the following experiments also the social dilemma is being addressed by introducing a second consumat that has access to the resource and may contribute to its depletion. The consumats here are interdependent because their individual consumption determines the size of the common resource. A consumat that is over-harvesting not only endangers its own future consumption, but also the future outcomes of the other consumat. In the present set of simulation experiments this situation has been formalised by confronting two consumats with a resource that is initially twice as large (5.0) as in the previous experiments with a single consumat. Just as in the previous experiment, the accessibility factor π has been set at 2, causing that when the resource has been halved, one's harvest per hour will reduce to a quarter. Both consumats expect that, in the present time-step, the other consumat will consume the same as they did in the previous time-step. Using identical settings for the minimal level of need satisfaction and time-horizon as in the previous experiment (LNSmin = 0.75, TH = 1) yields exactly the same outcomes as in the comparable single-consumat experiment with TH = 1 (Figure 7.2). An increase of the time spent working can be observed at $t = 8$ and $t = 11$. The only difference resided in the resource-size, which in this two-consumat experiment was exactly twice as large as in the comparable single consumat experiment.

The differences between the single-consumat experiments and the two-consumat experiments become apparent when the TH of both consumats is increased from 1 to 20. In the first time-steps we see (Figure 7.3) a stable proportion of time-worked of 0.5 due to the

repetitive cognitive process. However, at $t = 8$, the LNSs has decreased so much (below 0.75) that both consumats start deliberating. Due to the large TH they are using, they decrease their proportion of time worked so as to prevent the resource from depleting. Yet, we observe that only after $t = 50$ the resource size appears to reach a stable level.

Figure 7.3: Resource size, consumption level and proportion of work for two consumats with a TH of 20

In Figure 7.3 several small short-term oscillations can be seen starting at $t = 8$, when both consumats start deliberating. These oscillations are caused by the difference between how much each consumat expects the other to consume (c.f. equation 10), and what the other actually consumes. For reasons of clarity, this does not involve social processing yet. When, e.g., at $t = 8$ both consumats consume relatively little, they each deliberate on how much to consume in the next time-step, thereby assuming that the other consumat will remain consuming at this low level (c.f. equation 10). As a result, at $t = 9$ they both increase their consumption to a relatively high level. Deliberating about how much to consume in the next time-step, both assume that the other remains consuming at that relatively high level. Trying to avoid a resource depletion, both consumats decrease their consumption at $t = 10$ to maximise their long-term outcomes. The outcomes both consumats experience thus alternate between lower and higher than expected, and as a response the consumats adapt their behaviour in the opposite direction.

Conclusions

In the current experiments the consumat, while deliberating, expects the other consumat to perform the same behaviour as in the previous time-step. This is of course a very simple formalisation of such expectations, and more realistic formalisations are imaginable. Yet, this simple formalisation yields relatively stable behaviour after some time-steps. More important,

we observe that the resource depletes more in the 2-consumat experiment than in the corresponding 1-consumat experiment. For example, where the resource-size in the 1-consumat experiment with $TH = 20$ (Figure 7.2) is about 1.3 at $t = 30$, in the comparable 2-consumat experiment (Figure 7.3) this resource-size at $t = 30$ is about 2.4, where we would expect 2.6 ($2 * 1.3$). This indicates that the oscillating pattern in the early time-steps following from this simple expectation causes the consumats to consume more than in the corresponding 1-consumat experiment.

Introducing social processing

Thus far, the consumats have only engaged in individual processing styles (repetition and deliberation). This is because the uncertainty tolerance (UT) was set at 1, and the uncertainty (U) following from the difference between the expected outcomes and the actual outcomes never reached this maximal value (c.f. equation 7). If the expected outcomes and the actual outcomes differ to a degree that exceeds the setting of UT, uncertainty will be too high and the consumat will engage in social processing (social comparison and imitation). Because in the current simulation experiments we have not yet introduced a stochastic variable in the resource growth-function (c.f. equation 5, here $\lambda_v = \lambda_a$), U will remain at a relatively low level. This implies that UT has to be set at a low level to initiate social processing in the consumats. Setting UT at a level between 0.0 and 0.1 implies that a level of uncertainty tolerance can be defined that causes U to frequently exceed UT, thereby stimulating social processing.

Social processing involves the comparison with another, more or less similar consumat. To define the range wherein other consumats are considered as similar, the variable ϵ has been introduced (equation 13). If ϵ is set low, only consumats with about equal abilities will be accepted as comparable, whereas a large ϵ implies that also more differing consumats will be considered to be comparable. If a consumat is uncertain, and it perceives another consumat with abilities that fall within the range of acceptance of ϵ the consumat will use this consumat as comparison-other. While socially processing, the consumat will either imitate the behaviour of the comparable other (when $LNS > LNS_{min}$) or engage in social comparison (when $LNS < LNS_{min}$), thereby checking if adopting the behaviour of the comparison-other would yield higher outcomes.

The next experiment is a replication of the previous experiment, only with an UT of 0.05 and an abilities' comparison-factor ϵ of 0.5 (c.f. equation 13). Because the two consumats are identical, their equal ability implies that they always fall within the critical range of the comparison-factor. Running the simulation model with these settings showed that the consumats become uncertain only during the first two time-steps. This is because the decrease of the resource is the strongest at $t = 1$ and $t = 2$, causing that the resource decreases more than they expected. Because at that time both consumats are satisfied, they engage in imitation, copying the behaviour of the other consumat at $t - 1$. Because the consumats performed identical behaviour at $t - 1$, the outcomes of imitation do not differ from a situation where they engaged in repetition. After $t = 2$, the resource depletion decreases to such a degree that the resulting uncertainty never exceeds the uncertainty tolerance value ($U < 0.05$). The consumats thus engage in individual processing only. When the LNS of both consumats drops below the critical value at $t = 7$, both consumats engage in deliberation, just

as in the previous experiment. Consequently, the outcomes of this experiment are exactly the same as plotted in Figure 7.3.

To avoid both consumats performing identical behaviour two different consumats are being formalised. Therefore the harvesting-ability of consumat 1 is set at 1 and the harvesting-ability of consumat 2 at 0.60 (see the section on abilities). Moreover, to stimulate social processing UT is set at a very low level of 0.0025. Finally, LNSmin is set at 0.60 to stimulate automatic processing (consumats are easily satisfied). Figure 7.4 shows that both consumats perform the same behaviour during the first 18 time-steps.

Figure 7.4: Resource size, consumption level and proportion of work for two different consumats with a TH of 20, including social processing

Because during that time they are satisfied, they either engage in repetition or in imitation, depending on the value of U. As a consequence, no new behaviour will be performed. This changes at $t = 19$, when consumat 2 is the first to change its proportion of time spent working. This is because the lower ability of consumat 2 causes its LNS to drop below the critical level of 0.60 at $t = 19$. Consequently, consumat 2 starts deliberating, and decides to increase its time spent working. This causes its LNS to increase above 0.60 again, inclining consumat 2 towards repetition at $t = 20$, thus sustaining the increase in time spent working. Both consumats are satisfied again at that time, consumat 2 working somewhat more than consumat 1. However, the increase in working by consumat 2 results in an increase in consumption at $t = 20$, causing the resource to deplete at a higher rate. As a consequence, consumption decreases with a level that exceeds their expectations, and at $t = 21$ both consumats become uncertain. This uncertainty combined with their satisfaction (both consumats then have a LNS above 0.60) implies that both consumats engage in mutual imitation. For consumat 1 this implies an increase in its time spent working, to 'catch up' with

consumat 2. This maintains its LNS above the critical level of 0.60. While imitating consumat 1, consumat 2 decreases its time spent working back to 0.50. At $t = 22$ consumat 1 decreases its time spent working back to 0.50 on the basis of imitation. During $t = 22$ consumat 2 is satisfied and certain, thus repeating this time spent working of 0.50. At $t = 23$ both consumats are repeating this time spent working of 0.50. However, this was and still is not enough to keep consumat 2 satisfied, and at $t = 24$, its LNS has dropped below the critical value, which causes consumat 2 to engage in deliberation. As a consequence, at $t = 24$ consumat 2 decides to increase its proportion of time working. This in turn increases uncertainty in both consumats, resulting in imitative behaviour of consumat 1 at $t = 26$. The process of mutual imitation repeats itself once more, and from $t = 31$ both consumats remain working for 0.75 of the time while imitating each other. It is interesting to see that consumat 1 works more than optimal, because working somewhat less would yield a higher level of need satisfaction (increase in LNSI > decrease in LNSs). On the basis of imitation it copied the behaviour of consumat 2. Because this was satisfactory, and uncertainty dropped, consumat 1 continued working for 0.75 on the basis of repetition, thus engaging in some sort of habitual over-harvesting. This effect may be called the *imitation-effect*. Because of its lesser abilities, consumat 2 is not capable of consuming enough to be satisfied. Despite continuous deliberation, it does not find a more satisfying behaviour than working for 0.75 of the time.

To demonstrate that this imitation-effect may yield non-optimal behaviour, we replicated the previous experiment, setting the comparison-factor ε at 0.5., the harvesting-ability of consumat 1 at 1 and the harvesting-ability of consumat 2 at 0.60, and LNSmin for both consumats at 0.60. The only difference with the previous experiment is that the uncertainty tolerance is set at the maximum level of 1 ($UT = 1$), so that social processing does not occur. In Figure 7.5 the results of this experiment are presented, depicting the resource size as found in the previous experiment including social processing (Figure 7.4) as reference data.

Because the consumats are not uncertain, they only engage in individual processing. Consumat 1 remains satisfied, and thus does not change its behaviour, while continuing to work for half of the time (8 hours). Consumat 2, having less ability and thus consuming less, becomes dissatisfied at $t = 19$. As a result, it engages in deliberation, and calculates that increasing the proportion of working time to 0.625 (9 hours) is optimal. This causes consumat 2 to be satisfied until $t = 27$, where it again engages in deliberation and calculates that working for 0.75 (12 hours) of the time is optimal. This is satisfactory until $t = 30$, where its LNS again drops below 0.60. However, consumat 2 does not find a more satisfying behaviour at $t = 30$, and it remains working for 0.75 of the time, yet being dissatisfied. Working for more hours would only yield a small increase in LNSs, at the cost of LNSI, thereby decreasing overall LNS.

Figure 7.5: Resource size, consumption level and proportion of work for two different consumats with a TH of 20, excluding social processing

Conclusions

The above experiments demonstrate that the effect of social processing is only visible when the consumats perform different behaviour beforehand. This necessitates the formalisation of consumats with different abilities. Most interesting is that in the experiment which included social processing, the resource depleted more strongly (see Figure 7.5, the reference resource data) than in the last experiment without social processing. It appears that under the condition of a limited resource, imitation may result in harvesting more at the cost of the achieved level of need satisfaction in the long run. These experiments thus demonstrated that imitation might cause a consumat to perform non-optimal behaviour.

Experimenting with 25 consumats

The next experiment investigates if the effect of social processing also holds in a large group of consumats. Therefore 25 consumats were formalised. Five subgroups were created, each group consisting of 5 consumats. These subgroups differed with respect to the harvesting ability of the consumats, respectively having an ability level of 1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4 and 0.2. Just like in the previous experiment, LNSmin was set at 0.60 and ϵ at 0.5 for all consumats. The initial resource size was 2.5 units per consumat, thus a total of 62.5. The accessibility factor π (c.f. equation 6) was set at 1, implying that when the resource-size has been halved, one's harvest per hour will also be halved. The resource is thus more vulnerable for depletion than in the previous experiments where π was set at 2. The current settings are likely to increase the difference between developments in the resource size as following from different settings of time-horizon and uncertainty tolerance. The settings of uncertainty tolerance (UT) were varied, so that a condition was created where the consumats only engage in individual

behaviour ('no social': $UT = 1$), and a condition where the consumats engage in all four behavioural processing styles ('social': $UT = 0.0025$). For both conditions simulation-experiments were performed with the consumats having a time-horizon of either 5 or 20 time-steps ($TH = 5$ or $TH = 20$). In Figure 7.6 the resource size is being presented for the resulting four conditions as a function of time.

Figure 7.6 shows that in the two 'uncertain' conditions where the consumats can perform social processing ($TH = 20$, social and $TH = 5$, social) the resource is depleting faster than in the two conditions where the consumats only process individually ($TH = 20$, no social and $TH = 5$, no social). This is in line with the effects found in the previous simulation experiment, which demonstrated that particularly imitation stimulates an increase in harvesting at the cost of the level of need satisfaction in the long run. The groups of consumats with a lower harvesting ability will be the first to engage in deliberation because they are the first to become dissatisfied. As a consequence they increase their consumption, which in its turn seriously affects the resource size and thus yields uncertainty in the consumats. Only in the social condition ($UT = 0.0025$) this causes the consumats with a higher ability, which are still satisfied at that moment in time, to engage in imitative behaviour. The increased time spent working thus spreads through the population, resulting in a faster depletion of the resource than had they engaged in repeating their previous behaviour.

Figure 7.6: Resource size for 25 different consumats under 4 conditions

Whereas the two social-processing conditions ($TH = 5$, social, and $TH = 20$, social) show a remarkable difference regarding the development of the resource-size, the two no-social processing conditions hardly show any difference between them (Figure 7.6). The similarity between the $TH = 5$ and $TH = 20$ conditions for the no-social processing conditions is caused by the fact that all consumats expect that the other 24 consumats will continue their

previous behaviour. Consequently, when deliberating, the consumats expect that their own consumption level does not significantly affect the future resource-size. Hence, it hardly matters if the consumats deliberate with a TH of 5 or a TH of 20. The slightly higher time spent working resulting from deliberating with a TH of 5 does not cause a much larger consumption from the resource. As can be seen in Figure 7.6, in the TH = 5 no-social condition the resource-size is only slightly lower than in the TH 20 no-social condition.

Regarding the two social processing conditions, it appears that the use of a large time-horizon (TH = 20) results in the resource being depleted at a slower rate than if a short time-horizon (TH = 5) is used. Remarkably, in the latter condition (TH = 5, social) it can be seen that the resource reaches its lowest level at $t = 25$, and afterwards shows a small increase. This is being caused by the fact that at that time all the consumats engage in deliberating, and with a TH of 5 they calculate that a decrease of consumption is necessary to increase their level of need satisfaction. The difference between the two social processing conditions resides in the fact that the consumats do not elaborate on new consumption options while engaging in social processing. Only when they deliberate they may find a new optimal behaviour. The consumats that are most likely to start deliberating are the consumats with the lowest ability, because their LNS will be the first to drop below the critical value. How much they will increase their time spent working so as to increase consumption, depends on the time-horizon they use in deliberating. Consumats with a TH of 5 will increase their time spent working more than consumats with a TH of 20. This causes the consumats with a TH of 5 to bring about a greater disturbance in the resource size, resulting in a larger uncertainty in all consumats. Moreover, the consumats having a TH of 5 provide a behavioural example that involves working for more hours than the behavioural example provided by the consumats with a TH of 20. Consequently, the consumats with a higher ability to harvest are more likely to engage in imitation under the TH = 5 condition, and in that condition they have a higher chance of being confronted with high consumptive exemplary behaviour. Imitating this behaviour causes a rapid depletion of the resource, as can be seen in Figure 7.6.

Conclusions

The current experiment demonstrated that the effects of social processing also occur in larger groups of consumats. Moreover, it appears that a short time-horizon may create the conditions that facilitate the imitation effect to happen.

To further investigate the robustness of the effects of social processing, we have to perform many more simulation experiments under varying conditions. The introduction of a stochastic resource is an important step in manipulating consumats' uncertainty. This will be done in the next section.

Experimenting with different types of resources

In the previous section a series of experiments has been presented in which consumats were confronted with a resource having a non-stochastic growing function ($\lambda_t = \lambda_a$, c.f. equation 4 and 5). This section is aimed at investigating the effects of introducing a stochastic growing function of the resource (equation 5: $\lambda_t = \lambda_a + N(0, \sigma)$). On the basis of the results of the previous experiments it is expected that a higher value for σ will yield a higher uncertainty of the consumats, and the ensuing social processes cause them to consume more from the resource.

Introducing environmental uncertainty

The previous section demonstrated the significant role of uncertainty in the management of a renewable resource. In these experiments uncertainty resulted from irregularities in the resource growth, which often were caused by the changing consumption patterns of (one of) the consumats. This would incite social processing only when the uncertainty tolerance (UT) was set very low. However, in real life the irregularities in the resource growth are not only caused by consumption, but they are also originating from the often very complex dynamics of the resource. For example, the growth of a fish-stock is not only depending on the catch of the fishermen, but also on weather conditions, sea temperature, the food situation in the sea and pollution, to name a few factors. In the experiments below, such irregularities are formalised in the resource growth in the simplest way by introducing a stochastic function in the resource growth. This implies that simulation-runs with the same initial settings may show different developments regarding the resource growth and the consumat behaviour. Consequently, experiments aimed at revealing the effects of different initial-settings require that for each initial-settings-condition several simulation-runs be performed. This allows for the comparison of the different conditions within an experiment.

The following experiments are being focussed at the effects of different levels of uncertainty tolerance (UT) and a varying minimum level of need satisfaction (LNSmin) on the management of the resource. For LNSmin (see the section on the needs of the consumat) 10 values have been selected ranging from very easy to satisfy (LNSmin = 0.05) to very hard to satisfy (LNSmin = 0.95). For UT (see the section on uncertainty) 10 values have been selected between 0.005 and 0.095, which range appears to capture consumats that seldom engage in social processing (UT = 0.095) and consumats that very frequently engage in social processing (UT = 0.005). Pairing the ten values for LNSmin with the ten values for UT yields a design with 100 (LNSmin, UT) conditions. For each condition 10 simulation runs are being performed, resulting in 1000 simulation runs for the overall experiment. The conditions in the experiment are expected to yield differences regarding the prevailing cognitive processing rules. For example, setting UT and LNSmin both at a low level will increase the likelihood of the consumats engaging in imitation, as they are quickly uncertain (low UT) and easy to satisfy (low LNSmin) (see the section on cognitive processing).

Each run starts with an initial resource size of 5. The standard deviation σ in the resource growth-function (c.f. equation 5) is set at 0.02 to introduce a small random part in the resource growth. The accessibility factor π is set at 1, implying that when the resource has

been halved, it becomes two times as difficult to harvest. Two consumats are confronted with this resource. Both consumats are given a time-horizon (TH) of 20. Consumat 1 has a harvesting ability of 1.0, whilst consumat 2 has an ability of 0.5. The LNSmin and UT of both consumats are varied according to the above design, resulting in 100 conditions.

Figure 7.7 shows the resource size after 30 time-steps for the 100 (LNSmin, UT) conditions. The resource size at $t = 30$ is chosen for presentation because at that time the long-term effects of consumption are clearly visible. Each intersection of the 10×10 lines in the landscape of Figure 7.7 (including the borderlines) represents the average resource size of 10 runs under that particular (LNSmin, UT) condition.

Figure 7.7: Resource size at $t = 30$ for different values of LNSmin and UT and two differing consumats, $\sigma = 0.02$

It appears that consumats that are easy to satisfy (low levels of LNSmin), through their repetitive consumption, have almost depleted the resource at $t = 30$. The higher the consumats' LNSmin is, the higher the resource-size at $t = 30$. This is because the more frequent the consumats deliberate (which is associated with higher levels of LNSmin), the earlier they reduce their consumption to prevent future resource depletion. Consumats with a low LNSmin are easier to satisfy, and thus are most likely to engage in automatic processing. As a consequence, they do not anticipate future resource depletion. Only when the resource has been depleted to a considerable extent, their behaviour is not satisfactory any more, forcing them to engage in reasoned processing. However, because of the substantial depletion of the resource at that moment in time, the consumats cannot find a satisfying behavioural opportunity. Because of the depletion of the resource, their consumption will be very low.

Consequently, they remain dissatisfied, continuing to process in a reasoned manner (engaging in either deliberation or social comparison).

For consumats with a higher LNSmin (≥ 0.45), Figure 7.7 reveals an effect of uncertainty tolerance (UT). This effect implies that for consumats with a low UT the resource is being more strongly depleted than for consumats with a higher UT ($UT > 0.035$). Consequently, the consumption of the consumats with a low UT is relatively low at $t = 30$, yielding a relative low LNSs. The higher the UT of the consumats, the less they engage in social processing. Consumats with an $UT \geq 0.045$ rarely become uncertain for more than one time-step, because the uncertainty seldom exceeds their critical UT-level. Consequently, these consumats engage almost exclusively in individual processing. As a consequence, their consumption will depend exclusively on their LNSmin, as can be seen in Figure 7.7. It hardly matters for resource consumption if the consumat has an UT of somewhere between 0.045 and 0.095, as can be seen in Figure 7.7.

For consumats with a relatively low uncertainty tolerance ($UT \leq 0.045$) and which are not too quickly satisfied ($LNSmin \geq 0.35$), it can be observed that the lower UT, the more depleted the resource is at $t = 30$. This effect is particularly strong for relatively high levels of LNSmin (0.65 – 0.85) and an $UT \leq 0.015$. Under these conditions consumat 1 (high ability) often engages in imitation, thus copying the higher proportion of time spent working of consumat 2. This usually causes consumat 1 to work more than is required to satisfy its needs. This effect thus resembles the *imitation-effect* that was found in the deterministic experiment as depicted in Figure 7.4. Consumat 2, having a lower ability and thus more often being dissatisfied, is most likely to engage in social comparison. When consumat 1 engaged in imitation, this causes both consumats to engage in the same behaviour. In that case social comparison does not reveal alternative behavioural opportunities, and consumat 2 continues the high proportion spent working. Consequently, in this situation the consumats are not capable of finding a new behaviour, e.g., reducing their time spent working now so as to preserve the resource and guarantee future consumption. For as long as both consumats experience an uncertainty larger than their uncertainty tolerance ($U > UT$), they are trapped in this high proportion of working time. This effect, where intensive social processing may impair the adaptive capacity of the consumats to find new, not previously consumed opportunities, is being labelled as the *adaptation-effect*. This period of over-harvesting can only come to an end if one of the consumats starts deliberating for one time-step, and decreases its consumption to optimise future consumption. However, over-harvesting appears to be the behaviour that is most likely to be sustained because it satisfies the needs in the short-term, not taking the TH into account. Consequently, uncertainty stimulates the imitation and sustaining of an over-harvesting habit, resulting in the resource being depleted to a larger extent

Remarkably, for $UT = 0.005$ and $LNSmin = 0.95$, Figure 7.7 reveals a high level of the resource at $t = 30$. Under this condition the consumats do not engage in automatic processing, but will often socially compare and occasionally deliberate. The high level of the resource under this condition can be explained as follows. When (occasional) deliberation occurs in the first time-steps, the resource has not been depleted to a large extent. Consequently, the consumat will be able to find a behavioural opportunity (consumption

level) that prevents the resource from further depletion, thereby obtaining a relative good harvest in the long run. In later social comparisons the consumats thus only consider this relatively sustainable behavioural opportunity (consumption level).

Conclusions

The above experiment demonstrated that the resource size at $t = 30$ is strongly affected by the uncertainty tolerance (UT) and minimal level of need satisfaction (LNSmin) the consumats have. An over-harvesting habit may originate from imitating the behaviour of the other consumat, causing stronger resource depletion in the longer run (imitation-effect). Moreover, when consumats almost exclusively engage in social processing, they may be unable to adapt their behaviour to changing circumstances such as a strong depletion of the resource (adaptation-effect).

Increasing environmental uncertainty

The previous simulation experiment was replicated to further investigate the effects of uncertainty on resource management. Again, 10 values have been selected for LNSmin (ranging from 0.05 to 0.95) and UT (ranging from 0.005 to 0.095). For each of the 100 (LNSmin, UT) conditions 10 simulation runs have been performed, resulting in a total of 1000 runs. This time however, the stochastic function in the resource growth function is being doubled ($\sigma = 0.04$), whereby environmental uncertainty is larger. It is expected that this increased environmental uncertainty causes the resource to deplete more strongly in comparison to the previous experiment (Figure 7.7). Figure 7.8 shows what the resource size is after 30 time-steps for varying levels of UT and LNSmin.

The most remarkable difference with the previous stochastic-resource experiment is the smaller resource size at $t = 30$ for $LNSmin = 0.45 - 0.85$ (c.f. Figure 7.7). For example, for $LNSmin = 0.55$ and $UT = 0.055$ the resource size at $t = 30$ dropped from 1.51 (Figure 7.7) to 1.25 (Figure 7.8). The fact that the lower resource size is equally large for middle and high levels of UT makes clear that this cannot be a pure social-processing effect. This lower resource size for $LNSmin = 0.45 - 0.85$ can be explained as follows. Environmental uncertainty may lead to optimistic and pessimistic expectations regarding resource growth. Deliberating during a coincidental downward fluctuation in the resource growth ($N(0, \sigma) < 0$) causes the consumats to have ‘pessimistic’ expectations regarding resource growth. Consequently, a deliberating consumat will reduce its proportion of time working to prevent the depletion of the resource and to guarantee future outcomes. Because this behaviour is based upon a pessimistic expectation of the resource growth, the consumption may be denoted as under-harvesting. This under-harvesting causes the consumats to remain dissatisfied, thus sustaining them to reason (deliberation or social comparison) about consumptive behaviour.

The chances are large that a following time-step shows an upward fluctuation in the resource growth ($N(0, \sigma) > 0$). An upward fluctuation results in consumats having optimistic expectations regarding the resource growth. A deliberating consumat will then increase its proportion of time spent working. The resulting over-harvesting usually results in a higher satisfaction, which stimulates the consumats to engage in automatic processing. However, this automatic processing makes them insensitive for future negative fluctuations for as long as

they are satisfied. The higher the environmental uncertainty is, the more frequent consumats will be ‘captured’ in automatically over-harvesting on the basis of this *optimism-effect*. The optimism effect thus occurs only in situations where consumats can engage in both reasoned and automatic processing alternately. The optimism-effect does not occur for low and high levels of LNSmin. For low LNSmin it does not occur because the consumats do not get to engage in reasoned processing, and thus never have (optimistic) expectations regarding future outcomes. For LNSmin = 0.95, the effect does not occur because the consumats will not get engaged in automatic processing, and thus cannot be ‘captured’ in automatically over-harvesting.

Figure 7.8: Resource size at $t = 30$ for different values of LNSmin and UT and two differing consumats, $\sigma = 0,04$

Regarding the *imitation-effect*, this second stochastic-resource experiment shows a larger effect than in the previous experiment. Whereas in the previous experiment the imitation-effect occurred for LNSmin (0.65 – 0.85) and $UT \leq 0.015$, here the effect is stronger for LNSmin (0.65 – 0.85) and $UT \leq 0.025$, as can be seen from Figure 7.8. It appears that an increase in environmental uncertainty also increases the imitation effect.

For LNSmin = 0.95 we also see an effect for UT 0.005 – 0.075. However, this cannot be an imitation-effect because the consumats here engage purely in reasoned processing (either deliberation or social comparison). Close observation of these conditions showed that for consumats with a LNSmin of 0.95, the more frequently they engage in social comparison, the more slowly they adapt their behaviour. This is caused by the fact that only when one of the consumats engages in deliberation, a new and more sustainable behavioural opportunity

(consumption level) can be found and be available for comparison. Because the consumats with $LNS_{min} = 0.95$ and $UT = 0.005$ still engage in deliberation (about 20% of the time, when the stochastic part in the resource growth is relatively small causing that $U < UT$), they are still able to prevent the resource from collapsing. However, because they deliberate less frequently than in the previous stochastic-resource experiment, they do not succeed in keeping the resource at such a remarkably high level.

Conclusions

These two stochastic-resource experiments ($\sigma = 0.02$ and $\sigma = 0.04$) demonstrate that three differing effects cause the consumats to increase their harvesting under conditions of high environmental uncertainty. First there is the *optimism-effect*. This effect holds that deliberating consumats, when confronted with a positive fluctuation in the resource growth, are more likely to develop an over-harvesting habit. Second there is the *imitation-effect*. Just as in the previous deterministic (one-run) experiments, it can be observed here that while uncertain, consumat 1 (higher ability) is prone to imitate the more intensive working behaviour of the other consumat, even when this behaviour is less optimal than one's own previous behaviour. Third there is the *adaptation-effect*. The adaptation-effect holds that, because during social processing no new behavioural opportunities are introduced, the more frequent consumats engage in social processing, the less capable they are of adapting their behaviour to changing circumstances, such as a depletion of the resource.

Experimenting with the accessibility of the resource

In this section we will present some experiments in which the accessibility level (or depletion dynamics) of the resource is being varied. Accessibility here stands for the possibility to exploit the resource up to depletion (c.f. equation 6). The previous stochastic-resource experiments were performed with a resource that was reasonably accessible, because when the resource had halved, it became twice as difficult to harvest (accessibility factor $\pi = 1$). Under this condition the consumats never completely depleted the resource. The question is how the consumats react to resources that are more or less accessible for harvesting. It is expected that a more accessible resource (lower value for the accessibility factor π) will be more vulnerable to depletion. To answer this question, stochastic-resource experiments have been performed with a less and a more accessible resource.

A less accessible resource

The following experiment is a replication of the first stochastic-resource experiment that has been presented in Figure 7.7. Again 10 values have been selected for LNS_{min} (ranging from 0.05 to 0.95) and UT (ranging from 0.005 to 0.095). For each of the 100 (LNS_{min} , UT) conditions 10 simulation runs have been performed, resulting in a total of 1000 runs. The only difference with the first experiment is that the resource is made less accessible. Whereas the first experiment the accessibility factor π has been set at 1, in the current experiment π is set at 2, effectuating that if the resource is halved, it becomes four times as difficult to harvest,

making it very difficult to deplete the resource. In Figure 7.9 we graphically depict the results of this simulation experiment. Not surprisingly, it appears that this less accessible resource results in the resource remaining at a higher level.

Figure 7.9: Resource size at $t = 30$ for different values of LNSmin and UT and two differing consumats, depletion rate $\pi = 2$, $\sigma = 0,02$

The most striking difference with the previous experiments lies in the “valley” in Figure 7.9. Whereas the first stochastic-resource experiment showed a monotonous increase in the resource size at $t = 30$ the larger LNSmin (starting from LNSmin = 0.45, see Figure 7.7), in Figure 7.9 we observe the resource size at $t = 30$ decreasing when LNSmin increases from 0.55 to 0.75, except for UT = 0.005. This effect can be attributed to the *optimism-effect*, discussed in the previous section. For LNSmin ≤ 0.45 both consumats are easily satisfied and always engage in automatic processing. For LNSmin = 0.55, consumat 2 (low ability) is the first to become dissatisfied. Engaging in deliberation combined with a positive fluctuation in the resource growth causes consumat 2 to increase its consumption. Then being satisfied again, it will subsequently engage in automatic processing, thereby continuing this over-harvesting behaviour. For LNSmin = 0.65, the optimism-effect also applies to consumat 1, who will then first become dissatisfied and engage in deliberation, and increase its consumption following a positive fluctuation in the resource growth. As a consequence, consumat 1 may also develop an over-harvesting habit, causing that the resource size at $t = 30$ is even smaller. Moreover, for LNSmin of 0.65 the optimism-effect will occur earlier in time for consumat 2, also causing the resource to be smaller at $t = 30$. For LNSmin = 0.75 the resource size at $t = 30$ is slightly smaller still, because both consumats become dissatisfied earlier in time and the optimism-effect will thus occur earlier in time. For higher levels of

LNSmin the consumats are so quickly dissatisfied that they do not continue their over-consumptive behaviour for longer periods. Instead, they will engage very frequently in deliberation, thereby adapting their consumptive behaviour to changes in the resource size, while taking account of the time-horizon. Remarkably, the consumats that always engage in reasoned processing (LNSmin = 0.95) have depleted the resource somewhat more than the consumats with LNSmin ≤ 0.45. Because these latter consumats never deliberated on how much to work, they kept working for the same proportion of time whilst being satisfied. However, the consumats that engaged only in reasoned processing calculated that they could increase their consumption without depleting the resource. Apparently, the consumats with LNSmin ≤ 0.45 are under-harvesting.

Let us now consider the effects of uncertainty. For a low UT some irregularities in the valley can be observed. These can be attributed to the fact that under these conditions the consumats are engaging in social processing (imitation and social comparison) for a considerable time. However, occasionally there are periods of relative stability in the resource growth, resulting in individual processing because of decreased uncertainty. Scrutinising this experimental condition (low UT, LNSmin 0.65 – 0.85; see Figure 7.9) it was noticed that it mattered especially what behaviour consumat 1 performed just before entering such a period. If consumat 1 was working a lot (copied after consumat 2), a period of automatic individual behaviour results in habitual over-harvesting behaviour, thereby depleting the resource to a value of 2.5 at t = 30. When consumat 1 was working less before such a period, a less over-harvesting habit persists for some time, resulting in a resource size at t = 30 of 4,5 and sometimes even about 5. These conditions thus appear to be more susceptible to coincidence, which is causing the irregularities in the ‘valley’ as shown in Figure 7.9.

This simulation experiment has been replicated with a higher environmental uncertainty ($\sigma = 0.04$). Basically, the effects on the resource size were the same. Only the slope of the ‘valley’ starting at LNSmin = 0.45 was a bit steeper, and the bottom of the ‘valley’ was somewhat less regular for low values of UT, indicating that the effect of periods of relative stability as described before was even stronger.

A more accessible resource

In the next experiment, the resource has been made more accessible than previously. The first stochastic-resource experiment is replicated once again, only here the difficulty to harvest was made independent of the resource size (accessibility factor $\pi = 0$, c.f. equation 6). Consequently, it is always equally difficult to harvest, no matter how much depleted the resource is. This resembles the resource dynamics used in the first experiments described before. In Figure 7.10 we depict the results obtained with this very accessible resource.

What can be observed is that for a LNSmin of 0.05 to 0.85 consumption is such that the resource completely depleted. Only when the consumats engage exclusively in reasoned behaviour (i.e., LNSmin = 0.95), they manage to prevent the resource from complete depletion at t = 30, at which time the resource size is 3,5. The UT of the consumats appears to have no effect whatsoever under this condition. This is due to the fact that the accessibility of the resource is high, and therefore the stochastic fluctuation in the growth function has no effect on the direct harvesting of the consumats. Consequently, the consumats harvest what

they expected to harvest, and thus they will not experience any uncertainty, despite the fluctuations in the resource growth-function. Even the consumats with a low UT are processing individually for as long as the resource is not fully depleted.

Figure 7.10: Resource size at $t = 30$ for different values of LNS_{min} and UT and two differing consumats, depletion rate $\pi = 0$, $\sigma = 0.02$

This dramatic effect mirrors the resource-crash in the $n = 1$ experiment reported earlier, where repetition was introduced, and it can be explained as follows. The high accessibility of the resource causes at least consumat 1 to engage in repetition as processing style for as long as the resource is not completely depleted and $LNS_{min} < 0.95$. Processing automatically, consumat 1 does not take account of the gradual depletion of the resource. Only when the resource is fully depleted, consumat 1 starts deliberating, but then, however, there is nothing left to reason about.

For conditions where $LNS_{min} < 0.85$, consumat 2 engages in the same process as described above for consumat 1. Only when $LNS_{min} = 0.85$, consumat 2 starts reasoned processing, which leads to a strong decrease in consumption, aimed at optimising consumption in the long range. However, because consumat 1 continues to over-harvest, this results only in a small postponement of the moment when the resource is fully depleted.

Replicating this experiment with a larger environmental uncertainty ($\sigma = .04$) yielded about the same results. Only the resource size was a bit smaller (3.28) for consumats with an LNS_{min} of 0.95. Consequently, the simulations show that the more accessible the resource, the smaller the effect of uncertainty.

Conclusions

The experiments with the accessibility of the resource demonstrated that the less accessible the resource is for consumption, the larger the resource-size is at $t = 30$. Moreover, it was found that consumats that are relatively easy to satisfy are more likely to develop an under-harvesting habit in case of a less accessible resource. In case of a very accessible resource, the consumats will not experience uncertainty because they always harvest what they expected to harvest. As a consequence, they develop an over-harvesting habit leading to the complete depletion of the resource. Only consumats that engage exclusively in deliberation are capable of preventing this depletion in optimising long-term consumption.

General conclusions

In the previous sections the consumat approach has been formalised for a simple commons or resource dilemma, and a series of experiments has been performed to study how the behavioural rules as formalised in the beginning of this chapter operate in this setting. The simulation experiments revealed several dynamical processes such as the imitation-effect, the adaptation-effect and the optimism-effect that affect resource consumption. This concluding section provides general remarks on the consumat approach, while linking the simulation results to results of empirical research.

The behavioural rules

The behavioural simulation rules that have thus far been used are very simple, and the simulated behaviours of the consumats do not represent real human behaviour. Yet, the behavioural rules capture some basic behavioural processes, and as such they allow experimentation with various behavioural dynamics. It was no surprise that ‘deliberation’ appeared to be the cognitive process that usually resulted in the best outcomes (LNS and resource size) in the long run. The introduction of ‘repetition’ as a cognitive strategy revealed that the more accessible the resource is, the more likely it is that consumats engage in habitual repetitive behaviour, thereby quickly depleting the resource to a serious extent. The introduction of social processing (social comparison and imitation) yielded some remarkable effects. In the first place, social processing appeared to promote the spreading of over-harvesting behaviour. Second, it appeared that a higher proportion of social processing was associated with a slower behavioural adaptation to a depleting resource, because no new behavioural opportunities are being adopted during social processing. Third, it appeared that more social processing led towards less stable outcomes, making the process of resource management more vulnerable to irregularities in the resource growth.

The effects that several variables had on the management of a common resource and on the behavioural processing style of the consumats, are discussed in the following sections.

Time-horizon as a cognitive ability

The first experiments, in which a single deliberating consumat was confronted with a resource, illustrated that the time-horizon the consumat is able to employ, largely determines the degree to which the resource is being depleted. The longer the time-horizon, the earlier

the consumat anticipates possible resource depletion. The less frequently consumats engage in deliberation, the more important the time-horizon gets. If consumats are deliberating very frequently, a short time-horizon will suffice to prevent the resource from depleting. Flexibility is guaranteed because each time the consumats are deliberating they are capable of engaging in new behaviour, which may stabilise during repetition. However, if the consumats rarely engage in deliberation and repeat themselves very frequently, this flexibility is lost. In such situations the time-horizon the consumat employs becomes very important, because it matters if the consumat occasionally looks forward for 20 time-steps or just 5. Here, employing a short time-horizon while deliberating may lead to the adoption of a new behaviour that results in depletion occurring only beyond the time-horizon, whereas the consumat with a long time-horizon has a better chance of finding a more sustainable consumption level. Consequently, the less frequently the consumat engages in deliberation, the more important the time-horizon of the consumat becomes.

Minimal level of need satisfaction

The minimal level of need satisfaction (LNS_{min}) appears to be an important behaviour-determining factor. If the actual level of need satisfaction drops below the critical LNS_{min}, the consumats start reasoned processing. A consumat with a high value of LNS_{min} is hard to satisfy and thus will frequently engage in reasoned processing. In the section on different types of resources (the stochastic-resource experiments, see Figures 7.11, 7.12 and 7.14) it was demonstrated that reasoned processing (taking account of a long time-horizon) results in a more sustainable use in case of a relatively accessible resource. This causes the somewhat contradictory effect that those consumats that are the most easily to satisfy (low LNS_{min}) are also the ones that are most likely to deplete a resource. For a less accessible resource (Figure 7.9) the effect turns around, showing that consumats with a higher LNS_{min} (less easy satisfied, more reasoned processing) are less likely to under-harvest. It is concluded that a higher LNS_{min} results in more frequent occurrence of reasoned behaviour, thereby decreasing the likelihood of over-harvesting and of under-harvesting if TH is sufficiently large.

Uncertainty

In the stochastic-resource simulations a stochast ($N(0,\sigma)$) was introduced in the resource growth function, which represented environmental uncertainty (c.f. equation 5). This environmental uncertainty causes the actual outcomes the consumat gets to often differ from what they are expected to be. A difference between expected and actual outcomes causes the consumats to experience uncertainty (U). The uncertainty tolerance (UT) of the consumat expresses for what value of U the consumats will engage in social processing (either imitation or social comparison). Uncertainty appears to be an important factor in the simulation experiments, because it stimulates social processing, which in its turn may lead towards an increased consumption from the resource under certain conditions.

In the literature on resource dilemmas a distinction is made between environmental uncertainty and social uncertainty (Messick, Allison and Samuelson, 1988). Social uncertainty is associated with the absence of knowledge on the intended behaviour of others. Strictly spoken, our consumats (so far) do not experience social uncertainty because they expect the other consumat(s) to perform the same behaviour as in the previous time-step. This is not to

say that these expectations always come true. Because the consumats do not experience social uncertainty, it can be stated that all uncertainty in our simulations is environmental uncertainty. In the literature on social dilemmas, environmental uncertainty is formalised as the lack of precise information regarding the resource-size (Wit and Wilke, 1998; Hine and Gifford, 1996; Rapoport, Budescu, Suleiman and Weg, 1992; Messick *et al.*, 1988). This formalisation of environmental uncertainty differs from the formalisation of environmental uncertainty in the consumat, which bears a more process-oriented character. For the consumat, uncertainty U depends on the difference between the actual and expected resource size development. If this difference exceeds the critical level of the uncertainty tolerance (UT), the consumat will engage in social processing. Unlike the experiments reported in the literature (see above), here a (reasoned processing) consumat knows the exact resource-size and has a precise expectation regarding the resource-size. The resource size may have developed in an unexpected manner only because of the consumptive behaviour of the other(s) and because of a stochastic part in the resource growth-function. Consequently, uncertainty in the consumat experiments does not bear a pure environmental or social character, but rather reflects the state of the consumat. This resembles real-life situations, where the resource dynamics and behaviour of other people also interact and cannot be separated into pure types of uncertainties. Moreover, uncertainty is in the end a psychological construct that reflects the impossibility to predict outcomes accurately.

People may display different sensitivities to uncertainty. This may be a stable personality factor, because uncertainty orientation is related to the Openness to Experience factor of the Big Five personality structure (Hodson and Sorrentino, 1999). This suggests that people differ regarding their uncertainty tolerance, which determines their tendency to engage in social processing when confronted with uncertainty. This indicates that not the fluctuations of the resource, but rather the person's sensitivity to these fluctuations triggers feelings of uncertainty. Consequently, uncertainty tolerance can be hypothesised to be a mediating factor for the cognitive process people engage in.

The simulation experiments reveal three different effects of uncertainty, respectively the optimism-effect, the imitation-effect and the adaptation-effect. To recapitulate, *the optimism-effect* holds that deliberating consumats, when confronted with a positive fluctuation in the resource growth, are more likely to adopt an over-harvesting habit through repetition of satisfying behaviour. The *imitation-effect* implies that consumats, when uncertain and satisfied, are likely to imitate the behaviour of the other consumat(s), even when this behaviour yields less optimal outcomes in terms of need satisfaction than one's own previous behaviour. The *adaptation-effect* holds that no new behavioural opportunities are being adopted during social processing, and as a consequence the consumats are not capable of adapting their behaviour to changing circumstances, such as a serious depletion of the resource. These three effects are all *process-effects*, that is, they describe the process that leads towards a given outcome pattern. To validate these effects empirically, it is necessary to observe the extent to which these effects also occur when real people are confronted with a representative resource management task.

Many experiments have been performed regarding the management of resources. Relatively few of these have explored the effects of (environmental and social) uncertainty on people's harvesting behaviour (e.g., Wit and Wilke, 1998). The behavioural processes the

subjects engaged in have not been studied in these experiments. Consequently, it is impossible to validate the process-effects as found in our simulation experiments on the basis of existing psychological experiments. To validate the process-effects obtained, it is necessary to have data on the behavioural *processes* people engage in during resource management tasks.

Despite the fact that the formalisation of uncertainty in the consumat differs from the formalisation in experimental research with real people, the effects of uncertainty observed in the simulation experiments are pointing in the same direction as experimental research with human subjects. Several researchers reported that an increase in uncertainty causes people to harvest more from a collective resource. The more uncertain people are regarding the resource size and growth, and thus the optimal collective harvest (OCH) of a collective resource, the more they tend to harvest from that resource (Rutte, Wilke and Messick, 1987; Messick *et al.*, 1988; Suleiman and Rapoport, 1989; Budescu, Rapoport and Suleiman, 1990, 1992, 1995; Rapoport *et al.*, 1992; De Vries and Wilke, 1992, 1995, Suleiman, Budescu and Rapoport, 1994; Budescu, Suleiman and Rapoport, 1995; Hine and Gifford, 1996; Wit and Wilke, 1998).

Three explanations for this effect are discussed. First, it has been said that uncertainty leads towards an overestimation of the resource size. This 'environmental optimism' prompts individuals to harvest more (Rapoport *et al.*, 1992; Budescu *et al.*, 1990). Rapoport *et al.* (1992) attribute this effect to the tendency of people to overweight the positive endpoint in a probability distribution. This would give rise to an optimistic estimate of the resource-size. Because the estimation of the resource took place before harvesting took place, this optimism effect is fundamentally different from the optimism-effect that has been found in the consumat experiments, which is a *process*-effect.

A second explanation of the increased consumption under conditions of environmental uncertainty states that the overestimation of the resource-size is no 'environmental optimism effect' but a post-experimental cognitive defence strategy to justify one's over-harvesting behaviour. Obviously this effect could not occur in the simulation experiments.

A third explanation is that people are assumed to be more risk-seeking under conditions of uncertainty (Biel & Gaerling, 1995; Biel, Gaerling and Gustafsson, 1998).

The optimism-effect and the imitation-effect provide alternative explanations for these experimental results obtained with human subjects. It may be assumed that in those experiments the participants were, on the average, not that motivated to engage in reasoned processing at every time-step, but not that unmotivated either to engage only in automatic processing. Switching between reasoned and automatic processing may cause the optimism-effect to occur. Thus, it might well be that pre-experimental optimism (see above) actually has nothing to do with over-harvesting behaviour. Moreover, it may be expected that in experiments where participants had the possibility to communicate with each other, they will engage in social processing more often. As a consequence, it may be expected that the imitation-effect occurs, thereby further contributing to resource depletion.

Both the imitation- and the optimism-effect stimulate over-harvesting, which may result in a higher satisfaction in the short run, but in a more depleted resource in the long run. However, only when the resource management task comprises a sufficient number of time-steps, these effects may manifest themselves to their full extent. Thus in experiments that

consider only 10 time-steps - a number frequently reported in experimental studies on resource management - too short a period of time is considered for the imitation- and the optimism-effect to manifest themselves fully.

A next question is whether the optimism, imitation and adaptation effects appear to occur in real world settings, which would signify their ecological validity. The *optimism-effect* can be used to describe the process that occurs in the management of fisheries. A fish-stock can be considered as a complex resource that has a random component in its grow function. Following a series of good catches, fishermen are likely to have an optimistic expectation regarding the fish-stock. Consequently, they will harvest a lot, thereby being satisfied, not reasoning and thus tending to ignore (scientific) information that suggests that the resource may be depleting. However, after a series of bad catches, they may be convinced of the necessity to reduce their harvesting. Because they will be dissatisfied, they start reasoning, the first news that the fish-stock is increasing will be elaborated, and they then will be very eager to increase their harvesting again, getting back to (more intense) repetitive behaviour.

The *imitation-effect* can be exemplified with hoarding. When people are satisfied, but confronted with uncertainty (rumours) regarding the future availability of a certain good (e.g., food), they tend towards imitating the behaviour of others. When some people start hoarding (creating a private stock) because they fear a future scarcity, other people may imitate their behaviour. The social spreading of such behaviour may lead towards large-scale hoarding. In the short run this may sustain satisfaction in the hoarding people, but in the long run it may cause serious scarcity problems.

The *adaptation-effect* applies to situations where people are mainly engaging in social processing. The buying of a car appears to be a situation that incites much social processing, because for many people it is an import constituent of their (social) image. Uncertainty regarding how other people perceive the image characteristics of the various car models may explain 'cars' being a favourite conversation topic. Because people are perceiving what model of car other people drive, and discuss this with friends and family, really new behavioural options, such as new small cars or new public transportation services, are less likely to be discussed. This may be an important factor determining the speed at which a new (transport) product penetrates the market. It makes it obvious that it is a (intuitively) smart strategy of car-manufacturers to make surprising advertisements so as to incite discussion (i.e. social processing), and thereby suppressing individual deliberation.

Accessibility of the resource

The effects of accessibility of the resource were quite straightforward: the more accessible the resource for harvesting, the quicker it is depleted. A very accessible resource causes consumats to be certain and satisfied, because they actually harvest what they expected and wanted to harvest. Consequently, they repeat their previous behaviour without elaborating on the future depletion of the resource. The consumats thus persist their over-harvesting habit, until the resource is completely depleted. Consequently, it is found that a more accessible resource tends to provoke repetitive behaviour to be performed habitually, until the resource is empty. A resource that is less accessible for harvesting will not be depleted. Here, consumats that are easy to satisfy may develop an under-harvesting habit. Empirical research is necessary to prove the existence and the size of such effects.

Further research

In this chapter the consumat approach has been applied to the well-known field of harvesting behaviour in commons or resource dilemmas. However, the generic character of the consumat approach implies that many other behavioural phenomena can also be studied using simulation experiments. A next issue for demonstrating the consumat approach is the ‘lock-in’ phenomena (e.g., Arthur, 1989), which indicates the process by which one product conquers the market by and large, whilst other equally good products are purchased much less. In Chapter 8 the behavioural dynamics behind the lock-in effect will be investigated using the consumat approach explicated so far.

8

The lock in of consumption patterns¹²

In this Chapter we will apply the consumat approach to study the behavioural dynamics behind the process of consumption patterns that ‘lock-in’. When specific goods or technologies come to dominate a consumer market in such a way that a reversal is virtually impossible, the situation is often called a ‘lock-in’. For example, this text is being written in Word on a Microsoft Windows platform using a QWERTY keyboard. Although we have no specific preferences for these products, their popularity would be difficult to change. The university supports a limited number of software applications, and learning to type efficiently on a non-QWERTY keyboard would take (too) long, although ergonomically it would be more efficient.

The ‘locked-in’ QWERTY keyboard (David, 1985), Microsoft software and VHS recording machines all have or had their alternatives, which were at least as good or sometimes even better. Which product finally locked-in depended on rather unpredictable historical events and behavioural processes (Arthur, 1989). A better understanding of the conditions that stimulate processes of lock-in may help to develop policy measures to stimulate preferable lock-ins (for example, products which are efficient as regards energy and materials use), or to limit or prevent undesirable lock-ins.

Previous studies of lock-in effects

Previously, studies of the process of lock-in have been focussed on price dynamics and increasing returns (e.g., Arthur, 1989). This implies that the more a product is being used, the lower will be the costs per unit of production, which in its turn accelerates the market penetration of the product. This insight, for example, stimulates software companies to give away free software in order to stimulate a lock-in that would position their software as the standard. An interesting example is the battle between Netscape and Microsoft on the web-browsers Netscape Communicator and Microsoft Internet Explorer. The lock-in of one of the two browsers will be of high financial importance for the two companies.

There are various studies on modelling the lock-in of technologies. Arthur (1989) provides a general framework about competing technologies to define under what circumstances an adoption market may end up being dominated by a single technology. An essential attribute for a lock-in to occur is that the products have increasing returns. This implies that the more agents adopt a certain technology, the higher the returns for others to adopt the same technology. Arthur describes lock-in dynamics by means of agents that are making a choice in every time-step on the basis of probabilistic models. The probabilities are related to the previous behaviour of the other agents. The more agents have adopted a certain technology, the higher the probability that an agent will do so too in the next period. The decisions of particular agents are therefore related to the decisions of other agents. Random

¹² This chapter is based on Janssen and Jager, 1999.

events in the early stage of the product choice process, leading to a minor dominance of one product, may determine whether all agents will adopt the one or the other product.

Various scholars have developed sequential decision models in which each agent uses information on the previous decisions made by other agents, in order to make a decision for oneself (Granovetter and Soong, 1986; Banerjee, 1992; Bikchandani, Hirshleifer and Welch, 1992; Kirman, 1993). An illustrating example is the choice of a restaurant (Banerjee, 1992). In choosing between two restaurants that are both more or less unknown, people who arrive in sequence are influenced in their decision-making by the choices made by those arriving before them. The more people have chosen restaurant A, the higher the chance that the next person will also choose restaurant. In addition to the well-known 'bandwagon effect' (Leibenstein, 1976), Granovetter and Soong (1986) distinguish a 'reverse bandwagon effect'. This is the effect that some consumers choose the quiet restaurant if it is 'too busy' in restaurant A.. Granovetter and Soong (1986) show that such counteractive forces may lead to chaotic patterns of consumer behaviour.

The stochastic models that the above mentioned authors use may successfully mimic lock-in behaviour, but they do not provide insights into the behavioural processes that determine specific consumer decisions. For example, social processes may play an important role in the lock-in of, e.g., the personal car being the dominant mode for person transportation, fashion habits amongst different subgroups (businessmen, 'skaters', religious orthodox groups) and the brand of cola that is being preferred by groups of people. These examples of lock-ins cannot be explained as an increasing-returns-to-scale effect. Therefore, the aim of this chapter is to apply the consumat approach in order to get a better understanding of the behavioural processes that underlie the process of lock-in. First, the current modelling type of lock-in dynamics is illustrated. In a subsequent section the consumat approach will be formalised for a specific case to study lock-in of consumption patterns. The next sections describe a number of experiments that have been performed with the consumat approach. The chapter will end with conclusions regarding the circumstances in which processes of lock-in may occur.

Simple models on lock-in dynamics

A very simple model, which simulates lock-in, is the following. Consider a market of two products ($x = 0$ or 1) and N agents i . The agents' probability of choosing product 0 or 1 depends on the proportion of agents that chose the particular product during the previous time period. The more agents chose a particular product, the higher the chance that others follow in the next time step, which gradually results in a lock-in.

The probability that an agent consumes product 1 ($x(t) = 1$) depends on how much other agents i consumed product 1 in the previous time-step $x_i(t-1)$. A probability value PV , ranging from 0 to 1, is being calculated by dividing $x_i(t-1)$ through the number of agents (N). The more agents consumed product 1 in the previous time-step, the higher the value of PV . Now, for each actor a random value between 0 and 1 is being selected out of an uniformly distributed variable $UV[0,1]$. If $UV < PV$, then the actor will consume product 1. If $UV > PV$, then the actor will consume product 0.

This simple rule implies that the closer UV gets to either 0 or 1, the larger the chance is that a lock-in occurs. If $PV = 0$ or 1, all actors consume the same, implying a total lock-in. In Figure 8.1 three illustrative pathways of market shares are being depicted. All three pathways start with an about equal market share at the beginning ($t = 0$). The dark pathway, although closely reaching a lock-in of product 1 (share of product 1 almost 1), does not end up being locked-in. The dotted pathway shows a lock-in of product 1 at $t \approx 64$. The thin black pathway shows a situation where both products keep considerable market shares.

Figure 8.1: Share of product 1 for 3 possible runs of the very simple model.

The simplest model is complex enough to simulate lock-in patterns but it does not provide insights regarding how and when lock-in occurs.

A somewhat more advanced approach is to consider price-based consumption choices and ‘learning-by-doing’ dynamics in the production process. We start with two products ($i = 0,1$). We assume that the demand equals the supply of both products. Therefore, the supply of product i (S_i) equals the share for product i (Sh_i) of the total demand D (equation 1).

$$(1) \quad S_i = Sh_i * D$$

In the simulation model the demand follows a fixed exogenous scenario, and the share for product i is being simulated.

Usually it takes some time before an improvement penetrates the market. For example, a refrigerator has an average lifetime of 15 years, and hence it takes a long time before an innovation has fully penetrated the market. This is being formalised by introducing a time-delay that determines the speed with which the developments in the actual market share for product i over time (dSh_i/dt) follow the indicated shares ($IndSh_i$). This time-delay depends on the adjustment time (t_a). This adjustment time indicates the speed with which price changes affect the actual market shares.

$$(2) \quad dSh_i/dt = (IndSh_i - Sh_i) / t_a$$

The indicated share of product i ($IndSh_i$) depends on the relative prices of both products. The higher the price of one product relative to another product is, the lower its share gets. This is being formalised by a multinomial logit function of the prices of the products, in which the relative prices (P_i) are weighted (equation 3). Here, the variable η is being used to formalise the sensitivity for price-differences. If $\eta = 0$, then the indicated share is insensitive for price-differences. This implies that each distribution of prices will yield a market-share of 50% for both products. The higher η gets, the more sensitive $IndSh_i$ gets for price-differences.

$$(3) \quad IndSh_i = \frac{EXP(-\eta * P_i)}{(EXP(-\eta * P_1) + EXP(-\eta * P_2))}$$

The price of a product P_i is a function of the fixed costs (FC_i) and the variable costs (VC_i) per product unit. The fixed costs are not depending on the market-share. The variable costs increase along with the share of the product. The costs of the product are being multiplied by the learning factor LF_i . This learning factor implies that producers improve their production process over time, and hence reduce the product costs. The resulting costs of product i are being divided by the share of product i (S_i) to calculate the price per product unit.

$$(4) \quad P_i = LF_i * (FC_i + S_i * VC_i) / S_i$$

The learning factor for product i (LF_i) decreases by cumulative production of product i (CL_i) according to the principle of learning-by-doing (Arrow, 1962). This principle holds that the more of product i has been produced, the lower the cost price per unit of i gets. The more products i have been made, the less additional improvements in the production process of i will occur. Hence, the more products have been produced (cumulative production), the smaller the price reduction following additional production. CL_{i-in} indicates how much cumulative production has been reached at the start of the simulation. The higher CL_{i-in} , the lower the speed with which LF_i will decrease. The parameter γ determines the rate at which the product costs decline for a doubling of the cumulative production.

$$(5) \quad LF_i = (CL_i / CL_{i-in})^{-\log_{10}(\gamma) / \log_{10}(2)}$$

The cumulative production increases per unit with the market-share times the demand. In our simulation the total demand is fixed at a value of 1, but markets with increasing or decreasing demands can easily be imagined.

$$(6) \quad dCL_i / dt = S_i * D$$

If two products initially have an equal share and equal economic characteristics (that is, the same values on γ , FC and VC), their market share remains equal in the long run. Figure 8.2a shows the market developments for two equal products.

In the next run, we introduced a stochastic term in equation 1, thereby simulating unexpected events in the supply of products. This stochastic term, $N(0, \sigma)$, is a normal distribution with zero mean and standard deviation σ (equation 1').

$$(1'a) \quad S_1 = \text{MIN}(S_{h1} * D + N(0, \sigma), D)$$

Moreover, we assume that the supply of specific products does not exceed the total demand.

$$(1'b) \quad S_2 = D - S_1$$

If the agents sensitivity for price-differences (η , see equation 3) is large enough, we observe lock-in effects. Figure 8.2b shows the results of such run in which product 0 becomes to dominate the market.

Figure 8.2a: Possible development of a market share given two identical products ($t_a = 2$, $\gamma = 0.9$, $\sigma = 0.5$, $FC = 10$ and $VC = 10$), with agents having a low sensitivity for price differences ($\eta = 0.5$).

Figure 8.2b: Possible development of a market share given two identical products ($t_a = 2$, $\gamma = 0.9$, $\sigma = 0.5$, $FC = 10$ and $VC = 10$), with agents having a high sensitivity for price differences ($\eta = 0.65$).

This somewhat more advanced model demonstrates that lock-in occurs more frequently when η is higher and thus the agents are more sensitive to price changes. However, the model remains unsatisfactory because it gives us very limited insights into consumer decision-making. In the rest of the paper we will therefore replace equations (1-3) by various equations from the consumat approach.

Applying the consumat approach

The conceptual model of behaviour as described in Chapter 5 and formalised in Chapter 6 is the starting point for a simulation to study the lock-in of consumption patterns. A cellular automata approach has been chosen because this allows a modelling of the spatial dynamics of local interactions between agents. For a more extensive description of the cellular-automata, see Chapter 3 on cellular automata.

The consumption of the agents is described on the basis of a simple cellular automaton A defined by a lattice L (the environment), a state space X describing the possible behaviours the agents can perform, a neighbourhood template δ describing the spatial reach of local interactions and a local transition function f that describes when an agent changes its behaviour. In formula: $A = \langle L, X, \delta, f \rangle$.

A lattice L of 30x30 grid cells is used, yielding a total of 900 cells. The corresponding edges of the grid have been 'pasted together', resulting in a three-dimensional solid called a torus (see Chapter 3). Each cell represents a single agent. These agents have two behavioural opportunities X , namely to consume product 0 ($x = 0$) or product 1 ($x = 1$). A Moore neighbourhood template δ is being used to define which neighbours are taken into consideration. This template consists of the eight adjacent cells of the agent. The transition function f implies that the agents can change their opportunity consumption in discrete time steps, and all 900 agents do (or do not) change their opportunity consumption simultaneously. This local transition function f is actually the consumat model. A change in consumption implies that the cells change state. The consumat model is being used to determine such transitions. In the following we will discuss the formalisation of the consumat approach for this issue.

Shortly, in this application, four types of needs have been formalised: identity, personal taste (associated with freedom of choice), leisure and subsistence. These consumat-needs have been formalised in order to include these various aspects in the consumats behavioural processes.

Identity

The level of satisfaction for the need identity (LNS_i) depends on the number of neighbours (in the template δ) that consume the same product, that is, the satisfaction of the sense of belonging to a group. We assume that LNS_i increases linearly with the proportion of neighbours consuming the same product. The more neighbours (N) consume the same product, the higher the LNS for identity of the consumat on position ij of the torus:

$$(7) \quad \text{LNS}_{ij} = 1 - \sum x_{ij} N_{ij} / 8 \text{ if } x_{ij} = 0 \text{ else } \text{LNS}_{ij} = \sum x_{ij} N_{ij} / 8$$

Starting with a random product distribution implies that both products have on the average an equal need satisfying capacity for identity.

Personal taste

Personal taste (associated with freedom of choice) is assumed to be an individual characteristic of an agent. The agents thus may have a different taste for products 0 and 1. This is formalised with a taste value β for both products, which may be different for the consumats ij (β_{0ij} and β_{1ij}). The level of need-satisfaction for personal taste (LNS_t) is therefore equal to the individual ‘taste’ for the consumed product x_{ij} . For simplicity’s sake we assume that the agents know the taste of the products.

$$(8) \quad \text{LNS}_{t,ij} = \beta_{0ij} \text{ if } x_{ij} = 0 \text{ else } \text{LNS}_{t,ij} = \beta_{1ij}$$

Personal taste for the products may be distributed randomly over the consumats. This implies that on the average both products have the same need-satisfying capacity for personal taste.

Leisure

Leisure is related to the price of the products, assuming that the lower the price of a product the less time one has to spent on working to earn the money to buy the product. This of course is a crude assumption, but it gives the possibility of balancing leisure time and working time. Essential in the calculation of the level of need-satisfaction for leisure is the budget the consumat has available (B_{ij}). For as long as the price (P) of the product is lower than the available budget, $\text{LNS}_{l,ij}$ will be larger than 1 (equation 9). This implies that $\text{LNS}_{l,ij}$ is considered to be 1 (maximum value). When the price is larger than the available budget, the consumat is forced to go working, which goes at the cost of $\text{LNS}_{l,ij}$. Fore example, when the product price is twice as much as the available budget, the $\text{LNS}_{l,ij}$ will have a value of .5.

$$(9) \quad \text{LNS}_{l,ij} = B_{ij} / P_0 \text{ if } x = 0 \text{ else } \text{LNS}_{l,ij} = B_{ij} / P_1$$

When both products initially have the same price, both products have an identical need-satisfying capacity for leisure. However, it is also possible to start with different product prices. Moreover, it is possible to equip the consumats with different budgets (financial ability).

Subsistence

The need for subsistence is assumed to be related to the degree of pollution. Upon consumption, each product i is assumed to contribute λ_i units of pollution. A given concentration of pollution at time t (C_t) decays every time step t with ratio μ . The total consumption of respectively product 0 and product 1 is being used to calculate the increase in pollution concentration.

$$(10) \quad C_t = C_{t-1} * (1 - \mu) + \lambda_0 * X_0 + \lambda_1 * X_1$$

Individual sensitivity to pollution (α_{ij}) and the concentration of pollution (C) determine the individual level of need-satisfaction for subsistence. A smaller α_{ij} indicates a smaller tolerance for pollution, thus a larger sensitivity (Equation 11).

$$(11) \quad LNS_{s_{ij}} = 1 - \exp(-\alpha_{ij}/C)$$

Both products may be equally polluting, however, it is also possible to make one product more polluting than the other. Moreover, it is possible to equip the consumats with different sensitivities for pollution.

The total level of need satisfaction of agent (i,j) is a Cobb Douglas type of utility function in which each level of need-satisfaction is weighted by γ_{needij} .

$$(12) \quad LNS = LNS_i^{\gamma_{Tij}} * LNS_t^{\gamma_{Tij}} * LNS_l^{\gamma_{Lij}} * LNS_s^{1 - \gamma_{Tij} - \gamma_{Lij} - \gamma_{Lij}}$$

The way in which the different needs are formalised implies the manifestation of four different feedbacks: (1) the need for identity is related to the behaviour of the consumats in the local (neighbourhood), (2) the need for personal taste is related to individual preferences, (3) the need for leisure relates individual (financial) abilities to macro-level factors (product prices), and (4) the subsistence need leads to a product-related feedback, because pollution is caused by the consumption of specific products.

As described in the conceptual model, it depends on the level of need satisfaction (LNS) and uncertainty (U) the consumat experiences which of the four cognitive processing types will be employed. Whereas the level of need satisfaction is clearly related to the four needs discussed above, it is not obvious how one could define a quantitative measure for the agents' uncertainty. We assume that the summarised difference between the expected LNS and the actual LNS of each need k can be used to measure uncertainty (U_{ij}). For simplicity's sake, we have assumed that the expected LNS is equal to the experienced LNS in the previous period. Thus, uncertainty is formalised as the absolute difference between the previous and current level of need-satisfaction summarised over all four needs:

$$(13) \quad U_{ij, t} = \sum_k^4 \text{ABS}(LNS_{kij, t} - LNS_{kij, t-1})$$

The consumat is likely to engage in social processing when this level U_{ij} exceeds its uncertainty tolerance ($U_{ij} > UT$). In the following sections the four cognitive processing rules that operate under different conditions of uncertainty and needs satisfaction are formalised for consumats' decision which product to use (see also Chapter 6, table 5.4).

Repetition

If the consumat is satisfied ($LNS_{ij, t} > LNS_{min}$) and certain ($U_{ij, t} < UT$), it will consume the same product as in the previous period.

$$(14) \quad x_{ij,t} = x_{ij,t-1}$$

Deliberation

Consumats engage in deliberation if they feel certain ($U_{ij,t} < UT$) and if the level of need satisfaction does not reach a predefined minimum level of need satisfaction ($LNS_{ij,t} < LNS_{min}$). The consumat will check which of the consumption opportunities yields the best outcomes in terms of LNS, where LNS and its components can be defined as in equations 7 - 12.

$$(15) \quad x_{ij,t} = \text{Max} (LNS(x_{ij} = 0), LNS(x_{ij} = 1))$$

Imitation

Consumats engage in imitation when their uncertainty level exceeds their uncertainty tolerance ($U_{ij,t} > UT$) and when their needs are satisfied above a minimum level ($LNS_{ij,t} > LNS_{min}$). While imitating, the consumat adopts the behaviour that the majority of its neighbourhood performed in the previous time-step. If more than 4 consumats out of the 8 neighbours consumed product x_0 at $t - 1$, the consumat will also consume product x_0 .

$$(16) \quad x_{ij,t} = 0 \text{ if } \#(x_{N_{ij,t-1}}=0) > \#(x_{N_{ij,t-1}}=1) \text{ else } x_{ij,t} = 1.$$

Social comparison

When the level of need satisfaction drops below a threshold value ($LNS_{ij,t} < LNS_{min}$) and the consumat is feeling uncertain ($U_{ij,t} > UT$), then it will engage in social comparison. This implies that the consumat first starts reasoning on which other neighbouring consumats are comparable. This is being done by first observing the abilities of the eight neighbours. Abilities are assumed to be related to the individual (financial) budgets B_{ij} (see equation 9). The socially comparing consumat thus first observes the budgets the neighbours had in the previous time-step. The comparison factor ϵ is being used to determine how much the budget of another consumat must be similar to the own budget to be considered as comparable. The larger the comparison factor ϵ , the more consumats are considered to be comparable. Consumats will consume that product which has been consumed the most by comparable neighbours.

$$(17) \quad x_{ij,t} = 0 \text{ if } \#[(x_{N_{ij,t-1}} = 0) \text{ and } (B_{ij,t} * (1-\epsilon) \leq B_{neighbours,t-1} \leq B_{ij,t} * (1+\epsilon))] > \#[(x_{N_{ij,t-1}} = 1) \text{ and } (B_{ij,t} * (1-\epsilon) \leq B_{neighbours,t-1} \leq B_{ij,t} * (1+\epsilon))] \text{ else } x_{ij,t} = 1.$$

Because each consumat has a fixed position in the lattice, and has a limited number of eight neighbours for social processing, the latter has been formalised in a simpler manner than was

suggested in Chapter 6. This has been done to allow for social processes even if the (fixed) neighbours have different financial abilities.

Experimenting with two similar products

We start with two products x_i ($i = 0, 1$), with similar characteristics in regarding dynamics and pollution (see section above). The 900 consumats in the 30×30 lattice differ regarding their financial budgets (related to their leisure need), their individual preferences (referring to their personal taste) and their sensitivity for pollution (related to their subsistence need). In the initial situation, the distribution of consumption of products 0 and 1 is randomised. First a typical model run will be discussed in detail, after which the general characteristics of the lock-in dynamics being simulated with the consumat approach will be explored. In Figure 8.3 we depict a simulation in which a local lock-in can be observed, that is, groups of consumats emerge that consume the same product.

Figure 8.3: Spatial pattern of consumats consuming product 0 (white) and 1 (black), for 3 differing points in time ($t=0$, $t=10$ and $t=100$), within a $30 * 30$ lattice of cells.

The three panels of Figure 8.3 show a typical evolution of consumption patterns. Initially, the distribution of product consumption is random, but after 10 time steps the consumption begins to show a certain spatial distribution, which, after some changes leads to a stable spatial pattern ($t=100$). In the beginning of the simulation there is a high level of uncertainty that stimulates social processing (Figure 8.4). This uncertainty disappears due to the lock-in of consumption, that is, the more consumats consume the same as during the previous period, the smaller the difference between expected LNS and actual LNS. At the end of the simulation period the consumats engage mainly in repetition and deliberation, depending on their level of need satisfaction. The share of automated behaviour increases due to a higher satisfaction of in particular the leisure need. This follows from the decreasing prices of the products, whereby consumption becomes more easy given the available budget.

Figure 8.4: Relative frequencies of types of cognitive processes for the population of 900 consumats (light grey = deliberating; dark grey = social comparison; white = repetition; black = imitation)

As this example indicates, two types of lock-in can be observed, where we consider lock-in as a stable state after a number of iterations of consumption.

- *Local lock-in*: a stable pattern of consumption occurs within clustered groups of consumats who all consume the same product.
- *Global lock-in*: one product becomes to dominate the whole lattice of consumats.

The acknowledgement of local lock-in implies that a 100 per cent product adoption is not necessary for (potential) lock-in effects to occur.

Variables that affect the chance of a lock-in to occur

Because of the many variables that affect consumer behaviour we have performed a large number of model runs (1000) using stochastic values (from a uniform distribution) for the parameters $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $\bar{\gamma}=1$, $LNS_{min} \in [0, 0.5]$ $UT \in [0, 0.1]$ and $\varepsilon \in [0, 1]$. This large number of simulation runs using stochastic values is being performed to determine the parameter values that produce lock-in effects. Figure 8.5 depicts the proportional distribution of the consumption of product 1 after 100 time steps, when the pattern has been stabilised. It can be observed that for most random values of the parameters, the consumption share of product 1 (and hence also product 0) is near 50%. In only 33 cases a global lock-in situation occurred. It appears that a global lock-in occurs only for particular parameter values. In Table 8.1 the average values for the global locked-in and not global locked-in runs are being presented. It can be observed that in case of a global lock-in, the value of γ_T (the weight for taste) is near zero, γ_L (the weight for leisure) is higher than average and γ_I (the weight for identity) is somewhat higher than average. Also LNS_{min} and UT are higher than the average value. These results can be explained as follows.

Figure 8.5: Distribution of the consumption share of product 1 at time-step 100 across 1000 model runs. If this share is equal to 0 or 1 a global lock-in has occurred: all consumats choose either product 0 or product 1.

The weight of the need for personal taste is very important because strong specific preferences for a certain product will reduce the possibility of a lock-in (one does not easily copy others). If the need for personal taste is not weighted substantially in the cognitive processing, and the price-dependent need for leisure is weighted significantly, consumats will choose the cheapest product, which in return reduces its price due to ‘learning-by-doing’ cost reductions. The relatively high values of LNSmin and UT for the locked-in simulation runs suggest that deliberation is an important cognitive process for achieving a global lock-in. In sum, a global lock-in of one of two similar products occurs if consumats, when deliberating, choose the cheapest product, and stay with this choice (i.e., on the basis of repetition) because it satisfies their needs. The initial (random) distribution of consumption and the consumats’ characteristics determine which product will eventually lock-in.

	General	Global lock-in
γ	0.251 (0.142)	0.290 (0.147)
γ_T	0.253 (0.142)	0.020 (0.018)
γ_L	0.250 (0.146)	0.424 (0.164)
γ_S	0.245 (0.141)	0.266 (0.166)
LNSmin	0.499 (0.291)	0.594 (0.272)
UT	0.493 (0.291)	0.680 (0.214)
ϵ	0.499 (0.285)	0.434 (0.241)
#	1000	33

Table 8.1: Statistics for the experiment of 1000 model runs: the average values of the model parameters and the standard deviation (in brackets).

For each consumat is being calculated how many different products the 8 neighbours are consuming. In this model the neighbours of a consumat consume at least one product (all

product 0 or 1), and at most two types (both product 0 and 1) of products, and hence this number will be either 1 or 2. The average of this number is being calculated over the 900 consumats, and yields a distribution-indicator. In Figure 8.6, this distribution-indicator is depicted for the 1000 model runs.

Figure 8.6: Distribution of the average different types of products consumed by the neighbours in time step 100. If the average of this distribution-indicator is 1, a macro-level lock-in has occurred. If this average is 2, the consumption is randomly distributed over the lattice. A low average suggests spatial patterns.

If the distribution-indicator is equal to 1, each of the 900 consumats consumes the same product as its 8 neighbours, indicating a global lock-in. As we have seen, this occurs in 33 simulation runs. If the distribution-indicator is 2, all consumats have neighbours who consume products 0 and 1, indicating that consumption is distributed rather randomly over the lattice. Figure 8.6 shows that 93 simulation runs end up with all consumats having neighbours consuming both products. Moreover, Figure 8.6 shows a relatively high number of observations starting at about 1.4 to about 1.9, indicating the occurrence of local lock-ins.

If the distribution-indicator values are related to the parameters that have been varied in this experiment using a multiple regression analysis, a simple linear relationship is been found (Table 8.2). In this relation, γ has been excluded because the two products are assumed to have the same pollution rate. The linear equation with the (non-standardised) weights as presented in Table 8.2 explains about half of the variance of the distribution-indicator of Figure 8.6, as the R^2 of 0.489 indicates. The equation implies that a higher value of the distribution-indicator is more likely, the more important the personal taste need, the higher the minimal level of need satisfaction, and the less important the leisure and identity needs and the lower the uncertainty tolerance. Thus, conversely, a higher weight of identity (γ_I) goes along with lower distribution-indicator, i.e., a higher degree of local lock-in, as does a higher weight of the need for leisure (implying consuming the ‘cheapest’ product). A higher weight on individual taste (γ_T) leads to a higher distribution-indicator, i.e., to a lower degree of local lock-in. This is of course in line with the findings of Table 8.1. The role of the leisure need is less important but it is in line with the price effect as presented in Table 8.1. Furthermore it is

Multiple R ²	0.489	
	β - weight	t-value
Const.	1.789	(53.15)*
γ	-0.538	(-11.48)*
γ_r	0.685	(14.58)*
γ_L	-0.196	(-4.25)*
LNSmin	0.159	(8.54)*
UT	-0.237	(-12.78)*
ϵ	0.004	(0.21)
# of runs	1000	

Table 8.2: Multiple R², β -weights and t-values (in brackets) for a multiple regression analysis on the results of 1000 model runs. * = $p < .05$

found that a higher minimum level of need satisfaction (LNSmin) leads to lower degree of local lock-in. A higher uncertainty tolerance (UT) appears to stimulate processes of lock-in, suggesting that social processing is an important process for a (local) lock-in to occur.

Conclusions

The simulation experiments have revealed that two types of lock-in processes can be distinguished, each with their own dynamics. The global lock-in effect is most likely to occur under conditions where consumers have no strong personal taste for one of the two products (the need for personal taste is low) and the price of the product is playing an important role (the need for leisure is important, see Table 8.1). Moreover, it appears that global lock-ins are more likely to happen when the consumers engage more in deliberation (higher LNSmin and UT, see Table 8.1).

Local lock-ins are most likely to occur when consumers find it important to consume the same product as their neighbours (a high need for identity, see Table 8.2). For example, one can often observe that a small group of people is using one product, while the majority uses another. On the basis of the simulation experiments we expect that this is most likely to occur under conditions where (1) people have no personal preference for the taste of a product, (2) the price of the product is playing a modest role, and (3) people prefer to consume the same as their 'neighbours'. Moreover, local lock-ins are more likely to happen when the consumers engage more in social comparison (higher LNSmin and lower UT, see Table 8.2). In trying to expand their share in a locally locked-in market, the suppliers of both products should employ different strategies. To increase the share of the product with a low market-share it would be most beneficial to make the taste of the product a more important issue. For the market-leader, it would be a good strategy to approach individuals in the groups that use the other product, and make them a special offer. If one or two group members

change their consumption, the others may follow. In a market of similar goods, like cars and softdrinks, commercials often emphasise the ‘identity’ of their product by showing role models using the product, thereby suggesting that their products satisfy the need for identity.

The introduction of an alternative product

In this section it will be analysed under what conditions an alternative product will lock-in to a consumer market. We start with a market in which product 0 has reached a global lock-in. Initially, the alternative product 1 has a market share of, say, 1 percent and it differs from the locked-in product 0 in that it does *not* pollute. The zero-pollutant alternative also has a much lower cumulative learning factor, CL_{I-in} is 1, compared with the locked-in product, for which CL_{I-in} is 100 (c.f., equation 5). This implies that the price of the alternative product will decrease significantly when cumulative consumption rises, whereas the already high cumulative production of the locked-in product causes its price not to decrease much further following an increase in cumulative consumption.

As in the previous section, 1000 runs have been performed with the consumat model. The average share of the alternative product 1 shows a slight increase, on average, to 20 per cent at time step 100 (Figure 8.7). Only in a small number of cases will the zero pollutant lock-in (Figures 8.11 and 8.12).

Figure 8.7: The average total consumption share of product 1 for $t = 1$ to $t = 100$

Figure 8.8: Distribution of the consumption share of product 1 at time-step 100 across 1000 model runs. If this share is equal to 0 or 1 a global lock-in has occurred: all consumats choose either product 0 or product 1.

Figure 8.9: Distribution of the average different types of products consumed by the neighbours in time step 100. If the average of this distribution-indicator is 1, a macro-level lock-in has occurred. If this average is 2, the consumption is randomly distributed over the lattice. A lower average (well above 1) suggests local lock-in.

Conclusions

Often marketeers and engineers are surprised by the fact that a new product does not conquer the market, despite the fact that it is far better than already existing products. The current simulation experiment suggests that two processes hinder the introduction of a new product. Firstly, when consumats are satisfied they process automatically, thereby copying their own previous behaviour (repetition when they are certain) or someone else's previous behaviour (imitation when they are uncertain). It is clear that as long as consumats perform automatic behaviour, no new product will enter the market. If 1 per cent of the consumats uses the new product, as was the case in the last experiment discussed above, the chances of any other

consumers copying this new behaviour are very small. A second process that is often neglected is that the need satisfaction derived from consuming a given product, is not only provided by the product itself, but also by information regarding which other people already consume this product too. In situations where consuming the same product as the neighbours satisfies one's need for identity, a strong barrier exists for a new product to conquer a market.

This simulation experiment thus suggests that it is very hard to introduce a new product in a locked-in market where most consumers are reasonably satisfied and prefer to consume the same as their neighbours. To facilitate the introduction of an alternative product it is advised to approach a group of consumers with a special offer in order to get a starting point in the market. This group approach makes it possible appeal to the identity needs of the group of consumers, and the special offer may comprise a price reduction that satisfies the need for leisure to a larger extent than the locked-in product.

Discussion

Many policy measures are aimed at changing consumption patterns. In the context of consumer behaviour change it is important to understand the dynamics of lock-in phenomena. In this chapter, the consumer approach, as presented in Chapters 5 and 6, has been used instead of the more traditional probabilistic models, to study the dynamics of consumption patterns that lock-in. This provided several insights about the conditions under which lock-in of consumption patterns occurs. It was found that global lock-in especially occurs if consumers engage relative frequently in deliberation, the need for 'personal taste' plays a negligible role, and the need for leisure, which is related to product prices, is very important.

Our simulation experiments revealed that the local lock-ins generally occur when the consumers engage relative frequently in social comparison, the need for identity is highly weighted and the need for taste is not very important. This leads to spatial clustering of product consumption, which may be less in line with the individual preferences of consumers.

These results demonstrate that the formulation of new hypotheses for empirical testing is an interesting advantage of working with simulation models. The model-based results suggest that the effect of what the neighbours consume may be very significant in certain conditions. It might be interesting to perform empirical research to discover under what conditions (e.g., product type, consumer characteristics) consumers are most likely to copy the product choice of certain other consumers.

There are various starting points for improving the current simulation model for studying lock-ins. For example, satisfaction of the identity need is currently related to the proportion of neighbours consuming the same product as the subject consumer itself. This relates to the 'belongingness' associated with this need. However, real people may differ in the interpretation of identity. For example, some people may stress the uniqueness of their identity, and consequently prefer to consume a different product than their neighbours. Such interpretations of the need for identity could also be included in the formalisation of the consumer.

Another possible improvement of the simulation of lock-in phenomena is a more advanced description of the supply dynamics. We could, for example, enlarge the model with the simulation of behaviour of companies leading to a co-evolutionary approach to consumption and production. Here, producers adapt their product characteristics to the demand of the market, and they may find new niches in markets. Along with the consumat model, we can imagine that producers may deliberate about the market developments, imitate and socially compare with other producers and engage in repetition (habitual production without innovation). However, before we start an endeavour in modelling the behavioural dynamics of the supply side, it is first important to further improve our knowledge of the consumer dynamics as simulated with the consumat approach. Therefore, in the next chapter we aim to apply the consumat approach in a more complex environment, to study the potential of the consumat approach in an integrated environmental-economic modelling context.

9 Formalising the consumat in an ecological-economic model¹³

Many integrated models have been developed to study the dynamics of natural systems. As was concluded in Chapter 1, human behaviour is an important factor determining such dynamics, because natural resources are often being (over)exploited. However, integrated models usually formalise human behaviour according to the rational-actor approach, which is not capable of incorporating processes of social comparison, imitation and habit formation (see Chapter 1). As these processes are highly relevant in the context of resource management, the consumat approach was developed to provide a psychologically rich model of human behaviour, that can be applied in the context of integrated modelling. In the previous chapters the consumat approach has been tested in relative simple environments. The present chapter is aimed at testing the applicability of the consumat approach in connection with a more complex ecological-economic model. Moreover, it is being investigated to what extent variations in micro-level processes seriously affect macro-level outcomes. To demonstrate the effect of micro-level variations, in the simulation runs to be reported a *homo economicus* and a *homo psychologicus* are being formalised. The *homo economicus* is formalised as a consumat that engages purely in deliberation, and it thus resembles the rational actor, whereas the *homo psychologicus* has all four cognitive strategies at its disposal. These consumats are placed in the ecological-economic model of *Lakeland* (see below), and their behaviour is being contrasted so as to demonstrate the effects of variations in behavioural processes at the micro-level.

Lakeland

“Lakeland” (De Greef and De Vries, 1991) is a relatively simple ecological-economic model, which comprises two natural resources: a fish-stock in a lake and a nearby gold-mine. The lake is being modelled as a simple ecological system of fish and shrimps. The quantities of fish and shrimp are being modelled as a set of Lotka Volterra equations simulating a predator-prey system (Lotka, 1925; Volterra, 1931). As an addition, the shrimps are being made susceptible to the pollution of the lake. The pollution is not only concentrated in the water, but also in the sediment of the lake, from which it may be released when the pollution concentration of the water drops.

The introduction of consumats in Lakeland implies that different behavioural processes, such as social comparison and imitative behaviour, underlie the consumats’ harvesting behaviour. Sixteen (16) consumats are being placed in Lakeland, and these consumats catch fish from the lake to satisfy their need for food. Moreover, they may also export fish, and the returns can be spent on assets such as luxury goods. Import of fish from an international market is also allowed. If the gold-mine is opened, consumats may also dig for gold. The money that is earned by mining can be spent on fish imports and/or on luxurious assets. The consumats thus may engage exclusively in mining, thereafter buying fish for food. The pollution that is caused by mining is reducing the carrying capacity of the lake for the fish and shrimp populations. The consumats determine how they allocate their time on leisure, fishing and mining. They are equipped with abilities for

¹³ This chapter is based on Jager, Janssen, De Vries, De Greef and Vlek (in press)

fishing and mining, and they want to satisfy their four needs: leisure, identity, subsistence and freedom. These needs are selected out of the larger set of needs as distinguished in the conceptual model (Chapter 5). It is assumed that the satisfaction of the leisure need relates to the share of the time spent on leisure. The identity need is satisfied by the relative amount of money the consumat owns in comparison to consumats with similar abilities. The subsistence-need relates to the consumption of food. The need for freedom is assumed to be related to the absolute amount of money the consumat owns, which can be spent on whatever (luxurious) assets the consumat prefers (autonomy). These assumptions are of course very crude, but they allow us to formalise different needs in a simple manner.

Figure 9.1 depicts the variables used in this simulation model in the framework of the conceptual behaviour model as presented in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.5).

Figure 9.1. The variables used in the simulation model placed in the schematic representation of the conceptual meta-model of behaviour (Figure 5.5). The white lines refer to feedbacks within the consumat.

To study how the different possible behavioural processes may affect the interactions with the simulated environment, it was decided to focus on experimental manipulations of consumats' supposed tendency to engage in particular behavioural processes, thus contrasting the *homo economicus* with the *homo psychologicus*. These experiments were performed in two set-ups of Lakeland, one in which only fishing is allowed, and a second

in which mining is allowed besides fishing. First the results obtained with Lakeland where only fishing is allowed will be described, and in a next section the results of introducing mining in Lakeland are presented.

Fishing in Lakeland

In the first simulation experiments the set-up of Lakeland does not allow consumats to dig gold, and thus they fully depend on their fishing capacities to satisfy their needs. Varying the minimal level of need satisfaction and the level of uncertainty tolerance allows for the specification of consumats that engage in one or more of the four behavioural processes distinguished in Figure 9.1. Two types of consumats have been formalised to show how different types of behaviour affect the management of the fish-stock. The first type is relatively quickly satisfied but also quickly uncertain ($LNS_{min} = 0.05$, $UT = 0.05$). This leads this type of consumat to engage in all four behavioural strategies. This consumat, having a large degree of freedom regarding the behavioural strategies, will correspondingly be denoted as the *homo psychologicus*.

The second consumat type is virtually never satisfied or uncertain ($LNS_{min} = 0.95$, $UT = 0.95$). This causes this type of consumat to engage exclusively in outcome-optimising deliberation. This consumat can be considered as a simple version of the optimising agent in economic models, and it will consequently be denoted as the *homo economicus*. The *homo economicus* is self-supportive, i.e. not learning from the behaviour of other consumats nor making explicit assumptions about the decisions of others. The consumats employ a time-horizon (cognitive ability) of 10 time-steps when engaging in reasoned processing (deliberation and social comparison). Moreover, the consumats have a fishing ability of 6600, indicating that they are capable of catching 6600 units of fish per time-step when the fish-stock is on its carrying capacity level (the maximum number of fish-units is about 23000). Factors that affect the actual catch are the fish-density (in our model 0.0000002 when the fish-stock is maximal, indicating that there is an occasional fish in the water), the fish growth function (in our model about 2.3, indicating that each time step the number of fish is multiplied by 2.3 for as long as the maximum is not reached) and the length of the fishing season (in our model .80 of the time). Consequently, we have a very viable fish-stock, which renews itself very quickly, and hence is quite difficult to deplete.

To introduce environmental uncertainty in the model, a stochastic function in the fish catch has been formalised. For both experimental conditions (*homo economicus* and *homo psychologicus*) 100 model runs have been performed, for which the average outcomes will be presented. Each experiment involved 16 identical consumats inhabiting Lakeland. Thus, all consumats were either *homo economicus* or *homo psychologicus*, depending on the experimental condition. The consumats start with an equal financial budget. Because they are depending on each other regarding the management of the resource, the consumats are actually caught in a commons dilemma.

In reporting the results we will focus on a few essential variables. First, the behaviour and behavioural processing of the consumats will be observed. Second, the developments in the fish-stock will be considered. Third, the developments in the need satisfaction of consumats will be observed. Finally, attention will be given to the developments in the financial budget of the consumats, which provides a material index of welfare in the model.

Each simulation experiment involves 50 time-steps, in which consumats have to decide how much time to spent on fishing and leisure in order to satisfy their needs.

Results

Looking at the behavioural processes the consumats engage in, it appears that the *homo psychologicus* engages in all four behavioural strategies, as was intended. Figure 9.2 shows for time-step 1 to 50 the proportion of time each behavioural process is engaged. These results are an average outcome of 100 simulation runs under the condition of all consumats being *homo psychologicus*.

Figure 9.2. Proportional distribution of the four behavioural processes for the *homo psychologicus*.

The sudden shift from much repetition to much deliberation at $t \approx 18$ is caused by the fact that the initial financial budget, that the consumats use to buy luxury goods or to import/buy fish, has depleted around that time. This worse financial situation causes the consumats to be dissatisfied more often, causing them to engage in deliberation more often. Because the consumats are occasionally uncertain and hence engage in social processing (imitation and social comparison), this decrease in need-satisfaction also causes the relative high proportion of imitation before $t \approx 18$ to change towards social comparison (see Figure 9.2). The *homo economicus* engaged purely in deliberation, as it was defined to do.

Figure 9.3 shows the development in time of the fish-stock for these two conditions (100 simulation runs per consumat-type condition). It can be observed that the fish-stock depletes for the *homo economicus*, and remains at a high level for the *homo psychologicus*.

Figure 9.3. The development of the fish-stock in time for the two consumat-type conditions

These effects can be attributed to the proportion of time spent fishing, which is graphically depicted in Figure 9.4. *Homo psychologicus* slowly increases its fishing to 0.7 of the time, whereas *homo economicus* more rapidly increases its fishing to 0.8 of the time. The explanation of these effects will be done below in two separate sections for the *homo psychologicus* and *homo economicus*.

Figure 9.4. The proportion of time spent fishing for the two consumat-type conditions

Differences in time spent fishing have consequences for the financial budget of the consumats. Figure 9.5 shows that the higher proportion of time spent fishing by *homo economicus* yields a higher financial budget during the first 35 time-steps. However, starting from the moment that the fish-stock gets depleted, the financial budget of *homo economicus* quickly drops to zero. For the *homo psychologicus* a decline of the initial financial budget can be observed, until a relatively stable budget is reached that is purely earned by fishing.

Figure 9.5. The financial budget for the two consumat-type conditions

Homo psychologicus

As was shown in Figure 9.2, during the 100 experimental runs the *homo psychologicus* engages in all four behavioural strategies. Consumats start fishing for 60% of the time (initial setting). An occasional bad catch may yield a lower financial budget in comparison to other consumats. As a consequence, this consumat's level of need satisfaction for 'identity' drops below the critical level, causing it to engage in reasoned processing (deliberation or social comparison). When deliberating, this consumat will increase its time spent fishing to about 80% (while the satisfied consumats remain at 60%) to increase its financial budget. This is mostly a satisfactory action, and as a consequence this consumat will continue to process automatically. This implies repetition of its own previous behaviour, or imitation of the behaviour of similar consumats. The latter may cause the consumat to decrease its time spent working again. Other satisfied consumats may simply imitate the increase in time spent working without ever engaging in reasoned processing. However, most of them remain fishing for 60% of the time. In some runs, however, the number of consumats that imitate the increase in time spent fishing is so large that the resource gets seriously depleted. This causes the slightly downward development of the fish-stock beyond step 36 that can be seen in Figure 9.3. On the average, the proportion of time the consumats spend fishing increases to about 67%.

The consumats that increase their time spent fishing will be more likely to catch a surplus of fish that they can sell on the market. This allows them to earn some money for luxury products, which satisfies their need for freedom. Moreover, their level of need-satisfaction for identity is relative high because they have more money than the consumats that did not increase their time spent fishing. However, the increase in time spent fishing is not that large that their level of need-satisfaction for leisure drops significantly. Finally, they catch enough fish to satisfy their need for subsistence. Because the needs of the consumats that increased their time spent fishing are staying at a sufficient level, they experience a high general level of need satisfaction, causing them to remain processing in an automatic manner. This implies repeating their own previous behaviour, or imitating the behaviour of similar consumats.

The consumats that did not increase their time spent fishing in the beginning (say, the first 15 time-steps) will catch somewhat less fish, using it exclusively for their own consumption. Not selling fish on the market implies that their financial budget declines, which causes the over-all decline of financial budget for the *homo psychologicus* condition (Figure 9.5). As a consequence, these consumats cannot afford to buy luxury goods at a

given moment in time. Because of that, their need for freedom decreases below the critical level around $t = 20$, causing them to deliberate and socially compare regarding better opportunities. However, often they calculate that increased working may increase their level of need satisfaction for freedom, but at the cost of their level of need satisfaction for leisure and identity. Despite the fact that they remain dissatisfied as regards freedom, they do not change their behaviour because there is no other behavioural opportunity yielding a higher over-all level of need satisfaction.

In most cases the consumats have a reasonable level of need satisfaction for subsistence, identity and leisure and a low level of need satisfaction for freedom. In about half of the simulation runs a subgroup of consumats increases their time spent fishing in an early stage, resulting in a higher level of need satisfaction for freedom in the long run.

To obtain an indication of distribution of income, Lorenz (1905) and Gini (1912) developed income-disparity indexes. The Gini index (Gini, 1912) is a measure for distributional equality, and provides a macro-level indicator of economic equality in a society. In the simulation experiments, the Gini index is being used to indicate financial equality. A Gini index of 1 denotes complete financial equality, a Gini index of 0 complete financial inequality. In the experiments with Lakeland the consumats all start with an equal financial budget, which implies a Gini index of 1.0. In the first 20 time-steps a drop to about 0.20 was observed. After this sharp decline in the Gini index, in about half of the simulation runs an increase towards 1.0 can be seen, whereas the other half shows an irregular pattern, oscillating between 0.20 and 0.30. This oscillating pattern occurs in the simulation runs where a group of consumats increased their harvesting behaviour in the early time-steps because they experienced 'bad luck' regarding their harvest. Moreover, some consumats not experiencing this 'bad luck' may still increase their time spent fishing because they imitate the consumats that had 'bad luck'. Especially this last group of consumats will earn a lot of money. Because the consumats that increased their time spent fishing earn more money than the other consumats, the Gini index remains low, indicating distributional inequality.

Homo economicus

Homo economicus, which is never satisfied and never uncertain, exclusively engages in deliberation. The consumats in this condition immediately increase their time spent fishing to maximise their outcomes. Despite the fact that the consumats, having a time-horizon of 20, anticipate the collapse of the fish-resource, they continue fishing intensively. Around time-step 40, the fish-stock has depleted and the level of need-satisfaction of the consumats drops to 0.0. This situation typically resembles the tragedy of the commons, showing that behaviour following individual rationality may lead towards a collective disaster. The consumats implicitly 'expect' that all other consumats will continue their over-harvesting. Consequently, each consumat 'realises' that their individual behaviour hardly affects the depletion of the resource. Following the principles of individual rationality, all consumats consider a high harvesting level as optimal, and consequently they do not succeed in reducing their harvest to a more sustainable level. This situation resembles a sort of self-fulfilling prophecy, as the fish-stock depletes because the consumats expect it to deplete. This outcome is a typical example of what happens if no property rights exist on an exhaustible resource and the fishermen behave in an own-outcome maximising manner.

Using the same decision rules for a single 'meta-actor' with needs and abilities that are 16 times as large as those of each of our 16 consumats, would result in the meta-actor decreasing its harvesting now so as to maximise its outcomes over the forthcoming 20

time-steps. This is due to the fact that it has full control over the fish-stock because it is not being confronted with 15 other consumats.

In the condition of the *homo economicus* the consumats earn an almost equal amount of money for as long as the fish-stock is not depleted, resulting in a Gini index of about .97. When the fish-stock is depleted at around $t = 40$, and consumats' income has dropped to 0, some consumats will run out of money earlier than other consumats do, causing the Gini index to drop to a level of .60. Very quickly all consumats have finished up their finances, and this equal financial situation for all consumats obviously yields a Gini index of 1.0.

No variation in fish-catch

Some variations of the default case have been performed to assess the sensitivity of several crucial assumptions. In the previous experiments, the harvest of a single consumat at a given time-step was partly dependent on chance, just like any real-world fisherman may have lucky days and bad days. In the present condition, all random variation in the fish catch of the consumats has been eliminated. For the rest, the previous experimental consumat-type conditions (*homo economicus* and *homo psychologicus*) are being replicated. Removing random variation now causes the *homo psychologicus* to be certain all of the time, which would cause it to engage exclusively in individual processing (deliberation and/or repetition). Because the *homo psychologicus* does not experience occasional 'bad luck' regarding the harvest, its level of need satisfaction remains at a satisfactory level. Consequently, the *homo psychologicus* engages only in repetition, fishing for 60% of the time instead of increasing the time spent fishing to about 67% as found in the previous experiment that included a stochastic function in the fish catch. These results, showing an increase in harvesting when uncertainty increases, are in accordance with the results obtained with a simple resource (see Chapter 7). The *homo economicus*, however, did not alter its harvesting behaviour in response to removing all random variation in the fish catch. This is due to the fact that the *homo economicus* has a high tolerance for uncertainty ($UT = 0.95$), and thus is less sensitive to variations in the harvest.

Introducing mining in Lakeland

In the next series of experiments the set-up of Lakeland allows the consumat to engage in mining starting from the first time-step. Consumats thus can alternately fish and mine to satisfy their needs. Besides a fishing ability of 6600 (see previous section), the consumats have a mining ability of 100, indicating they are capable of harvesting a maximum of 100 units of gold per time-step. It depends on the market dynamics (e.g. world fish-price versus local fish-price) how much fish they can buy for a unit of gold. As a starting condition, the consumats are fishing for 60% of the time, and they do not yet engage in mining. For the rest the design of two consumat-type conditions as used in the first series of experiments is being replicated. Because the mining of gold induces pollution of the lake, which in its turn affects the fish-stock, data on the development of pollution concentration in the lake will also be presented.

Results

Figure 9.6 shows the time spent fishing and mining for *homo economicus* and *homo psychologicus* respectively. It can be seen that *homo economicus* very quickly switches to mining, but instead

of a smooth transition an oscillating pattern between time spent fishing and mining can be seen. *Homo psychologicus* shows a slow increase in mining, until at about $t = 20$ the transition is completed.

Figure 9.6. Time spent fishing and mining for the two consumat-type conditions for $t = 1$ to $t = 50$

Looking at the consequences for the fish-stock (Figure 9.7), first it can be observed that for *homo economicus* the fish-stock does not fully deplete within 50 time-steps, as it did in the previous condition (Figure 9.3). The introduction of mining implies that the consumats spent less time fishing. Because *homo psychologicus* spends less time fishing than *homo economicus*, the latter depletes the fish-stock to a larger extent. However, *homo psychologicus* depletes the fish-stock at a higher rate than in the previous condition, despite the fact that it spends less time fishing. A major reason for this is that the slow but persistent move towards mining increases the pollution that causes the fish-stock to decrease (Figure 9.8). This further accelerates the transition to mining, as the fish catches per hour keep decreasing.

Figure 9.7. The fish-stock for the two consumat-type conditions for $t = 1$ to $t = 50$

Due to the mining, the consumats are capable of earning more money than in the previous condition without mining. As Figure 9.9 shows, this yields a higher financial budget for both types of consumats than in the previous experiment (Figure 9.5) Continually deliberating, *homo economicus* succeeds in attaining a higher financial budget than *homo psychologicus*.

Figure 9.9. The financial budget for the two consumat-type conditions

Homo psychologicus

Homo psychologicus shows a transition from a fishing society to a mining society. In the first time-steps some consumats may have bad luck and harvest such a small number of fish that they become dissatisfied. Because this will cause them to engage in deliberation, they perceive mining as a satisfactory alternative opportunity. At about $t = 18$ more consumats become dissatisfied and start mining. The more consumats engage in mining, the larger the chances are that uncertain consumats that are fishing will also start mining on the basis of imitation or social comparison. At that moment the transition from a fishing society to a mining society becomes manifest. Occasionally a mining consumat may engage in fishing for a few time steps on the basis of imitation. However, this will usually lead to dissatisfaction within a few time-steps, and the consumat will go mining again. Nevertheless, imitation causes that in some simulation runs always a few consumats remain fishing. At the micro-level a lot of behavioural change occurs in the working behaviour of *homo psychologicus*. At the macro-level a decrease can be observed in the Gini index from 1 at the start to about .25 at $t = 20$. After the transition to a mining-society, the Gini index rises again to a level of about .80, indicating that income differences between consumats have decreased as a consequence of them all engaging in mining.

Homo economicus

The oscillating pattern demonstrated by *homo economicus* (cf. Figure 9.6) is caused by the fact that all 16 consumats change their behaviour at the same time. This repetitive switching between more mining/less fishing and more fishing/less mining may be explained by the fact that each consumat, being in the deliberation mode, has been formalised so as to expect that all others will behave as in the previous time-step. The consumat thus deliberates that when all others increase their time spent mining, increasing the time spent fishing may yield the highest outcomes, and vice-versa. However, all the consumats reason in this direction at the same moment, and as a consequence, they all end up doing about the same in the same time-step. Over time the extremes in these oscillations converge, indicating that in the long run a more stable working time distribution is likely to emerge. Because all the consumats behave more or less the same, the Gini index remains at a level of about .99, indicating that the incomes of the consumats are almost equal.

Introducing diversity in consumats' abilities

In the previous experimental conditions all consumats in both consumat-type conditions had equal abilities regarding fishing (6600 fish-units per time-step) and mining (100 units of gold per time-step). However, in real life a differentiation in abilities can easily be observed. The multi-agent approach makes it very easy to formalise consumats having different abilities. The central question is how such a differentiation affects the behaviour of the consumats and the ecological-economic system as a whole. To formalise this, the consumats are equipped with differing fishing and mining abilities. Four different levels of fishing ability and 4 different levels of mining ability make $4 * 4 = 16$ different ability settings, thus equipping each consumat with a unique set of abilities. As settings, the average is rather arbitrarily chosen to be equal to the previous experimental conditions, the consumats with the highest ability having twice as much ability as the consumat with the lowest ability. Table 9.1 shows the design with respect to the allocation of the two abilities to the 16 consumats:

		Mining ability			
		67	89	111	133
Fishing ability	4400	Consumat 1	Consumat 2	Consumat 3	Consumat 4
	5867	Consumat 5	Consumat 6	Consumat 7	Consumat 8
	7333	Consumat 9	Consumat 10	Consumat 11	Consumat 12
	8800	Consumat 13	Consumat 14	Consumat 15	Consumat 16

Table 9.1. The design of 16 consumats with different fishing and mining abilities

As in the previous experiments, the average mining ability is 100 gold units/time-step and the average fishing ability is 6600 fish-units/time-step. The consumats will socially compare to or imitate only the behaviour of approximately similar other consumats. In the present experiment the similarity is expressed in two variables: level of need satisfaction for subsistence (LNSs) and financial budget. Hence, if consumats are engaging in social processing, they compare themselves with consumats having about the same quantity of food and money. Regarding food the consumat considers other consumats having 30% more or less food as similar to themselves. Regarding money this percentage is set at 20%. Formalising similarity on the basis of changing variables implies that the group of consumats whom a consumat compares with may change continually, depending on its own state and the state of other 'similar' consumats. Again two consumat-type conditions are created to contrast *homo economicus* and *homo psychologicus*.

Results

The results of this experiment are depicted in Figure 9.10. These results look very similar to those of the previous experiment (Figure 9.6). However, closer observation shows that in case of *homo psychologicus* the transition from a fishing to a mining society takes more time, starting earlier and ending with the consumats spending more time fishing than in the previous experiment with equal abilities. This quicker start of the transition is caused by the consumats with a low fishing ability and a high mining ability, which will be quickly dissatisfied because of their low fish-catch, and then perceive mining as a more attractive opportunity. In contrast, the consumats with a high fishing ability and a low mining ability are more likely to continue fishing, causing that at $t = 50$ the time spent fishing is about twice as large as in the previous experiment. As a consequence, the average fish harvest of a population of consumats having unequal abilities is larger than the harvest of a population of equal consumats. In other words, harvesting behaviour is differentiated depending on differing abilities.

Figure 9.10. Time spent fishing and mining for the two-consumat type conditions with consumats having unequal abilities

Looking at the consequences for the fish-stock (Figure 9.11), it can be observed that in the beginning the fish-stock depletes more rapidly in the condition of *homo economicus* (see further below).

Figure 9.11. The fish-stock for the two consumat-type conditions for $t = 1$ to $t = 50$

However, despite the fact that *homo psychologicus* spends less time fishing, after time-step 43 the fish-stock depletes more strongly than in the case of *homo economicus*. This is caused by the fact that the intensive mining by *homo psychologicus* pollutes the lake, which causes the fish-stock to further decrease.

Due to the pollution of the lake (Figure 9.12), the fish population decreases, and also the average catch decreases. This will make mining a relatively more attractive opportunity, and it may thus stimulate consumats to go mining. Even when the pollution causes the fish-stock to collapse, consumats can satisfy their needs by importing fish. It can easily be imagined that in such a case the eventual depletion of the gold mine will leave the consumats with no opportunity at all to satisfy their needs.

Figure 9.12. The pollution concentration for the two consumat-type conditions for $t = 1$ to $t = 50$

Homo economicus

Looking at *homo economicus*, two major differences with the equal abilities experiment (Figure 9.6) can be seen. First, the oscillating pattern dissipates more quickly in the unequal abilities experiment (Figure 9.10). This is due to the fact that the consumats do not behave equally because they all have different abilities. The resulting behavioural diversity causes that each consumat has less extreme expectations regarding the average time spent working of the other consumats. This in its turn causes the consumats to behave less extreme for themselves. As a consequence, the oscillations in time spent working converge, thereby further stabilising the expectations, and hence the time spent working. The second difference with the equal abilities experiment is that the times spent fishing and mining are lower. Due to this effect the fish-stock is depleted less severely at time-step 50 than in the condition with equal abilities. The explanation for this is that consumats with a high ability do not want to harvest as much as they are capable to, and the consumats with a low ability are not capable to harvest as much as they want to. Consequently, the consumats' ability is not linearly related to their actual harvesting behaviour.

Homo psychologicus

In contrast with *homo psychologicus*, for *homo economicus* the average harvest of a population of consumats having equal abilities is larger than the harvest of a population of unequal consumats. These results demonstrate that an increase in the diversity of consumat abilities may have different effects on the sustainability of a system, depending on the behavioural

processing the consumats engage in. Apparently the effects of increasing diversity are not unidirectional, which emphasises the need for more research to investigate the role of diversity in resource management situations.

The introduction of diversity has an impact on the equality of the income of consumats. In Figure 9.13 the Gini index is presented for *homo economicus* and the *homo psychologicus*, both for equal abilities and for unequal abilities. It comes as no surprise that adding variance in the consumat abilities causes the Gini index in general to be lower than in the no-variance condition. Logically, more variance in ability results in more variance in income. Moreover, it can be observed that *homo psychologicus* generally displays a lower Gini index than *homo economicus*, indicating that non-outcome-optimising behavioural processing strategies contribute to diversity in behaviour and in resulting income.

Figure 9.13. The Gini index for equal and unequal abilities

For *homo psychologicus* with equal abilities the relatively quick transition from fishing to mining causes a relatively short period where the one consumat is fishing, whereas the other consumat switches to mining. This yields large income differences concentrated in a short period of time, which is being reflected in the sharp drop in the Gini index around time-step 20. In the condition of *homo psychologicus* with unequal abilities, the diversity in income is larger on the average, as can be seen from Figure 9.13. However, because the transition is not as complete as in the equal-abilities condition, and less compressed in time, there will be no short period of time where the diversity of income is being concentrated. Apparently, a faster transition leads to larger income differences among consumats.

Introducing learning and technological innovation

The following experiment introduces technological innovation and learning by consumats to increase their harvest of fish. Here, mining is not allowed, making the consumats again fully dependent on the fish-stock for the satisfaction of their subsistence, identity and freedom needs. It is assumed that technological innovations only emerge when a consumat is deliberating. During deliberation there is a random chance that the consumat detects a new fishing opportunity that yields more fish per hour fishing. This is being formalised as an increase in fishing ability. This increase in fishing ability resembles a

technical innovation, e.g., engines with more power or better fishing nets. Once a consumat adopts a new technology, the other consumats can also adopt the new technology by deliberation, social comparison or imitation. In this condition all consumats start with equal abilities. Regarding fishing, they start with an ability to catch 6600 fish-units per capita. Two types of innovations have been experimentally tested, namely small technological innovations, implying an increase of 100 fish-units in fish catch per capita, and large technological innovations, implying an increase of 200 fish-units in fish catch per capita. Again two consumat-type conditions are created to contrast *homo economicus* and *homo psychologicus*.

Results

Figure 9.14 shows the development of the fish-stock for *homo psychologicus* and *homo economicus* given the two types of innovation.

Figure 9.14. The fish-stock under conditions of small and large technological innovations

In the case of *homo economicus* and large technological innovations, the fish-stock collapses very fast because of the fast dissipation of new technology. If a single consumat discovers a new innovation, the next time-step all other consumats will also be aware of this innovation. In case of small technological innovations, the collapse occurs somewhat later. In case of the *homo psychologicus*, it can be observed that the fish-stock starts decreasing relatively late. This is due to the fact that the consumats (easily satisfied) do not engage in deliberation that often, and consequently have a smaller chance of detecting an innovation. Moreover, due to the fact that many consumats engage in repetitive behaviour for considerable periods of time (because they are satisfied and certain), they remain unaware of the innovation. This causes that the dissipation of the innovation through the population of consumats proceeds at a slower rate.

These experiments indicate that technical innovation which increases the productivity by which resources are exploited may significantly affect the depletion rate of a resource. It also suggests that the rate at which this happens is strongly tied to the social conditions under which innovations may be diffused.

Conclusions

In mainstream economy, the behaviour of man in relation to renewable resources is traditionally formalised following the 'rational actor' approach. In this approach, usually large aggregates of people are represented by a single, rational actor with perfect foresight and a single, individual set of preferences. As has been demonstrated in this chapter, the consumats in Lakeland will follow different behavioural strategies depending on their own situation and the situation of the environment. The 'deliberating' consumat, which has been denoted as *homo economicus*, closely resembles the 'rational actor', only with this difference that 16 consumats have been formalised instead of a single actor. The deliberating consumat includes the notion of maximising one's own insatiable needs within a finite time horizon with a positive discount rate and no direct comparison with other agents (see Chapter 6 on deliberation). Obviously, this is a quite narrow rationality from a larger system's perspective and the deliberating agent might well extend its rationality to include a broader system perspective - which is what governments are assumed to do.

In this chapter, however, the focus is not on an extension of the rational actor but instead on social comparison, imitation and repetition as supplementary strategies for the individual agent. Our simulation experiments demonstrate that switching between these strategies, as is the case with *homo psychologicus*, may significantly alter the temporal development of macro-system variables such as the fish resource and consumats' average income. More importantly, it explains such macro-behaviour in a way which is totally different from an explanation derived from a macro-model that has been parameterised so as to reproduce the same time path. The consumat model, for instance, uses exchange of information among agents as an important explanatory variable, and it can consequently suggest policy actions that are related to this information exchange. Also, the consumat model allows for the calculation of quasi macro-variables such as income distribution. This provides an interesting heuristic to explore hypotheses between (in)equality and (economic) growth. In successive experiments it would be of interest to follow the recommendation by Kumar, Gore and Sitaramam (1996) of studying the volume of poor people, the severity of the poverty and the distribution of poverty in combination. This would draw a more profound perspective on distributional equity and the behavioural dynamics affecting it. Moreover, it would be interesting to equip the consumats with cultural perspectives (e.g., Thompson, Ellis and Wildavsky 1990) or basic orientors (Bossel, 1996; Krebs and Bossel, 1997) and explore how these co-determine the dynamics of ecological-economic systems.

10 **The general applicability of the consumat approach**

In the previous chapters, many discussion points about the various simulation experiments have been addressed. This concluding chapter will draw a more general picture of the applicability of the consumat approach. First the advantages and disadvantages of the consumat approach will be discussed. Second, we will sketch a general perspective concerning the validation of simulation research using the consumat approach. Third, we will discuss for what types of issues and for which users the consumat approach may be a suitable research tool.

The advantages and disadvantages of the consumat approach

The advantages of the consumat approach reside in several matters. First of all, the conceptual meta-model of human behaviour on which the simulation approach is based, provides a valuable tool to analyse various practical issues. Much applied psychological research has and still is focussing on attitudes of people and on strategies to change attitudes, thereby assuming that an attitude change affects the related behaviour. The meta-model provides a much broader, multi-theoretical and more dynamical perspective on behaviour and behavioural change. This may lead to a better understanding of, e.g., the dynamics of habit-formation and how undesired (e.g., environmentally harmful) habits can be changed.

Second, the consumat simulation approach offers a tool that allows for the introduction of more realistic behavioural dynamics in simulation research. This makes it possible to experiment with micro-macro dynamics and to explore dynamical (feedback) effects of individual behaviours. Especially when simulation research is used in combination with empirical social-psychological experiments, it would be possible to obtain a better understanding of the dynamics behind certain social phenomena. The operation of more realistic behavioural dynamics in integrated models leads to a better modelling of processes of social change. Moreover, it permits the use of indicators of people's quality-of-life, based upon changing levels of need satisfaction for a variety of human needs.

The disadvantages of the consumat approach mirror its advantages. Because the consumat approach is rather complex, its formalisation for a specific domain requires more effort and deliberate choices than a (much simpler) rational actor approach would. Especially when the issue being modelled becomes more complex it will be a lot of work to formalise the full consumat model. Here, the need-satisfying capacities and resource demands of many different opportunities may have to be assessed, if one wishes to include these in the simulation model. The researcher who is willing to take this effort must be convinced of the relevance of sophisticated behavioural dynamics in the system to be modelled. However, in many cases one may well use a simplified ('necessary and sufficient') version of the consumat

model. When the researcher is interested in a particular process within a given system, such as adding habitual behaviour to a consumers' optimisation strategy, it may already be worthwhile to incorporate only certain elements from the consumat approach in existing models.

Incorporating the full consumat approach in integrated ecological-economic models may yield outcomes that are less transparent with respect to the precise behavioural processes underlying these outcomes. Here, the issue of validity comes into question, because it has to be estimated to what extent the outcomes of a model are relevant, realistic and hence applicable. The next section will therefore discuss the issue of empirical validation of the consumat approach from a generic perspective.

Prospects for validating the consumat approach

The issue of validity has been discussed in chapters 7, 8 and 9. It was concluded that it is difficult to validate results from simulation experiments because often the necessary empirical data are not available. For example, despite the fact that there exists an abundance of empirical research on the management of a common resource, no data are available regarding the cognitive processes that people employ in deciding how much to harvest. As a consequence, the behavioural dynamics found to affect the harvesting behaviour of consumats, have not been demonstrated in real people. To do so, it would be necessary to try and replicate the most relevant versions of the simulation experiment using real people. Here, a particular perspective on the relation between empirical and simulation research becomes clear. First, simulation research makes it possible to run many experiments, thereby offering a tool to explore the dynamics of behaviour in a way that would be very costly and hard to do with real people. If some interesting dynamical process has been identified to occur under certain conditions, it is worthwhile to investigate the magnitude and robustness of such an effect in various empirical settings. Simulation here functions as an explorative tool to search for issues that are promising for empirical study. An example would be the empirical study of the *imitation-effect* that has been discussed in Chapter 7.

The other way around, questions emerging from empirical research can sometimes be placed on the agenda of simulation research. For example, often effects have been found in empirical studies, which are hard to explain unambiguously because of the behavioural complexities of interacting people. An example would be the manifestation of aggression in large crowds, which has been documented quite well, but without systematically exploring the underlying behavioural dynamics. In such cases simulation models may be developed to unravel the behavioural dynamics underlying such effects, providing suggestions for further empirical study. Simulation research and empirical study can thus be considered as tools that can be mutually stimulating in exploring behavioural dynamics.

Regarding experimental research, the integrated use of empirical studies and simulation studies is feasible because empirical experiments are replicable, and thus the simulation results can be validated against real world data using correlational techniques such as regression analysis. Whereas in this dissertation no empirical work has been done to validate the behavioural dynamics that have been demonstrated especially in Chapter 7 and 8, it is imaginable and strongly recommended that such work be done.

The consumat approach also allows for experimentation with behavioural dynamics that are less susceptible to empirical study. As was concluded in Chapter 2, on the limitations of experimental games research, many real-world commons dilemmas involve longer time-series, more people involved, and more serious outcomes than can be feasibly captured in empirical research. Moreover, as concluded in Chapter 1, there is a demand for incorporating behavioural dynamics in integrated ecological-economic models. Empirical research reduces real-world systems to an extent that replication of experimental findings is possible. This amounts to using the strict falsification principle of Popper (1963), to test hypotheses concerning behavioural effects. Modelling the dynamics of real-world systems, such as an ecological-economic system, confronts the researcher with a complex system with corresponding varied behaviours. The complexity of a real-world system implies that very different courses of development can originate from the same starting point, making it impossible to formulate confident predictions about system developments. This uncertainty bears a fundamental character, as the Laplacian universe has ceased to exist (see Chapter 2 on metaphors as modelling paradigms). As a consequence, the validation of the outcomes of model runs against historical data is of limited value because these data could well have been very different. This implies that a badly formalised model may yield results that mirror empirical data, whereas a conscientiously formalised model may yield outcomes that differ from empirical data. This implies that Popper's (1963) falsification principle of is less suitable for validating models of more complex systems. The replication of real-world time-series of some complex system thus may reflect only a superficial validity.

The question now becomes: "how can models of complex systems be validated if empirical replication is not conclusive?". The bedrock of this validation resides in the capacity of a model to convince peers in the scientific community that the model adequately captures the processes that determine real-world developments. This validation does not require an empirical replication of the outcomes, but it involves questions about the extent to which the model constitutes an unificational metaphor (see Chapter 3 on modelling as a metaphor). This holds that researchers must search for agreement on the conviction that the same processes guide the developments in the real world and in the model. Van Dijkum and Van Kuijk (1999, p. 15) state that validation procedures should be aimed at both the level of theory and the level of facts (outcomes).

At the level of theory, the validation procedure should be aimed at hypotheses that can be derived from the theoretical basis of the model and the associated structure of the relations between the variables included in the model. The questions that appear to be relevant in determining this theoretical validity are (based on Dijkum and Van Kuijk (1999, p. 15):

- Are all the variables relevant for the system being modelled included in the model?
- Are the relevant feedback-loops of the real-world system included in the model?
- Are the feedback-loops that are included in the model relevant, and do they actually exist in the real-world system being modelled?
- Do the (difference) equations and rules of the model make sense?
- Are the parameters used in the equations and rules meaningful, and do they relate to values that have been empirically observed in the real-world system?

At the level of outcomes, the validation procedure should be aimed at questioning the realism of the observed behaviour (outcomes) of the model. The relevant questions here are:

- Is the sequence of developments of a real-world system being replicated in the model outcomes?
- Does the model yield outcomes (e.g., dynamical processes) that help to understand the real-world system and that can be recognised in the real-world system?
- Is the model free from anomalies such that outcomes are not too extreme to be imaginable to happen in the real-world system?
- Is the model 'sparse' in the sense that all variables and feedback-loops are necessary to produce the dynamics that are typical for the real-world system?
- Do changes of critical model parameters (e.g., simulated policy measures) result in changing outcomes that can be related to corresponding changes in the real-world system?
- Are processes of change (e.g., societal transitions) relatively insensitive to small plausible changes of parameter values of the model variables? Here the reader must bear in mind that we focus on processes rather than outcomes, as the same process may lead to very different outcomes, as the lock-in dynamics (Chapter 8) demonstrate.

Whereas the criteria mentioned above are not 'hard' in the sense that they are conclusive, the rules constituting our consumat (cf. Especially Chapter 6) appear to meet these criteria better than 'rational-actor' agents and agent rules that are currently being used in game theory. This is not to say that the consumat approach passes all the above criteria. For example, it can be seriously questioned if all the variables relevant for human behaviour are included in the consumat model (e.g., explicit group norms and values have been omitted) and if the selected values of 'minimal level of need satisfaction' and 'uncertainty tolerance' make sense. Within the context of these criteria, the reader may conclude that the consumat approach is still in its childhood, and that much work has to be done to raise it to the status of a mature scientific tool. The criteria mentioned above therefore, are also valuable in setting a research agenda for the further development of the consumat approach.

The simulation experiments presented in this monograph demonstrate that validation can be based on different approaches simultaneously. In a series of simple simulation experiments it is possible to test and develop behavioural rules. Here, the replication of empirical (experimental) results serves as a guiding principle in the development of consumat rules. Next, applying these consumat rules in more complex simulation models requires that a full model is validated on a more theoretical and outcome-oriented basis. This combination has been used here to validate the consumat approach, and despite the fact that the empirical basis for replicative validity was weak, a first indication of the validity of the consumat approach has been found, because the simulated effects appear to be in accordance with empirical phenomena.

The overall conclusion is that the more realistic a model is, the more complex it will be, the more unpredictably and opaquely the model will behave, and the harder it will be to validate the model empirically. The best procedure is to work on various fronts simultaneously; validating parts of the model using empirical studies, and applying the validated model parts in more complex models.

Possible applications of the consumat approach

The consumat approach appears to be applicable to three main issues, namely: (1) the study of fundamental behavioural dynamics in itself, (2) integrated modelling of complex systems involving human behaviour, and (3) studying how policy makers manage complex systems that involve human behaviour.

Fundamental behavioural dynamics

Regarding fundamental behavioural dynamics, the consumat approach appears to be a promising tool to be used in combination with empirical studies. Whenever an empirically established effect or process is affected by personal factors, and the behaviour of people is highly susceptible to what other people do, it may be very difficult to attribute an observed effect to a certain combination of variables. Especially where process-effects emerge from interactions between individual and group factors (e.g., uncertainty and network-size), the consumat approach may be suitable for studying underlying behavioural dynamics. The consumat approach allows one to control for all the unwanted variance, and to check under what precise conditions an effect may occur and how the dynamics evolve over time. A subsequent empirical study may be performed to validate the results of the simulation. Simulations thus help to identify effects that are hard to perceive in reality, but which may play important roles nevertheless.

Several fundamental issues that involve behavioural dynamics can be thought of for applying the consumat approach. An interesting issue on which some preliminary experiments have been done is the introduction of social value-orientations, such as individualism, cooperativeness and competition (see Chapter 2 on individual factors), in the resource dilemma described in Chapter 7. These social value orientations reflect the preferences people have for the distribution of outcomes for themselves in relation to the outcomes for an interdependent other (McClintock, 1978). Simulation experiments can be designed to study how the management of a common resource develops when social value-orientations are distributed differently over a given population of consumats. A further perspective would be to allow the consumats to form networks on the basis of mutual cooperation. This would allow for formalising an institutional level with associated group norms and values in the consumat approach.

A second possible application is to try to formalise the consumat approach for ‘give-some’ games. Whereas the experiments presented in Chapter 7 and 9 involve consumats that are harvesting from a collective resource, thus reflecting a ‘take-some’ game, in a ‘give-some’ game the decision concerns the level of individual contribution to a public good. Practical examples of such ‘give-some’ issues are tax-paying, recycling behaviour (contribution of effort) and volunteering as a blood donor. Whereas the basic structure of these situations mirrors ‘take-some’ games, the psychological context is quite different. It would be worthwhile to test if these differences in some way can be replicated in simulation studies employing the consumat approach.

A third issue is the modelling of different markets in relation to dominating needs and social processes. Some preliminary results indicate that very different markets may emerge

from different settings of 'level of need-satisfaction' and 'uncertainty tolerance'. These results are interpretable in terms of, e.g., locked-in markets, fashion markets and competitive markets. Here, much work has to be done to formalise product development and marketing strategies that could be followed in introducing new products on a consumer market.

The dynamics of large crowds is a fourth issue that appears to be accessible for research using the consumat approach. Although this issue marked the onset of social psychology, in later years the attention for it has decreased because of the difficulty in performing realistic experiments on large crowds. However, several authors have developed theories explaining various phenomena manifested in large crowds. According to several modern authors (e.g. Reicher; 1987; McPhail, 1991), a main problem of these studies is that the process is studied from the macro-level, for example postulating a 'group-spirit'. However, the dynamics of behaviour in crowds have important determinants at the individual level (and vice versa). It would therefore be worthwhile to study the micro-macro dynamics in order to understand the relevant phenomena. Such an approach would not only sharpen our view of the micro-level determinants of crowd behaviour, it would also offer a more dynamical perspective to help us interpreting empirical data on crowd behaviour.

Integrated modelling of complex systems

To study processes of environmental degradation, and to assess how policy strategies may affect these processes, several integrated models have been and are being developed (see Chapter 1). Many processes of environmental degradation involve human behaviours. As was stated in Chapter 1, up to now, however, integrated models exclude many behavioural processes relevant for understanding the driving factors behind environmental degradation. Because human behaviour is being modelled in a rather implicit manner, these models also do not offer indicators for assessing social issues that are related to environmental degradation, such as quality-of-life, poverty and income distribution. Here, the consumat approach seems to offer points of application, as it includes behavioural processes and indicators for integrated assessment. However, as stated before, the formalisation of the consumat approach for a real-world issue is usually laborious without guaranteeing sufficient transparency of outcomes. Therefore, the consumat approach can also be used as a toolbox for introducing relatively simple behavioural dynamics into integrated models. In this way, the consumat approach can be used to implement, e.g., habitual behaviour, or to model the spreading of technological innovation via social processes. An example of this use of the consumat approach is the inclusion of habitual behaviour in modelling the choice behaviour of farmers in Rangelands (Janssen, Walker, Langridge and Abel, in press)

Regarding some well-defined issues the researcher's goal may be to study the behavioural dynamics that underlie a problem, and to explore which policy measures may be successful in changing relevant behaviours. In such cases it is recommended to formalise the full consumat approach, at least with respect to the cognitive processes and the most important human needs involved. For example, for the issue of domestic energy consumption (see, e.g., Giovanni and Baranzini, 1997; Jager, Janssen and Vlek, 2000), many empirical data are available, which are often analysed with the statistical technique of regression analysis to identify stable behaviour-determining factors. Regression analysis is also used to develop projections of possible scenarios of future household behaviours. On the basis of scenarios it

is possible to forecast the effect of changes in major behaviour-determining factors on consumption volumes, thereby identifying possible unfavourable trends. These scenarios can thus be used to investigate possible future situations, and thus can be regarded as some sort of guiding map that sets targets for the future of household consumption and attends us on possible futures that should be avoided.

However, knowledge concerning the preferred direction of developments does not automatically yield knowledge about the process of getting there. This is because household energy consumption is part of a complex dynamic system, where consumers develop preferences for certain appliances (e.g., giant refrigerators, jet-stream baths, waterbeds) and their use, partly on the basis of what other people in their environment do. This complexity is further enhanced because of the relation between the household consumption system and various other systems, such as the production system, the political system and the physical environment. Acknowledging this complex dynamic character of household energy use implies that policy making has to be focussed more strongly on understanding the total dynamics incorporating the household system. To explore the dynamics of this system, it would be worthwhile to formalise the various cognitive processes into a model of household energy use. On the basis of a more generic understanding of the household system dynamics it is possible to diagnose unforeseen and unwanted developments in an early stage, and to develop appropriate policy measures.

Managing complex systems involving human behaviour

Policy makers usually have a certain representation of the important dynamics of the system they are managing, and policy measures are developed on the basis of this representation. Often, the latter is partly constructed on the basis of scenarios and predictions that have been formulated on the basis of multiple regression models. For example, developments in consumption volumes are frequently being predicted using such models, and the effects of policy measures estimated. However, policy domains in which consumer behaviour plays an important role are usually so complex that it is hard to acquire a representation of the relevant system. Moreover, scenarios and predictions based on regression models usually bear an indicative character, and therefore actual developments may take a different or even a contradictory course. An incomplete or incorrect system representation may lead to unexpected and often unwanted outcomes of policy measures, fostering beliefs such as “nothing can be done to manage consumer behaviour” or “the price-mechanism is the only effective basis for changing consumer behaviour”. Effects like this have been found in experiments where decision-makers had to manage an artificial system, of which the underlying dynamics were only known to the researchers (e.g., Strohschneider, 1991, 1994a; 1994b; Brehmer and Dörner, 1993).

The consumat approach may be used as a tool to let policy makers experience plausible dynamics of consumer behaviour, and to help them in developing a more dynamical perspective on behavioural change. For this, it would be worthwhile to develop a relatively simple model that clearly demonstrates effects of habitual behaviour, the trickling down of new behaviour, and the occurrence of herd behaviour, and that allows for experimentation with various policy measures to study the effects on behavioural dynamics.

Directions for further research

As has been discussed in the sections above, the consumat approach provides tools that can be applied to various substantive issues. However, before starting to run, it is wise to learn to walk properly first, and therefore two important steps for a possible fruitful application of the consumat approach are suggested.

First, in order to increase our grip on the processes that evolve in non-deterministic simulations, it is necessary to develop procedures for statistical analysis of simulation runs. Referring to the non-deterministic resource experiments of Chapter 7, this implies the manipulation of large data sets. One simulation run yields data on several variables (e.g., resource size, behavioural process, levels of need satisfaction) for two or more agents for every time-step of the simulation. Using large numbers of experimental conditions in more complex simulation designs yields very large data sets (megabytes) that cannot be analysed in a straightforward manner by the current statistical software for personal computers. Especially when effects are being studied that require a large number of consumats, e.g., the effect of heterogeneity in consumat populations, the resulting data sets will be very large. To test certain hypotheses it would be possible to develop macro-level indicators, which in turn can be analysed using standard statistical software. For example, the Gini-index, which has been introduced in Chapter 9, provides a measure for the skewness of consumats' income distribution. On the basis of this Gini-index it should be possible to develop similar indicators for a distribution of the level of need satisfaction. Performing a relatively simple calculation on the original data set, it should be possible to derive a significantly smaller data set containing macro-level variables. Such a file would be more accessible for analysis using standard statistical software.

Second, an important step refers to the validation of the process-effects that have been identified in Chapter 7 on the management of a simple common resource. Recall that these effects are the *imitation-effect*, the *optimism-effect* and the *adaptation-effect* (see Chapter 7). It is proposed to test if these process-effects can be reproduced in laboratory experiments with human subjects. An essential requirement for such experiments is that valid data are obtained regarding the cognitive process the subjects actually engage in. One obvious method to obtain such data is to measure cognitive effort on a physiological level, e.g., using an E.E.C. Another possible method is to monitor how people retrieve relevant information by means of a computer display. By allowing subjects at each time-step to retrieve information on the state of the resource (environmental information) and on the past harvesting behaviour of other subjects (social information), the cognitive process could be monitored well. Such an experimental setting is suitable for testing which factors affect the quantity and type of information (environmental and/or social) the subjects retrieve. Several hypotheses can be tested, such as that when the subjects can monitor each other's behaviour (allowing the subjects to engage in social processing) and are quickly satisfied (allowing to engage in automated processing) an increase in the stochastic part (unpredictability) of a resource-growth function will elicit an imitation-effect. If these and other simulated effects are reproduced in representative experiments with real people, simulation research may gain a broader acceptance in mainstream social psychology too.

Summary

Introduction (Chapter 1)

Human existence cannot be separated from the natural environment humans live in. People are constantly interacting with their environment to maintain and improve their living conditions. This interaction with natural systems supports the existence and viability of societies and cultures. However, often people consume natural resources at a rate that endangers their existence and viability on the long run. Whereas this led to societies collapsing in the past (e.g., Ponting, 1993), during the last decades awareness has grown that the environmental impacts of our current socio-economic system not only affect the regional or national level, but also affect the world as a whole. These global changes, such as global warming, the thinning of the stratospheric ozone layer and large-scale deforestation, seriously jeopardise basic existential conditions. The critical question in understanding environmental problems is why many people so frequently over-exploit and damage natural resources, thereby endangering their own (future) living conditions, whereas other people use the same type of natural resources with moderation to preserve them. The commons dilemma is excellently suited for studying the behavioural factors and processes that determine when and why people tend to overexploit common resources, or exploit them in a sustainable manner. This monograph is aimed at presenting an integrative perspective on these factors and processes. To do so, we developed a multi-theoretical meta-model of behaviour. This meta-model will be formalised in a computer simulation model, which provides a tool to study processes of resource use and consumption.

The commons dilemma (Chapter 2)

Many studies in the commons dilemma paradigm have been performed to study the factors that affect people's harvesting behaviour from a collective resource. Chapter 2 discusses the commons dilemma paradigm, and states that four dilemmas can be recognised in the environmental commons dilemma. First, the everyday *benefit-risk dilemma* relates the benefits of behaviour to the associated risks. Second, the *temporal dilemma* relates positive outcomes now to possible negative outcomes in the future. Third, the *spatial dilemma* relates local outcomes to more general outcomes, such as the quality of the seas and forest areas. Fourth, the *social dilemma* relates personal outcomes to outcomes for the collective. Next, an inventory is provided of the factors at the group and individual level that have experimentally been found to affect harvesting behaviour, such as uncertainty, number of people involved and social norms. However, experimental research is often limited in comparison to real commons dilemmas because of the limited time-scale of experiments (typically less than an hour), the small number of people involved and the insignificance of the experimental outcomes for the daily lives of the subjects. Computer simulation models offer a tool to overcome these limitations.

A methodology of modelling (Chapter 3)

Chapter 3 is focussed on the methodologies used in scientific simulation models. First, attention is given to the roles metaphors play in scientific modelling of natural systems, and their applicability. For example, to what extent is an equation-based model of a natural system valid, and for which purposes may it be used? Next, the modelling paradigms

associated to certain metaphors are shortly presented. These paradigms involve multiple regression models, stochastic simulation models, rational-actor optimisation, system dynamics and agent-based models. All mathematical models share a general biased starting point by assuming that the world is not only knowable by a rational process of observation and reflection, but is also assumed to be controllable. This holds in different degrees for various modelling approaches. For example, multiple regression models are assuming a much larger controllability than e.g. models of adaptive systems using genetic algorithms. Because these differences stem from different (implicit) assumptions of how the real world system works, these various modelling approaches seem to fit the concept of paradigm. Because our ‘consumat approach’ entails an agent-based model, a separate section is devoted to the conceptual tools used in this modelling paradigm. These tools involve genetic algorithms, cellular automata and artificial intelligence. The chapter concludes with a section on the application of models.

Simulation models in the social sciences (Chapter 4)

Chapter 4 provides an overview of historic developments and current issues in the use of simulation models in the social sciences. Regarding the commons dilemma, two main directions can be distinguished in the application of simulation models. First, several researchers have tried to increase the realism of natural resource systems by developing computer simulations of complex natural systems (e.g., fish-stocks). Such simulations provide a tool to study the behaviour of people in more realistic yet controllable situations, thereby compressing long-term processes into short-term experimental simulation sessions. Second, several researchers have developed simulations of behaviour itself, formalising agents via algorithms that represent certain decision processes. This approach allows for testing different algorithms against each other, and to evaluate these in terms of the sustainability of the resulting behaviour. Moreover, this approach in principle allows for experimentation with far-reaching outcomes, such as famines when a food resource is being over-harvested, and the ‘death’ of unsuccessful agents.

However, while many different behavioural factors and processes guide the harvesting behaviour of real people, such as human needs, abilities, habitual behaviour and social imitation, it appears that the ‘psychological lay-out’ of agent rules is usually quite poor, or based on only a single theory of behaviour. To improve the ‘behavioural richness’ of simulation models, we need a multi-theoretical meta-model of human behaviour as a guiding framework for the development of agent rules.

A conceptual meta-model of human behaviour (Chapter 5)

The consumat approach is based on a conceptual meta-model that integrates various theories that are relevant for understanding consumer behaviour. This model is graphically depicted in Figure 1. As can be seen in Figure 1, the consumat model consists of different parts. On the left side the macro-level driving factors of consumer behaviour are represented. These macro-level factors involve the natural environment, (involving natural resources), and the human environment, which involves technology, economy, demography, institutions and culture.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the conceptual meta-model of behaviour

On the right side of Figure 1 the micro-level of the individual consumer is modelled. The driving factors of consumer behaviour reside in the available opportunities for consumption, the actor's abilities, needs, level of need satisfaction and uncertainty, and the opportunity consumption of similar others. These driving forces determine which cognitive processing type the consumer will engage in. When an actor is not satisfied but certain, he/she is most likely to engage in (individually reasoned) *deliberation* so as to find more satisfying and feasible consumption opportunities. When the actor is not satisfied and uncertain, he/she is most likely to engage in (socially reasoned) *social comparison*, elaborating on the possible outcomes of imitating the consumptive behaviour of other actors with about the same abilities. When an actor is satisfied and certain, he/she will simply (individually automated) *repeat* the previous behaviour. Frequent repetition is the cognitive basis of habitual behaviour. Finally, when an actor is satisfied but uncertain, he/she will be most likely to (socially automated) *imitate* the behaviour of other actors with about the same abilities. Under cognitive processing the actor uses the information available in his/her mental map (memory). Only when the actor engages in reasoned processing (deliberation or social comparison), the actor will store new information in his/her mental map. Figure 1 also reflects that the opportunity consumption following from the cognitive process is aggregated across all actors and affects the macro-level driving factors of behaviour.

Policy measures aimed at changing consumptive behaviour are affecting the driving factors of behaviour either at the macro-level (e.g., economic climate) or at the micro-level (e.g., personal abilities). The conceptual model appears to be suitable to understand the principles behind dynamical processes of consumption such as herd behaviour and habit formation.

Formalising the conceptual model (Chapter 6)

This chapter first deals with the level of detail that is required in the agent rules. The agent rules must be simple enough for the results of simulation runs to be clearly interpretable, but not so simple that mundane realism is lost.

The subsequent parts of the chapter describe how various agent rules are formalised on the basis of the conceptual model of Chapter 5. The agents are called ‘consumats’, and formalisation of several interacting consumats yields a multi-agent simulation model.

The driving forces at the collective (macro-) and the individual (micro-) level determine the environmental setting for consumat behaviour. The collective level refers to the world consumats are living in. The individual level refers to the consumats themselves, which are equipped with various needs that may be more or less satisfied, and which have various abilities for consumption. Consumats are confronted with different opportunities, which, when consumed, may contribute to their level of need satisfaction. Furthermore, consumats have a certain degree of uncertainty, depending on the difference between expected and actual outcomes of their behaviour.

Consumats may engage in different cognitive processes while deciding how to behave, depending on their level of need satisfaction and their degree of uncertainty (cf. Chapter 5). Consumats having a low level of need satisfaction and a low degree of uncertainty are assumed to *deliberate*, that is: to determine the consequences of all possible decisions given a fixed time-horizon, in order to maximise their level of need satisfaction. Consumats having a low level of need satisfaction and a high degree of uncertainty are assumed to engage in *social comparison*. This implies comparison of their own previous behaviour with the previous behaviour of consumats having about similar abilities, and selecting the behaviour yielding a maximal level of need satisfaction. When consumats have a high level of need satisfaction, but are also highly uncertain, they will *imitate* the behaviour of other similar consumats. Finally, consumats having a high level of need satisfaction and a low level of uncertainty simply *repeat* their previous behaviour.

A mental map is formalised which serves as a memory to store information on abilities and opportunities, and on characteristics of other agents. Only when consumats engage in reasoned behaviour (deliberation and social comparison) they will update the information in their mental map. Otherwise they will stick to the (possibly outdated) information they obtained in the past.

After consumption of opportunities, the consumat will obtain a new level of need satisfaction and uncertainty, which affect its cognitive processing during the next time step. Moreover, consumption (of the self and other consumats) may cause changes in personal abilities, available opportunities and the world they ‘live’ in, which will affect consumption in succeeding time steps.

Consumats in a commons dilemma (Chapter 7)

In a first series of experiments we investigate how consumats perform in a simple resource management task (Jager, Janssen & Vlek, 1999). We are particularly interested in the effects of uncertainty and satisfaction on the harvesting behaviour of simulated agents. Existing research with real subjects managing a resource revealed that an increase in uncertainty caused people to increase their harvesting (Wit & Wilke, 1998; Hine & Gifford, 1996; Rapoport et al., 1992; Messick et al., 1988).

The simulation experiments reveal three different effects of uncertainty: the *optimism-effect*, the *imitation-effect* and the *adaptation-effect*, respectively. The *optimism-effect* holds that deliberating consumats, when confronted with a positive fluctuation in the resource growth, will have too optimistic expectations regarding the future resource size, and hence engage in over-harvesting. This over-harvesting yields high outcomes (on the short run), and as a consequence the consumats may become satisfied and engage in repetition (over-harvesting habit), without perceiving a possible future depletion.

The *imitation-effect* implies that consumats, when uncertain and satisfied, are likely to imitate the behaviour of other consumats, even when this behaviour is less optimal than one's own previous behaviour. The *adaptation-effect* holds that when consumats engage in social processing, they are considering the behaviour of other consumats and (when engaging in social comparison) their own previous behaviour, and hence they do not discover new opportunities for behaviour. As a consequence, the consumats are not capable of adapting their behaviour to changing circumstances, such as a serious depletion of the resource. These three effects are all process-effects, that is, they describe the process that leads towards a certain outcome.

The minimal level of need satisfaction of a consumat appears to be an important behaviour-determining factor. If the actual level of need satisfaction drops below the critical level, the consumats starts processing in a reasoned manner. Consequently, a consumat with a high aspiration level is hard to satisfy and thus will frequently engage in reasoned processing. Consumats engaging more often in reasoned processing reach a more sustainable use in case of a relatively accessible resource. This yields the somewhat contradictory effect that consumats which are the most easily to satisfy, are also the ones that are most likely to deplete a resource, due to their easy engagement in an over-harvesting habit. For a less accessible resource the effect turns around, showing that the tendency of easy-to-satisfy consumats to engage in habitual behaviour causes them to develop an under-harvesting habit. We conclude that a higher aspiration level for need satisfaction results in more frequent reasoned behaviour, thereby decreasing the likelihood of over-harvesting *and* of under-harvesting. These experiments demonstrate that the consumat approach is capable of replicating existing empirical effects, and adding to the explanation of these effects.

The lock-in of consumption patterns (Chapter 8)

Lock-in denotes a phenomenon of dominating technologies or consumer goods in a certain market. Such lock-ins of consumptive patterns cannot always be explained by superior characteristics of the good or technology in question. Previous (economic) studies mainly used probabilistic models to study lock-in effects. We experimented with the consumats to identify relevant processes of lock-in dynamics of consumption patterns. In these experiments, the consumats were equipped with four different needs: identity, personal taste, leisure and subsistence, respectively. Identity is satisfied better if more neighbouring consumats consume the same product. Personal taste implies that consumats can have their own initial preference for a product. Leisure implies that the cheaper the product becomes, the more time remains available for leisure. The price of a product depends on its market share; the more a product is sold, the cheaper it becomes due to learning-by-doing in the production process. Subsistence is related to the level of pollution associated with the products. Important to realise is that not only the product

characteristics affect the need-satisfying capacity of a product, but also whether other consumats consume the product.

In the simulation experiment nine hundred consumats in a checkerboard space of 30 times 30 cells are confronted with two similar products. The product choice of a particular consumat is visualised by the colour of the cell. At the start of the simulation, consumption is random, thus a scattered pattern can be observed in the checkerboard. However, after some time a certain pattern emerges, demonstrating that the consumats are changing their behaviour. Two types of lock-in are observed, namely, a local lock-in and a global lock-in. The local lock-in implies that groups of consumats emerge that consume the same product. Whereas the market-share of both products may remain the same, the spatial distribution may change drastically. This local lock-in is more likely to occur when consumats' need for identity plays an important role.

The global lock-in relates to price effects and occurs only if individual preferences are not significantly weighted during cognitive processing. In this case we observe that one of the two products will conquer a market-share of 100%. These experiments demonstrate that the consumat-approach is fruitful for exploring the behavioural dynamics that underlie processes of product lock-in.

Formalising the consumat in an ecological-economic model (Chapter 9)

Many ecological-economic models formalise consumer behaviour following the rational-actor approach towards optimisation. We are interested in how the introduction of the behavioural consumat rules may affect the behaviour of a group of agents managing a micro-world. Therefore we place the consumats in an 'micro-world' called "Lakeland" (De Greef & De Vries, 1991). Lakeland consists of two natural resources: a fish-stock in a lake and a gold mine. The lake is being modelled as a simple ecological system of fish and shrimps. We place 16 consumats in Lakeland, and these consumats catch fish from the lake to supply their need for food. Moreover, they may also export fish, and the associated income can be spent on assets such as luxury goods. Import of fish is also allowed. If the gold mine is assumed to be open, consumats may also dig for gold. The money earned by mining can be spent on (imported) fish and on luxurious assets. The pollution caused by mining is reducing the carrying capacity of the lake for the fish and shrimp populations. The consumats have to decide on how they allocate their time on leisure, fishing and mining. They are equipped with certain abilities for fishing and mining, and they want to satisfy their four needs: leisure, identity, subsistence and personal taste. We assume that the satisfaction of the leisure-need relates to the share of the time spent on leisure. The identity-need is satisfied by the relative amount of money the consumat owns in comparison to consumats with similar abilities. The subsistence-need relates to the consumption of food. Personal taste is assumed to be related to the absolute amount of money the consumat owns, which can be spent on whatever assets the consumat prefers.

Three important results were found, respectively pointing at the relevance of using a multi-agent simulation approach in modelling behaviour, the importance of different behavioural strategies (repetition, deliberation, social-comparison and imitation), and the role of agent diversity.

First of all, it appeared that 16 consumats that were exclusively engaging in deliberation (*homo economicus*), were not capable of using the fish-stock in a sustainable manner, because of the social dilemma trap. Each individual consumat, having only a marginal effect on the total fish-stock, 'thinks' that the depletion of the resource is

inevitable because it assumes that the other consumats do not change their behaviour. Consequently, all consumats try to maximise their outcomes, catching what they can for as long as there is still fish. This situation resembles a sort of a self-fulfilling prophecy, as the fish-stock depletes because the consumats expect it to deplete.

Using a consumat that could employ all four behavioural strategies (*homo psychologicus*) introduced new behavioural dynamics in the simulation model, such as habitual behaviour and imitation effects. This caused, for example, that the transition from a fishing to a mining society followed a smooth path and caused the consumats to spend more time mining (causing pollution) than in case of the *homo economicus*.

Finally, it appeared that introducing diversity in the consumats by equipping them with different fishing and mining abilities caused a further smoothening of the transition towards a mining society. In comparison to the situation where all consumats had equal abilities, we observed that after the transition for the *homo psychologicus* the time spent fishing rose, whereas for the *homo economicus* the time spent fishing and mining fell. Apparently much more research is needed to investigate how diversity in consumer abilities may affect the management of natural resources.

The current experiments show that it is possible and fruitful to introduce psychological models into ecological-economic models, thereby including relevant behavioural dynamics into ecological economic models.

The general applicability of the consumat approach for behaviour simulation (Chapter 10)

The concluding chapter first discusses the advantages and disadvantages of the consumat approach. The advantages reside in the multi-theoretical perspective on behaviour and behaviour change, which allows incorporating more realistic dynamics in simulation-based research. The disadvantages reside in the fact that a formalisation of the consumat approach for a specific (empirical) domain may require a lot of research effort, and results are difficult to validate against empirical data.

A prospect is sketched for the validation of simulation research employing the consumat approach. Here it is also suggested that empirical and simulation research should be used conjointly in exploring research questions regarding behavioural dynamics.

We finally discuss some possible applications of the consumat approach. Three main issues of possible application are distinguished. First, the study of fundamental behavioural dynamics is proposed, such as social value orientations in resource dilemmas, behaviour in 'give-some' dilemmas and market dynamics. Second, it is proposed to further experiment with simulated human behaviour in integrated models of complex systems. This would also allow to formalise 'quality-of-life' in integrated models, and to diagnose relevant behavioural dynamics of well-defined issues. Third, the consumat approach may be used as a tool to study how policy makers manage complex systems that involve human behaviour. For example, it would be worthwhile to develop a relatively simple model that clearly demonstrates effects of habitual behaviour, the trickling down of new types of behaviour, and the occurrence of herd behaviour. Such a model would allow both to study and to train policy makers' decision making regarding strategies to change consumer behaviours.

Samenvatting

Introductie (Hoofdstuk 1)

Voor zijn overleven en voor de verbetering van zijn levensomstandigheden is de mens afhankelijk van zijn natuurlijke omgeving. Omgekeerd geldt dat de natuurlijke omgeving deels afhankelijk is van de manier waarop mensen er omgaan. Als mensen in een gunstige omgeving leven, en de natuurlijke rijkdommen benutten, kunnen levensvatbare en krachtige maatschappijen ontstaan. Vaak belasten mensen echter hun omgeving dusdanig dat hun bestaanszekerheid op de lange termijn in gevaar komt. In de geschiedenis van de mensheid heeft dat (mede) geleid tot de neergang van verschillende hoogstaande culturen, zoals bijvoorbeeld de Mesopotamische en de Mayas (Ponting, 1993).

De laatste decennia is duidelijk geworden dat ons huidige sociaal-economische systeem niet alleen regionale of nationale milieueffecten heeft, maar ook milieueffecten op mondiaal niveau. Deze mondiale veranderingen, zoals klimaatverandering, verdunning van de ozonlaag en grootschalige ontbossing, vormen (op termijn) een bedreiging van onze bestaanszekerheid.

De kernvraag inzake milieuproblemen is: “Waarom worden natuurlijke hulpbronnen zo vaak aangetast en overbelast, terwijl in andere situaties zulke hulpbronnen wél op een duurzame manier worden gebruikt?”. Het *commons dilemma* is een theoretisch model dat goede aanknopingspunten biedt voor het verhelderen van de factoren en processen in ons gedrag, waarmee deze vraag kan worden beantwoord. In dit proefschrift wordt aan de hand van een multi-theoretisch gedragsmodel een overzicht gegeven van die factoren en processen. Dit gedragsmodel wordt vervolgens geformaliseerd in een computerprogramma, dat een stuk gereedschap vormt om belangrijke processen bij het menselijk gebruik van natuurlijke bronnen beter te leren begrijpen.

Het ‘commons dilemma’ (Hoofdstuk 2)

Veel onderzoek omtrent het *commons dilemma* is gericht op factoren die van invloed zijn op de hoeveelheid die mensen oogsten uit een gezamenlijke hulpbron, zoals bijvoorbeeld een visstand. In hoofdstuk 2 wordt dit *commons dilemma* besproken, waarbij wordt vastgesteld dat er eigenlijk vier typen dilemma's in te onderscheiden zijn. In de eerste plaats het ‘voordelen-risico dilemma’, waarbij de voordelen van bepaald gedrag worden afgewogen tegen de daaraan verbonden risico's. Ten tweede het ‘temporele dilemma’, waarbij de mogelijke uitkomsten in het heden worden afgewogen tegen mogelijke uitkomsten in de toekomst. In de derde plaats het ‘ruimtelijke dilemma’, waarbij lokale uitkomsten (hier) moeten worden afgewogen tegen meer verspreide uitkomsten voor een groter gebied. Ten vierde het ‘sociale dilemma’, waarin de afweging tussen eigenbelangen en gezamenlijke belangen wordt gemaakt.

Na de bespreking van deze vier dilemma's wordt een overzicht gegeven van de experimenteel gevonden factoren die van invloed zijn op ‘oogstgedrag’. Voorbeelden zijn: onzekerheid over wat anderen doen, het aantal betrokkenen in een dilemmasituatie en heersende sociale normen. In vergelijking tot echte dilemma's is laboratoriumonderzoek meestal beperkt omdat de experimenten kort duren, het gedrag van slechts kleine groepjes wordt bestudeerd, en het gedrag van de experimentele

proefpersonen niet echt belangrijke consequenties heeft voor hun dagelijkse leven. In computersimulaties spelen zulke beperkingen geen rol, waardoor simulatiemodellen mogelijk geschikter zijn om de dynamiek van echte commons dilemma's experimenteel te bestuderen.

Methodologie voor modelleren (Hoofdstuk 3)

In Hoofdstuk 3 wordt ingegaan op de methodologie van (sociaal) wetenschappelijk modelleren. Eerst wordt ingegaan op de rol die metaforen spelen bij het wetenschappelijk modelleren van natuurlijke systemen, en wat dat betekent voor de bruikbaarheid van modellen. Bijvoorbeeld, hoe realistisch is een op wiskundige vergelijkingen gebaseerd model van een visstand, en voor welke doeleinden kan zo'n model gebruikt worden? Daarna wordt een aantal methoden van sociaal-wetenschappelijk modelleren besproken die gebaseerd zijn op verschillende metaforen. Deze methoden zijn multiple-regressiemodellen, stochastische simulatiemodellen, *rational actor*-optimalisatie, systeem-dynamica en *multi-agent* modellen.

Alle wiskundige modellen gaan er in principe vanuit dat verschillende processen in natuurlijke (sociale) systemen niet alleen zijn vast te stellen, maar ook bestuurbaar zijn. Deze assumptie geldt voor de verschillende modelleermethoden in verschillende mate. Multiple-regressiemodellen gaan bijvoorbeeld uit van een veel grotere bestuurbaarheid dan op groeiprocessen gebaseerde modellen van adaptieve systemen. Omdat deze verschillen voortvloeien uit verschillende aannames over de werkingsprincipes van natuurlijke systemen, kunnen de verschillende modelleermethoden worden beschouwd als wetenschappelijke paradigma's.

Omdat onze 'consumat'-benadering gebaseerd is op een *multi-agent* benadering wordt in dit hoofdstuk extra aandacht besteedt aan de technieken binnen dit laatste paradigma. Deze technieken zijn genetische algoritmen, cellulaire automaten en kunstmatige intelligentie. Hoofdstuk 3 besluit met een discussie over de toepasbaarheid van modellen.

Simulatiemodellen in de sociale wetenschappen (Hoofdstuk 4)

Hoofdstuk 4 geeft een overzicht van de geschiedenis en tegenwoordige toepassingen van simulatiemodellen in de sociale wetenschappen. Binnen het *commons dilemma* kunnen we twee hoofdtypen van simulatiemodellen onderscheiden. In de eerste plaats hebben veel onderzoekers geprobeerd om de betreffende hulpbron realistischer te maken, waardoor mensen zich realistischer kunnen gaan gedragen. Daartoe zijn verschillende simulatiemodellen van natuurlijke hulpbronnen (o.a. visstand) ontwikkeld. Zulke simulatiemodellen zijn geschikt om mensen meer realistische maar toch experimenteel controleerbare situaties aan te bieden, waarbij langdurige natuurlijke processen in korte tijd kunnen worden nagespeeld. Ten tweede hebben diverse onderzoekers het gedrag zélf tot doel van simulatie gemaakt, door *agents* te beschrijven als rekenregels (algoritmen) die bepaalde beslissingsprocessen voorstellen. Deze aanpak maakt het mogelijk om verschillende rekenregels met elkaar te vergelijken en om te beoordelen hoe duurzaam ze met de gezamenlijke hulpbron omspringen. Ook maakt deze aanpak het mogelijk om meer extreme uitkomsten te simuleren, zoals bijvoorbeeld het 'verhongerren' van *agents* als de natuurlijke hulpbron uitgeput raakt.

Het gedrag van echte mensen wordt door diverse psychologische factoren en processen bepaald, zoals behoeften, vaardigheden, gewoonten en sociale imitatie. De

psychologie in de rekenregels van *agents* is vaak afwezig, of zij is gebaseerd op slechts een enkele gedragstheorie. Om deze psychologische opmaak te verbeteren is het nodig om bij het ontwikkelen van *agent*-gedragsregels meerdere psychologische theorieën in samenhang te gebruiken.

Een conceptueel meta-model van consumentengedrag (Hoofdstuk 5)

In het ‘consumat model’ worden verschillende theorieën geïntegreerd die relevant zijn om consumenten gedrag te begrijpen. Een beknopte versie van dit ‘meta-model’ wordt geschetst in Figuur 1.

Figuur 1: Schematische weergave van het conceptuele gedragsmodel

Zoals in Figuur 1 valt te zien, bestaat het consumat-model uit verschillende onderdelen. Aan de linkerzijde worden de drijvende krachten van consumentengedrag weergegeven die op het macro niveau spelen. Deze krachten hebben betrekking op de natuurlijke omgeving (hulpbronnen), en op de menselijke omgeving, die factoren omvat als technologie, economie, demografie, instituties en cultuur. Deze macro-krachten zijn van invloed op het microniveau van de individuele consument(en), die aan de rechterzijde van Figuur 1 worden weergegeven. De drijvende krachten bestaan hier uit de beschikbare gelegenheden (opportunities) voor consumptie, de vaardigheden van de consument, zijn/haar behoeftenbevrediging, onzekerheid, en het (voorbeeld)gedrag van vergelijkbare andere consumenten. Deze micro-factoren bepalen welk cognitief proces de actor volgt bij het maken van een gedragskeuze. Vier verschillende processen worden onderscheiden, afhankelijk van de (on)tevredenheid en de (on)zekerheid van de betreffende actor.

Wanneer een actor ontevreden maar zeker is, is de hij/zij geneigd om (individueel beredeneerd) te *delibereren* over de consumptiegelegenheden die uitvoerbaar en bevredigend zijn. Als de actor ontevreden en onzeker is, is hij/zij geneigd om zich *sociaal* (beredeneerd) te *vergelijken* met andere actoren, waarbij de aantrekkelijkheid van

het consumptieve gedrag van anderen wordt ingeschat en eventueel nagevolgd. Als een actor tevreden en zeker is, zal de actor zijn/haar eerdere gedrag gewoonweg (individueel automatisch) *herhalen*. Tenslotte, als de actor tevreden maar onzeker is, zal de actor het gedrag van vergelijkbare anderen eenvoudigweg (sociaal automatisch) *imiteren*. Bij de vier genoemde processen maakt de actor gebruik van de informatie die aanwezig is in zijn geheugen (*mental map*). Alleen als de actor beredeneerd gedrag vertoont (*deliberatie* en *sociale vergelijking*) wordt nieuwe informatie opgeslagen in het geheugen. Figuur 1 laat ook zien dat de consumptie van gelegenheden over alle individuen wordt geaggregeerd, en dus op zijn beurt weer van invloed is op de drijvende krachten op het macroniveau.

Beleidsmaatregelen gericht op gedragsverandering grijpen aan op hetzij het macroniveau (bijvoorbeeld het economische klimaat) of het microniveau (bijvoorbeeld persoonlijke vermogens). Het conceptuele gedragsmodel lijkt bruikbaar om de principes achter dynamische processen van consumptief gedrag te begrijpen, zoals ‘kuddegedrag’ en gewoontevorming.

De operationalisatie van het conceptuele model (Hoofdstuk 6)

In dit hoofdstuk wordt eerst aandacht geschonken aan de mate van detail die gewenst is voor gesimuleerde *agents*. Enerzijds moeten de regels voor de *agent* simpel genoeg zijn om de uitkomsten van experimenten te kunnen begrijpen. Anderzijds moeten ze ook weer niet zo simpel zijn dat de uitkomsten onbruikbaar zijn om processen in de werkelijkheid te begrijpen. In dit hoofdstuk wordt verder beschreven hoe op basis van het conceptuele gedragsmodel uit het vorige hoofdstuk de verschillende *agent*-gedragsregels worden geformaliseerd. De *agents* worden *consumat* genoemd, en het formaliseren van meerdere *consumaten* levert een *multi-agent* simulatiemodel op.

De drijvende krachten op het collectieve (macro-) en het individuele (micro-) niveau bepalen de situatie voor de *consumat*. Het collectieve niveau staat hier voor de (gesimuleerde) wereld waarin de *consumaten* ‘leven’, en het individuele niveau staat voor de *consumat* met zijn verschillende behoeften en vaardigheden. *Consumaten* worden geconfronteerd met verschillende gelegenheden voor consumptie, welke, als ze (in combinatie) geconsumeerd worden, kunnen bijdragen aan de bevrediging van verschillende behoeften. Verder kunnen *consumaten* meer of minder onzeker zijn, afhankelijk van het verschil tussen de verwachte en daadwerkelijke uitkomsten van hun gedrag.

Afhankelijk van zijn mate van (on)tevredenheid en (on)zekerheid, zal een *consumat* in één van de vier cognitieve processen terecht komen (zie ook Hoofdstuk 5). Een ontevreden en zekere *consumat* zal *delibereren*, waarbij consequenties van mogelijke keuzen, gegeven een bepaalde tijdshorizon, in beschouwing worden genomen, en het gedrag met de beste behoeftebevrediging wordt gekozen. Een ontevreden en onzekere *consumat* zal overgaan tot *sociale vergelijking* met vergelijkbare andere *consumaten*. Vervolgens zal de *consumat* het (eigen of andermans) gedrag met de beste uitkomsten kiezen. Als een *consumat* tevreden maar ook onzeker is, zal deze het gedrag van andere vergelijkbare *consumaten* eenvoudigweg *imiteren*. Tenslotte, een tevreden en zekere *consumat* zal zijn eigen eerdere gedrag simpelweg *herhalen*.

De *consumat* is uitgerust met een geheugen waarin informatie over de eigen vaardigheden, consumptiegelegenheden en het gedrag van andere *consumaten* is opgeslagen. Alleen wanneer de *consumat* beredeneerd gedrag vertoont (*deliberatie* en

sociale vergelijking) wordt de informatie in het geheugen ververst. Bij automatisch gedrag (imitatie en herhaling) wordt de (mogelijk verouderde) informatie niet ververst.

Na het feitelijke consumptieve gedrag zal de consummat nieuwe niveaus van tevredenheid en onzekerheid bereiken, welke weer van invloed zijn op het gevolgde cognitieve proces in de volgende tijdsstap. Verder kan het consumptieve gedrag van invloed zijn op de toekomstige vaardigheden van de consummat, de beschikbaarheid van consumptiegelegenheden (bijvoorbeeld schaarste), en de wereld waarin de consummaten leven. Dit is op zijn beurt weer van invloed op het consumptieve gedrag in volgende perioden.

Consumaten in een ‘commons dilemma’ (Hoofdstuk 7)

In de eerste simulatie-experimenten onderzoeken we hoe de consummaten zich gedragen in een simpel ‘*resource dilemma*’ (Jager, Janssen & Vlek, 1999). We zijn daarbij vooral geïnteresseerd in de effecten van onzekerheid en tevredenheid op het ‘oogstgedrag’ van de consummaten. Bestaand empirisch onderzoek met ‘echte mensen’ laat zien dat bij een toename van onzekerheid over de grootte van de hulpbron, mensen geneigd zijn om méér te gaan oogsten (Wit & Wilke, 1998; Hine & Gifford, 1996; Rapoport *et al.*, 1992; Messick *et al.*, 1988).

De simulatie-experimenten laten een drietal effecten van onzekerheid zien: het *optimisme-effect*, het *imitatie-effect* en het *adaptatie-effect*. Het *optimisme-effect* houdt in dat delibererende consummaten die geconfronteerd worden met een positieve schommeling in de omvang van de hulpbron optimistisch worden over de toekomstige groei van de bron. Daardoor gaan ze meer oogsten, waardoor ze sneller tevreden worden, en als gevolg daarvan automatisch gedrag gaan vertonen. Doordat ze dan hun geheugen niet meer ‘verversen’, wordt ook een dreigende uitputting van de hulpbron niet meer waargenomen, en raakt deze snel uitgeput.

Het *imitatie-effect* houdt in dat onzekere en tevreden consummaten geneigd zijn het gedrag van andere consummaten te imiteren, ook als dit gedrag minder gunstige uitkomsten (bijvoorbeeld overconsumptie) met zich meebrengt. Het *adaptatie-effect* houdt in dat hoe meer consummaten aan sociale informatieverwerking (*sociale vergelijking* of *imitatie*) doen, des te kleiner de kans wordt dat echt nieuwe gedragsmogelijkheden worden waargenomen, omdat bij sociale processen alleen het bestaande gedrag van andere consummaten in beschouwing wordt genomen. Als gevolg daarvan kan een populatie van zeer onzekere consummaten niet adaptief reageren op veranderende omstandigheden, zoals een uitputting van de hulpbron. De drie genoemde effecten zijn alle drie zogenaamde proceseffecten, dat wil zeggen dat ze het proces beschrijven dat leidt tot een bepaalde uitkomst.

Het niveau van behoeftenbevrediging waarbij de consummat tevreden is (zijn aspiratieniveau) is erg belangrijk voor het gedrag van de consummat. Als de consummat ontevreden is zal hij zich beredeneerd gaan gedragen (deliberatie of sociale vergelijking). Een consummat met een hoog aspiratieniveau zal niet snel tevreden zijn en zich dus meestal beredeneerd gedragen. Dit betekent dat ze een gemakkelijk benutbare (uitputbare) hulpbron op een duurzamer manier benutten dan consummaten die meer automatisch gedrag (*herhalen, imiteren*) vertonen. Consummaten met een laag aspiratieniveau (die dus sneller tevreden zijn) zullen, doordat ze een overconsumerende gewoonte ontwikkelen, de hulpbron sneller uitputten dan consummaten met een hoog aspiratieniveau. Voor een moeilijk benutbare hulpbron wordt het omgekeerde

gevonden, namelijk dat consumaten met een laag aspiratieniveau eerder een onderconsumerende gewoonte ontwikkelen, dat wil zeggen dat ze minder consumeren dan de hulpbron toestaat.

Samengevat: een hoger aspiratieniveau van de consumat leidt tot meer beredeneerd gedrag, waardoor de kans op zowel onderconsumptie als overconsumptie afneemt. De simulatie-experimenten in dit hoofdstuk laten zien dat de consumatbenadering effecten repliceert en verder verklaart die in experimenteel onderzoek met menselijke proefpersonen ook zijn gevonden.

De 'lock-in' van consumptiepatronen (Hoofdstuk 8)

Het fenomeen 'lock-in' slaat op situaties waarin bepaalde producten of technologieën na verloop van tijd een markt gaan domineren. De 'lock-in' van een bepaald consumptief gedrag wordt niet altijd veroorzaakt door de superioriteit van betreffende producten of technologie. In eerdere economische studies wordt het fenomeen 'lock-in' beschouwd als een toevalsproces. Wij experimenteren met de consumat-benadering om de gedragdynamica achter 'lock-in' te bestuderen. In deze experimenten rusten we de consumaten uit met vier behoeften: identiteit, persoonlijke smaak, vrije tijd en overleven. Naarmate meer 'buren' hetzelfde product consumeren stijgt de bevrediging van de identiteitsbehoefte. De persoonlijke smaak houdt in dat consumaten een eigen voorkeur hebben voor een bepaald product. Hoe goedkoper een product, hoe minder tijd je hoeft te werken om het te kunnen kopen, en dus hoe hoger de bevrediging van behoefte aan vrije tijd. De prijs van een product is afhankelijk van het marktaandeel: hoe meer een product wordt verkocht, hoe goedkoper het wordt. De overlevingsbehoefte is gerelateerd aan de vervuiling die door producten veroorzaakt wordt. Het zijn dus niet alleen de producteigenschappen die de mate van behoeftebevrediging bepalen, maar ook het aantal andere consumaten dat het product gebruikt.

In het simulatie-experiment worden negenhonderd consumaten op een 'schaakbord' van 30 keer 30 cellen geplaatst, en kunnen ze kiezen tussen twee producten. De productkeuze wordt weergegeven door de kleur van de cel. Aan het begin van een simulatierun is de consumptie toevalsgewijs verdeeld. Na enige tijd wordt echter een meer systematisch patroon zichtbaar, hetgeen er op wijst dat de consumaten hun gedrag hebben veranderd. Twee typen van 'lock-in' kunnen worden waargenomen, namelijk een locale en een totale 'lock-in'. De locale 'lock-in' houdt in dat groepen van consumaten ontstaan die hetzelfde product gebruiken. Hoewel het marktaandeel van beide producten 50% kan blijven, zoals in het begin, verandert de ruimtelijke verdeling van het consumptiegedrag drastisch. Vooral als de identiteitsbehoefte belangrijk is zal deze locale 'lock-in' optreden.

Als de prijs van het product belangrijk wordt gevonden, en de persoonlijke smaak geen rol van betekenis speelt, zal sneller een totale 'lock-in' optreden. In dat geval zal één van beide producten een marktaandeel van 100% bereiken. Deze simulatie-experimenten laten zien dat de consumat-benadering vruchtbaar kan worden gebruikt bij het onderzoeken van de gedragdynamica achter processen van 'lock-in'.

De operationalisatie van de consumat in een ecologisch-economisch model (Hoofdstuk 9)

In veel ecologisch-economische modellen wordt menselijk gedrag gemodelleerd als een uitkomsten maximaliserende *rational-actor*. In dit hoofdstuk kijken we naar de effecten van de ontwikkelde gedragsregels op het gedrag van een groep gesimuleerde *agents* die in een virtuele micro-wereld 'leven'. Daartoe plaatsen we de consumaten in 'Lakeland' (De Greef & De Vries, 1991), een virtuele wereld (model) die bestaat uit een meer met vis en een goudmijn. We plaatsen 16 consumaten in Lakeland, en dezen kunnen vissen om aan voedsel te komen. Ook kunnen ze vis exporteren, waardoor ze geld verdienen om bijvoorbeeld luxe goederen te kopen. Ook kunnen ze vis importeren. Het geld dat ze verdienen met mijnbouw kunnen ze uitgeven aan vis en luxe goederen. Echter, de mijnbouw verontreinigt het meer, waardoor er minder garnalen en vissen in het meer overblijven. De consumaten moeten nu beslissen hoeveel tijd ze besteden aan respectievelijk vissen, mijnbouw en vrije tijd. De consumaten hebben zekere vaardigheden om te vissen en goud te delven, en ze willen vier behoeften bevredigen: vrije tijd, identiteit, overleven en persoonlijke smaak. De behoefte aan vrije tijd wordt bevredigd door de hoeveelheid vrije tijd die ze hebben. Naarmate een consumat meer geld heeft dan vergelijkbare andere consumaten (relatief inkomen) is zijn behoefte aan identiteit meer bevredigd. De overlevingsbehoefte wordt bevredigd door het eten van vis. Naarmate de consumat meer geld heeft om te besteden aan luxe goederen (absoluut inkomen) zal zijn persoonlijke smaak meer bevredigd zijn.

Als alle zestien consumaten uitsluitend delibereren over hun gedrag (als *homo economicus*), zijn ze niet in staat om de hulpbron duurzaam te gebruiken omdat ze hun individuele belang boven het collectieve belang stellen (de sociale-dilemmaal). Elke consumat heeft maar een beperkte (1/16) invloed op de totale visvangst, en omdat elke consumat aanneemt dat alle andere consumaten hun gedrag niet zullen veranderen verwachten ze alle dat de uitputting van de hulpbron onvermijdelijk is. Daarom is het aantrekkelijk om te vissen onder het motto 'er uithalen wat er (nog) inzit', waardoor er een soort boemerangeffect optreedt: de hulpbron wordt uitgeput omdat men verwacht dat hij wordt uitgeput.

Het introduceren van een consumat die alle vier de cognitieve strategieën gebruikt (*homo psychologicus*: delibereren, sociale vergelijking, imiteren en herhalen) introduceert nieuwe gedragsdynamische effecten in het model, zoals gewoontegedrag en onderlinge imitatie. Dit zorgt er bijvoorbeeld voor dat de verschuiving van een vissersmaatschappij naar een mijnbouwmaatschappij vloeiend gaat in plaats van heftig wisselend zoals bij de *homo economicus*, en dat men uiteindelijk meer tijd besteedt aan mijnbouw.

Voorts blijkt dat als de consumaten onderling verschillende vaardigheden hebben om te vissen en goud te delven, de verschuiving van een vissersmaatschappij naar een mijnbouwmaatschappij nog vloeiender gaat. In vergelijking tot de situatie waarin alle consumaten gelijke vaardigheden hebben, zien we hier dat de *homo psychologicus* meer tijd gaat besteden aan vissen, en de *homo economicus* minder tijd besteedt aan zowel vissen als goud delven. Om de effecten van variaties in vaardigheden op het duurzaam gebruik van natuurlijke hulpbronnen beter te begrijpen is verder onderzoek nodig.

De huidige experimenten laten zien dat het zowel mogelijk als nuttig is om psychologische theorie te formaliseren in ecologisch-economische modellen.

De algemene toepasbaarheid van de consumat benadering voor gedragssimulatie (Hoofdstuk 10)

In het afsluitende hoofdstuk worden eerst de voor- en nadelen van de consumat-benadering besproken. De voordelen betreffen de multi-theoretische benadering van gedrag en gedragsverandering, waardoor gedragsprocessen meer realistisch gemodelleerd kunnen worden. De nadelen betreffen vooral de hoeveelheid werk die nodig is om de consumat-benadering op een concreet domein toe te passen, en de problemen om vervolgens te controleren of de simulatieresultaten kloppen met processen in de werkelijkheid (validatie).

Aangegeven wordt hoe gedragssimulaties volgens de consumat-benadering empirisch gevalideerd kunnen worden. Ook wordt voorgesteld om empirisch onderzoek (experimenten met menselijke proefpersonen) en simulatieonderzoek te combineren om gedragsdynamische processen te bestuderen.

Tenslotte wordt een aantal mogelijke toepassingen voor de consumat-benadering besproken. Drie toepassingsmogelijkheden worden onderscheiden. Ten eerste stellen we voor om fundamenteel onderzoek te verrichten naar gedragsdynamische processen, zoals de effecten van sociale waarde-oriëntaties (bijvoorbeeld individualisme) op het oogstgedrag in *resource dilemmas*, onderzoek naar zogeheten *give-some* dilemmas (bijvoorbeeld belasting betalen) en naar marktdynamische processen (bijvoorbeeld mode-verschijnselen). Ten tweede stellen we voor om verder te experimenteren met de consumat-benadering in geïntegreerde modellen van complexe (natuurlijke) systemen. Dit zou het mogelijk moeten maken om indicatoren van 'kwaliteit van leven' op te nemen in zulke modellen en om de belangrijke gedragsprocessen achter bepaalde ontwikkelingen te vast te stellen. Tenslotte kan de consumat-benadering worden gebruikt als een instrument om het beslissingsgedrag van beleidsmakers te bestuderen. In die zin zou het nuttig zijn om een eenvoudig model te ontwikkelen waarin gewoontegedrag, het verspreiden van innovaties en 'kuddegedrag' kunnen worden gedemonstreerd. Zo'n model is tevens bruikbaar bij het trainen van beleidsmakers in het herkennen van en reageren op bepaalde gedragsprocessen bij consumenten.

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